

Equality, Justice and Harmony

We fight for Equality among gender, Justice to all and Family Harmony

SILENCING THE TRUTH

STUDY ON MEN

TRUTH IS OUT HERE

AUTHOR: RUDOLPH D'SOUZA

Date: 09/June/2021

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Chapter 1:

SILENCING THE TRUTH

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Summary

This article highlights the tactics used by vested interest stake holders and well-wishers of Feminists to silence the truth when they are exposed. This paper specifically demonstrates how SSRN (Social Science Research Network) handled the articles written and published and then on a flimsy accusation deleted them to hide the truth.

Total 14 articles were written by the Author and seven of them were peer reviewed and accepted for publication. Most of the papers were liked and downloaded many times making them the TOP 10 articles within 60 days. However, this instigated the feminists to take it down from the site at any cost.

Key Findings

All of these articles were related to Men's Issues, and their struggle in this biased world. This incident has made it clear that there is no scope for men, and they cannot even publish the real facts with evidence as it affects the vested interest of the Feminists.

Methodology

Information for this report is sourced from SSRN (Social Science Research Network), various secondary sources, and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics, etc.

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Introduction

It is the mostly men who are against men. It is the men law makers who make laws against men which are favoring women. It is the Male judges who give biased Judgments with harsh punishment to men and being lenient to women for a similar Crime. There are no studies on men addressing the following questions: Why men commit suicide? How men are harassed? How legal terrorism is impacting their health? How do they suffer in silence? Why do they suffer in silence? How stressful life they lead, when they face abuse and humiliation at the hands of their beloved ones. So, we at MyNation utilized the free time during COVID-19, collecting supporting material pertaining to such issues and wrote some articles on subjects relating to men. These study articles/reports/Papers were based on reviews of literature obtained from legal journals, medical journals, main stream media articles, NCRB and references from other study reports and published on SSRN from August 2020 onwards. Total of 14 articles were submitted and out of 14, only 7 were peer reviewed and accepted for publication by SSRN.

SCREENSHOT OF ALL THE ARTICLES:

INACTIVE PAPERS | [Instructions](#)

This section contains papers that have been made inactive by the author or by SSRN (e.g. due to a major revision). These papers do not display on your author page and are not available to the SSRN or external search engines.

Review	Abstract ID	Title	#Document	Date Created	Submitted By	Status	Views	Comments
			Public View	Last Updated			Downloads	
	3720586 APS	BIAS BY BIRTH - DISCRIMINATION AGAINST MEN	Yes No	11/07/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	172 95	View
	3722563 APS	GOLD DIGGERS - HOW TO MAKE EASY MONEY IN INDIA - WOMEN SPECIAL	Yes No	11/01/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	357 142	View
	3723153 WPS	COVID-19 - A CHINESE FLU - STATISTICS AND CONSPIRACY THEORIES - THE YEAR WORLD STOOD STILL	Yes No	10/31/2020 11/02/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	67 7	View
	3717515 WPS	MEN'S LIVES MATTERS - SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH	Yes No	10/23/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	204 58	View
	3712952 APS	SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN	Yes No	10/16/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	359 105	View
	3710115 APS	STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH	Yes No	10/12/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	676 339	View
	3704275 APS	CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN	Yes No	10/03/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	274 96	View
Review	3699991 APS	Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism	Yes No	09/06/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	671 229	View
	3697049 APS	WMD's of India - Weapons of Men's Destruction	Yes No	09/02/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	DISTRIBUTED	897 131	View
	3695517 APS	Legal Terrorism in Matrimonial Disputes - Solution for Legal Terrorism	Yes No	08/19/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	DISTRIBUTED	539 172	View
	3695149 WPS	The National Commission for Women, Exposed	Yes No	08/18/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	154 29	View
	3673754 APS	Violence Against Men - False Accusation of Sexual Harassment	Yes No	08/14/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	DISTRIBUTED	635 242	View
	3665518 APS	Section 498-B IPC, - A Much Needed Reform	Yes No	08/05/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	REMOVED	116 60	View
	3665274 WPS	Domestic Violence: The Wife Struggle to Survive and Mental Health	Yes No	08/01/2020 11/16/2020	Rudolph D	DISTRIBUTED	1,517 456	View

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About Author

My Papers

Rudolph D (Author ID: 4309387)

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Rudolph D Author Rank is 39,918 out of 537,540

The early Indian men's rights movement was started in 2000 in Mumbai by activist and false accusation victim Rudolph D'Souza (Rudy) to help other victims of psychological abuse in marriage and false claims of dowry harassment.(Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Men%27s_rights_movement_in_India#2000%E2%80%93005)

Links to articles on SSRN published and later deleted:

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3726686 - BIAS BY BIRTH - DISCRIMINATION AGAINST MEN

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3722850 - GOLD DIGGERS: HOW TO MAKE EASY MONEY IN INDIA - WOMEN SPECIAL

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3717515 - MEN'S LIVES MATTERS – SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3712962 - SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN Yes

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https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3710115 - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3704275 - CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3699991 - Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3697040 - WMD's of India – Weapons of Men's Destruction

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3695617 - Legal Terrorism in Matrimonial Disputes – Solution for Legal Terrorism

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3695149 - The National Commission for Women, Exposed

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3673754 - Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3665508 - Section 498-B IPC, – A Much Needed Reform

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3665274 - Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health

On 19th November 2020 I received an Email with Subject line as [#M79-A24-3W9N]

Ticket received: Your SSRN Papers.

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With a below message.

[#M79-A24-3W9N] Ticket received: Your SSRN Papers Inbox SSRN

SSRN Help Desk <support@ssrn.com>

Nov 19, 2020, 6:21 PM (6 days ago)

to me

Dear Rudolph D'Souza,

Thank you for contacting SSRN. This is an automated acknowledgement to confirm we have received your message, "Your SSRN Papers".

A Help Desk ticket has been opened on your behalf. Tracking ID M79-A24-3W9N

The SSRN Support Team aims to respond within 3 business days, however, it may be delayed if we are experiencing high volumes of requests. If your message requires a response, you will receive an email notification once our team has replied to your ticket.

You can view the status of your ticket here:

<https://support.ssrn.com/ticket.php?track=M79-A24-3W9N&email=rud%31%40gmail.com&Refresh=13276>

While you are waiting, we encourage you to try one of our self-service support options.

SSRN Help Desk Knowledgebase at <http://support.ssrn.com/>

SSRN FAQs at <https://www.ssrn.com/en/index.cfm/ssrn-faq>

Thank you,

SSRN Support

<https://support.ssrn.com>

It's saying *A Help Desk ticket has been opened on your behalf: Tracking ID M79-A24-3W9N*

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Case Tracking ID: M79-A24-3W9N

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Your SSRN Papers

Tracking ID: M79-A24-3W9N (Ticket number: 752806)

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Created on: 2020-11-19 15:15:14

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Last replier: Rudolph D'Souza

Category: General

Replies: 2

Date: 2020-11-19 15:15:14

Name: Rudolph D'Souza

Email: rudu3@gmail.com

Print

Message:

Dear Rudolph D'Souza,

After further review of your papers on SSRN and due to baseless inflammatory rhetoric, we are removing all of your papers from the site.

If you choose to resubmit or upload any future submissions they must be free of inflammatory rhetoric and properly cited to avoid unsubstantiated conclusions.

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With a message

After further review of your papers on SSRN and due to baseless inflammatory rhetoric, we are removing all of your papers from the site.

So, I sent the following reply:

Dear Sir/Madam

I received your email stating that you have removed all my articles from your journal. In your justification for removing my articles, you have mentioned that my articles contain inflammatory rhetoric and unsubstantiated conclusions. You have also mentioned that I did not cite my conclusions and data properly.

I hereby raise strong objections for the removal of my articles which are already verified, published and in this regards I would like to ask you some questions from you:

1. Can you please provide 2 or 3 examples from my articles where you have found the substance of inflammatory statements?
2. All the data and facts given to my articles are properly cited and are based on data published by government agencies and a well-credible source. Please can you provide 2 or 3 examples from my articles where such data is not cited properly.
3. It is shocking to me that I was not given any opportunity to provide proper objections/justifications before my articles were taken out. Can you please explain why I was not given such an opportunity?

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Sir / Madam, I published my work with you because your journal has a good reputation. Please answer all my objections objectively.

Thanking you.

Date: 2020-11-19 16:50:42

Name: Rudolph D'Souza

Message:

Good Day

I received this below message

"Thank you for contacting SSRN. This is an automated acknowledgement to confirm we have received your message, "Your SSRN Papers".

A Help Desk ticket has been opened on your behalf: Tracking ID M79-A24-3W9N"

I did not opened any such support ticket.
Please let me know, who opened this request.

Regards

Date: 2020-11-19 17:26:23

Name: Rudolph D'Souza

Message:

Dear Sir / Madam

I received your email stating that you have removed all my articles from your journal. In your justification for removing my articles, you have mentioned that my articles contain inflammatory rhetoric and unsubstantiated conclusions. You have also mentioned that I did not cite my conclusions and data properly.

I here by raise strong objections for the removal of my articles which are already verified, published and in this regards I would like to ask you some questions from you:

1. Can you please provide 2 or 3 examples from my articles where you have found the substance of inflammatory statements.
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Sir / Madam, I published my work with you because your journal has a good reputation. Please answer all my objections objectively.

Thanking you.

I sent reply on 19th November 2020 and my message was

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After responding it has been many days now and there is no reply from SSRN, that shows that they do not have words to justify their move which is totally unethical for such an Organization.

As SSRN removed our articles on their website, but at the same time we replicated same Articles on our site <https://mynation.net/>, which can be found in below URLs

Links to articles on MyNation:

<https://mynation.net/voice/bias/> - BIAS BY BIRTH - DISCRIMINATION AGAINST MEN

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3722850/> - GOLD DIGGERS: HOW TO MAKE EASY MONEY IN INDIA - WOMEN SPECIAL

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3717515/> - MEN'S LIVES MATTERS – SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3712962/> - SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN Yes

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3710115/> - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3704275/> - CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3699991/> - Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism

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<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3697040/> - WMD's of India – Weapons of Men's Destruction

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3695617/> - Legal Terrorism in Matrimonial Disputes – Solution for Legal Terrorism

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3695149/> - The National Commission for Women, Exposed

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3673754/> - Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3665508/> - Section 498-B IPC, – A Much Needed Reform

<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3665274/> - Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health

We have the same Articles uploaded and available to readers. Anyone can read and Judge what the truth is and what SSRN is trying hard to hide or silence.

As per our understanding it is not willfully removed by SSRN, as this was previously peer reviewed and accepted for publication Articles by them only. Now they have taken the extreme step of deleting by labeling it baseless, inflammatory, rhetoric articles. If these articles are baseless inflammatory rhetoric then why were they approved and published in the first place? And all of a sudden how did they find that all these are baseless? For sure they are influenced by someone and it can be none other than the Feminists because only they have vested interests in the issues covered in these articles.

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Most of the articles openly exposes with valid data or media reports and other articles which affect false propaganda and money-making business of these organizations.

It is not that SSRN wanted to remove, but they were forced to remove the articles. If vested Interested influenced SSRN to remove it then I have right to demand on what basis vested Interests have asked to remove it? Have they provided any proof of their claim? If SSRN failed to ask then, SSRN is part of the same vested interest, feminist lobby.

SSRN Please provide me the proof of my claims being baseless.

Voice against vested Interests is always inflammatory, rhetoric and that's how feminist lobby term it. In our article, for every claim we have provided various proofs like NCRB data, Public Poll Data, mainstream media coverage and statements from the general Public, Victims of Legal Terrorism. If vested interest calls these articles as baseless, inflammatory, rhetoric and without any evidence, then it is another attempt to silence the Truth, Voice of the Voiceless.

In my mail to SSRN I requested ***“Please provide 2 or 3 examples from my articles where you have found the substance of inflammatory statements.”*** But for days now there is no reply from SSRN and neither do I expect any response from them coz they do not have any. This shows SSRN removed my articles on pressure from their masters, the Feminists. If SSRN had a moral responsibility they would have asked me to justify every word I wrote in the articles proving it baseless, inflammatory, rhetoric but instead like a coward they removed all peer reviewed and accepted publication Papers, the articles submitted but not reviewed by Peers and the Author Profile as well. That shows it's not

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about baseless inflammatory rhetoric statements, it's about whom I write against. Which makes them so much afraid of my articles and me.

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Our message to these Vested Interest, Feminists Lobby and Legal terrorists is that you can hide the truth, silence the truth, but you cannot erase the truth. Sooner than later there will be many voices echoed across the Globe, then there will be judgment and you will be judged.

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We men face many types of Terrorism, like Legal terrorism, Alimony terrorism, Tax terrorism, Systematic Political Terrorism and now this MEDIA TERRORISM. We are happy to know that our articles reached the right place where it intended. Feminists lobby, and Legal terrorism supporters like UN Women, WCD/NCW and Police are feeling the heat of it and in no time, it will burn them soon.

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Chapter 2:

Domestic Violence-The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental health.

Voice of Voiceless

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This survey and study report is based on Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims, and not collected as Women organizations collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories which have no valid backing.

Summary

The term "Domestic Violence/Abuse" covers a broad range of violent acts committed by one member of a family or household against another. It often refers to the mistreatment of a child or spouse and can include not only physical harm, but also threats and verbal, psychological, and sexual abuse. Most of the time, domestic violence against men only gets any attention when a Celebrity/Politician or highly reputed person is the victim of some kind of noteworthy physical harm, rest perceived as isolated incidents and much of the public and private speculation presumes the man did something to deserve it.

The exact numbers on domestic violence on men overall is difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men are suffering abuse. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman.

Key Findings

Majority men are ashamed to come forward to report domestic violence/abuse on them by their wives, as there are no laws or Authority to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like 498A IPC / PWDVA 2005 on them, that make's men to suffer in silence.

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Methodology

Information for this report was sourced from various secondary sources, all listed in the Reference List. Data from NCRB and various News publications and testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Domestic violence also proved valuable. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of Men who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is not ready to Publish Domestic Violence/Abuse on Men or their Mental health.

Introduction

MyNation analysis of statistics on Domestic Violence shows the number of men attacked/abused/harassed/killed by wives and girlfriends is much higher than ever thought. Its report, Domestic Violence: The Male struggle to survive, states: "Domestic Violence is often assumed as women as victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations."

MyNation Hope Foundation with a presence on the internet for over 15 years and having more than 10,000 families registered with them that include men, women and old aged parents. The study conducted between January 2018 and March 2020 by Social workers, Researchers, Doctors, IT Engineers, Bankers and MyNation. From all over India, 90% of the respondents and 10% NRIs had suffered Domestic Violence more than once in their lives. The study covered men of Indian origin from various socio-economic groups but

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most of the respondents, according to the researchers, come from the upper middle class and middle class.

About three in five of Domestic Violence instances are on men, contradicting the widespread impression that it is almost always women who are left battered and bruised. About 3000 men aged between 25-55 years, selected through random sampling are interviewed using a schedule adapted from the WHO multi-country study on Men's Health and Domestic Violence.

The study looked at all four aspects of Domestic Violence, Emotional, Physical, Sexual and Economical. Emotional violence is found to be the most common with 43.2% respondents mentioning they had faced it at least once, followed by Physical (26.8%), then by Sexual (19.8%) and Economical violence (10.2%)

“The violence is found to be more on men. This clearly indicates lack of awareness and support among masses regarding emotional violence on men. The men, who are contributors to the society in the name of father, son, brother, husband, entrepreneur, taxpayer, army soldier and more are often subjected to emotional violence which is not lesser than any heinous crime.” says **Dr. Bharat Bhushan**.

“An interesting finding is that the probability of violence increased significantly with the duration of marriage particularly if it was more than five years old” says one of the researchers. "So much for the law to promote domestic violence against Indian men and wonder no NGO or Social organizations have done any research, no one demanded the data of Crime against men by women and crime against women by another women. Indian government is mostly interested to promote 'Beti Bachao' by funding more than

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INR 25,000 crore yearly but none to men and his families. Indian Gender Biased Laws have major impact on failure of marital relationship and are affecting the normal growth of children involved. Very soon the Indian Civilized Institution of marriage system will be dwindled and in coming years there will be many children alienated from father." he said.

Objective of the Study:

Men assaulted by their partners are often ignored by police. Cases are not filed. Mostly the women attackers go scot free. Men have far fewer shelter homes to flee to. Compared to women, men don't have any protection laws from domestic abuse.

“National Commission for Women is taking very good care of the desires of unscrupulous wives/daughters-in-laws. Wives can falsely accuse their husband and in-laws, then blackmail them for money. Wives can extort money by threatening their husband of filing a false case. Wives can kick their husband and in-laws from the marital house under domestic violence laws. Wives can have extramarital affairs proudly with anybody even when the husband and in-laws are fully aware of it. In short, it is simply great to be born as a woman in India. Whatever she does, she will always be considered a victim. Surely, these women will be extremely thankful to NCW for legalizing their adultery. What is illegal is now legal. Adultery is not illegal in India now, so What more do the women want now?” asks **Dr. Vikas Singh Rawat**.

According to the research, 53 per cent of Indian wives admitted to having had an intimate relationship outside their marriage (ref: <https://supari.org/40-percent>) she can have sex in

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front of her husband at his home, but he cannot do anything legally as Section 497 IPC scrapped by Indian judiciary to promote and empower women.

Today, legally any woman can file a case on man and all her allegations are assumed “possible” as they stayed under one roof and closed walls. These baseless allegations can be shattered through proper investigation, but India has Investigation Officers and Protection Officers who do not even know the basics of complaint verification process. There are scenarios, where the bride has comeback after a year of eloping with someone, but the Groom's family had spent that one year in jail on charges of bride’s murder. Corruption also plays a major role in the misuse of these gender biased laws.

The latest health statistics paint a grim picture of India’s mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health Profile 2018 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths—a whopping 1,33,623 in a year.

This translates into 366 suicide deaths every day and 15 an hour.

The data also show increasing vulnerability of Indian men vis-à-vis women.

Nearly 70 per cent of all suicide deaths in India involve males. Of the 1,33,623 people who killed themselves, 68.49 per cent (91,528) were men as against 42,088 women.

The number of suicides by men has risen from 66,032 in 2000 and 80,544 in 2008 to 91,528 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

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According to the latest data, the highest suicide burden is in Maharashtra (16,970 deaths), followed by Tamil Nadu (15,777) and Bengal (14,602)

Health data also reveal that suicides are the highest in the productive age group of 30 to 45. Trends call for massive shift in government policy to address the rising burden of mental health disorders, an emerging challenge under the larger non-communicable disease bracket.

WHO's Global Disease Burden released last month also underlined the need for member nations to contain suicide deaths by tweaking policy. WHO asked all member states to ensure employers factor in mental health when crafting recruitment policies? (Source: <https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/archive/nation/-one-indian-commits-suicide-every-4-minutes-men-more-vulnerable-609058>)

Data from the Survey show that men made up about 45% of Domestic Violence victims each year between 2018-19 and last year for which figures are unavailable. In 2016-17 men made up 43.4% of all those who had suffered partner abuse in the previous year, which rose to 45.5% in 2017-18.

The 2018-19 survey shows one in three men had experienced domestic abuse since the age of 16. As per MyNation, men are often treated as "second-class victims" and that many police forces and councils do not take them seriously. "Male victims are almost invisible to the authorities such as the police, who rarely can be prevailed upon to take the man's side," said **Aman Kumar**, a Banker by profession. "Their plight is largely overlooked by the media, in official reports and in government policy, for example Women organization like WCD/NCW are ministry for women with around 25,000 crore

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yearly funding but none for Men, even though most of the taxpayers are Men” says **Vikrant Banode** an IT Professional.

The official figures underestimate the true number of male victims, **Amit Nishania** a Finance professional said. "Culturally it's difficult for men to bring these incidents to the attention of the authorities. Men are reluctant to say that they have been abused by women, because it's considered as unmanly and weak."

"Both men and women can be victims and we know that men feel immense pressure to keep up the pretense that everything is OK, Domestic abuse against a man is just as abhorrent as when a woman is treated as the victim always." said **Ramesh Thatiseti** an NRI, "

No provisions of refuge or Legal Aid for men:

“Male victims are almost invisible to the authorities and Government” says **Rudolph Dsouza** of MyNation, an Initiative, a helpline for Male victims, He added "It's a scandal that even in 2020 all Domestic Violence victims are still not being treated equally. Men are not only abused with Emotional, Physical, Sexual, and Economic violence, but also with LEGAL TERRORISM. We reject the gendered analysis that so many in the Domestic Violence establishment still pursue, that is the primary focus should be female victims only. Each victim should be seen as an individual and helped accordingly."

Shocking! Indian wives rank third in beating their husbands:

We often hear stories of husbands thrash their wife for various reasons, but the other side of the story is husbands too are persecuted in large numbers. So much so that Indian women are ranked third in the world for abusing or beating their husbands. A study

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conducted by the UN in a couple of years ago (2016) has revealed shocking statistics of domestic violence on husbands. These figures indicate that domestic violence is the most frequent in Egypt, while UK stood second followed by India.

The survey states that wives used items like belts, shoes, utensils etc. to beat their husbands. It was also trending on twitter at that time.

Users commented that when a woman becomes a victim then the whole world stands by her, but the society turns a blind eye when a man is found to be on the receiving end. Husbands who suffer such abuse find no other way to defend them and knock the doors of law to save themselves from abuse and assault.(Source : <https://www.orissapost.com/shocking-indian-wives-rank-third-in-beating-their-husbands>)

False Propaganda of Women Organizations:

As these Women ministry claim "Many women sufferings abuse want to go to their mother's house, but during the lockdown, they can only be sent to state-run shelter homes, where the risk of overcrowding and poor hygiene runs high."

When WCD/NCW has 25,000 crores of yearly funding why these shelter homes are unhygienic? ask **Neeraj Pattath** a MyNation members.

"For the first week, the number of calls we get fell, and we believe this is because women were basically locked in with their abusers," Swetha Shankar, director of client services at the Women organization.

India's Domestic Violence Act gives the woman a right to shelter. Let her stay home in her house, with her kids, and let the man be sent to a shelter home if he is going to abuse

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the woman in the middle of a pandemic. "Why should a woman escaping abuse in the middle of a lockdown be sent to a shelter home where she risks catching coronavirus?" Vrinda Grover, a leading feminist lawyer.

As earlier said by these women organizations, they are not getting any calls, then how they know these women are harassed or abused. Either they should know magic or telepathy, stated one of the survey participants.

WCD/NCW opposes any sort of law for men against women or setup Ministry, as they have strong feminist lobby, they opposed dilution and punishment for filing false cases of 498a/DV Act too. so without giving any option for men to complain or disclose about being abused by their wives, they just want to showcase that only women are harassed by men and portray them as villains and only women are the real victims. (Source: <https://thewire.in/gender/section-498a-domestic-abuse-ncw>)

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How Women Harass:

Emotional, Physical, Sexual and Economical abuse on men: Men are abused by women, it happens, and it matters:

So, what is abuse? A pattern of controlling behavior, Abuse in intimate relationships is a pattern of behavior where one partner dominates, belittles or humiliates the other over months and years.

Abuse of men by their partners happens when the partner uses emotional, physical, sexual or intimidation tactics. She does it to control the man, get her own way and prevent him from leaving the relationship. The abused man is always adapting his behavior to do what his partner wants, in the hopes of preventing further abuse.

The primary motive for abuse is to establish and maintain power and control over a partner. The abused partner may resist the attempts to control him. In turn, the abusive woman takes additional steps to regain control over her partner.

Abuse in intimate relationships is not typically an isolated incident. Abuse happens overtime. Typically, if abuse is allowed to continue, it becomes more frequent and more severe.

Abuse is always a choice. Whatever people's background or experience, they must take responsibility for their actions. No one has the right to abuse someone else, and no one deserves abuse.

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Control Tactics:

Four kinds of abuse

Often when people think about abuse, they think of emotional abuse, physical abuse or sexual abuse. Abuse may also include intimidation tactics.

Emotional Abuse:

Emotional abuse happens without other abuse tactics involved; emotional abuse is almost always present. Some men say it is harder to deal with emotional abuse than physical abuse. Emotional abuse includes:

- ✓ Putdowns: Insults or humiliates her partner at home or in public
- ✓ Blames him
- ✓ Lies to him
- ✓ Insult/abuse husband Family members.
- ✓ Curse/Grumble/Insult husband.
- ✓ Give threat of False 498a/DV criminal cases
- ✓ Give threat to alienate children from him.
- ✓ Embarrass in front of friends/Family members.
- ✓ Shaming
- ✓ Name calling, specially to mother-in-law
- ✓ Isolating her partner and restricting his freedom
- ✓ Controls her partner's social interaction
- ✓ Isolates him from friends and family
- ✓ Treats him like a servant

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- ✓ Monitors his phone calls
- ✓ Restricts his ability to get around
- ✓ Controls access to information or participation in organizations and groups.
- ✓ Insults
- ✓ Accusations on character and conduct etc.
- ✓ Preventing you or a child in your custody from attending school, college or any other educational institution
- ✓ Preventing you from taking up a job, forcing you to leave your job
- ✓ Preventing you or a child in your custody from leaving the house
- ✓ Preventing you from meeting any person in the normal course of events
- ✓ Forcing you to get married when you don't want to marry
- ✓ Preventing you from marrying a person of your own choice
- ✓ Forcing you to marry a particular person of his/their own choice
- ✓ Threaten to commit suicide
- ✓ Any other verbal or emotional abuse

Spiritual Abuse:

- ✓ Ridicules or insults her partner's spiritual beliefs
- ✓ Makes it difficult for the partner to be with others in his spiritual community

Emotional violence has become more common against men and openly neglected as there is no law to support men who are in abusive relationships and are victims of domestic violence. This kind of Emotional violence is more common in Indian family which is often neglected by court of law, police authority and society as a whole.

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Physical Abuse:

This includes any activity that can cause physical pain or injury.

In an intimate relationship, physical abuse happens when the abusive person:

- ✓ Shoves, slaps, hits, kicks or bites
- ✓ Throws/drop things on him
- ✓ Uses a weapon
- ✓ Intentionally interferes with basic daily requirements for food, shelter, medicine and sleep
- ✓ Beating
- ✓ Throw things/hot water/hot oil/Acid
- ✓ Mix life threatening things or slow poison in eatables.
- ✓ Beating, slapping, hitting, biting, kicking, punching, pushing, shoving or causing bodily pain or injury in any other manner.

Sexual Abuse:

- ✓ Uses force or pressure to get her partner to have sex in a way he does not want
- ✓ Ridicules or criticizes his performance
- ✓ Withholds affection and sex to punish him for violating her rules
- ✓ Withhold sex without reason.
- ✓ Abuse for weaker sexual drive or size.
- ✓ Accuse of having Affair. (Even some men reported, that abusing and accusing to having sex with mother)
- ✓ Doubting of relation with neighbors/co-worker

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- ✓ Forced sexual intercourse
- ✓ Forces to look at pornography or any other obscene pictures or material
- ✓ Any act of sexual nature to abuse, humiliate or degrade you, or which is otherwise volatile of dignity or any other unwelcome conduct of sexual nature

Economical Abuse:

- ✓ Controlling finances
- ✓ Withholds financial information from her partner
- ✓ Steals money from him
- ✓ Makes financial decisions that affect him without asking or telling him
- ✓ Desert without any grounds and claim Maintenance
- ✓ File False case of Domestic violence also take children with her and claim alimony
- ✓ File False case of Dowry (IPC 498A) and force man to settle out of court with huge sum of money and property
- ✓ On False Ground of Domestic violence occupy husband home making him homeless.
- ✓ Not providing you money for maintaining you or your children
- ✓ Not providing food, clothes, medicines etc. for you or your children
- ✓ Stopping you from carrying on your employment or disturbing you in carrying on your employment
- ✓ Not allowing you to take up an employment or taking away your income from your salary, wages etc.
- ✓ Forcing you out of the house you live in
- ✓ Stopping you from accessing or using any part of the house

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- ✓ Not allowing use of clothes, articles or things of general household use
- ✓ Not paying rent if staying in a rented accommodation.

Other than Economic Terrorism, Women use Legal terrorism to make money, most of the dowry cases (IPC 498A) and DV Act 2005 filed, man under pressure succumb to her demand and settle out with huge amount of money. Any time women can walk out taking children and file any False case on husband, no proof or evidence needed. On the basis of these Fake DV cases judge order maintenance of huge amount, there are many such judgments, even Men are unemployed still court order Alimony/Maintenance. In an exceptional order, the Punjab and Haryana High Court has made it clear that a husband may beg, borrow or steal for paying allowance to his wife and child, as his first and foremost duty was to maintain them (Source : <https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/archive/haryana/beg-borrow-or-steal-to-pay-wife-child-hc-679957>) and another court said do not use word BEG or Steal but order maintenance just because women is asking (Source: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/avoid-beg-borrow-steal-adage-when-making-husbands-pay-maintenance-hc-to-family-court/articleshow/62515380.cms>) If women runaway with Lover, that's her choice, her body, she can have intimacy with anyone of her choice; but a man who does the same, society and judiciary term it as desertion or running away from responsibilities.

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Other Intimidation Tactics:

These include any words or actions the abusive partner uses to scare her partner. For example:

- ✓ Destroy property
- ✓ Throw or smash things
- ✓ Trash his clothes or other possessions
- ✓ Destroy keepsakes
- ✓ Break furniture or windows
- ✓ Threaten
- ✓ Threaten to harm or kill him
- ✓ Threaten to harm or kill herself or children, family, friends or pets
- ✓ Threaten to lie to authorities to put his child custody or legal status at risk
- ✓ Create a sense that punishment is just around the corner
- ✓ Stalk or harass
- ✓ Follow him after they have separated
- ✓ Show up at his workplace
- ✓ Go to his house and park outside
- ✓ Phone or send him mail repeatedly
- ✓ Phone or send mail to his family, friends or colleagues

Whether or not there are children involved, a man may stay in an abusive situation because:

- He feels afraid or guilty

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- He feels he is financially insecure
- He feels a sense of obligation to his female partner
- He wants to honor his religious convictions or cultural expectations
- His partner reminds him of religious convictions or cultural expectations
- He still has hope for the relationship
- He feels ashamed to admit he is being abused

A man with children may stay in the relationship because:

- He doesn't want to lose access to his children
 - He doesn't want to leave the children with his abusive partner
 - He may not trust the courts to handle child custody fairly
 - He doesn't want to be the one that "breaks up" the family
- ✓ Show up in party or function hosted by husband family with dirty or revealing cloths, create scene, flirt or act weird, shout, cry without reason, Abuse husband etc.

Society's attitudes can make it harder

Our society is beginning to recognize and study the abuse of men by their partners. Society's beliefs and attitudes about men have kept this kind of abuse hidden. Because of these beliefs, men who are abused by female partners may not admit it. They may not want to tell anyone. Additionally, sometimes police and other professionals may not take the abuse seriously.

As a result, a man in an abusive relationship may have some of these feelings:

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- Afraid to tell anyone
- Depressed or humiliated
- Afraid he has failed as a lover and partner
- Guilty about leaving her or scared of coping alone
- Furious she could do or say the things she did
- Confused because sometimes she acts loving and kind
- Frustrated and sad because he has tried everything
- Afraid of continued violence or harassment if he leaves
- Panicked he may lose his male identity if people know what has been going on
- Worried about his financial security
- Believes he deserved it

An abusive environment does harm children now and their future

Sometimes people abused by their partners think their children do not know about the abuse or that the abuse does not harm the children. But children are harmed, even if they are not directly abused.

Being exposed to anger and violence affects children's brain development.

- Brain scans show that children in abusive environments use much of their brain to watch out for danger. Less of their brain is available for healthy growth and development
- This affects their physical, emotional and mental development
- It affects their ability to form healthy relationships

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- It affects them even when the children are not consciously aware of the abuse in their home

When a child is in a threatening environment over time, such as in a home where the adults are abusive, systems in the child's brain undergo changes. These changes result in emotional, behavioral, intellectual and physical symptoms. Children can show all the same signs of trauma as if they were abused themselves.

All children in a threatening environment are affected by fear. They might:

- Feel anxious or panicky
- Have an increased heart rate — babies in violent or angry homes have faster heart rates even in their sleep
- Be very watchful and attentive all the time, as though they are on “red alert”
- Because their brains are distracted by fear, they may:
 - Find it hard to concentrate or pay attention
 - Have difficulty sleeping
 - Have difficulty learning

Children in a threatening environment use different ways to cope.

Some children react by becoming more aggressive. They might:

- Be defiant
- Act impulsive
- Have angry outbursts
- Act bossy or pushy

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➤ Bully or hurt others

Sometimes these loud children do not appear to be affected. They look like they feel confident and in charge. But their aggressive behaviors grow out of fear expressed outwardly as anger. Some children react by becoming quiet and withdrawn.

These children might:

- Try to stay safe by becoming “invisible”
- Go into their own fantasy world and tune out the world around them
- Be more obedient or passive than other children
- Be numb and disconnected from their own feelings
- Be detached from other people
- Have a hard time getting along with others
- Be depressed

Sometimes these quiet children, do not look like they are affected by what is going on around them. They do not appear to react. However, this “unaffected” appearance is a danger sign. In the face of fear and feeling helpless, they have disconnected from their environment.

You may think that the abuse between adults in the home does not affect children, or that you can shield them from what is going on. That is not true. As long as children live in an abusive environment, the trauma will continue to affect their brains. They will not be able to heal.

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Findings:

Men have suffered physical violence at the hands of an intimate partner or family member. In India after Domestic Violence Act, 2005 enacted, as it suffers from inherent flaws which tempt women to misuse their provisions and men to dread being prosecuted under the law without any rhyme or reason. The notable flaw in this law is that it lends itself to such easy misuse that women will find it hard to resist the temptation to teach a lesson to their male relatives and will file frivolous and false cases. One can be certain that there is something sinister about a law when it intimidates and instills fear in innocent people. When a person who has not committed any crime begins to fear punishment under the provisions of a law, it will certainly create panic amidst men. Now-a-days, filing cases under the Domestic Violence Act by women has become a common one. Therefore, a neutral and an unprejudiced law is needed to protect the genuine victims of domestic violence irrespective of their gender.

Domestic violence (also named domestic abuse, spousal abuse, intimate partner violence, battering, or family violence) is a pattern of behavior which involves violence or other abuse by one person against another in a domestic setting, such as in marriage or cohabitation. Intimate partner violence (IPV) is violence by a spouse or partner in an intimate relationship against the other spouse or partner. Domestic violence can take place in heterosexual and same-sex family relationships and can involve violence against children in the family. Domestic violence can take a number of forms, including physical, verbal, emotional, economic, cultural and sexual abuse, which can range from subtle, coercive forms to marital rape and to violent physical abuse such as female genital

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mutilation and acid throwing that result in disfigurement or death. Domestic murders include stoning, bride burning, honor killings, and dowry deaths.

Male victims of family violence and abuse - like women - often face many barriers to disclosing their abuse:

- They are likely to be told that there must be something they did to provoke the perpetrator's abuse
- They can suffer shame, embarrassment and the social stigma of not being able to protect themselves
- They can fear that if they disclose the abuse there will be nowhere for them and their children to escape to
- In cases of intimate partner violence, they can fear that if they disclose the abuse or end the relationship, their partner might become more abusive and/or take the children
- They can feel uncertain about where to seek help, or how to seek help
- Services are less likely to ask whether a man is a victim of family violence, and when they do ask, they are less likely to believe him (indeed many health departments have mandatory domestic violence screening for young women, but no such screening for young men) Male victims can be falsely arrested and removed from their homes because of the assumption that because they are male, they must be a perpetrator and not a victim. When this happens, children can be left unprotected from the perpetrator of the violence, leading many men to suffer the abuse in silence in an attempt to protect their children.

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Because of these barriers, men are much less likely to under report being a victim of family violence compared to women.

In India, family violence against men is almost legal as there is no provision in any law to protect a man, who faces violence from wife or other female family members. There are several cases where a husband has been battered, abused, tortured by wife in connivance with her own family. Many a times the violence is so brutal that the husband suffers extreme injuries, in some cases he is killed as well. This situation is mainly due to patriarchal thinking in the society, that men are stronger than women and they can defend themselves with physical force. It's high time India keeps pace with the rest of the world and makes the laws against domestic violence gender neutral.

Most abused men do not run away from their abusers and apply for divorce, because they are either afraid of losing access to their children or they are afraid of getting implicated in false cases of dowry harassment. They also dread huge financial losses and long drawn litigations in the process, given the insensitive and lackadaisical attitude of the Indian Judiciary, especially towards men.

In 2004, the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) has found that about 1.8% or an estimated 60 lakh women have perpetrated physical violence against husbands without any provocation. However, men are more likely to be threatened and attacked by male relatives of the wife than the wife herself. The strange aspect however is, men are not asked if they are victims of domestic violence in these surveys.

As per MyNation, when physical violence and threats against men by wife's relatives are taken into account, an estimated 3 crore men are facing domestic violence in India.

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As there is a lot of social stigma towards men abused by women, most of the male victims do not come out in open and do not share their ordeal with family, friends or colleagues. Male victims of domestic violence are ridiculed and considered as unmanly. Such thinking is chauvinistic and is harmful.

Violence on men can range from anything like - physical violence including slapping, pushing, hitting by wife, her parents and her relatives; emotional violence with wife threatening suicide to intimidate and control the husband; verbal abuse if husband remains in contact with his parents or comes home late from work; throwing objects like utensils, mobile phones and crockery at the husband; sexual abuse if husband denies sex to mental abuse by constant threats of implicating the husband and his family under false case of dowry and domestic violence.

Today, many women have serious anger management issues. They also seem to bring the stress of the workplace to the home. This is one of the main reasons of domestic violence against men. The other reasons include intolerance and anger at non-fulfillment of expectations.

Sometimes, inability of husband to meet monetary demands of wife also leads to abuse and violence

Times are changing and there are many men whose wives are more educated than their husbands and earn more. However, the burden of running the house still rests on the man owing to 16th century patriarchal beliefs and this paves the path for abuse of men. Such a law could allow such husbands to seek maintenance from an abusive wife and lead a dignified life free from abuse.

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Male victims of family violence go through low self-esteem and their performance at workplace suffers. Thousands of such men are approaching psychiatrists, who are not of much help, when a law to provide protection to men and restrain the women does not exist.

Most parents of women blame the son-in-law for the breakdown of the marriage, without accepting that their daughter is abusive, or she has serious anger management issues. They somehow think their daughter can never be wrong and expect the son-in-law to tolerate her. They get violent at son-in-law to teach him a lesson or seek revenge. Police rarely accepts any complaints filed by husband about the violence he is suffering, claiming that this is a family issue. They also refuse to provide any protection to the man.

The patriarchal thinking that “Mardko Dard nahi hota” (Men do not feel pain) eulogizes and patronizes emotional castration of boys from a very young age which teaches them to tolerate abuse and feel glorified about making sacrifices. Owing to this social conditioning, a vast majority of victimized men wear a plastic smile and hide their scars and suffer in solitude.

The survey conducted by National Family Health Survey which throws light on unprovoked violence against men by women is evidence in the face. Notwithstanding the fact that double the numbers of men commit suicide compared to women, it should not be a surprise to ask for a law to protect men as such a law for women already exists. In fact, it would be preposterous in this age of gender equality, not to have such a law. Such a law to protect men from domestic violence would act occurs to millions of those men who feel victimized and left out.

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It would also provide them with a legal platform to come forward and share their pain and get some semblance of relief.

These days MEN are becoming victims of domestic violence, abuse against men in the home is on the rise. When we talk about Gender Equality, we shall not forget our age-old culture. When we talk about Women Empowerment, need not to think about disempowerment of men. When we talk about Justice for all, need not to forget that men are a part of all". Indian Men Suicide is rising after marriage, rising and rising anyone can check Crime Bureau Report of India for more detail.

Men can be reluctant to say that they are victims, and they worry that they won't be believed. Constitution of India says "All people of India shall be guaranteed and secured social, economic and political justice; equality of status and opportunities before law; and fundamental freedom." then

WHY Indian men have no Equality in Laws?

WHY Indian Domestic Laws are biased towards men?

WHY It takes 7 Years to get Divorce to men and only 6 months to Indian women?

WHY Indian Fathers are denied to Child Custody, Even Mother is criminal?

WHY Indian men have no Protection Laws?

WHY Men do not get Reservations too?

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When there is no law / Judiciary support, how can a man lead normal happy life... All these facts are a clear indication that Indian husbands are harassed more than Indian women, at home and judicially

“Domestic violence against men in India is not recognized by the law. The general perception is that men cannot be victims of violence. This helps women get away scot-free,” and the judiciary almost always favors the woman. “Domestic violence cases are supposed to be resolved in six months, but this never happens. Once a case is filed, the husband has to attend every hearing — which takes place once every 10 days — otherwise he is viewed as the wrongdoer in the court’s eye. Mind you, there are no questions raised if the woman doesn’t attend hearings.”

Like women, men also find it hard to get out of abusive relationships, but situation is worse for men, as they not only fear being away from their children but are also worried about a false dowry case being filed against them. Men who are accused of domestic violence get marginalized by society and even friends and family turn their backs on them, for men, it is huge emotional battle, one which proved to be too much for a man. If any Man approaches the police after he was assaulted by his wife, and the cops not only ridicule him, sometimes Police even call his wife and ask her to file a case against him. So as to force him to take his own life, when there are no options left for him.

NCRB Statistics

498A

Year	Case	TOTAL	Persons	Conviction
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	Registered	PERSONS Arrested	Acquitted (cases)	Rate
2011	99135	180701	83580	20.6
2012	106527	197762	92867	15.0
2013	118866	222091	97622	15.2
2014	122877	225648	94765	14.0
2015	113403	187067	88203	15.7
2016	110378	198851	82075	10.10
2017	104551	135340	84679	12.19
2018	103272	110789	70171	09.93

DVA

Year	Case Registered	Total Arrest	acquitted	Conviction Rate

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2011	107753	205279	94757	22.8
2012	114760	222180	103113	16.7
2013	126949	245955	108003	16.7
2014	135492	255107	104805	15.7
2015	125558	213835	98899	17.7
2016	9683		18025	
2017	86001			
2018	89097			

Why men suffer in silence

Protect children:

Just like women, men worry that leaving their spouses will harm their children or prevent them from having access to them. Obtaining custody of children is always challenging for fathers, as is the prospect of raising them alone.

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Feel ashamed: Many men feel ashamed at being beaten by a woman or feel that they have failed in their role as a protector and provider for the family.

Fear of false cases:

The biggest fear in Indian men is being slapped with a dowry harassment case. Not only is it hard to shake off the social stigma that comes with being charged with such an act, but the cases also tend to drag on for years and are almost always in the woman's favor.

Parental pressure:

Even today, most men continue to live with their parents even after getting married. When differences arise, parents generally step in and can sometimes make matters worse with their own demands.

Denial:

Just as with female domestic violence victims, denying that there is a problem only prolongs the abuse. Men believe that they can help or change their abuser, but change can only happen once the abuser takes full responsibility for her behavior and seeks professional treatment.

Emotional abuse:

Emotional abuse of men is the same as emotional abuse of women: it is act including verbal assault, that make a person feel less self-worth or dignity. Emotional abuse of men makes them feel like less of a person.

Male victims of emotional abuse may experience partners that:

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- Yell and scream
- Threaten them and try to induce fear
- Insult and demean them; tell them they are not worth the trouble
- Socially isolate them
- Lie or withhold information
- Treat them like a child or servant
- Control all the finances

Some believe that men are more sensitive to emotional abuse than woman and can "brush off" physical abuse more easily. Male victims of emotional abuse who are called a "coward," "impotent," or a "failure," maybe more affected by these remarks than their female counterparts.

Controlling and emotionally abusive behaviors elicited by women may include:

- Falsely accusing or threatening to accuse a man of assault on them or their children
- Threatening to take away custody of the children
- Threatening to kill themselves or others
- Making the man feel like "he's crazy"
- Minimizing the abuse; blaming the victim of the abuse
- Playing mind games
- Making the man feel guilty
- Falsely obtaining a restraining order
- Withholding affection
- Stalking

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Like women, many men stay in emotionally abusive relationships. This can be for many reasons but certainly in part due to the toll that emotional abuse can take on a man's self-worth. He may not believe he is worthy enough to leave the relationship or he may believe he deserves the emotional abuse.

Men may also stay in emotionally abusive relationships because:

- Of threats made by their abuser
- To protect the children
- They feel dependent on the abuser

Reproductive rights of man

"Reproductive rights" are the rights of individuals to decide whether to reproduce and have reproductive health. This may include an individual's right to plan a family, terminate a pregnancy, use contraceptives, learn about sex education in public schools, and gain access to reproductive health services.

Historically, in India people do not publicly discuss about the reproductive rights due to the moral, ethical, and religious undertones of birth control, abortion, and family planning. Today, the subject of reproductive rights continues to be an emotionally and politically charged issue, especially in light of new technologies and recent laws.

The Indian Constitution does not explicitly mention a right to reproduce, however, the Supreme Court has recognized it as a personal right that is deemed "fundamental".

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Do Men Have Reproductive Rights?

While reproductive rights have been legally recognized as a woman's right - especially in matters involving abortion, adoption, and procreation - men's reproductive rights have been less certain.

Constitutionally, laws must only guarantee that men and women are treated the same if they are "similarly situated" - which they are not in matters of reproduction.

Abortion is the single most controversial issue involving Reproductive Rights. The issue turns on whether a woman should have the "right" to terminate a pregnancy that would amount to a living human being if remained untouched without her partner consent.

Indian court decided that the abortion falls within a person's constitutional right to privacy, believing the choice to terminate an "unborn fetus" lies with the individual and her doctor. Hence, a man does not have rights to decide whether his wife can abort a child or not.

The World Health Organization defines reproductive rights as “rest[ing] on the recognition of the basic right of all couples and individuals to decide freely and responsibly the number, spacing, and timing of their children and to have the information and means to do so, and the right to attain the highest standard of sexual and reproductive health. They also include the right of all to make decisions concerning reproduction free of discrimination, coercion, and violence.

Women are also under no legal requirement to identify the father of their child and if the father is not listed on the birth certificate, he has no legal rights at all. Certainly, men can

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pursue legal rights by establishing paternity, but it is up to men to enforce their rights. Women can, and do, surrender infants for adoption without notifying or identifying the father of the child. These are very high-risk adoptions for the adopting couple, because there is always a chance the father will appear and attempt to assert his rights, but the fact remains that women can, once again, relieve themselves of all social, legal, financial and moral responsibility for a child they do not want.

The WHO says reproductive rights require that no person be coerced into parenthood, meaning that men do not have reproductive rights, as long as that coercion exists.

Worst is not over for Indian single man:

Adoption: Single women and men are allowed to adopt but single men can only adopt boys. Adoption agencies harbor biases against single people specially for man. In 2015, the Ministry of Women and Child Development issued the Central Adoption Resource Agency (CARA) Guideline which permits a single woman to adopt a kid of any gender. The Juvenile Justice Act does not lawfully prescribe a single male to adopt a female child. Single men and live-in couples will soon not be able to adopt in India.

The Ministry of Women and Child Development is set to notify a new set of guidelines for adoption, which are far stricter about couples who are not married, and single men.

They also specify the age at which married couples and single women can adopt.

Surrogacy: In August 2016, the Union Cabinet passed a bill banning single men, women, and gay couples from opting for surrogacy. As per the new bill, surrogacy for foreigners and persons of Indian origin is also banned in the country. Commercial surrogacy (paying

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someone to be a surrogate) is prohibited; only blood relatives between the age of 25 to 35 years can now become a surrogate. Also, the woman opting to become a surrogate mother should be married and with a child of her own.

The Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill, 2019: The surrogacy bill prevents single parents, same-sex couples, divorced or widowed persons, transgender persons, live-in partners and foreign nationals from using a surrogate mother.

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These are media coverage of men murdered in the hands of their wives. This is just a tip of the iceberg as very few news media dare to publish, there are 100 times more such cases which are not covered or termed as suicide/accidental deaths or if women kill that termed as she killed in her defense.

MyNation dare to challenge any Women organization, if they can produce such murder reports committed by men and killed their wives.

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Conclusion

As long as Indian government is under control of Feminists lobby, there will be no law for men, nor will they get any relief. It is assumed men are always the abuser and women are always the victim this common misconception should change but that's impossible dream as long as there is no option for men to complain/report of their domestic abuse.

Recommendation:

Need of ministry for men and gender-neutral laws.

Testimonials:

(In victims' own words – no any change or even spell check)

1) **Dr. Bharat Bhushan:** Emotional violence, not an uncommon Story:

My dentist wife left no stone unturned to harass me mentally every day when she compared my house to her native and went on to say that she was raised as princess by her parents where her every demand was met, never did household works and preferred to keep her earnings to herself without contributing anything to the family. She was often

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reluctant to mingle with my parents and family and refused to stay in my native with my parents but wanted every financial decision of the family to be taken under her behest. Me and my parents were ridiculed for no reason whenever her lavish demands were not met. We failed to acknowledge her attitude as she was new to our place and we felt that it was just a casual misunderstanding between the newly married couple.

Further, her verbal abuse, constant criticism, intimidation, refusing to listen, refusing to communicate, blaming, shaming, refusal to ever be pleased and constant interference from her family members left our whole family in pain. This went on for more than a year and whole family was literally broken. Finally, my wife left me without any reason, filed false cases of domestic violence on my family and now demanding money to withdraw cases. The emotional violence she has committed on me in particular and my family as a whole has left us in cross roads.

I was surprised to get support from my neighborhood as they were aware of abusive and rude nature of my wife but police refused to take any action as the law has tied their hands to act against abusive women even though she is a culprit. Furthermore, being a well-qualified dentist, she is demanding maintenance from me and it was very surprising that she hid her qualification details from court of law under the guidance of her lawyer brother. Knowingly or unknowingly some lawyers and police are often encouraging the emotional violence in the form of fake cases to extort money like this as they are very well aware of lack of law to punish false accuser.

In this context, it is very much needed to address the issue of all forms of domestic violence on men who are suffering due to lack of law on domestic violence on men by the spouse and punishment to false accusers.

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2) **Vardharajan A:** Fake case which runs for years, all our hard-earned money is going into the pockets of lawyer's and government bodies who least bother to protect us. Each case which is not closed with mutual consent minimum runs for 5 years.

No one can compensate the father's pain during this journey. Our health, time, hard earned money and parents' happiness is completely ruined by this feminist mafia.

Above all our children are forced to get alienated from their beloved ones which put their future in deep trouble.

3) **Ankit Kulshrestha:** While victims of domestic violence men too face abuse in their house however the law doesn't treat them as victims, when men try to register their complaint or narrate problem or harassment within marriage to police station no one listen to them.

Sometime he continues to stay in violent relationship due to many reasons like love towards children, fear of societal blame but it is equally important to understand consequence of such act on his health. In most of the cases against male his wife uses more mental verbal emotional violence rather than physical

4) **Vivek Kumar:** On upcoming generation citing scar on young minds when their mothers, grandparents live in the terror of such litigations. Also, about how state doesn't want to discuss or take steps towards equality and follows bad prudence from other counties like divorce laws in property. One side it takes steps like decriminalizing adultery and then other side doesn't put a cap on maintenance for short-lived marriages and extorts husbands for lifetime.

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5) **Vikrant Banode**: Fed up of wife's emotional, mental and financial harassment, husband thinks of committing suicide; saved by his family and friends, files a divorce. Wife and in-laws in with huge financial approaches supreme court and get the case transferred to another State.

Wife later files a fake Domestic Violence case along with a false rent agreement. At the time of her submission of evidence and cross examination in both cases, wife and in-laws heads towards compromise of issues.

After joining back to matrimonial life, wife starts the same thing. She makes a false complaint to human rights and Police.

So there seems no change in women and all our hard-earned money is going into the pockets of lawyer's and government bodies who least bother to protect us. Our health, time, hard earned money and family happiness get completely ruined. Children are getting alienated.

This is a gross misuse of laws and a personality disorder that seems growing day by day and our government rather to dilute the issues are making more and more stricter, gender biased laws, resulting in family breakages.

6) **Sharan Shetty**: Most of these gender biased marital cases are only done to terrorize men and their family so u bow down to the demands ,love was never there and no questions about it the only person to blame for the whole scenario is a fake women (wife/ gf) who have made all the women even the real ones suffer, Now why is a general educated middle class man targeted it's just because he has lot to lose(career, time, money and Respect) not to forget the agony of his family which consists of women too,

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Transparency accountability, justice are not common daily words but I have seen none of them in the police and then in judiciary , when just with a blink of eye you can separate the truth from the rest but still you are just provided dates which just add salts to your wounds. I am a professional engineer travelled and worked around the world and now I am trapped in a mythical cage with nil presence in modern world or maybe some greed of my ancestors were in they did not act quickly to abolish the root cause this punishment is just because I did not settle the matter with all the concerned parties, The key everybody suggest for this door is how much amount you can shelve, the door will open quicker only when your key is bigger, I choose to fight my way through so I can feel better.

7) **Shriram Yadav**: Soon after few days of marriage, wife started creating issues of trifle things. Wife bid husband for abortion; when made understand, exclaimed and refused by husband, wife along her parents tried to create a scene and deserted the husband. Even then the husband carried out his duty and tried for reconciliation, but in vein. Wife tried to humiliate and defame husband in the society.

These are modern women and their ego of being in power, as the Gender biased laws are in their favor. They enter and keep on ruining a man's life and Indian government supports them.

8) **Amit Nishania**: After 18 months of marriage my wife left home and after many requests from my side, I failed to make her stay together. Later she demanded divorce for no reason and demanded a hefty amount with share in my father's property. I accepted the divorce call but was not willing to give anything as she failed to state any reason for divorce. Later almost after 1 year of separation she filed FIR against me and my family with a DV case in addition, demanding Rs 10 lakhs as compensation and Rs 20,000 per

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month as maintenance. With the help of group and continuous study of law and case study I was able to make her understand by my reply against petition that she will gain nothing. They approached many times for mutual divorce but after 1 year of case filed, I accepted their proposal and choose to move ahead in life. Within 18 months of case filed I am free from my cruel wife. But I know I need to fight against this cruel and biased law, so will continue my fight.

9) **Aman Kumar**: Due to a near fatal bike accident in 2003, I am partially paralyzed (60%) from last 17-years and at present working with bank since 2014.

Got married in June 2016.

Initially She agreed to live with me and mine aged parents, however, soon within 20 days of marriage, she left her matrimonial home.

Together we have a 3-year-old baby girl.

Our relationship was on and off, she returned again in September 2017 after daughter's birth.

She left home once again in March 2018 and filed a case of dowry harassment and domestic violence against me and my complete family.

Her main demand was that I should separate from my mother, moves into a separate home and also, she must get a share in my mother's property. I was physically assaulted too.

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I have to fight up to Supreme court, finally divorce was granted and the custody of the daughter remained with wife with visitation rights, but she never honored this

10) **Ramesh Thatiseti**: An arranged marriage where you say YES in few days of first meeting and keep taking it further in hope of better days, even though u get to know you are cheated in few weeks.

They deceived us by showing as a respectable family. There is no dowry and is even admitted by them in first complaint.

They are dominating every decision even before marriage and we never thought it is an issue.

She always finds fault in everything. She literally doesn't know how to treat any person.

Forget about she doing even a bit of house hold works, it would be a great day if she did not find any fault in my cooking, cleaning, serving her and her needs of shopping, roaming outside and what not.

And soon, it turned out to be shouting, warning and criminal intimidations on me and family if her expectations are not met.

They frequently intimidated saying like they are known Rowdy Sheetters and can knock off anyone.

No one could help me, instead warned to be careful with them as they are dangerous rowdies.

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I tried to get help from courts but for them mine is an interesting story and only suggestion is to pay them and get rid of them.

I am not allowed to meet my son, even on his first birthday they allowed just 10 minutes to be with him and then took him away.

They filed multiple cases, corrupted police and put absolutely fake allegations.

Dragged all my family into cases, even when they have not met her for years.

DV is a very small word for the pain, I am going through. I am directly warned to be killed.

Her father is a criminal, now that they decided to break the marriage, they want to go extreme ways.

Unfortunately, many complaints on them have fallen to deaf ears. I get the complaint copy stamped and all that is it.

NO LAW for MEN. I can't fight those criminals. They corrupted every department and section.

11) **Niraj Upadhyay**: The women in India can invoke and abuse the one-sided legal provisions in the name of domestic violence or 498A or CrPC 125 and ask for huge compensation. No matter married for 3 months or 3 years or 30 years. They control and brainwash the kids while the breadwinner is slogging in office for livelihood. Only rights and no obligations. It is a loose situation for men emotionally, physically and financially. Worst is when you are treated as ATM machine for your kids being biological father

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means nothing. Aakhir Mard Ko Dard nahi hota is the spirit in which Indian Laws operate. She can destroy his life, family and everything at any point just at the drop of hat. I am facing an extortion game planned by my wife and her parents using my 12-year-old kid as blackmailing tool to fund her luxurious desires and old age pension account for her cunning parents. Lost my mother and physically ailing father with brain stroke and myself suffering a stroke. Denial of access to child till ransom is paid. Law book says something but legal system interprets it feminist way. But wait I am there to take up the challenge and it is a fight for existence as have nothing to lose now. Beware of me.

12) **Sandeep Kumar Nath:** My marriage was solemnized in 2010. After the 4th day of marriage my wife started make quarrel in home and stated to humiliate my parents and other family member. She doesn't try to do household chores and always stayed in her room. She always used to harass us and tried to torture on the name of fake case. She always warned us either my father's transfer property on her name or she will file fake case on our family because her uncle is in police. In February 2011 a girl baby born and we take care for her as per we can but she never changed her behave.

Then my father disowned me and arrange a rental accommodation for me and my wife.

On rental accommodation she lives near about 11 months and she always started quarrel in rental home also.

Once day in January 2013 when I went to shop, I got a call from police and they tell me your wife give a complaint and now you come to police station. When I went there, they handcuffed me on the name of fake harassment. Then she made a fake agreement there that she didn't want to pursue complaint.

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After that she made 3 to 4 bogus complaints but never came back.

after many requests from my side I failed to make her stay together. Then she filed fake 498A, domestic violence and other cases.

After 4 years of mentally harassment to me and my family the honorable court dismissed her petition and clearly write in his judgment that the case filed by the wife is clearly a case to harass in-laws and relative.

Court clearly says it is the misuse of the law and process. But I know I need to fight against this cruel and biased law, so will continue my fight.

13) **Prasad Challapalli**: She left my house within 16 days in between she stays in my home only 6 days and demanding Rs 30 lakhs, she gave nothing and Marriage also performed by us, after one year she filed false 498A package on 12 members of my family and relatives now I am fighting for divorce without any alimony.

14) **Rajendra Sharma**: I was working in a reputed MNC. Got married in year 2013. Marriage was done without any dowry item exchange. However, my family gifted lot of jewelry to my wife. Just after few days of marriage we get to know she had major medical condition and she is a psychic girl. Her treatment was done at various hospital prior to marriage, she came to my house with full of medicines. She was unfit for the marriage, she was unable to handle household, unable to produce child. She and her family hide all these facts from us. When I and my family get to know it, she and her parents started threatening us of killing and fake cases. Soon she left my house on her own. She started abusing and blackmailing me and my family on phone. Soon she gave

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complain for dowry harassment at her hometown. Police started harassing us on the name of settlement. Soon fake dowry case was filed on me and my innocent family.

We hired a lawyer, but these lawyers are big dacoits, for any such matrimonial issue lawyer are big villain. Such girls, police, lawyers, court are blood sucker of innocent men.

As men has no law to save himself, I was also helpless. I and my family went to depression, money problem, emotional problem.

She is PhD still she is unable to maintain herself, however she was earning before marriage.

On the name of taking cases back she is asking 50 lacs as alimony.

Such harassment can only be stopped when all the laws will be made gender neutral and there is strict punishment for fake cases. Accountability of judges and police are also important, if they file fake cases and run them in court then they should also be sent to jail. By shutting down all the women NGO and their loot, they motivate women to break their marriage. No lawyer should be allowed during matrimonial case. Alimony should be illegal as dowry. Social boycott of such family who files fake cases.

15) **Ramu G:** Even though my wife and her family knew that she is suffering from Epilepsy disease and other medical issues, they concealed it intentionally before our marriage. When I came to know about her Epilepsy disease just 2 weeks after our marriage, my parents then advised that as the marriage is already completed, it was our responsibility to take care of her and provide her further medical treatment. My wife

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frequently had epileptic attacks approx. every 1 or 2 months and I used to take her to that same doctor, who was treating her initially. While Me and my family always treated my wife with due care and provided her complete medical care due to her medical condition, my wife started ill-treating my Parents and other family members when they visited us. I have silently observed all her ill and cruel behavior towards me and my family right since our marriage and one day when I questioned her the same, she was very rude with me and even threatened me that she will reach Police authorities with complaints. Citing health reasons, she left my home within 6 months of our marriage and lodged a false dowry complaint on me and my entire family who were living separately. My wife started demanding a huge amount of Rs 30 Lakhs in the name of settlement with an intention to extort money from me. Due to these false cases, my and our family members are subjected to intolerable mental agony, financial burden and stress driving entire family into depression and health issues. Me and my family became a scapegoat for NO FAULT OF US. As I showed my helplessness to pay that huge amount, Police have registered the FIR and even opened a Charge Sheet on my entire family without even any verifications and I'm currently attending court with a hope that I would get justice.

16) **Abhishek Sharma**: Within first 15 days of my marriage, my wife separated us from my parents by regular quarrelling with us ,refusing to do any work, spreading lies in my ears against my parents, using foul language against me and my parents, calling her divorced mother/ relatives to accompany her to quarrel and do as she says or threaten us that they will injure us and separate us from my parents. After separation from my parents she along with her mother and relatives harassed me by quarrelling with me every day in groups that I bring money, FD and part of my property from my parents and they will help me by hook or crook. She Kept all her and mine things and threw me out of the

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house in association with her mother. it seemed like she was very well prepared by her divorced mother. My parents got us a rented furnished accommodation where she first refused to stay with me, then came only to quarrel with me daily, create situations for fight, threatening me for calling police to make me fear her by saying u r harassing me, beating me, not letting me sleep by disturbing me , hiding my things like car keys, spec, phone etc., coming to my office and start creating situations by crying etc. Disturbing me and colleagues. Tried harassing me in every possible way. left house at times for hours without telling, throwing kitchen items on floor, sent false complaints to my office.

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Chapter 3:

Section 498B IPC – A Much Needed Reform

Spouse or Relative of Spouse of a Husband Subjecting Him to Cruelty

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False cases, abuse, Domestic violence and harassment against men by their spouse and family members has become an important issue in today's generation and judiciary called it **LEGAL TERRORISM**. But because of feminist lobby and National commission of women (NCW) or WCD strong opposition to make it gender neutral, men still face threats in their everyday life.

Most of the cases of abuse and threats go unreported so it is difficult to get exact number on fake cases and threats and it is even more difficult to figure out that how many men are suffering from abuse, fake cases threat of or domestic violence.

The main reason that most of the abuse, fake cases against the men are unreported, because Indian society think men cannot be victims in the hands of women and the traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness, shame to admit or confess of falling victim to a woman.

There is no study on men, nor Government of India made any efforts evaluate psychological / mental trauma on men because of such abuse and violence. So, we from MyNation foundation came up with amendment to INDIAN PENAL CODE (IPC) SECTION 498B A MUCH-NEEDED REFORM.

Section 498B. Wife/Partner/Live-in, here after called spouse or relative of Spouse of a man subjecting him to cruelty

1.[498B. Spouse or relative of Spouse of a husband subjecting him to cruelty. — Whoever, being the spouse or the relative of the spouse of a man, subjects such man to cruelty shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years and shall also be liable to fine.

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Explanation

For the purpose of this section, “cruelty” means —

(a) any willful conduct which is of such a nature as is likely to drive the man to commit suicide or to cause grave injury or danger to life, limb or health (whether mental or physical) of the man; or

(b) harassment of the man where such harassment is with a view to coercing him or any person related to him to meet any unlawful demand for any property, Alimony, Maintenance or valuable security or is on account of failure by him or any person related to him to meet such demand.

Classification of Offence

Punishment — Imprisonment for 3 years and fine-Cognizable if information relating to the commission of the offence is given to an officer in charge of a police station by the person aggrieved by the offence or by any person related to him by blood, marriage or adoption or if there is no such relative, by any public servant belonging to such class or category as may be notified by the State Government in this behalf

—Non-bailable—Triable by Magistrate of the first class

—Non-compoundable.

Comments

Demand for Money/assets and Ill-treatment

(I) The man petitioned for divorce on the ground of persistent demand made on him by his spouse and in-laws. The High Court took the view that there was nothing wrong in

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these demands as money was needed by the man, not for his personal use but to run the home and in such a case wife should extend help.

(ii) The spouse and her parents were greedy people. Their desire for money and valuable was insatiable. They went on demanding money, transfer assets/Property or handover salary even just after of marriage, and since the man could not meet these, they started ill-treating him with a view to coercing him to give money or salary.

Adultery/Extra marital Affair

Adultery is no longer punishable offence in India, and is almost a cult in certain societies. Yet, even here as elsewhere a habit of adultery is a vice and cannot be considered a reasonable wear and tear of married life. No reasonable person marries to bargain to endure habitual extra marital affair, a disgusting conduct. And yet it is not an independent ground of any matrimonial relief in India. But it may constitute treatment with cruelty, if indulged in by a spouse and continued, in spite of remonstrance's, by the other. It may cause great anguish, harassment and distress to the man who never suspected what he was bargaining for and may sooner or later find living together not only miserable but unbearable. If it was so, she may leave him and may, apart from cruelty, even complain of constructive desertion.

Object

Section 498B was added with a view to punishing spouse and her relatives who harass or torture the man to coerce him or his relatives to satisfy unlawful demands of money. The hyper-technical view would be counterproductive and would act against interests of man and against the object for which the provision was added. There is every likelihood that

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non-exercise of inherent power to quash the proceedings to meet the ends of justice would prevent man from settling earlier.

Section 498B vis-a-vis section 113 of Evidence Act

Section 498B of the Indian Penal Code or section 113A of the Indian Evidence Act has not introduced invidious classification qua the treatment of a married man by his spouse or relatives of his spouse vis-a-vis the other offenders. On the other hand, such women form a class apart from those who are married more than seven years earlier to the commission of such offence, because, with the passage of time after marriage and birth of children, there are remote chances of treating a married man with cruelty by his spouse or her relatives. Thus, the classification is reasonable and has close nexus with the object sought to be achieved, i.e., eradication of the evil of alimony in the Indian social set-up and to ensure that the married men live with dignity at their own homes;

Unhappiness between husband and wife

Where the prosecution relied only on incident of unhappiness of deceased with his spouse and the allegation was only in form of suggestion, it does not establish criminal offence under either or both of the charges, hence conviction under section 498B is improper;

Willful Conduct

The allegations against the spouse were that he abused and beat his wife, forced him to move to her family home as Ghar jamai or forcing him to take care of her parents, accused him of adultery and impregnate someone else, threats of suicide or take away children, threats of false case or false accusations and such other acts. This amounted to a willful conduct of cruelty towards man;

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Chapter 4:

Violence Against Men False Accusation of Sexual Harassment

The Monstrous Pandemic Is Here: Are We Ready?

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What is Sexual harassment?

- Unwelcomed Behavior of verbal or physical sexual advances, pressure/requests for sexual favors, conduct of a sexual in nature like making signs, sounds, jokes or comments. Make unwelcomed sexual looks or gestures, deliberately touching, leaning over, cornering, hugging, kissing, patting, stroking or pinching. Making phone calls, sending messages or contents is comes under sexual harassment.
- But as per UN a world body (Ref: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/pdf/whatissh.pdf>) it applies only to women, and terming only women can be victim and men are always perpetrator. Sexual assault can happen to anyone, and not only on women, men are also assaulted not only by men but women too no matter your age, sexual orientation, or gender identity. Men and boys who have been sexually assaulted or abused may have many of the same feelings and reactions as other women survivors of sexual assault, but they may also face some additional challenges because of legal aspects, society, social attitudes and stereotypes about men and masculinity.
- False case of raping daughter filed by mother against father quashed.
- Brother-in-law falsely accused of raping daughter to settle property dispute.
- Father acquitted in false rape case filed by minor daughter.

Such stories are now available at the click of the mouse, from almost every corner of India. False cases of rape, sexual assault, sexual harassment and sexual abuse are a dark reality of the Indian society that devastates the falsely accused man's soul, shatters his self-respect and for many, purges the hope to live. No wonder male suicide rates for

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entire India is 14.3 per 100,000 population¹. As compared to females, the value ranges up to 3.5 times for men.

Table 27: Suicide incidence rate (per 100,000 population) across NMHS* states

	AS	CG	GJ	JH	KL	MP	MN	PB	RJ	TN	UP	WB	India
Total	11.1	22.4	11.7	4.0	23.9	11.9	2.0	3.3	6.3	23.4	1.7	15.5	10.6
Gender													
Male	15.8	29.3	14.6	5.3	40.0	14.2	2.2	4.6	9.1	30.3	2.0	19.0	14.3
Female	6.8	15.1	9.1	2.6	11.7	10.6	1.3	1.8	3.7	14.3	1.6	12.2	7.2

*NMHS: National Mental Health Survey, carried out by National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences (NIMHANS)

Not long back, a man would return back home from work happily to find solace in his family i.e. wife, children, relatives, neighbors. However, rapid social development, unchecked and blatant misuse of gender-specific laws (as opposed to gender-neutral laws in advanced nations), easy access to luxury, competition for money etc. are some factors that might have facilitated the slow unnoticed change of society with such high rate of suicides, one to which we might have already seem to have come to terms with.

¹ National Mental Health Survey, 2015-16, pg. 93 <http://indianmhs.nimhans.ac.in/Docs/Report2.pdf>

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Why women file case cases with police and courts?

- (1) The lust for money;
- (2) The lust for ego protection/ satisfaction;
- (3) The lust for sex; and
- (4) Hatred of men

The above can be abbreviated as MESH which also means “the web”. The existing mechanisms of the executive, police and the judiciary offer not much support and hope.

No wonder, the family has become the most unsafe place for a man. The problem is still unrecognized, and a common man has become even more vulnerable, with existing vulnerability to mortality due to communicable diseases, non-communicable diseases, and mental health conditions has been topped with high incidence of suicides among men.

As per Section 209 of the Indian Penal Code, “Whoever fraudulently or dishonestly, or with intent to injure or annoy any person, makes in a Court of Justice any claim which he knows to be false, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to two years, and shall also be liable to fine”. The essential ingredients of an offence under Section 209 are:

1. The accused made a claim;
2. The claim was made in a Court of Justice;
3. The claim was false, either wholly or in part;

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4. That the accused knew that the claim was false; and
5. The claim was made fraudulently, dishonestly, or with intent to injure or to annoy any person.

Despite all the ingredients of Section 209, the victims of such false and fraudulent cases are either not aware or are so shaken that they don't file prosecution. In some cases where he does have the courage and the money left, the system ensures that he leaves the battle in between. Rarely does a man fight to the finish, but there have been convictions, including in the false allegations against former Chief Justice of India Mr. Ranjan Gogoi.

The Consequences

- Physical, mental, psychological, social and economic health of the victim is severely affected
- Job loss, loss to business in these competitive times
- Our media editorials rarely highlight the plight of such victims.
- False propaganda leading to loss of social status and support
- Though society recognizes the need for social support for female victims of abuse, there is almost nil support for the male victims of abuse.

The Way Forward

1. Social recognition of the problem of male abuse through false cases
2. Community awareness programs

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3. Funding of NGOs willing to support such victims
4. Special funding from government to help them rise to their feet
5. Free legal services (or to be borne by the party filing false cases when proved) in all cases proved to be false as this is a crime against the state and the victim is merely helping the state in restoring the trust in its justice system
6. Academic institutions to introduce this as a research topic in law, social sciences and humanities.
7. Central Board of Secondary Education should introduce this as a chapter in social science textbooks for students' awareness, debate and understanding of the ill-effects on the society.
8. Promote research by academic institutions on 'False Cases' to ascertain reasons, conduct investigations, and find solutions

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Chapter 5:

NCW Exposed – Promoting Legal Terrorism

(NCW An Agent of WCD)

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NCW:

The National Commission for Women was set up as statutory body in January 1992 under the National Commission for Women Act, 1990 (Act No. 20 of 1990 of Govt of India) to:

Review the Constitutional and Legal safeguards for women;

Recommend remedial legislative measures;

Facilitate redressal of grievances and

Advise the Government on all policy matters affecting women.

TOTAL BUDGET OF 2020: 29664.90 Crore Rupees.

I. महिला और बाल विकास मंत्रालय के संबंध में 31 मार्च, 2020 को समाप्त होने वाले वर्ष में व्यय के लिये आवश्यक धनराशि का अनुमान।

I. Estimates of the amount required in the year ending 31st March, 2020, to defray charges in respect of **MINISTRY OF WOMEN AND CHILD DEVELOPMENT**

	राजस्व Revenue	पूंजी Capital	जोड़ Total	(₹ करोड़) (In ₹ crores)
भारित Charged :	
स्वीकृत Voted :	29664.89	0.01	29664.90	

II. शीर्ष जिनके अन्तर्गत महिला और बाल विकास मंत्रालय की ओर से इस अनुदान का हिसाब दिखाया जाएगा।

II. The Heads under which this Grant will be accounted for on behalf of the **MINISTRY OF WOMEN AND CHILD DEVELOPMENT**

मुख्य शीर्ष Major Head	वास्तविक 2017-2018 Actuals	बजट अनुमान 2018-2019 Budget Estimates	संशोधित अनुमान 2018-2019 Revised Estimates	बजट अनुमान 2019-2020 Budget Estimates
राजस्व भाग REVENUE SECTION				
सचिवालय-सामाजिक सेवाएं Secretariat-Social Services	2251	42.83	43.62	44.42
सामाजिक सुरक्षा और कल्याण Social Security and Welfare	2235	3187.89	3998.89	2797.54
पोषाहार Nutrition	2236	12.12	14.00	13.20
पूर्वोत्तर क्षेत्र North Eastern Areas	2552	...	2445.39	2451.27
राज्य सरकारों को सहायता अनुदान Grants-in-aid to State Governments	3601	17116.29	18355.96	19635.32
संघ राज्य क्षेत्र की सरकारों को सहायता अनुदान Grants-in-aid to Union Territory Governments	3602	148.21	342.33	271.74
जोड़ - राजस्व भाग Total-Revenue Section		20507.14	25199.99	25213.49
पूंजी भाग CAPITAL SECTION				
सामाजिक सुरक्षा और कल्याण पर पूंजी परिव्यय Capital Outlay on Social Security and Welfare	4235	13.31	0.01	45.13
जोड़ - पूंजी भाग Total-Capital Section		13.31	0.01	45.13
कुल जोड़ GRAND TOTAL		20520.45	25200.00	25258.62

(टिप्पणी: उपरोक्त अनुमानों में नीचे दिखाई गई वस्तुसिध शामिल नहीं हैं, किन्तु व्यय में से घटा कर अंतरों में समावेशित कर दिया जाता है।)

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Question is what WCD/NCW do with 29664.89 Crore Money?

Few years back former union minister for women and child development Maneka Gandhi said that the role of men in gender sensitization was critical since "**All the violence is male-generated**".

News Source : <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india/all-violence-is-male-generated-maneka-gandhi/story-QzbDLrEhuCO5Rjst9KD4O.html>

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This shows hatred towards men, WCD/NCW has no policy to make any home happy home, instead they promote domestic Violence. There is not a single event NCW promoted make a marriage successful. Instead minister spit venom calling men as All violence is generated by Men.

Real Face of WCD/NCW

WCD/NCW always claim 498A IPC or PWDVA is not misused when now and then someone raise this issue if so;

why do they not allow camera and CCTV in mediation centers and women's police stations where they force men to agree to women demand?

Why they oppose Punishment for filling False 498A IPC or PWDVA and innocent men and his family acquitted?

In 2015 when Indian government planning to Amend dowry law (IPC 498A) WCD/NCW along with senior Supreme Court lawyer Indira Jaising strongly opposed, terming Women need freehand to misuse the law.

The Law Commission recommended that the offence under Section 498A should be made a compoundable offence with the permission of Court.

Justice Malimath Committee on Criminal Justice Reform also recommended that it should be made compoundable as well as bailable.

Last year, the Home Ministry had asked all state governments to be judicious in slapping Section 498A of IPC in matrimonial disputes as the provision may be used as "weapons rather than shields by disgruntled wives".

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Opposing the move to dilute the anti-dowry provision of the law, senior Supreme Court lawyer Indira Jaising said it is a law which gives relief and protection to harassed woman and it should be continued.

"Violence against women is a violation of human rights. There is no compromise of that. I would disagree with the government move," says Jaising

News Source : <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/government-plans-to-amend-anti-dowry-harassment-law/articleshow/46571163.cms>

In 2017, Supreme Court judgment on Sec 498A (Rajesh Sharma and Ors. Vs State of UP and Anr., Crl. Appeal. No. 1265/2017) and the Minister of Women and Child Development Maneka Gandhi's order on setting up windows for men who allege that false cases have been filed against them., it was eyewash to media and world and WCD/NCW never heard any complaint from men.

Many women organizations who mint money by providing false statistics to WCD/NCW to get financial support opposed to dilution of 498A, The petitioners said women's organizations and others who work on the ground with women survivors of violence, such as the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Swayam, Shramajibi Mahila Samiti and Vimochana, said "Judicial decisions regarding women's right to a life of dignity and free of violence, both physical and mental, in the matrimonial home, cannot be premised on hearsay, and anecdotes echoing embedded prejudice," they said, urging the authorities to take all necessary steps to ensure that women's access to justice is not diluted or obstructed.

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In her response, Lalitha Kumaramangalam, Chairperson, NCW, said “it is necessary to delink the emotional issues being raised on misuse of Section 498A and argue for its effective use on purely legal logic and rationale,” said a release issued by rights organizations.

So, WCD/NCW not only call All men are violent but oppose punishment for misusers of law 498A IPC or PWDVA, they not only protecting women who misuse law but Promote **LEGAL TERRORISM** also.

Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 with the intention of protecting wives from marital violence (cruelty to married women), abuse and extortionist dowry demands, but this law is drafted so cunningly, that many Girl families gives money as stridhan, it's another word for dowry to keep girl side safe from section 3 of Dowry Prohibition Act, but marriage turn soar same stridhan they term it as dowry and man demanded it, and the history of this law not a single Women is charged under DP3 so far.

Not only woman is protected under DP3 but force accused man to prove all baseless allegation on him. All this was done in accordance with 91st Report of the Law Commission of India (1983) on ‘Dowry Deaths and Law Reform; Amending the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 the Indian Penal Code, 1860 and the Indian evidence Act, 1872’41, and 185th Report of the Law Commission of India (March 2003) on Review of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872. Even in this case, where a person is prosecuted for taking or abetting dowry or for demanding dowry, the burden of proof was placed solely on the accused.

Why WCD/NCW oppose dilution of 498A IPC or PWDVA or punishment for misusing because they show the FIR figure to get Funds from the Government. It's a bread and

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butter for them, if 498A IPC or PWDVA diluted and ask women to prove her all false allegation and if found false if she punished, total Fir count will be reduced.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate - merely 12.1 per cent - among all cases of crimes against women.

According to the latest data on crimes, released by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), more than 3.3 lakhs cases of crimes against women were registered in 2016. Of these, 1.1 lakhs cases related to 'Cruelty by husband or his relatives'.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate - merely 12.1 per cent - among all cases of crimes against women.

“Assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty”, kidnapping, and rape, which formed the next three major chunks of crimes against women, had conviction rates of 21.8%, 21.4% and 25.5% in 2016, according to NCRB.

Close to 10,000 cases were also registered under the Dowry Prohibition Act in 2016, but conviction rate here too was just over 15%.

(News source: <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/section-498a-dowry-most-firs-least-convictions-4969913/>)

NCRB data shows 85% Dowry Prohibition Act are fake but WCD/NCW nowhere shows how many cases men are acquitted. They only show how many complaints are filed. **Now You Know Why WCD/NCW Oppose Dilution of These Laws.**

Not only WCD/NCW promote Legal terrorism, oppose dilution of these laws,

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Women ministry also claim "Many women sufferings abuse want to go to their mother's house, but during the lockdown, they can only be sent to state-run shelter homes, where the risk of overcrowding and poor hygiene runs high."

When WCD/NCW has **29664.90 Crores Rupees** of yearly funding why these shelter homes are unhygienic?

(News source: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/04/locked-abusers-india-domestic-violence-surge-200415092014621.html>)

Elderly Women is not coming under WCD Mandate

If any anyone want to test our claim, can call them for help, if a woman really harassed and if she calls for help, that help never arrive. If she is an elderly then not at all. Here is proof of our claim.

This is a letter from WCD/NCW says elderly women is not coming under their mandate.

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भारत सरकार
GOVERNMENT OF INDIA
राष्ट्रीय महिला आयोग
NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR WOMEN
4. दीन दयाल उपाध्याय मार्ग
4, DEEN DAYAL UPADHYAYA MARG
नई दिल्ली-110 002
NEW DELHI-110 002
Website : www.ncw.nic.in

LETTER

CASE NO. 8/C0500721/VI/MSH/NEW/2006

DATED - February 03, 2007

The complaint filed by Mrs. [REDACTED]

To,

Address - Post Box No.
Karkala Post, Udupi,
District Udupi, Karnataka - 574104.

Dear Madam/Sir,

I am directed to refer to your complaint which was placed before the Commission.

Thereafter, upon perusing the complaint, the Commission has passed the following order -

Your matter/complaint does not fall under the mandate of the Commission.

Hence, the case has been closed by the Commission and you are accordingly informed.

ANJALI PATHAK
(CO-ORDINATOR)

As per WCD/NCW only young women are coming under mandate, Older women, Mother-in-laws are not Women.

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Recently on twitter, NCW created a poll regarding the gender facing the domestic violence. But when the poll results were showing men as highest percentage domestic violence victims, the poll itself was immediately deleted by NCW.

<https://twitter.com/NCWIndia/status/1263765495016124418?s=19> (Now deleted - actual Twitter link)

NCW
@NCWIndia

Cast your poll 1/5

For [@NCWIndia](#) next Live Session on 'Bystander Intervention' with [@kapoors_s](#) [@SayftyCom](#) - we are running a poll to understand some of - [#BystanderEffect](#)

1. Who is usually at risk of harassment?

Men	74%
Women	8%
Non-Binary	2%
All Above	16%

1,016 votes • 16 hours 38 minutes left

3:05 PM · 22 May 20 · [Twitter Web App](#)

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WCD/NCW has 29664.90 crores rupees (2020) Government Funding, anyone can guess what they do with that money?

Why no real woman is not getting any help?

There are many women approach Men's NGO like MyNation Hope Foundation, asking for help, WCD/NCW is scam ministry, same was reported here. These are not our finding but from well know news media.

90% of NGOs seeking funds under WCD scheme found fake

NEW DELHI: In a disturbing revelation, the women and child development (WCD) ministry has found that nearly 90% of around 1,400 NGOs seeking financial grants under a major training and employment scheme were fake.

Top officials in the ministry said applications were invited from NGOs to impart skill development training to women in rural areas under its Support to Training and Employment Programme (STEP) which has a corpus of Rs 30 crore.

"We had received 1,400 to 1,500 applications of which 90% are fake. The scrutiny of applications revealed that most of the NGOs have applied multiple times giving false names and details," a senior official said. STEP is a major programme being implemented by WCD ministry, aimed at providing employability skills to women. The official said the ministry has decided to upload the names of all fake NGOs on its website so that they can be "exposed" and "identified" by other ministries as well.

(News Source: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/centre-ngo/90-of-NGOs-seeking-funds-under-WCD-scheme-found-fake/articleshow/46790570.cms>)

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Not only this WCD/NCW keep on inventing new ways to make money, get funds creating useless survey/study/research etc. here is yet another new scheme to ask money from government. They are getting crores of funds for last 30 years still they have not done these studies, which they keep on repeating again and again

Next exposure target of WCD/NCW -
<http://ncwapps.nic.in/WriteReadData/ScanDocuments/Eproposals/OfficeOrder/GuidelinesFY2019202001082019.pdf>

But they forgot to add their actual business modules.

How to make easy money filling fake 498A/PWDVA cases?

How to kill husband and not get caught?

How to harass aged in-laws and kick them out of their house?

Hundreds of news reports of Killing of Men by their wives reported in this study report for the year 2020.

(Ref: <https://mynation.net/voice/study-report-dv-on-men/>)

Still some judges/ministers says, time has not come to make laws for men

(News Source: <https://www.livelaw.in/webinar/we-have-not-reached-the-point-where-men-need-protection-from-women-justice-hima-kohli-158147>)

This Is the Real Face Of WCD/NCW.

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Chapter 6:

Legal Terrorism in Matrimonial Disputes – Solution for Legal Terrorism

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Introduction:

MyNation analysis of statistics on Matrimonial disputes shows the number of men attacked/abused/harassed/killed by wives and girlfriends is much higher than ever thought. Its report, Domestic Violence: The Male struggle to survive, states: "Domestic Violence is often assumed as women as victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations."

This survey and study report is based on Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims, and not collected as Women organizations collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories which have no valid backing.

Summary:

Matrimonial disputes and Domestic Violence/Abuse" covers a broad range of violent acts committed by one member of a family or household against another. It often refers to the mistreatment of a child or spouse and can include not only physical harm, but also threats and verbal, psychological, and sexual abuse. Most of the time, domestic violence against men only gets any attention when a Celebrity/Politician or highly reputed person is the victim of some kind of noteworthy physical harm, rest are perceived as isolated incidents and much of the public and private speculation presumes the man did something to deserve it.

The exact numbers of domestic violence on men overall is difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men are suffering abuse. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman.

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Key Findings:

Majority men are ashamed to come forward to report domestic violence/abuse on them by their wives, as there are no laws or Authorities like Police/Court/Judge/Minister to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A IPC (Indian Penal code) / Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 on them, that make's men to suffer in silence.

Methodology:

Information for this report was sourced from various secondary sources, all listed in the Reference List. Data from National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) and various News publications and testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Domestic violence also proved valuable. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of Men who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is not ready to Publish Domestic Violence/Abuse on Men or their Mental health.

Marriage is a sacred institution. To a common man, it is a socially and ritually recognized union between spouses that establishes rights and obligations between them, with their children, etc. The institution of marriage carries different connotations under different religions. Traditionally, for the Hindus, it is sacrosanct. Muslims see marriage more as a contract. For the Christians, marriage is a union between a man and a woman as ordained by God, meant to last for the life time. India is a secular Nation and it comprises of persons from many religions/castes.

Marriages in India are regulated both by the Personal Laws of the community as well as the specific laws duly enacted on the subject from time to time. The subject 'Marriage and Divorce' falls in the Concurrent List under the Seventh Schedule to the Constitution (Entry 5) and hence

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both the Union Government and the State Governments possess the power to make laws on this subject.

With the overall social progress, the country has experienced over the past half a century, the perception about women in India has undergone a perceptible change. From a simple home maker with little or no awareness or education, she has moved up in the society to the level of an equal partner with men in almost all walks of life. For a couple of decades now, women are seen working shoulder to shoulder to men which has lent in them some sense of freedom, autonomy and self-dependence in their approach. This big change in the perception of woman has greatly affected the matrix of husband-wife relationship and has given new dimensions to matrimonial disputes. In this backdrop, Parliament of India have enacted a number of laws from time to time for regulating the marriage and divorce in the country and also for the protection of women in the newly emerging scenario.

The incidence of matrimonial disputes in the country has been seen moving upwards over the past several years and the trend does not seem to show any signs of control or reversal. But whatever may be the incidence of matrimonial disputes in the country in terms of numbers, its impact is devastating on the litigating parties, the institution of marriage and the society generally. Matrimonial disputes are telling heavily on the parties to the marriage, their families in terms of time, money and peace of mind.

The fortification of women particularly through the initiatives like changes in Criminal Laws in the year 1983 and the enactment against domestic violence of 2005 have no doubt been able to put a curb on the atrocities against women, but, in fact, these protective initiatives of Government in favor of the women have tilted the balance much to the disadvantage of the male community. This has been protested upon vehemently by the male community in the past years

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but with little relief. The Government probably fears that any dilution in the existing set of laws may weaken the protective cover that has been built around the women over the years.

The National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), the Ministry of Home affairs wing that collates annual data on crime in the country, came out with its figures for 2016 on 30th November 2017. While overall crime in the country has increased by 2.6% - from 47,10,676 cases in 2015 to 48,31,515 cognizable crimes in 2016, other worrying trends too have come to light.

Most number of crimes are registered against women (especially old mother-in-law and sister-in-law) by estranged Daughter-in-law, which is covered under Section 498A and other Indian Penal Code sections, because daughter-in-law has protection and support from Government, and law is ready to punish more men and women in the name of protecting one woman i.e. daughter-in-law.

After widespread complaints of the “misuse” of the 498A and section - offences registered under which are non-bailable, a division bench of the Supreme Court had on 27th July 2017 directed that no arrest or action be taken on such complaints without ensuring the veracity of the allegations made by daughter in law and her family members.

However, on 29th November 2017 the court said it can't frame guidelines on how to probe cases of dowry harassment, as this would mean going beyond statutory provisions.

Also, contrary to the perception, that “disgruntled wives” file false cases under various Matrimonial disputes, data has found that complaints declared false on similar grounds are far higher in IPC cases such as cheating and kidnapping.

Indian Penal Code (IPC) Section 498A was introduced in 1983 with an objective to protect married Indian women from cruelty, including dowry harassment. The offence under this section is cognizable, non-bailable, and non-compoundable with provision to lodge a complaint

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against the husband or any relative of the husband of that woman. The section reads as hereunder: -

“Whoever, being the husband or the relative of the husband of a woman, subjects such woman to cruelty shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years and shall also liable to fine.”

The objective of 498A of IPC is to protect married Indian women from cruelty, including dowry harassment. The offence under this section is cognizable, non-bailable, and non-compoundable with provision to lodge a complaint against the husband or any relative of the husband of that woman. The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act 2005 provides for the first time in Indian law a definition of "domestic violence". This definition is broad and including not only physical violence, but also other forms of violence such as emotional/verbal, sexual, and economic abuse. It is a civil law meant primarily for providing protection.

The advent of both these laws have tilted the scales too much in favor of the wife and against the husband. This fact has repeatedly been professed by husbands and acknowledged by the courts as well. After widespread complaints of the "misuse" of section 498A IPC, a Division Bench of the Supreme Court had on 27th July 2017 directed that no arrest or action be taken on such complaints without ensuring the veracity of the allegations. Thereafter, on 29th November 2017 the court went on to say that it can't frame guidelines on how to probe cases of dowry harassment, as this would mean going beyond statutory provisions. On the same lines, the Madras High Court Bench has observed that Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 suffers from inherent flaws which tempt women to misuse their provisions and men to dread being prosecuted under the law without any rhyme or reason.

For the past few decades, it is a ground reality that whenever there is a marital discord, and one of the parties to the marriage seeks a legal recourse, the litigation grows wild and out of

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proportion on a pre-set pattern. For example, if the husband takes the first step and files a case for restitution of conjugal rights or for divorce, the wife in the first place strongly contests the case with all sorts of counter allegations. By way of retaliation, the women side is also seen invariably invoking provisions of the Section 498A of the IPC as also the PWDVA. Apart from this, claims are put up by the parties (generally the wife) before the matrimonial court for maintenance of wife pending continuation of divorce proceedings/ maintenance of wife or children under Section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code before the Criminal court of appropriate jurisdiction. Besides all this, the wives also tend to invoke through separate criminal proceedings sections IPC 406 (criminal breach of trust), 307 (attempt to murder), IPC 312 (causing miscarriage), IPC 313 (causing miscarriage without woman's consent), 354 (molestation), 376 (rape) on husband's father/brother or any other male relative, and 377 (unnatural sex) on husband to "strengthen" their 498A IPC / PWDVA case. Hereafter called "*Matrimonial disputes.*"

Along with 498A IPC and PWDVA, women are now also seen invoking the provisions under Sections IPC 406 (criminal breach of trust), 307 (attempt to murder), IPC 312 (causing miscarriage), IPC 313 (causing miscarriage without woman's consent), 354 (molestation), 376 (rape) on husband's father/brother or any other male relative, and 377 (unnatural sex) of the Indian penal Code (IPC) on husband and his family members to rope them in and also to "strengthen" their 498A IPC / PWDVA case. These provisions of the Indian Penal Code are being grossly misused and abused by unscrupulous women, who tend to use law as a weapon for ulterior motives, to satisfy their ego and as a vengeance tool to settle the score. In case of 498A, the FIRs get registered merely on the verbal testimony of the unscrupulous Women who do not spare any family member of the husband in FIR including infants, children, bed ridden senior citizens, married/unmarried sister-in-law or brother-in-law, pregnant women relatives, even those staying in far off places, or abroad.

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Unfortunately, all these Penal Code Sections allow police/Govt. law enforcement agencies unlimited power to harass the innocent by threatening the entire family of the husband to be put into jail or denial of bail. As these Penal Code Sections do not have any checks and balances and their implementation is at whims and fancies of the ever-obliging Police Department, all this has created massive, irreversible damages and havoc in the age old, traditional, most sacred and stable Indian Family System and has taken thousands of lives of many innocent men/Families, since the inception of these draconian laws. There is rapid and steep raise in men committing suicides due to wives harassing hapless and innocent young men than women committing suicides due to dowry harassment.

133,623 suicides in India were reported in India in 2015, of which 91,528 (68%) were by men and 42,088 were by women, according to data from National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) of the 86,808 married persons who committed suicides in 2015, 64,534 (74%) were men, 26% women.

That by a mere verbal testimony of the complainant; FIR is registered; thereby husband, his entire innocent family and distant relatives go through mental trauma, torture and immense harassment. It is a fact that Unscrupulous Women do not spare any family member of the

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husband in FIR, that includes Infants, children, bed ridden senior citizens, married/unmarried sisters-in-law or brother-in-law, pregnant women relatives, even those staying in far off places, or abroad, and even dead people.

When this provision was enacted, lawmakers had never imagined or foreseen that women would ever stoop so low, and misuse law, that is tilted so much to their favor. There was presumption that women would never destroy their own family by filing FIR under the *Matrimonial disputes*, but over the period such presumption has been totally proven wrong by the ever-increasing number of cases filed by wives and the acquittals as evident from the NCRB data and other such credible entities. Hence it is a dire need of the hour, to address this pernicious problem and stop the rampant misuse of these provisions, which was done in good faith.

Government of India is also a signatory member of UN- *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (UDHR) and Person is innocent until proven Guilty is duly applied under **Article 11(1)** **Whereas under the *Matrimonial disputes* the moment FIR is filed, entire family is presumed to be guilty and treatment meted out by Law enforcement agencies is a worst kind of mental, physical and emotional torture to them, which honorable supreme court, famously said that this is “LEGAL TERRORISM”.**

Why and how matrimonial disputes are misused?

That the *Matrimonial disputes* law is being misused rampantly by greedy and unscrupulous women and their family members. The number of instances the *Matrimonial disputes* are misused to harass and extort money from Husband and in laws is phenomenally more than the instances when the real victim of Domestic Violence actually using these provisions to get justice. It is often argued that every law is misused. But it is a fact that no law is misused and abused so extensively as 498A and domestic violence along with other sections. Further; none

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of the laws, when it is misused, will put an entire family of the husbands to suffer, which include even innocent infants, children to aged and retired senior citizen, married and unmarried sisters and other men and women relatives to siblings because there is no Punishment for misusing or harassing with these laws nor there is no accountability to Police or Judges.

That the abuse of 498A is now a widespread epidemic and has reached every nook and corner of this country and not even towns/villages are left out in this pandemic. Even after SC's Arnesh Kumar (2014) or Rajesh Sharma (2017) Judgment; neither ground situation nor the attitude of police officers have changed. To circumvent SC's caution/guidelines; Women have started filing False Outraging Modesty (IPC 354), Rape (IPC 376) / or Unnatural Sex (IPC 377) cases against husband and other male relatives and Attempt to Kill (IPC 307), Causing of Miscarriage, Injuries to Unborn Children (IPC 312-318), Criminal Breach of Trust (IPC 406) on in-laws and Sisters of Husband who are married and staying faraway. These are so serious offenses which are now being filed in casual and routine manner.

That the gravity of the situation can be assessed from the fact that there are several cases of dowry deaths, wherein the supposedly 'dead victims' have even come back alive, and several cases where the same women have repeatedly alleged same charges under this law, in each of their repeat marriages.

This law is being misused by women to enable a get-rich-quick-scheme make quick money in short span of time by extorting huge amounts of money from innocent husbands and in laws families. Women, their parents, instigators have used this law to extend threats and hold innocent families to ransom, thereby pressurizing them to accede to unjustified demands with threat of serious consequences, if not agreed;

This law is being misused and abused by women to not only alienate the husband from his aged parents and siblings, but also to gain control over his finances and social behavior, including his

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lifestyle and make him a money extracting puppet dancing to the tunes of the wife and her parents. Growing instances of abusive behaviors towards elders in the families, including parents and senior citizens, are another ramification of its misuse, abuse; separating the husband from his parents has been clearly defined as cruelty by the honorable courts on many occasions.

This law is also rampantly misused by those brides and their parents, who conceal true facts about her mental health, premarital affairs/relationships if any and educational level at the time of marriage, thereby adopting fraudulent means to forge the alliance. When these facts are unearthed by the groom and his family, the bride and her family threaten and silence the groom and his family with the threats of filing of these *Matrimonial disputes* against them.

This law is being misused as bargaining tools by those women who indulge in Adultery are caught red-handed. When their nefarious acts are exposed, they take recourse to misusing this law, thereby deflecting the needle of crime on innocent husband and his family. This law being an exception in Criminal Law which presumes the accused as guilty until proven innocent; hence the women's word is taken as a gospel of truth. And from there begins the saga of unending trials, tribulations and destruction for an innocent man and his family;

The law is being misused to enable divorce so as to revive any pre-marital relationship that the wife may have had as she may have unwillingly given her consent for marriage to satisfy her parents;

The law is being misused to deny custody of child/children to the father and his family. In fact, several cases abound, where children have been wrongfully deprived of fatherly care and affection through such indiscriminate, rampant misuse of this law; thus, even young children lose the loving care and affection of a father in their tender age, which can seriously hamper the mental wellbeing of the traumatized child. Apart from separating children from their Father, these laws are also being used stop Father's from meeting their children, and these innocent

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children are used as blackmailing tool to get maintenance or forced to agree to their greed. In some cases, they even physically harm the little children and share the pictures with the husbands and family members to put mental pressure on them and make them agree to their demands.

This law is being misused to inflict sufferings on husband and his family to settle scores and to wreak vengeance, thereby posing a grave threat to the very existence of a peaceful family unit in society. Law is to protect, not to destruct. Law is as much for protecting the innocent as it is to punish the guilty.

The language, content and structure of this law has enabled implication of millions of innocent people in false cases. A complaint, without any authenticity and without any weight of evidence, is enough to arrest the husband, in-laws and anyone else named in the complaint, irrespective of whether a crime has occurred or not. This has led to the arrest of lakhs innocent citizens (thousands of families), with many committing suicides as they are unable to bear the indelible social stigma on their honor and reputation.

India is the only country in the world where just on the basis of verbal statement of a woman, entire family is put behind bar. That over 85% of acquittals (as per NCRB data) clearly suggest that there is emergency like situation, and this widespread cancer of misuse of Matrimonial disputes in the society, ought to be fixed by Lawmakers by suitably bringing in legislations and penalizing the culprits.

Aftermath Impact: Family Suffering, Humiliation, Social Stigma and Loss of Livelihood: That once the *Matrimonial disputes* complaint is filed; All relatives, friends, neighbors, acquaintances and other known people immediately cut-off relationship with accused family members who are involved in these false matrimonial disputes. Once implicated in the *Matrimonial disputes*, it becomes a social taboo which assumes that “all accused are criminals”.

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Office employees/colleagues, managers or even subordinates stop respecting such people, as soon as they come to know about the *Matrimonial disputes*/proceeding against husbands or his relatives (Male or Female). Their professional growth such as promotion, salary increment is seriously affected since employers start treating such employees in an extremely biased way.

In this immense and cut-throat competitive job market, no company would like to keep any person who is involved in serious criminal cases like the *Matrimonial disputes* thereby denying them their livelihood. Right to livelihood is fundamental right, guaranteed under article 21, which supersedes any other law enacted by parliament. Thereby if Indian Husbands / his relatives lose their job due to criminal proceedings under the *Matrimonial disputes* then their livelihood also gets irreversibly and seriously affected.

Husbands who live and work abroad, live in constant fear of losing their jobs i.e. livelihood, frightened of being arrested, horrified that any time their family members in India may get harassed, tortured and arrested.

If husbands and their family members are settled abroad/NRIs then their passports are impounded, Lookout Circular (LOC) and Red Corner Notice (RCN) are issued treating them at par with Terrorists.

Even innocent Women relatives of husband are seen as perpetrators of crimes against these Legal terrorist wives, and face social bias and are ostracized by Society.

If Husband has Younger Male/Female Siblings; their prospect of marriage would be ruined completely.

The married life of sisters and aunts also get affected seriously as her in-laws / husband are made to suffer in police cases/courts proceedings without any fault of theirs and just because woman is happened to be a sister/ aunt of the husband.

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Role of police, their attitude and treatment, shoddy investigation and false charge sheet: that after the *Matrimonial disputes* are filed against husband and his family members; Police or law enforcement agencies would often and invariably terrify, harass, threaten entire family in the name of investigation, instilling fear of losing property, and court cases running for years and bias of law towards women, delayed justice and extort huge sums of money. This has become an organized industry, breeding huge corruption in the law enforcing agencies.

That when Police even after knowing that accused husband or his family members are staying in different cities, different states and even different countries/continents, continents and no way related to the matrimonial home or cases, they would deliberately and repeatedly ask them to appear in police station in the name of enquiry/investigation, just to extract huge sums of money.

That the moment the *Matrimonial disputes* FIR is filed, in the name of enquiry/investigation husband and entire family will be asked to stand in line holding slate and their photographs will be taken from various angles like hardcore criminals /terrorists.

That police without sending any written notice; would either arrest them or call accused over the phone in the guise of enquiry on a Friday/Saturday and then upon visiting, they would detain them or put them in jail, till court grants them bail, only to torture them in the ensuing 24-48 hours, when they are heavily bribed by the complainant (wife and her family members) or to demand huge bribes from the accused.

That police do not investigate such FIRs and sit on it for years and then file charge sheet without any proof/investigation by copying, pasting of FIR content to their charge sheet, even when the husband show all the evidences and proofs of his innocence, which are simply ignored. Same trend is continuing in court also, in maintenance and custody cases, all the evidence provided by husband is ignored and whatever women says is taken as a Gospel truth.

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That as per NCRB data charge sheet rate of 498A is over 93%, and acquittal rate is over 85%, similarly in PWDVA in 2015, over 125558 charge sheeted and conviction rate is only 17.7% clearly shows police department is in connivance with law abuser the women / wives are exploiting this provision to extort, harass, torture and oppress husband and his entire family.

No cruelty laws for men: Reverse the above situation where, Wife demands house, car, luxurious items, jewelries etc. and when mental, physical cruelty are inflicted upon men by their wives; Men have no remedies under law to file complaint against wife. When such men approach the police, they are made fun of and simply turned away that, they cannot do anything and there is no law for them to act.

That Men are presumed to be protectors / care takers of their wives but when Protectors are harassed / tortured under legal provision, it would be impossible for Men to reconcile to live with their estranged wives who have filed false 498A or PWDVA.

NCRB Statistics:

That the following statistics corroborate the above contention of the petitioner:

NCRB STATISTICS 2011 TO 2015

498A

Year	Case Registered	Women Arrested	Total Arrest	acquitted	Conviction Rate
2011	99135		180701	83580	20.6 %
2012	106527		197762	92867	15.0 %
2013	118866		222091	97622	15.2 %
2014	122877	44218	225648	94765	14.0 %
2015	113403	35733	187067	88203	15.7 %

PWDVA

Year	Case Registered	Women Arrested	Total Arrest	acquitted	Conviction Rate
2011	107753		205279	94757	22.8 %
2012	114760		222180	103113	16.7 %
2013	126949		245955	108003	16.7 %
2014	135492	49912	255107	104805	15.7 %
2015	125558	40927	213835	98899	17.7 %

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About Half Million 498A Cases are pending at end of 2015

(Figures compiled from NCRB Data)

Rate of Conviction: All other IPC vs. 498A IPC

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Year	Total Cases where trial completed in that year	Convicted	Acquitted	Withdrawn	Total Cases Pending at the end of the year	Conviction Rate of Cases under 498-A in %	Average Conviction Rate of all IPC crimes in %
2006	31261	6857	24404	5679	206431	21.9	42.9
2007	32622	6831	25791	6364	228614	20.9	42.3
2008	34347	7710	26637	7310	251759	22.4	42.6
2009	37323	7380	29943	7111	278921	19.8	41.7
2010	40751	7764	32987	6601	309991	19.1	40.7
2011	40338	8167	32171	7450	339902	20.2	41.1
2012	46054	6916	39138	8162	372706	15	38.5

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2013	45423	7258	38165	8218	412438	16	40.2
2014	46853	6425	40428	8922	443885	13.7	45.1
2015	46217	6559	39658	10318	477986	14.2	46.9

Source: NCRB, Government of India.

That Acquittal rate in the NCRB statistics shows IPC 498A and PWDVA grossly misused than used and all other claim of Women organizations about no misuse of the Section are blatant lies and are totally baseless. And it is to be seriously noted, that not a single marriage has ever survived after 498A of IPC or PWDVA, which is a serious indicator of disruption and destruction of families and in this process we are destroying homes by making innocent young children a part of family which is broken, if children are not taken care of properly by both parents studies suggest that such children can, become delinquent or criminals in the future.

India's International Image and Credibility having Biased Laws: That 498A IPC and PWDVA has become so infamous for being draconian which has seriously damaged India's reputation, image and credibility for having unfair, biased and anti-men, gender biased laws

Many countries had issued warning to their citizens not to marry Indian Women to save themselves from 498A/Dowry laws.

2006: USA issues travel advisory to its citizens traveling to India to be unsafe for US men to marry an Indian woman. An old screenshot of the advisory is as under:

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USA

http://travel.state.gov/travel/cis_pa_tw/cis/cis_1139.html

A number of U.S.-citizen men who have come to India to marry Indian nationals have been arrested and charged with crimes related to dowry extraction. Many of the charges stem from the U.S. citizen's inability to provide an immigrant visa for his prospective spouse to travel immediately to the United States. The courts sometimes order the U.S. citizen to pay large sums of money to his spouse in exchange for the dismissal of charges. The courts normally confiscate the American's passport, and he must remain in India until the case has been settled. There are also cases of U.S.-citizen women of Indian descent whose families force them against their will into marriages to Indian nationals.

Government of Canada still advises its citizens to **beware of Marital Frauds and Misuse of Dowry Prohibition Act**. The website (<http://travel.gc.ca/destinations/india>) says *“used to blackmail men through false allegations of dowry extortion”*

Government of Australia (Refugee Review Tribunal) issued India Country Advise in 2010, heading *“India – IND37679 – Domestic violence – False dowries – Male victims – State protection – Police – Corruption”*.

Heavy Criticism by Supreme Courts, High Courts and Other Authorities: That the misuse of Section 498A of IPC has been acknowledged/condemned by leading authorities;

The Honorable **Supreme Court of India** in *Sushil Kumar Sharma vs. U.O.I (2005)* said that any misuse of this provision of law amounts to unleashing **Legal Terrorism**. It acknowledged that there are growing instances of women filing false charge.

Even Additional Solicitor General for the Gov. of India admitted In the **Supreme Court of India** in *Rajesh Sharma and Ors. vs. State of U.P. and Anr (2017)* case that *“There is a growing tendency to abuse the said provision to rope in all the relatives including parents of advanced age, minor children, siblings, grand-parents and uncles on the strength of vague and exaggerated allegations without there being any verifiable evidence of physical or mental harm*

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or injury. At times, this results in harassment and even arrest of innocent family members, including women and senior citizens.”

The World Health Organization (WHO), in its Report of India clearly cited Section 498A as one of the major reasons for growing Elder Abuse in India.

The Law Commission in its 154th Report, the Malimath Committee Report (on Reforms of Criminal Justice System, 2003) and the 111th Report of the Parliamentary Standing Committee on Home Affairs, have all acknowledged that Section 498A is being widely misused;

The Center for Social Research (India), in a study on implications of Section 498A IPC state that “educated and independent minded women misuse the section”.

That there is no remedy/provision in this law:

For punishment to people who misuse and abuse this law.

For people who are proved innocent after being falsely implicated under this law; for the indelible stigma that falsely accused people are forced to live with for the rest of their lives;

For the immense financial, social and personal loss borne by the falsely accused;

For resurrecting the lives of falsely accused and maligned people;

For discouraging people from filing false cases.

For punishment to guilty and corrupt law enforcement agencies who connive and collude with complainants to harass and torture and falsely accused;

For preventing the media from maligning and defaming the falsely accused innocent men; and

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For citizens to file complaints against women who inflict cruelties and atrocities on them and their family members.

That the Supreme Court of India in Sushil Kumar Sharma vs. U.O.I and others (JT 2005 (6) SC 266) clearly said that it is for the legislature to find ways on how to deal with misuses of this law as well as on how to wipe out the ignominies suffered during and after the trial by the falsely accused.

It is often argued that there are remedies available under existing IPC to punish those who misuse law such as 182 IPC. However, the fact remains that police never initiate 182 despite of knowing the fact that complaint is false. This can be also corroborated by Charge sheet Filing Rate (> 93%) vis-a-vis conviction rate (<15%) which is lowest among all IPC crimes. Further IPC 182 can be initiated by police and not by the victims who are implicated in false *Matrimonial disputes*. The victims have no remedies left.

That Unfortunate stand/view taken by honorable Women and Child Minister that “**All violence is MEN Generated in India**” that itself shows the prejudice and bias against MEN.

Petitioner's Caveat: That is true that under constitution of India under article 15(3); Special provisions / laws can be enacted for women and children. But this law not only violates article 14 and 21 but also creates prejudice within Women Gender class for which this law was enacted. When under the *Matrimonial disputes* it is presumed that woman “young married daughter-in-law” whereas sister-in-law, mother-in-law and other female relatives cannot even take recourse when they are subjected to similar cruelty inflicted by daughters-in-law.

That it is settled principle in the law that “*It is better that ten guilty persons escape than that one innocent suffers*” But under the *Matrimonial disputes* to punish 1 guilty person, 10 innocents are made to suffer. It is therefore to give justice to Woman cannot be at the expense

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of other MALE Gender. Where even Other Women relatives are also victim of misuse of the *Matrimonial disputes*.

Neither Petitioner, undersigned signatories in this petition are denying that there are some women who genuinely suffer due to dowry demands. But this does not give the license to the government to presume all men are guilty of such conduct as two wrongs do not make a right.

All the above statements are not work of fiction they are the real-life examples of our 10,000 odd members who are victims of the estranged, cantankerous, and greedy wives, and corrupt law enforcement agencies. To cite an example a Widow approached NCW (National Commission of Women) for help as she was not able to see her was harassed with False 498a IPC against him and his suffering but in case No **8/C0500721/VT/MSH/NCW/2006** dated 03 Feb 2007. NCW replied saying **her case is not coming under their mandate or purview**, that just shows their biased attitude towards Mother in law (parents of husband) terming her not as a Women. This is not just one case, there are plenty of cases where NCW could have made a difference in the lives of Women who approach the commission but they show only their apathy and indifference towards them, and they are in no mood to help other women or even at least guide them. Why is NCW getting crores of Funds in the name of Women? If they don't help or even listen or work towards providing relief to the women who approach the commission.

There are plenty of such cases where the 498A section is being misused, I want to quote one last scenario where the wife filed complaint against the brother of the husband who migrated to Australia 5 years before the said crime which is attempt to murder IPC 307 (Case Crime No. 37/2011, u/s 498-A, 307 323, 354, 406, 506, IPC and 3/4 D.P. Act in Mahila Thana, Hazratganj, Lucknow and Charge sheet No. 46/2011 dated 03.08.2011) despite repeated appeals in the court they were rejected now the only option left for accused is to approach Supreme court for the relief.

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To cite another example a criminal case (Criminal complaint No. Regular Cr. CC No. 317 of 2000 U/s 498(A), 323, 504, and 506 IPC) is pending for the past 18 years before the Honorable Court of Jt. Civil Judge JD and JMFC Vasai, Thane, Maharashtra ; the complainant who filed this case has not attended a single hearing in the court since the beginning, despite repeated appeals for the relief is being denied by the judge and even appeal at Bombay High court (Criminal Writ Petition No. 2820 of 2013) is pending for last 5 years.

Why are innocent husbands harassed by the wives, police and the courts?

Why Law is not taking *suo moto* and punishes misuser of the law?

Why no action NBW/LOC/RCN on who abused process of law made mockery of law? Accuser absence itself shows Case is False, still why law is turning blind on such cases? Why accused employee lawyer and spend money on this?

Who will compensate all money spend on such cases?

Why there is no Accountability on Public servant in Matrimonial disputes?

Lastly, If any of these *Matrimonial disputes* are true then when money paid out of court, as much as demanded there will be no 498A IPC, No Domestic violence or Rape case, that clearly shows motive behind these False cases, majority of *Matrimonial disputes* being used as blackmailing tool rather than for seeking relief from marital dispute as none of the marriage survive once marital dispute reach to Police.

Remedies/Solutions

That suitable provision to be specifically inserted/amended in the *Matrimonial disputes* so as to make it punishable for whosoever misuses or abuses it, if case is quashed or dismissed.

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Empower Criminal courts to take *suo motu* cognizance to determine if the complaints filed before it (by party undergoing a matrimonial dispute) were false/frivolous and mandatorily pass appropriate orders on it.

That direction to polygraph test and request made by husband and his family for such test if they are willing to pay expenses should not be denied by any court to bring out the truth and with the best interest of law. No complainant should deny or refuse to be subjected to polygraph test/lie detector test if her complaint is true, refusal itself proves that she is telling lies, direction to polygraph test at the time of charge sheet can filter out all possible false cases, which can help to reduce backlog of cases and save precious time of judiciary which is reeling under pressure of crores of pending cases.

Make provision to compensate that party to the matrimonial dispute which has suffered in terms of loss of time, money, reputation, mental torture, etc. on account of misuse of the laws or by fake and frivolous allegations by the other party in Matrimonial disputes.

That advisories issued by Law ministry/Home affair etc.; made no impact on misuse of *Matrimonial disputes* so far as latest NCRB data shows acquittal rate is over 85%. That suitable provision be specifically inserted in the *Matrimonial disputes* so to hold the Police accountable and severely punished for the illegal arrest or call for enquiry without 41A notice and without getting sufficient evidence by the petitioner women.

That the new Misuse Clause to be inserted in all the *Matrimonial disputes* which may be read as follows for example:

“Whosoever misuses and abuse IPC 498A or PWDVA, in any way, to cause mental, emotional, physical or any type of torture or harassment by filing false cases will be tried by the same court and sentenced to a term of minimum of 10 years and complainant would also pay a fine,

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equal to Rs.10,00,000/- (Rs. Ten Lakhs) per year to the opposite party for the same period. Further there shall be departmental action against Investigation Officer (IO), Police Inspector (PI) and Superintendent of Police (SP) and Commissioner of Police (CP) or any other such authority to be penalized /demoted /suspended / Removed from job for filing false cases shoddy investigation, incompetency, delaying charge sheet and Other such factors depending on the case / facts and situation”

That if court finds the *Matrimonial disputes* complaint is false, frivolous and concocted, then apart from woman who abuses this provision; all other relatives and family members who have become witness in that trial must be charged under perjury and other suitable laws to prosecute them and also make them liable to compensate the financial loss suffered by the falsely accused in the process.

That the *Matrimonial disputes* complaint is included with false 307 IPC or other sections added without any proof, no court is giving Bail without approaching High Court, to be amended/insert clause so as to make itailable, non-cognizable and compoundable at lower court.

That without medical certificate/physical injury proof, police officers should not be allowed to register FIR under such serious sections.

That the PWDVA law, be made gender neutral, for protecting the interests of any innocent, be it a man or women.

That time bound trial should be made a statutory requirement under this law, with a 6-months maximum limit specified therein.

That Investigation Officer (IO) must not be allowed to file charge sheet without evidence against accused. Also, if IO doesn't file charge sheet within 6 months of filing the *Matrimonial*

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disputes complaint, FIR has to be made null and void and B Summary to be filed. Subsequently it is to be made mandatory for police to initiate criminal cases under section 182 IPC against women who filed false complaint.

That Indian NRIs implicated in the *Matrimonial disputes* must not be treated like hardcore Terrorists. Necessary laws / rules should be enacted that there should not be any LOC (Lookout circular) and Red Corner Notices (RCN) to be issued in the *Matrimonial disputes* complaint; until and unless complainants win the case. Further impounding passport by passport authorities is to be barred. Testimonies and statements can be taken on affidavit, duly signed in front of a consular officer or a local notary, be allowed to be considered by the investigating officers and the courts, without disrupting the life and job of NRIs. Also, they should be allowed to testify on Skype/video conferencing. If there is any irrefutable evidence is provided by the complainant or unearthed by the investigating officers, their passports may be impounded and they may be forced to return to India to face any such enquiry.

That necessary rules / laws to be enacted / amended where police / law enforcement agencies cannot deny police clearance (PC) mechanically in passport applications only because FIR is registered or case is pending.

That if women file multiple the *Matrimonial disputes/complaints* on the same incidents or same cause of actions, then necessary rules/laws may be enacted to punish such women who abuse the process of law.

That new subsection (3) under CrPC 256 may be included for all matrimonial disputes including IPC 498A which may be read as follows

CrPC 256(3): During Trial; If complainant does not appear for 3 consecutive dates even after receiving summons / notice, then magistrate shall dismiss the case and discharge the accused.

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As these the *Matrimonial disputes* has been become a Weapon to extort the money and to stop the misuse for such extortion/harassment; alimony/maintenance laws must be amended in which If women has filed false the *Matrimonial disputes* and husband is acquitted, then they are not liable for any maintenance/alimony and right to residence. This will also ensure that only genuine complaints would come to courts it would also reduce the burden of pending/backlog of cases. Also, the maintenance orders must be made effective from the date of conviction and not from the date of filing the complaint. It has been observed that once, the interim maintenance is awarded, the petitioner wives, disappear from attending the courts for years together. This will discourage the young, liberated women who leave the husband's family on flimsy grounds, to settle independently and to avoid taking care of the husband and his aged parents.

That If due to false *Matrimonial disputes* if husband or any of his family member commits suicide then sufficient penalty/punishment clause to be inserted, like 113A under Indian Evidence Act - where "Presumption as to abetment of suicide by a married Man or his any of family member" to be enacted. Further sufficient compensation clause to be added for filing false case.

That if a woman files the *Matrimonial Case* complaint after 1 year of cause of action/alleged incident; such frivolous complaints must be made time barred mandatorily and FIR should not be registered at all.

That if a woman files the *Matrimonial Case* complaint in revenge for husband filing for divorce or restitution of conjugal rights petitions, such FIR should not be registered at all.

That Minors / Infants, Sr. citizen Grand parents-in-law must not be included in FIR.

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That there should not be any FIR under the *Matrimonial disputes* against bridegroom and his family members before marriage. Similarly, there should not be any the *Matrimonial Case* complaint allowed against ex-husband and his relatives after divorce.

All the *Matrimonial Case* complaints to be registered with valid Aadhar Card/Phone number/WhatsApp number/Email details.

All Mediation/Counseling proceedings should be allowed to be recorded by either party. As most of the time IO/Counselor is found to be threatening husband and his family.

In many cases Child visitation / custody is denied to father on the basis that a *Matrimonial Case* is pending, make an amendment in the Guardians and Wards Act, that any parent can visit the child without any court order.

It is unfortunate that government keeps misleading general public about IPC 182 provision; which only allows public servant to file case against false complaint but not to the victim of false cases. If wife files false cases against husband and husband proves in the court of law there is no IPC provision which enables him to file case against false accuser. Therefore, we pray to issue direction to law commission and law ministry to immediately enact laws to curb the misuse of women centric laws so to punish those who files false cases. As NCRB statistics shows almost 80% acquittal but none of them are charged under section 182 IPC or any other section by Police or court.

Most of the time all *Matrimonial disputes* are filed when marriage is on the brink of divorce, or when the Husband files for divorce, caught her wrong doing [adultery/extra marital affair] or stop husband not to get child custody, so they file dowry cases even when marriage was held decade ago. The directions must be issued that no dowry demanded claims are accepted after a year of marriage.

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That an accused in *Matrimonial disputes* laws shall be considered a victim of civil loss and must be entitled to civil damages from state upon acquittal, and court fee, lawyer charges and other expenses for the same shall be waived off/borne by the state or by accuser.

That direction to all government entities that no action to be taken on Government employees, and suspend/terminate /departmental enquiry/action or hold promotion etc. based only on FIR being registered, other than final court order on any Matrimonial case.

That issue directions to Child Welfare Committee or court, not to make reason and barricade Father from visiting child just because matrimonial disputes are pending or FIR filed.

That issue directions or Amend in all *Matrimonial disputes*, the word man/women/husband/wife to spouse.

Recently Even Bangladesh enacted new law to tackle misuse of dowry law; similar law should be enacted to punish misuser of Law and compensation to victims of Legal terrorism.

That the Article 14 of The Constitution of India speaks of the Equality before law. The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of gender. In the light of the Constitution of India, Article 14, both men and women shall not be differentially treated in the case of harassment too. Along with millions of men, and women, have been the victims of gross violations of law. In order to vindicate their rights, to uphold respect for constitutional of India, and to deter future human rights abuses, the Government of India should consider this Petition, to form A Ministry for Men and his Family.

Finally, to counter misuse of Section 498A IPC there should be Section 498B IPC.

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Chapter 7:

WMD's of India – Weapons of Men's Destruction

Vicious Feminists Agenda

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This study article/report is based on Legal Journals, Indian Penal code, Code of Criminal Procedure of India, Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims, and not collected as Women organizations collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories which have no valid backing.

Summary:

The term "Weapons of Men's destruction (WMD)" covers a broad range of tactics, false cases, violent acts committed by one member of a family or household against another, especially by women against her male partner by using Women centric laws of India. These laws are biased against men and specially designed only for women and favor only young women; misuse of these laws Supreme Court of India called LEGAL TERRORISM.

As per National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reports and statistics almost 90% cases under various women centric laws end up dismissed / Quashed after man agree to pay hefty lumpsum. The exact numbers such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men are suffering abuse and face LEGAL TERRORISM. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman.

Key Findings:

Majority men are ashamed to come forward to report such abuse, misuse of law to terrorize them by their wives, as there are no laws or Authorities like

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Police/Judge/Minister to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A of Indian Penal Code / Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 these are few out of many WMDs of India, that make's men to suffer in silence.

Methodology:

Information for this report was sourced from various secondary sources, all listed in the Reference List. Data from NCRB and various News publications and testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Domestic violence also proved valuable. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of Men who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is not ready to publish misuse of law/Abuse on Men.

Introduction:

MyNation analysis of statistics on Weapons of Men's Destructions shows the number of men not only terrorized by various India's Women centric laws but attacked/abused/harassed/killed by wives and girlfriends is much higher than ever thought. In India it's often assumed as women as victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations. Because there are dozens of one-sided laws only for Women and None for Men

Some time back, United States of America was on the lookout for weapons of mass destruction (WMD) in Iraq, which it assumed, the country may use on itself or on its

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allies. These WMD can destroy all life instantly. But the American military did not find any so called WMD in Iraq. Well, in reality, these WMDs are not in Iraq but in INDIA. These are called Weapons of Men Destruction.

You may wonder which these Indian WMDs are:

1st Place goes to **IPC 498A** (DP3) also known as Dowry Law: Under this law, one word by a wife is enough to land husband in jail without any formal investigation. She can name anyone along with her husband, like his old parents, brothers, sisters, friends, neighbors, relatives and even servants. There are many news reports of even police arresting a 4-month-old breast feeding baby under this law. Any daughter in law can file a false case and there is no punishment for filling false cases and burden of showing proof lies on men. Police, Judges and Lawyers knows about this misuse, but for them it is a money-making opportunity and these cases go on for not less than 5 years minimum. These Police and Lawyers suck men blood by harassing them ruin their career, and if man is in a government job, he will lose his job as its criminal case, non bailable and non-compoundable. Under this Act, there is a 5-year punishment for giving dowry, but to date, no women or her family has been arrested for giving dowry. They report the case, only when the marriage is sore and on the brink of divorce. This Law was enacted in 1984.

2nd Place goes to **Domestic Violence Act** (PWDVA), this was enacted in 2006. Under this Law, daughter in law can file case on any male member of husband family, saying she was harassed mentally and physically. We have proof that some women have even filed a case just because she was asked to make tea for her husband and his friends. Under this law she can name any male members or husband's friends even if she has

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never met or seen them before and the police will take action on them. Burden of proof lies on men. In today's world, cooking and cleaning is considered to be harassment for women and today, most of the women do not know how to cook. Some have never been to the kitchen or do not even know where the kitchen is. They think their husband is a FREE ATM machine and he has to pay all her bills. That is his responsibility and he has no right to question what she is doing, where or with whom she is going and if questioned or the flow of money is reduced will be resulted in domestic violence false case.

3rd Place goes to **Maintenance** (HMA) if man wants a Divorce, then he has to maintain his wife, that's Law; but In India, even if a woman runs away with her lover or she want out of marriage citing some above False cases, the court will force the man to pay her. Most of the time, courts do not verify whether a man is capable to pay as much as women demand or he has that much source of income or not. There are judgments even on unemployed men; the court imposes maintenance by force. In one of Bombay HC case, the court forced the man to pay for the illegitimate child too. Here the women are not wrong to have illegitimate child, but if a man stop his wife from meeting her lover that leads to harassment. One Gujarat judgment says married women have the right to enjoy life outside marriage.

Divorce:

women can file a case for divorce citing any of above false cases or, even when she gets caught red handed with her lover, she can blame husband for this situation. With Divorce, she will get add-on package as interim maintenance and the man has to pay her for no fault of his. She will get divorce within a year. But for men, there are limited options for

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divorce, he has no supporting laws to file false cases as above, even if his wife has run away with her lover and to prove that she will not come back, he has to wait for 7 years.

Child Custody

Out of 10,000 custody cases only 1 or 2 fathers get his custody of his child. The law says the father is a natural guardian; well that's only in the law books. In reality, he never gets custody of his child. If a woman is prostitute or has deserted her child and goes abroad, she will get custody of her child by default. Till the age of 5, even the father has no right to ask for his child custody, but he has to pay for the child support only. This law is designed to make money for women from her husband, so the law gives her default custody till the child is 5 years, so women can raise her child and brainwash the child to hate his / her Father.

Outraging modesty

354 IPC: any women can file a case on any man for no reason and men are arrested without any formal investigation. Burden of proof lies on men, but if a woman does the same thing, a man has no supporting laws to protect him.

Above are already existing WMDs, but there are many more in NCW / WCD menu.

Marital Rape:

A wife can have consensual sex with her husband and the next day, she can report it to the police that she was raped by him.

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Marital Cruelty:

Promising a woman to marry her later and then get married to someone else, leads to cruelty to her. But if a woman does the same to a man, that's not a cruelty to him.

Sexual Harassment at work Place:

If a male employee shows or tells something which is even work related to a woman, she can report it to the police as sexual harassment for her. Man should not show that she is wrong, or if a female employee does not like some male employee, she can file a case against him simply to harass him and the burden of proof lies on men. Recently a women army major filed a case on her seniors, later she was proved wrong, but she did not have to compensate them for a year of false accusation or punishment for filing a false case.

Muslim Women Protection Bill:

which became law on 31st July 2019 - one more addition to the arsenal of Weapon of Men destruction in India. This regressive act made to put Men behind bars (specifically Muslim) for 3 years in spite the Apex court in Shayara Bano case (2017) declared Triple Talaq unconstitutional. This law already proved its effectiveness by throwing many men into prisons on short notice of disgruntled wife. There are reports that many women are misusing this as a shield and take revenge when marriage is on the brink of divorce, even there was no word of talaq issued 3 times, but for men it's difficult to prove they have not called for any Triple Talaq but Women word is taken as Gospel Truth.

Accusation:

In various accusation men and women file accusations to each other, in family related matters mostly divorce/maintenance/custody most of the time court hardly verify these

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minor accusations. In divorce cases, women can state in her petition to make her case stronger, that her husband was having affair, even if in reality, she was caught red handed having an extra marital affair. For women, no proof is required to write anything, but if man says something, it is regarded as harassment to her and NCW demands punishment for such accusation.

List of some other laws (criminal) misused by Indian women

Miscarriage

Causing Miscarriage 312 IPC Non-Cognizable 3 to 7 years

Causing Miscarriage without consent 313 IPC Cognizable. Life or 10 years

Death caused while causing miscarriage without Woman's Consent 314 IPC Cognizable.
10 years or Life

Act done to prevent child being born alive or to cause it to be after birth 315 IPC
Cognizable 10 years

Kidnapping

Kidnapping 363 IPC Cognizable. 7 years

Kidnapping women to compel marriage, seduced to illicit inter course, etc. 366 IPC
Cognizable. 10 years

Procuration of minor girl under 18 years 366-A IPC Cognizable. 10 years

Importation of girl 366-B IPC Cognizable. 10 years

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Sexual Assault

Punishment for Rape or Life time 376 IPC Cognizable 7 to 10 years

Intercourse by a man with him during Separation 376-A IPC Cognizable 2 years and Fine

Intercourse by public servant with woman in his custody 376-B IPC Cognizable 5 years and Fine

Intercourse by Superintendent of jail, remand home, etc. 376-C IPC Cognizable 5 years and Fine

Intercourse by any member of the management or staff of a hospital with any woman in that hospital 376-D IPC Cognizable 5 years and Fine

Unnatural Offences-carnal intercourse 377 IPC Cognizable Life or 10 years

Marriage

Cohabitation caused by deceitfully inducing her under belief of lawful marriage 493 IPC Non-Cognizable 10 years

Marrying again during life time of wife (away for 7 years) 494 IPC Cognizable 7 years

Going through unlawful marriage ceremony 496 IPC Cognizable 7 years

Enticing, detaining a during women with criminal intention 498 IPC Cognizable 2 years

Cruelty

Abetment of suicide 306 IPC Cognizable 10 years and Fine

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Cruelty by Husband or Relatives-Mental or physical 498A IPC Cognizable 3 years

Uses indecent language or behaves in a disorderly committed in manner in a public street the Presence or public place of police (KP Act-Karnataka Police Act) 92 -(o)- K.P.Act Cognizable if Fine of Rs.100

Uses in any street abusive or insulting words or affixes or exhibits any indecent, threatening abusive or insulting paper or drawing with intent to provoke 92-(r)-K. P. Act -do- -do5

Modesty

Outraging modesty, use of criminal force with intention to outrage her modesty 354 IPC Cognizable 2 years

Outraging modesty by Uttering gesture, sound 509 IPC Cognizable 1 year

Dowry Harassment

Dowry Death:

304B IPC Cognizable 7 years to life

A woman is caused by otherwise than normal circumstances within 7 years of her marriage and it is shown that soon before the death she was subjected to cruelty or harassment by her husband or relative for, or in connection with, any demand for dowry)

Penalty for giving or taking Dowry (D. P. Act) 3 Dowry Prohibition Act. Cognizable 5 years and fine

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Penalty for demanding Dowry (D. P. Act) Dowry Prohibition Act. Cognizable 6 months to 2 years and fine.

Immoral Traffic

Punishment for living on the earnings of prostitution, Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act
Cognizable 2 years or fine or both

Procuring inducing or taking woman or girl for the sake of prostitution Immoral Traffic
(Prevent) Action Cognizable 3 to 7 years and fine

Detaining a woman or girl in premises where Action prostitution is carried on. Immoral
Traffic (Prevent) Cognizable to 10 years And Fine

Seduction of a woman or girl in custody Immoral Traffic (Prevent) Action Cognizable 7
years or Life. and Fines

All above laws are misused widely, Women herself runaway with Boy then later claim she was kidnapped, have sex and claim sexually harassed or raped and Burdon lies on men to prove her wrong and that take years, and even man says truth no one believe and women Lies all Believe in her. Man has to prove with Proofs and for women just word and some crocodile tears are enough.

These Laws are very cleverly drafted without leaving any option for man to prove women is wrong or sue if misused and sure slow Death.

Gender Arsenal is all about the uncalled-for Gender War which has been initiated and is being fueled by reasons outside the purview of this article. Gender Arsenal pertains to the

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weapons available to both the genders in the war. Before going into the actual details about the arsenal, I will elucidate the positions of the two genders vis-à-vis each other.

National Commission for Women (NCW) came into effect in 1992 in India to work on women's issues. NCW has been instrumental in making awareness about a lot of problems faced by women, and has recommended various legal and social options to redress them. It also looks into complaints received by women. Additionally, women have around 3300 odd NGOs working for them, one union ministry and Rs. 26000 crores allocated for their cause annually from the union budget.

But No Laws for Men

I will now proceed to list down some laws meant specifically for women,

1. **Section 498A of the Indian Penal Code (IPC):** This section is formulated for married women who face physical and mental harassment from husband and in-laws and the cruelty is made for any unreasonable 'demand' (mostly dowry) from the woman and the cruelty is of such nature that it drives the woman to commit suicide or can be a danger to the life and limb of the woman.
2. **Section 354 of the IPC:** Assault or criminal force to woman with intent to outrage her modesty.
3. **Section 509 of the IPC:** Word, gesture or act intended to insult the modesty of a woman.
4. **Section 375 and 376 of the IPC:** Rape of a woman.

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5. **Section 498 of the IPC:** Enticing or taking away or detaining with criminal intent a married woman
6. **Section 98 of the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC):** Power to compel restoration of abducted females.
7. **Section 125 of the CrPC:** Meant to provide no-fault maintenance to wife from husband.
8. **Section 24 of the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 (HMA):** Though gender neutral, is largely used by women to extract maintenance from their husbands in pendency of a divorce.
9. **Section 25 of the HMA:** Meant to provide alimony to women from divorce.
10. **Section 18 of the Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act:** Another provision for maintenance to wives.
11. **Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961:** Though gender neutral in its definition, this Act is largely used to protect women and there are also some judgments for cases filed under this Act, which are gender biased towards women.
12. **Immortal Trafficking Prevention Act:** Deals with trafficking of women.
13. **Indecent Representation of Women Act:** Title is self-explanatory.
14. **Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act:** Empowers women to abort their unborn children legally.

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15. Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act: Meant to tackle Domestic Violence faced by women.

These are some of the laws and Acts made to protect and empower women true to the best of my knowledge; I might have missed a few of them. However, these are only illustrative and not exhaustive of the fact that women are not only over-protected but pampered in this so called **Male Dominated Society**, whereas men do not have even a single NGO funded by the Govt. of India to be fighting for men's cause let alone any law, section, Act or a commission or a ministry.

It should give a fairly clear idea as to how unequally men and women are placed in this gender war wherein actually men are dragged into uncalled for. On one hand, where women have weapons to the tune of AK47 to their kitty as their arsenal, men do not even have nothing at their disposal.

And, as I said, the list is merely illustrative and not exhaustive; NCW has in its offing more laws to castrate men, some of them being,

1. Proposal for compensation of Rs. 2 Lakhs to rape victims.
2. Sexual Harassment Bill.
3. Workplace Harassment Bill.
4. Law to protect maids and so on and so forth.
5. Marital Rape. (Proposed)
6. 50% husband Property rights to women on marriage.

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Again, the list of prospective laws is also true to the best of my knowledge and I might have missed many others in the offing.

Whilst there are neither any laws existing to protect men, nor in the offing, and the simple reason for this is, men do not fight for their right or stand up for other men who are fighting for men's rights.

And if things continue this way, the day won't be far when NCW will come up with a law like this one:

Inherent Protection of a Woman's Dream Act:

Any woman, who complains against a man that the man entered her dreams and molested her/outraged her modesty/raped her, shall be tried with a relevant section of the IPC. Any married woman who complains against her husband and in-laws that they entered her dreams and demanded dowry from her or harassed her and assaulted her for not bringing enough dowry shall be charged with IPC Section 498A/Dowry Prohibition Act/Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act etc.

Choice lies with men; they can allow more and more such laws to be passed by not supporting men's rights or take a stand against all such laws and pressurize the Government to rethink about the laws.

Most of these WMDs are proposed and designed by NCW (National Commission for women) and WCD (Ministry for Women and Child development) with one goal in mind i.e. to harass and blackmail men and ruin their careers and financial positions, so they cannot lead a happy life and die inch by inch every day. These Indian WMDs are worse than the so called Iraqi WMDs because WMDs of Iraq can kill people instantly but these

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Indian WMDs are meant for slow death of Men. These WMDs will not kill Indian Men, but drain him of all his Money / assets, ruin his future and dreams. Woman can do all this with the blessings of National Commission for women (NCW) and support from the Government of India which turn blind eye on the suffering of men.

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Chapter 8:

Study Report on Survey Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism

Survey on Victims of Legal Terrorism

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Introduction:

MyNation analysis of the survey shows that how men are harassed/abused and tortured by the Protectors of law, the Police along with the wives and girlfriends by various Women centric laws. In India it is often assumed that women are victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations. There are dozens of one-sided laws only for Women and None for Men

Methodology:

Information for this report was sourced from the testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Legal Terrorism. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by the Government of India, World Organizations. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is ready to publish misuse of law/Abuse or Legal terrorism on Men, in the name of Empower women all these atrocities are state sponsored.

Key Findings:

Majority men were ashamed to come forward to report such abuse, misuse of law to terrorize them, as there are no laws or authorities like Police/Judge/Minister to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A of Indian Penal Code / Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 these are few out of many Weapons of men's destructions (WMD) of India, that make men to suffer in silence. The exact number of such cases are difficult to assess as majority of the cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many

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men are suffering abuse and face LEGAL TERRORISM. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman. MyNation survey is first such survey where men came forward and submitted their say, as there is a limit to suffering or torture. When it is unbearable, they have no choice than admit it and open up themselves.

This survey and study report is based on Valid Statistics from the survey hosted on <https://mynation.net> for the period of 6 months and participated by more than 2000 people aged between 26 to 74 years. These statistics and testimonials are from the victims, and not collected as done by Women organizations which collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories and have no valid backing. Each entry of statement is from a unique IP, i.e., no multiple IPs data recorded or counted in the survey.

What Is Legal Terrorism?

A harassment by the state with the help of Law, judicial court or police by vexatious litigation, or by the individuals or unscrupulous persons to wreak personal vendetta or unleash harassment by filing of lawsuits to extort money/Assets or force to admit for their demands.

Supreme Court of India, in *Sushil Kumar Sharma vs Union Of India And Ors* on 19 July, 2005, Terming the misuse of provisions of dowry harassment by women as “legal terrorism”; a court has slammed such women who, in a bid to settle scores, drag all family members into a dowry harassment case though they may be “totally unconnected” with the case. “The provisions of Section 498A are not a law to take revenge, seek recovery of dowry or to force a divorce but a penal provision to punish the wrongdoers. The victims (women) are often misguided into exaggerating the facts by adding those

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persons as accused who are unconnected with the harassment under a mistaken belief that by doing so they are making a strong case,” additional sessions judge Kamini Lau said.

The court also expressed its displeasure over the misuse of the dowry harassment laws. “I am compelled to observe that provision in the recent years has become consummate embodiment of gross human rights violation, extortion and corruption and even the Apex Court of our country had acknowledged this abuse and termed it as legal terrorism”.

If a woman files a false complaint of dowry harassment, domestic violence, any other matrimonial complaint or women centric laws like Section 354 IPC, Section 375/376 and Section 377 IPC to a nearby police station against a Man and his relatives, they are arrested even if the investigation is incomplete still, they can be jailed on non-bailable terms.

Survey URL: <https://mynation.net/legal-terrorism/>

Understanding the state of violence committed on men through Data.

The survey was open to all and also sent via twitter to feminists also tagging to NCW/WCD and media channels to show this survey is not closed Survey only for men but it looks as if females were not interested to fill in their favor, because they know they cannot prove it if asked to show the evidence.

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Last Public Announcement Before Closing the Survey

MyNation Foundation
@MyNation_net

VICTIM OF LEGAL TERRORISM ? mynation.net/legal-terroris...
PLEASE TAKE PART, IT TAKE HARDLY 1 MINUTE
mynation.net/covidv/ @rsprasad @smritiirani @SmritiIraniOffc
@sharmarekha @SwatiJaiHind @LambaAlka @NCWIndia
@MinistryWCD @UN_Women @unwomenindia @kapoors_s
@SayftyCom @Judith_Char

srBachan and 9 others

8:08 AM · Sep 7, 2020 · Twitter Web App

Also on the face of it, it looks as if only males have replied hence it is in favor of men, just think opposite of that if it was replied by all females we would have thought that males are really bad and violent, our mind is so biased to trust females and not males though they were given an opportunity but selected to remain silent. This is the feminist mindset which gave birth to this law.

Let us delve today on a matter less discussed, less in the closed rooms, even lesser in parties, lesser in the society and seldom in the media, generally it is a unspoken taboo to speak in favor of Men and the issues that affect them physically, mentally and otherwise, such is the state of dismay that even men are unable to discuss it. To the rightfully thinking people it seems sometimes that men are some other species, but certainly not

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homo sapiens, they don't feel pain, emotions, are incapable of love, mental health issues don't affect them, they don't even get cancer it seems.

All of it seems true in the world we live in today, if we truly try to examine in an unbiased and scientific manner. Time and again science and technology has shown us that data and stats can be helpful to analyze a problem, if a problem really do exist in our body, physical, societal, national or if you may the world as a whole.

We at MyNation foundation have tried to do the same through one of our surveys and would like to share with you our findings,

Analysis of The Survey:

1) Gender of Victims:

GENDER

MALE - 97.55%

FEMALE - 2.45%

For this we sampled more than 2000 candidates, who are either directly or indirectly affected by violence or abuse whether legal or illegal, mainly in the home environment, or by a spouse or are related to spousal or familial violence and we found out 97.55% are Men and only 2.45% are Women.

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2) Education:

EDUCATION

Most of the victims of this kind of violence which is meted out in legal or domestic form are men, out of all the surveyed at least 80 percent are either graduates or post graduates, a majority of which are salaried professionals, and in a whopping 97.06 percent of the cases the oppressor is a woman

The general perception is that men or women who are uneducated or who are generally alcoholics or are from the low rung of the society indulge in such things like oppressing their partners, using unjust laws which were made for the protection of real victims of most heinous crimes against their partners just to extract money, resources or just to teach them a lesson and to the surprise most of them are women, and that to highly educated, above 86 percent of whom are either graduates or post graduates.

As we analyze the education part cases filed by educated and post graduate women is 92%. Now leaving apart that uneducated people don't see twitter fine. But do we expect this from educated people. The educated men are more vulnerable to domestic violence cases because the women are aware of the law and they know the pain their own men will have because of filing a case. To conclude educated women often file domestic violence cases to corner or harass the man's families. Uneducated families or couple on the other

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hand ignorant of law fight in the house and solve it next day. For a minute if we think that domestic violence law itself is scrapped, couples would solve problems internally in a day because they have no option but to live together. Hence the law is doing more harm than protecting families for which it was formed and promulgated.

3) Profession:

Most of these women despite being salaried professionals themselves (over 60 percent) or employed in some form or other, and most of them wedded partners (over 90 percent wives) who took an oath taking their respective God or Gods as witness to be together and strengthen each other, for the rest of their lives, file such false and unscrupulous cases and allegation not only on their life partners but also on the close family members and don't even spare far away relatives, many of whom are women, in such draconian sections of laws such as dowry, domestic violence, criminal force, intimation and even rape.

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4) Marital Status:

MARITAL STATUS

It is natural that married only will file a case and a very important point here is all cases are filed only by women. It is clear legal terrorism, the law wants to protect woman but it breaks families, it grants maintenance to give freedom to live alone and bear the expenses and so break the marriage and live freely on somebody's money and give them pain. Do we marry for purpose of living separately or together? In fact, love marriages should never be allowed to go to court for any case because they married according to their own will, which itself is an affidavit that a woman will live with an unknown person lifetime in as is where is condition. And the same with man, law should be gender neutral

5) Oppressor Gender:

OPPRESSOR GENDER

Out of 2000 peopled we surveyed 97.55% are men who faced Violence from Women. Above graph shows that's 97.06%. Again, the law gives a free hand for legal terrorism. But oppressor is not only of gender. We at MyNation have members just to give a broader view. The gender i.e., the female who is a wife is used by her side of members

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i.e., parents, brothers etc. to create a fight or spoil a family. We always say that terrorist has no religion so crime also has no gender. Is it written anywhere that only males are terrorists, goondas, hooligans or female hitters? No, if we had Kaikaey who as a mother had ordered her son to go to vanvas for 14 years, we had Kunti who abandoned her son in the river, we had Soornpankha and Pootna rakshas also. It is how the perception in the male side is the root cause for case, one of the latest cases was of Indrani Mukherjee who killed her daughter and hid the fact and filed a complaint that she is missing. What was that, does crime have a gender? i.e., men. This reminds me of a movie where people are born with a mark as criminals.

6) Oppressor Education:

OPPRESSOR EDUCATION

Most of the oppressors are well educated, who have knowledge of law and are aware that they can use these Women centric laws to harass, as there is no punishment for misusing these laws. That's why it's called LEGAL TERRORISM.

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7) Oppressor Profession:

OPPRESSOR PROFESSION

Most of the oppressor are not only well educated but employed too, most of them are in a very good position as in education and also in employment they have reservation even though they are not capable to handle the work. But when matter of maintenance comes they beg for alimony from husband, even if she is educated and earning well and her appeal is granted because of the biased legal system.

8) Who Is the Oppressor:

WHO IS THE OPPRESSOR

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And all the credit goes to WIFE as an oppressor. No wonder most of the surveyed choose Wife as oppressor, because that is truth, Indian society is blind. They always portray men as villain, Majority men are suffering silently without revealing their suffering in the hands of their wives and die young. But Women always tell everyone/ neighbors and her family that she was harassed even she is the one who harasses her husband and his family and everyone believe in her. Now we have given chance to men to express their views and here is the truth.

9) Which Case Filed on Victim:

WHICH CASE FILED ON YOU (M)

When a marriage breaks down the woman is often able to get her husband and many of his family members arrested by simply claiming Dowry demand, Domestic violence or cruelty even if she has no proof of her claim and persuading the local police to arrest the so-called wrongdoers. This is much more effective than initiating an ordinary case for

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divorce. Notorious Section 498a IPC take number one position followed by domestic violence.

10) How Long Case Is Running:

HOW LONG CASE IS RUNNING (M)

0 - 1 YEAR - 16.50%

LAST 2 YEARS - 32.04%

3 - 5 YEARS - 37.86%

MORE THAN 5 YEARS - 11.65%

MORE THAN 10 YEARS - 1.94%

Due to biased law it takes 5 years in our system for a husband and his family to prove himself innocent. This could cut down to months, if the complaint is found to be false the guilty should then be charged with same section and double penalty. That is gender neutral law. Which in turn would reduce pressing of false cases and our country would rank higher in world for sustainability of matrimonial life with proper legal consultation. This is the foundation stone for betterment of coming generations.

11) Case Filed on Whom:

CHARGES AGAINST WHOM (M)

ONLY ME - 11.90%

ONLY ON PARENTS - 0.79%

ME AND MY PARENTS - 36.11%

WHOLE FAMILY INCLUDING MARRIED SISTER WHO STAY FAR AWAY - 32.94%

WHOLE FAMILY AND ON RELATIVES - 9.92%

ME AND ONLY MALE MEMBERS OF THE FAMILY - 3.17%

NEIGHBORS, FRIENDS - 1.19%

OTHERS - 3.97%

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For women best way to harass her husband to get divorce or maintenance is filing case against his aged Parents along with him. Even though they never stayed with them or are staying far away, Police will add their name by default. It all depends with that Police have been bribed with and how influential the women's family is. Police even include brothers/sisters even breast fed 2/3 months old child of husband sisters have been included in many reports.

12) Pre-Investigation Procedures Followed?

PRE-INVESTIGATION ENQUIRY PROCEDURE FOLLOWED (M)

NONE - 32.55%

41 A NOTICE SERVED - 24.83%

41 A NOTICE NOT SERVED - 5.70%

POLICE CAME HOME - 17.79%

CALL FROM CAW - 19.13%

Most of the time Police just copy and paste what women or her Lawyer has given as complaint, they do not conduct a proper investigation or enquiry, No DIR (Domestic incident report), and they do not issue a 41A notice which is mandatory in every investigation.

13) Type of Complaint:

TYPE OF COMPLAINT (M)

POLICE FIR - 52.73%

CAW CELL - 23.05%

NCW - 3.91%

TO THE COURT U/S.156 CrPC - 20.31%

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In India, it is very easy for a Women to file a complaint with Police, anyone can go to Police station shed some crocodile tears, cry loudly and police are bound to register her complaint without verifying any of her claim or evidence. Height of all some claimed to be raped by a person who was miles away in another city or even if she claims she was raped in her dream, Police will register her complaint and start arresting whoever she names.

14) Type of Investigation/Enquiry By Police:

TYPE OF INVESTIGATION / ENQUIRY BY POLICE (M)

The type of Investigation police conducts when a woman complains, most of the time they just copy and paste all her statement as it is without any evidence or enquiry, they will file charge sheet. In some cases, they file charge sheet on same day of FIR and that's not speedy work of Police, but these charge sheets are filed without any ground,

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investigation or enquiry. Even without serving 41A notice or informing accused Police can announce them as absconding or not co-operating with investigation, all this depends on how much bribe is offered.

15) Accused If NRI:

ACCUSED IF NRI

PASSPORT IMPOUNDED - 9.43%

THREAT TO IMPOUND PASSPORT - 28.30%

THREAT TO ISSUE LOC - 20.75%

PRESSURE TO COME TO INDIA FOR ENQUIRY - 24.53%

THREAT TO ARREST OLD PARENTS IF NOT COMING TO INDIA - 16.98%

In the case of non-resident Indians (NRI) the process has often proved calamitous for the husband. When wife has differences and have an argument. She deserts and will fly back to India, often with children and as much of the valuable /assets as she can gather. She immediately starts a Section 498A case in India and then sues for divorce and custody in India and many manage to get Look out circular (LOC) issued. The husband cannot step foot in India because he will be arrested. Meanwhile his relatives in India are clamoring for him to settle up with his wife because they have been in jail or are fearful that that will happen. The Supreme Court of India has described such conduct as “legal terrorism. All because of Police involvement, they file case without any evidence, just on the words of the women. Without a need to say they take money, they threaten to impound passport or issue LOC, arrest relatives. Here as a result mostly police Impound the passport, even though only Passport Authority has the right to Impound.

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16) Investigation Method:

INVESTIGATION METHOD (M)

POLICE ABUSE - 28.99%

POLICE ALLOW ACCUSER TO ABUSE AND BEAT - 8.79%

NO WOMEN POLICE AVAILABLE - 9.45%

WOMEN AND SENIOR CITIZENS ABUSED / HARASSED - 24.43%

THREAT TO BEAT / ARREST ADD ADDITIONAL CASES - 28.34%

As soon as women files a complaint or women goes to the Police station with her problem, some Police only direct her to a lawyer whom they have nexus. Lawyer along with the Police draft a complaint and ask the women to sign, then Police will call her husband and most of the times his aged Parents and threaten to arrest, as per survey reply most of the time Police will abuse and manhandle also. If husband is not ready to agree to their terms, they will add additional sections to make their case stronger and abuse and trap the man.

17) Police Helped To Unite Or Solve The Problem:

POLICE HELPED TO UNITE OR SOLVE THE PROBLEM (M)

NO - 67.36%

YES - 9.62%

FORCE TO AGREE - 9.21%

FORCE TO PAY AS MUCH DEMANDED - 13.81%

Out of 2000 survey result only 9% said they are helped by Police to solve their domestic matter. When women go to Police station, she is just another client from whom they can make some money threatening her husband so both can bribe them. Police hardly help unless man pays more than women does or has some influential connections.

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18) Experience in Caw / Mediation Center:

EXPERIENCE IN MEDIATION CENTER / CAW (M)

ABUSED AND HARASSED - 16.67%

THREATENING ENVIRONMENT - 18.36%

NEUTRAL ENVIRONMENT - 6.50%

FRIENDLY ENVIRONMENT - 0.56%

AUTHORITY IS BIASED - 25.71%

NAMESAKE ENQUIRY - 32.20%

When Man/Husband is called to CAW or mediation center they will not allow anyone from husband's side, but they will allow women along with her relatives and lawyers, most of the CAW cells do namesake enquiries, they are always on women's side, and force man to agree to their terms / Pay her. Kick out his parents from him, abuse and threat are common in CAW only 0.56% said CAW is friendly environment.

19) About Investigating Authority:

ABOUT INVESTIGATING AUTHORITY (M)

POLITE - 5.67%

CORRUPT - 21.22%

RUDE AND ABUSIVE - 15.76%

SUPPORT WOMEN ONLY - 27.10%

NO RESPECT FOR ELDERLY - 13.45%

DEMANDED MONEY TO REMOVE NAMES - 11.13%

DONE PROPER INVESTIGATION - 1.26%

ADDED OTHER FAMILY MEMBER NAMES - 4.41%

In India no Judiciary or Police support man when women complaint against man. There is standing order from top, no matter who is guilty, women should not suffer, this woman

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is only Daughter-in-law, even National commission of women says husband Mother / Sisters are not coming under their mandate. Police always support young Women, there is no respect for elderly if they are Man's parents. Indian Police is not only corrupt and abusive they think women is always right and Man is a born criminal.

20) Result of FIR / Complaint:

RESULT OF FIR / COMPLAINT (M)

CHARGE SHEET FILED AFTER PROPER ENQUIRY - 1.97%

CHARGE SHEET FILED WITHOUT ENQUIRY - 29.56%

CALLING TO POLICE STATION DAILY - 5.67%

FAMILY MEMBER NAMES ADDED - 10.59%

FAMILY MEMBER NAMES REMOVED - 4.19%

TOOK MONEY AND FIR DISMISSED - 0.49%

TOOK MONEY AND OTHERS NAMES REMOVED - 2.46%

TOOK MONEY BUT CHARGE SHEET FILED - 6.65%

INVESTIGATION GOING ON FOR MORE THAN YEAR - 8.62%

FIR PENDING / POLICE DID NOTHING - 8.13%

CHARGE SHEET IS COPY PASTE OF FIR - 15.02%

CHARGE SHEET WITHOUT DIR - 6.65%

As said earlier most of the Women centric complaints end up in a charge-sheet without any CrPC 41A notice / investigation or enquiry. Police just copy paste women statement and turn it as a charge-sheet, they add other family members to pressurize and make the case complicated.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate — merely 12.1 per cent — among all cases of crimes against women.

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According to the latest data on crimes, released by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), more than 3.3 lakhs cases of crimes against women were registered in 2016. Of these, 1.1 lakhs cases related to ‘Cruelty by husband or his relatives’.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate — merely 12.1 per cent — among all cases of crimes against women.

“Assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty”, kidnapping, and rape, which formed the next three major chunks of crimes against women, had conviction rates of 21.8%, 21.4% and 25.5% in 2016, according to NCRB.

Close to 10,000 cases were also registered under the Dowry Prohibition Act in 2016, but conviction rate here too was just over 15%.

(News source: <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/section-498a-dowry-most-firs-least-convictions-4969913/>)

NCRB data shows 85% Dowry Prohibition Act cases are fake, which shows the real truth behind all these women centric cases.

False case of matrimonial issue which not only is enough to tarnish the image of a familial man, or person, or a family in the eyes of the society but often drive people to other extreme measure as harming themselves, creating depression and even driving many to end their precious God given life, and all this is not because women are victims, it’s just because they just could, and in turn they harm the same gender these laws were put in place to help; the real victim of such heinous crimes.

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It not only seems women have a free run with laws, the judiciary, the police but the society at large, some of these cases takes most of the good years of a man's life, the average being 5 years, consider being in litigation for 5 whole years of life and that is less the actual time for a person to come out of a divorce maybe 10 or 15 years.

If the accused is an NRI, then these harassments may take another form like passport impoundment, pressure to come back for enquiries or just plain harassment of relatives.

Many enquire, don't the police try to mediate? Although by now we should know the answer but sometimes they do (we are not saying that the entire police force is bad or corrupt) but why would a monkey stop two cats from fighting over a piece of bread.

Either we have lost all our wisdom where family was a unit of love, sacrifice, duty and service to each other or somewhere, someplace in imitating the west, western law. The blinded wave of feminism which sees the opposite sex as the enemy rather seeing the greatness of the creator, Mother Nature or whatever we may term it. Where social justice warriors don't know anything about justice, we have tipped the balance of well rooted culture, where humility, love and the wellbeing of children was the quintessential and unalienable motives for coming and being together through the ups and downs of life. This is just for the sake of fake narrative which in the end turns up to nothing to us as a person no matter the gender.

With this we would like to point out that although it is a general perception that females are usually at the receiving end of a hard bargain called marriage the current scenario is not such, men are equally even more oppressed and if we really want to create a just and equal society we must examine and clear the rot which is slowly but surely spreading

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through our society, we have done it many times when the world sees towards our great nation in awe that how a peninsula so ancient and seemingly archaic can shine such light on this planet and holding a beacon of rays of hopes in our hands and feel proud about it.

It is understandable that the judiciary wants to examine every case and follow the procedures of laws but the harassment begins even before the man reaches to the courts, the state of affairs of police functioning is not hidden from the citizenry of our nation, but our survey points out that in such cases no or little procedure is followed by the police as far as 32 percent cases don't even make an effort to make a call to ascertain the allegations even from the alleged male perpetrators.

Moreover there are specialized police station or cells and commission who go over and above board and law and start punishing and harassing the man openly and brazenly even before the cases reaches the court, most of the times the accused are made to sign forced pre filled questionnaires, even blank papers, or forced and coerced to agree to unjust terms of the women, and if someone doesn't agree to their terms they are threatened, charges are framed without any real enquires, bribes are demanded and the routine or extra law sections are inserted to harass and make the case stronger.

Police should always be the first line of defense to stop crime as well as violate law or misuse of law, but in India, Indian Police are first to misuse law and violate it. Above survey is enough to show how they support law misusers just for few hundred rupees, they have no value for the person who is aged, paralyzed or breast fed baby (<https://supari.org/zoya/> - **2 Month old Charged under 498a – Get Bail**), they blindly take any complaint if its filed by a Women. This shows the Police support for LEGAL TERRORISM, as they are the main part of this misuse.

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Chapter 9:

Study on Men Crimes by Indian Women

All the violence is male-generated, for the women, by the women.

“A society with a great number of prisons is a totally failed society because it has terribly failed to create a marvellous society where crime is not something widespread but an exception!” - Mehmet Murat ildan

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Summary:

The term "*Crimes by Indian women*" covers a broad range of atrocities, harassments, false cases, violent acts committed by Women on men mostly on her husband / partner. Some news also covers instances where men took the drastic step and killed the wife and her family when his tolerance reached the peak of harassment and was left with no option of solution under laws of India which are biased against men. Because of this many men suffer in silence and many a times die in the hands of women too.

Key Findings:

Majority of the men are ashamed to come forward to report such daily abuse in the hands of their wives. Most of the news report we collected reveal that most women use their gender to get away with the crime they committed, even if the partner/husband is killed. Indian courts are lenient towards women and they are sentenced to less than 2/3 years for the murder of the husband. Law always portray women as ABLA NARI (victim/innocent) and her husband was killed by her while defending herself of his abuse. Dead men will not speak, Indian Police will not investigate nor do Indian courts take any *suo moto* to charge such criminal women.

Methodology:

Information for this report was sourced from various secondary sources, and various news publications which are listed in the Reference List with source after every news report. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are

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neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies. Even the survey data study Institutes or Media is not ready to publish such abuse, harassment and killings of Men.

Introduction:

MyNation analysis of statistics on Crimes by Indian Women shows that the number of men attacked/abused/harassed and killed by wives and girlfriends are much higher than ever thought. If a Woman dies even by accident, news media reports the death as tragic and highlight it in the main page of main stream media. In India it's often assumed that the women are ABLA NARI, the victim and men are the perpetrator/abuser. But the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations.

Terming men as perpetrator is not only common by Feminists controlled Media but even Maneka Gandhi, the elected union minister of Government of India for women and child development. She openly mentioned that the role of men in gender sensitization was critical since "*all the violence is male-generated*", which implies that it applies even to her Father and son.

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All violence is male-generated: Maneka Gandhi

Courting controversy, union minister for women and child development Maneka Gandhi on Monday said that the role of men in gender sensitisation was critical since "all the violence is male-generated".

INDIA Updated: Sep 14, 2015 15:05 IST

HT IANS

SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india/all-violence-is-male-generated-maneka-gandhi/story-QzbDLrEhuCOr5Rjst9KD4O.html>

Union minister Maneka Gandhi's actual motive is to say is not only Brand men as violent but term Women as ABLA NARI. ABLA is a Hindi/Sanskrit word which means "helpless". Nari means women. By twisting meaning of one word she can justify two theories that all men are violent and all women are victims of Men.

These reports are exact copy of what is printed by news media, and posted here without any changes. Now it's up to the readers to decide what the truth is, as feminist's

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media shows and Government of India defend that all women are innocent victim of Men, even though she is a Villain / Criminal.

MURDERS BY WOMEN:

1) Man murdered by wife, her paramour in Tamil Nadu; arrests made 10 months after incident

A woman and her paramour were arrested in Tamil Nadu, ten months after they allegedly murdered her husband.

A man's charred body was found by the police in Tamil Nadu around 10 months ago. An investigation done by the police revealed that the man had been murdered by his wife and her paramour. Both the accused have been arrested.

Cuddalore: A man was allegedly murdered by his wife and her paramour in Tamil Nadu. The two accused were arrested in Cuddalore district of Tamil Nadu on Wednesday, around 10 months after the incident took place. The accused allegedly killed the victim when he learned about their affair.

The accused have been identified as- S Sudha and Sivaraj. Initially, Sudha made an attempt to evade arrest by cooking up a story. The deceased was identified as Sridharan.

Deceased's wife cooks up story

Sudha claimed that her husband had been on the run as he was unable to repay the loans he had taken from his family and friends. A police investigation, however, revealed the truth and the two accused were arrested.

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The incident first came to light when the Oomangalam police recovered a completely burnt body from a cashew grove. After the body was found, the village administrative officer registered a complaint on July 13. Meanwhile, the police registered a case under section 174 (unnatural death) of the CrPC and started investigating the case.

Accused used to work with deceased; According to the police, Sridharan used to work as a bus driver for a college, The Times of India reported. Sivaraj also used to work at the same college and with time, he became friends with Sridharan. As the friendship strengthened, Sivaraj started visiting Sridharan's home and after some time, he started having an affair with Sudha.

One day, Sridharan caught his wife and Sivaraj in a compromising position and allegedly attacked them. On being attacked, Sivaraj and Sudha allegedly used a belt to strangle Sridharan to death.

Following this, they rolled the bus driver's body in a bedsheet and hid it under a cot. Following this, Sivaraj took the body to the cashew grove in a car and dumped it there. Before leaving, the accused poured petrol over the body and set it ablaze.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/man-murdered-by-wife-her-paramour-in-tamil-nadu-arrests-made-10-months-after-incident/592098>

2) Woman, her paramour sentenced to jail by Punjab court for murdering husband

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On Wednesday, a woman and her alleged boyfriend were sent to jail in Punjab. The woman allegedly murdered her husband after he discovered her extra-marital affair. The deceased was identified as Jaswinder Singh

Sangrur: A court in Punjab sent a woman and her paramour to jail for murdering her husband. The incident took place in 2018). The convicts have been identified as Mandeep Kaur alias Aman and Mohammad Shehbaz. Mohammad is a resident of Malerkotla.

Mandeep is a resident of Changli. The order was given by additional sessions judge Rajneesh. The deceased was identified as Jaswinder Singh. The court awarded life imprisonment to the two convicts.

According to the court order, Jaswinder was killed by his wife and her alleged boyfriend. The judgement read, "No ground is made out to award any kind of mild punishment than prescribed in the statute. "

The incident first came to light when the man's body was found near the link road at Ahen Kheri village, the Hindustan Times reported. The police had booked the two accused under section 302 (murder), 120-B (criminal conspiracy) and 201 (disappearance of evidence of offence) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC). A FIR was registered at the Sandaur police station in 2018, soon after the incident was brought to the notice of the local police.

Woman smothers husband after he discovers her affair; cremates body using fake certificate

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In February this year, a woman allegedly killed her husband after he found out about her extra marital affair. The victim was identified as Mahesh Patel. Patel's wife Ujjawala Das murdered him with the assistance of her paramour and his friend.

The woman's paramour was identified as Arup. Arup used to work at a canteen in South Mumbai. The third accused has been identified as Sagar Sharma. The accused poisoned the victim using a tablet. After poisoning the victim, the accused allegedly smothered him with a pillow.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/woman-her-paramour-sentenced-to-jail-by-punjab-court-for-murdering-husband/565935>

3) Woman booked for driving husband to commit suicide in Pune

PUNE Updated: Dec 10, 2019 16:29 IST

The deceased's mother told the police in the complaint that the accused woman made her husband do the household chores, which led him to commit suicide

A woman has been booked by the Hadapsar police for abetment of suicide of her husband at their residence in Magarpatta, Hadapsar.

The deceased man has been identified as Pranay Milind Khutal, 29, a resident of Zinnia building in Magarpatta. He is suspected to have committed suicide, by hanging himself, on the night intermediate of December 6 and December 7.

The complaint was lodged by Sangita Khutal, 49, the mother of the deceased man.

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Khutal lives in Limboda village of Hatod taluka in Indore, Madhya Pradesh. The deceased's mother told the police in the complaint that the accused woman made Pranay do the household chores, which led him to commit suicide.

The complainant told the police that the wife would beat Pranay up, force him to wash clothes and utensils and make tea, according to the police.

The accused woman has been identified as Kanika Khutal, who is in her late 20s. While the deceased man was an employee at a private company, the accused woman is a housewife, according to the police.

“They have been married since 2015. They have lived in various places, including Bhopal and Indore, before moving to Magarpatta six months ago,” said assistant police inspector (API) VO Bhabad of Hadapsar police station, who is investigating the case.

When the man was found hanging, a case of accidental death was registered at the Hadapsar police station.

A case under Sections 306 (abetment of suicide) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) has now been registered at the Hadapsar police station.

SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/pune-news/woman-booked-for-driving-husband-to-commit-suicide-in-pune/story-EaUFQm1qIpfRgaXdYJf9qN.html>

4) Uttar Pradesh: Wife caught red-handed with lover; kills husband

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Shocking news has come to light from Lucknow where a 32-year-old woman killed her husband after he caught her red-handed with a paramour in their house in Madiyaon on Sunday. Husband's father filed FIR of murder against his daughter-in-law.

As per police, Akhilesh Kumar who is an electrician by profession was married to Priyanka (accuse) for 12 years. A few months ago, Akhilesh's acquaintance Ramesh who is a civil contractor grew close to the couple.

Since then he started visiting their house in his absence, Akhilesh objected and asked Priyanka to not let him in but Ramesh continued to visit. Owing to this both husband and wife used to fight quite often. On Sunday evening, when Akhilesh returned home early from work, he caught his wife and Ramesh together.

Both the men engaged in a physical fight and heat of the situation both Ramesh and Priyanka end up killing Akhilesh. After killing him they planned to dispose of the body at night, however, a friend of Akhilesh arrived and on seeing the body he immediately called the police.

Priyanka confessed to the crime whereas Ramesh is on run, as per SHO Vipin Kumar Singh.

SOURCE: <http://www.catchnews.com/amp/national-news/uttar-pradesh-wife-caught-red-handed-with-lover-kills-husband-183192.html>

5) Woman, her paramour sentenced to jail by Punjab court for murdering husband

An additional sessions judge in Punjab awarded life imprisonment to a woman and her paramour for murdering the former's husband.

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On Wednesday, a woman and her alleged boyfriend were sent to jail in Punjab the woman allegedly murdered her husband after he discovered her extra-marital affair the deceased was identified as Jaswinder Singh

Sangrur: A court in Punjab sent a woman and her paramour to jail for murdering her husband. The incident took place in 2018). The convicts have been identified as Mandeep Kaur alias Aman and Mohammad Shehbaz. Mohammad is a resident of Malerkotla.

Mandeep is a resident of Changli. The order was given by additional sessions judge Rajneesh. The deceased was identified as Jaswinder Singh. The court awarded life imprisonment to the two convicts.

According to the court order, Jaswinder was killed by his wife and her alleged boyfriend. The judgement read, "No ground is made out to award any kind of mild punishment than prescribed in the statute. "

The incident first came to light when the man's body was found near the link road at Ahen Kheri village, the Hindustan Times reported. The police had booked the two accused under section 302 (murder), 120-B (criminal conspiracy) and 201 (disappearance of evidence of offence) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC). A FIR was registered at the Sandaur police station in 2018, soon after the incident was brought to the notice of the local police.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/woman-her-paramour-sentenced-to-jail-by-punjab-court-for-murdering-husband/565935>

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6) Delhi Police solve 8-year-old murder mystery, woman killed husband with paramour's help

The accused Shakuntala had an alleged illicit relationship with Kalamal Singla before her marriage to Ravi Kumar, a resident of Kapashera in Delhi. Later, the two decided to get rid of Ravi from their lives.

Kapashera murder

The woman and her paramour took Ravi's body to Bhiwadi in a car and buried his remains into a pit along the Kishangarh Bas highway. Key Highlights Delhi Police claim to solve 8-year-old murder mystery Police say Ravi's wife and her paramour killed him in 2011 The wife of the victim is still on the run

Alwar: In a major breakthrough, the Delhi Police claimed to have solved an 8-year-old murder mystery of a man by arresting his wife's paramour. The wife of the deceased is still on the run.

The victim identified as Ravi Kumar, a resident of Kapashera locality in Delhi, was allegedly killed by his wife Shakuntala and her paramour Kamal Singla in 2011.

After the murder, the woman and her paramour took Ravi's body to Bhiwadi area of Alwar district in Rajasthan in a car and buried his remains in a pit along the Kishangarh Bas highway.

According to a report, the Crime Branch of Delhi Police has now recovered 27 bones of the victim from Bhiwadi on Saturday.

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Recently, the case was transferred to the crime branch of Delhi Police after a Heabous Corpus plea was filed by the family of the deceased in a court.

As the accused learnt that the case was transferred to the crime branch, the two accused went back to Alwar to dig out Ravi's remains to erase the evidence.

However, they managed to recover only some of the bones as the body was completely decomposed. Later, the accused buried the bones along the 70-km stretch on Alwar-Delhi Highway.

During the course of the investigation, Delhi Police came to know that Shakuntala was in an illicit relationship with Kamal Singla.

After the revelation, the police arrested Singla and sent him for a polygraph test. After the test, accused Singla revealed the murder plot to police.

Shakuntala had met Kamal in early 2010 at her village in Alwar. Both fell in love, but she had to marry Ravi in 2011 due to family compulsions.

Shakuntala, however, returned to her village a day after she was married. The two later planned to kill Ravi to get rid of him from their lives.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/video-delhi-police-solve-8-year-old-murder-mystery-woman-killed-husband-with-paramours-help/500867>

7) UP woman bludgeons boyfriend of 8 years, sets him ablaze to marry another man

Bareilly woman murder boyfriend

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28-year-old man was murdered by his girlfriend and her alleged paramour in Uttar Pradesh after he asked her to wait for 'marriage'.

Uma asked Yogesh to meet him near his shop at around 9.30 pm.

Key Highlights: A woman in Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh was arrested on Tuesday along with her paramour for allegedly murdering a 28-year-old man. The woman was in a relationship with the deceased. She decided to murder the 28-year-old man allegedly after he asked her to wait for marriage.

Bareilly: On Monday, the charred body of a 28-year-old man was found near the Kumar cinema hall in Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh. The police launched an investigation into the case to nab the persons behind the murder. Shailesh Pandey, senior superintendent of police (SSP) of Bareilly, announced a cash reward of Rs 15,000 for solving the case within 24 hours.

After the reward was announced, additional SP (crime) R K Bhartiya and his team started searching for suspects and collecting evidence. Within 24 hours, the cops managed to track down two persons who murdered the 28-year-old man.

Girlfriend of 8 years was behind murder

The deceased was identified as Yogesh Saxena. Saxena was in a relationship with Uma Shukla. Uma and Yogesh had been together for 8 years.

According to an investigation, Uma was married but in 2014, Uma moved out of her husband's house and started living separately. She had also filed a dowry case against her husband. Soon after she moved out, Uma and Yogesh began their courtship.

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Deceased asked his girlfriend to wait for marriage

The Times of India reported that Uma wanted to get married but Yogesh had asked her to wait. Yogesh could not get married as his elder sister was not married. After Yogesh asked Uma to wait, she allegedly decided to kill him. Desperate to tie the knot, Uma took the decision of marrying Sunil, a local storekeeper.

How it happened

On Sunday, Uma asked Yogesh to meet him near his shop around 9.30 pm. During this time, Sunil was waiting to attack Yogesh. When Yogesh arrived at the spot, Sunil sprayed red chili powder in his eyes and slit his throat.

Accused tried to burn body

After attacking Yogesh, Sunil fled the spot and met Uma who was waiting outside a private hospital. After some time, the two (Uma and Sunil) came back to the spot where Yogesh had been attacked to ensure that he had died. After checking that Yogesh had succumbed, the two accused burned his body after pouring petrol on it.

After completing the investigation, the police booked the two accused under relevant sections of the Indian Penal Code (IPC)

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/up-woman-bludgeons-boyfriend-of-8-years-sets-him-ablaze-to-marry-another-man/560670>

8) Tamil Nadu: Woman smashes ex-boyfriend's head in front of husband

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The victim identified as 38-year-old M Ravi, a film technician, was killed by a small-time TV actor in Kolathur area of Chennai after the victim insisted, she resumes her relationship with the man.

TV actor murders boyfriend

In the melee, the actor smashed Ravi's head with a hammer who collapsed after bleeding profusely and died on the spot.

Key Highlights: Woman kills ex-boyfriend in front of her husband in Chennai. Accused is identified as 42-year-old small time TV actor S Devi After killing Ravi, Devi reached police station and confessed to murder

Chennai: In a shocking incident, a woman allegedly killed her former boyfriend by smashing his head after he insisted that the woman resume her relationship with him. The victim has been identified as 38-year-old M Ravi, a film technician.

The 42-year-old woman, who is said to be a Television actor, killed the man after hitting him on his head with a log and a hammer at her sister's house in Kolathur area of the city.

According to a report in the Times of India, the accused actor identified as S Devi later surrendered to police. Police have also arrested Devi's husband, her sister Lakshmi and Lakshmi's husband in connection with the murder.

All four accused have been sent to jail by a local court. According to the police, the victim, a resident of Madurai, befriended the smalltime TV actor and started a relationship with her.

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Around two years back, the actor's husband came to know of her alleged affair with Ravi and persuaded her to end her relationship with the man to which she agreed.

After some time, the victim managed to trace Devi in Kolathur area where she had been living and running clothing her smalltime business.

On Monday, Ravi reached Devi's sister's house at around 1.30 am and pleaded her to help him get to reunite with the actor. Devi's sister Lakshmi lives in the same neighbourhood. After Ravi's insistence, Lakshmi allegedly called Devi to her residence in the middle of the night. Devi's husband also accompanied her to Lakshmi's house.

As Devi and her husband reached Lakshmi's home, Ravi kept the same demand before the actor and a heated exchange erupted.

In the melee, the actor allegedly smashed Ravi's head with a hammer who collapsed after bleeding profusely and died on the spot. Later, the actor reached Rajamangalam police station and confessed to killing the film technician.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/tamil-nadu-woman-smashes-ex-boyfriend-s-head-in-front-of-husband/534006>

9) Chhattisgarh: Woman commits suicide after murdering her sons

A woman hanged herself after murdering her two sons in a village near Chhattisgarh. The incident sent shockwaves across the village.

The 30-year-old woman was alone at her house with the two kids.

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Key Highlights A woman killed her two sons and then hanged herself in Chhattisgarh. An investigation into the matter has been initiated and policemen are questioning the kin of the deceased.

Raipur: In a horrific incident being reported from Chhattisgarh, a woman committed suicide after hanging her two little children as well. The crime was committed in Madeli village of the state and the entire area is stunned by it.

The woman, identified as Khilleshwari Sahu, had taken her life after hanging her two children, identified as 4-year-old Anirudh and 3-year-old Daksh. The news of this spread like wildfire and villagers gathered in large numbers at the scene of the crime.

According to a report in Amar Ujala, the 30-year-old woman was alone at her house with the two kids and when her husband returned home from the fields, he found the three bodies hanging from the ceiling from separate ropes.

He immediately raised an alarm and gathered the neighbors. Subsequently, police arrived on the site and took down the bodies of the three deceased. The bodies have been sent for post mortem to a local hospital and the results are awaited.

An investigation into the matter has been initiated and policemen are questioning the kin of the deceased to figure out the sequence of events.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/chhattisgarh-woman-commits-suicide-after-murdering-her-sons/532533>

10) WOMEN KILL HUSBAND - LOCKDOWN WAS THE FINAL STRAW

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65-yr-old woman who developed mental health issues after losing both her sons murders her husband; he was unable to get meds to control her temper

A mentally challenged woman who could not get medicines on time reportedly murdered her husband by attacking him with sharp weapons at their house, in the vicinity of the 4th phase of KIADB on the Hosakote-Hosur Main Road on Friday at around 3 am.

The victim has been identified as Ramaswamy Reddy, 70; the accused is Reddy's wife, Gowamma, 65. After losing both her sons one after the other, the woman is alleged to have been under severe mental shock and started displaying violent behaviour. Reddy is an agriculturist and his wife was a homemaker.

“After the death of her two sons, Gowamma developed mental health issues and was reportedly being treated at National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences (NIMHANS) for her mental illness. Due to the nation-wide lockdown, Reddy was unable to get her the tablets she needed. Gowamma's behavior was so volatile that fearing an attack, Reddy would sleep in their other house, close by. On Friday morning, her behavior got out of hand and she attacked her husband. The chaos woke the neighbors and when they came to check, she apparently tried to attack them too,” said an officer on part of the investigation.

“Seeing Reddy injured, the neighbors drove him to a government hospital in Malur. From there, he was being taken to another hospital in Kolar in the ambulance where he succumbed to injuries,” added the officer.

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It is said that the woman was not even aware of having killed her husband. When the relatives went to see her at the police station, she reportedly asked them to send her husband.

“After her arrest, her relatives brought to our notice that she is mentally challenged and even furnished copies regarding her treatment. The woman has been arrested and subjected to medical tests. Since she has already killed her husband, she would be a threat to even others,” the officer added.

A case of murder under section 302 of the Indian Penal Code has been registered against the woman.

Further investigations are on.

SOURCE: https://bangaloremirror.indiatimes.com/bangalore/crime/lockdown-was-the-final-straw/amp_articles/75213050.cms

11) Woman, her paramour held for killing husband

New Delhi: A 35-year-old woman and her paramour were arrested for allegedly killing her husband in North West Delhi.

According to police, on January 4, the complainant reported regarding missing of his brother. Subsequently, the search for the missing person was started.

During the investigation, an unidentified body was identified by complainant as his missing brother. He also raised suspicion over the wife of the deceased and her friend named Ajay.

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Deputy Commissioner of Police (north-west) Vijayanta Arya said during the investigation they arrested four people including deceased's wife for murder.

According to police during the investigation, it came to notice that there was an extramarital relationship between deceased friend Ajay and wife of the deceased.

Her husband restricted her to meet Ajay due to which she provoked Ajay for killing her husband so that they could live together freely.

It was also revealed that two friends of Ajay identified as Sonu and Suresh were also found involved in the crime. On the day of murder Ajay approached deceased in a friendly way and he along with Ajay and Sonu made him consume liquor with the preconceived motive to murder Satyanarayan.

SOURCE: <http://www.millenniumpost.in/amp/delhi/woman-her-paramour-held-for-killing-husband-397120>

12) Gujarat: 26-year-old woman teacher elopes with Class VIII boy

Ahmedabad: Cops in Gandhinagar fell in a catch-22 situation, when a state government employee approached them with a complaint that the 26-year-old woman class teacher of his 14-year-old son had gone missing taking his son in tow. The man, who works at Udyog Bhavan in Gandhinagar said the woman had seduced his teenage son, who studies in class VIII and taken him away with her. The boy had gone missing from 4pm on Friday, and the class teacher was also missing.

A police official said the woman teacher had been too intimate with the allegedly missing boy for around a year, and the school authorities had recently rebuked them. “As their

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relationship was unaccepted, they left their homes on Friday,” he said. It was rare to find a case of a woman teacher eloping with her teenage student, the official added.

SOURCE: <https://ahmedabadmirror.indiatimes.com/ahmedabad/crime/gujarat-26-year-old-woman-teacher-elopes-with-class-viii-boy/articleshow/73424615.cms>

13) Wife kills husband with devar

Husband used to torture so wife makes illicit relation with brother-in-law

Recently, a case of crime has come to light from Meerut where the police have revealed the killing of BSF soldier as shocking. In this case, he told, "Brother and wife killed the soldier due to illicit relations and due to illicit relations. BSF soldier Sanjeev Kumar, resident of Parikshitgarh of Durgeshpur area was killed and, in this case,, the police arrested the accused within 12 hours. The young man was killed by his wife and brother due to an illicit relation.

In this case, the pistol used in the murder has been recovered and the police arrested the wife and his brother-in-law. According to the reported news, CO Sadar Dehat Akhilesh Bhadoria said, "Sanjeev Kumar's posting was in Pulwama. He came on leave on Monday. He was shot and killed on the farm on Tuesday evening. Soldier's wife Gitanjali was detained and questioned. She was repeatedly changing statements. CDR of his mobile was taken out, in which a long conversation with brother-in-law Gulab Singh aka Gullu came out. Roses were also taken into custody. He strictly questioned the brother-in-law, in which he confessed to killing Sanjeev.

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In this case, the police say, "The woman said that Sanjeev used to harass her. She used to tell her brother-in-law, Gulab about it. This led to an illicit relationship between the two. They plan to kill Sanjeev. Under planning, the wife took Sanjeev to the farm where Gulab was already present. He shot and killed his brother Sanjeev." In this case, the police said that the wife and brother had planned the murder 5 days earlier and killed him as soon as the young man arrived.

SOURCE: <https://english.newstracklive.com/ampnews/wife-kills-husband-with-devar-sc103-nu-1064716-1.html>

14) Dehradun: Wife murders his husband along with 22-year-younger boyfriend

Recently, a new case of crime has come out from Juddli Aduwala village in Vikasnagar, Dehradun, where a man was murdered by his own wife along with his lover. The police have disclosed this fact within 24 hours after the incident.

The news has been received that SP Dehat Parminder Doval, while disclosing the matter said that, "The murder was done by shooting him in the head. The wife of Rohit (changed name) and her lover have been arrested. There have been reports that the lover is 22 years younger than the wife of the deceased and the police is searching for the weapon used in the murder in this case." He has announced a reward of Rs 2500 to the police team who made the revelations. In this case, news has been received that the police were suspicious of Rohit's wife since the incident and the reason was the circumstances, in which the husband is asleep next door and the wife is not aware of it. Doubt on the wife was also expressed by Rohit's father Molhar son Lal Singh resident Judli and in the tahrir to the

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police 'he had expressed doubt on the son's wife (42) as well as the lover (20) of the wife living in the neighborhood. "

After the news of this suspicion, the police questioned both in custody and both accepted their crime. In this case, news of both being produced in court has come to light.

SOURCE: <https://english.newstracklive.com/ampnews/wife-murder-husband-with-her-boyfriend-dehradun-sc103-nu-1082914-1.html>

15) Wife murders husband with boyfriend during lockdown

At present, cases of crime are going on increasing even in lockdown and every day some or the other case comes which is shocking. In such a case, the matter which has come up recently is of illicit love affair. Due to which the wife along with the lover killed her husband. According to the information, the murder of 26-year-old Ralu father Magan Singadia of village Nawapada under Meghnagar police station area of Jhabua district has been revealed four days before today.

The love affair was going on for three years between the wife of the deceased and Hursih Charpota living in village Jhabdara in Jhabua district. Both used to work in Gujarat. During this time, illegal relations also formed between them. Meanwhile, during the ongoing lockdown, all of them had come to their villages due to the work being stopped in Gujarat. Meanwhile, the wife of the deceased, seeing the husband coming in the love affair, planned to kill the husband with the lover. Thereafter, late on 11 May, the lover and the wife of the deceased tried to kill the husband by tying his hands and legs by strangling him with a rope, and the husband did not lose his life on several occasions.

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After that, the lover and girlfriend made several attacks on the deceased's private parts, which led to his death. In this case, Meghnagar police station in-charge Kaushalya Chauhan told, "Initially they were misleading the police, but both told the truth after adopting strictness."

SOURCE: <https://english.newstracklive.com/ampnews/woman-murder-husband-with-boyfriend-in-lockdown-sc103-nu612-ta294-1093472-1.html>

16) Noida: BHEL engineer booked over husband's suicide

The two got married in 2014 and were initially living without conflict at Sector 45. They began having fights soon after, due to which the man had to quit his job, the FIR alleged.

A BHEL engineer and her family members have been booked for allegedly abetting the suicide of her husband, who jumped off a high-rise building in Noida. The 39-year-old man jumped off the 10th floor of his residence around 10 am Monday.

Police suspected it to be suicide, and the man's family submitted a complaint the next day against his 32-year-old wife and her family, for allegedly torturing him mentally and physically.

"An FIR was filed under IPC section 306 (abetment of suicide) against the woman, her parents and two brothers. The man's family alleged the woman's family would harass him over the couple's financial issues. They claimed he was tired of the continuous torture. We will take statements of the accused family members and make arrests accordingly," said an officer from Expressway Police Station.

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Police said the woman worked in BHEL's Haridwar office as an engineer, and recently shifted to the Noida branch.

The man had worked as a computer engineer at an American firm.

The two got married in 2014 and were initially living without conflict at Sector 45. They began having fights soon after, due to which the man had to quit his job, the FIR alleged.

As the fights became more frequent, the man shifted to a new apartment, where he lived alone.

He tried to start his own business, which did not take off. The FIR also alleged that the woman's brothers beat him up, and demanded Rs 50 lakhs and a flat he owned. Following this, he became scared and withdrawn as a result, his family alleged.

Police said neighbors would often see him throwing utensils out of the balcony in anger.

The man's family told police that days before his suicide, he also received a death threat from the woman's parents.

SOURCE: <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/delhi/noida-bhel-engineer-booked-over-husbands-suicide-6105072/>

17) Moga man commits suicide in Canada, kin claim harassment from wife, in-laws for cash, property

The deceased's family alleged that for the past several months, he was being harassed by his NRI wife and in-laws, who were forcing him to transfer his family's land in their name or give them Rs 2 crore in cash.

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The deceased, identified as Baljinder Singh (30), allegedly hanged himself, said his family after receiving the news on Tuesday.

A man from Dhalleke village of Moga allegedly committed suicide at his home in Vancouver, Canada, Monday, allegedly because he was being harassed for cash and property by his wife and in-laws.

The deceased, identified as Baljinder Singh (30), allegedly hanged himself, said his family after receiving the news on Tuesday. They alleged that for the past several months, Baljinder was being harassed by his NRI wife and in-laws, who were forcing him to transfer his family's land in their name or give them Rs 2 crore in cash. His passport and PR card were also allegedly confiscated by his in-laws.

Narayan Singh Sidhu, Baljinder's father, said his son had married an NRI woman, who is originally also from Moga, in December 2017. She lived for two months with his family at Dhalleke and then went back to Canada. She delivered a baby girl there and in November 2018, Baljinder also went to Vancouver.

“The couple started having regular fights. Baljinder's wife refused to live with him in a separate house and said she will only live with her parents. Baljinder lived with them in their home for 4-5 months but was regularly abused and harassed. He asked his wife multiple times to shift with him but she refused. They turned him out of their house and demanded 2 crores in cash for giving a divorce. They were also pressurizing him to transfer two kilas of land that we own here, in their name. They refused to return his passport and PR card till the land isn't transferred in their name,” said the father, adding that this was Baljinder's wife's second marriage.

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“We had agreed because a relative was a middleman. Later we got to know that she had divorced her first husband after taking Rs 40 lakhs. Baljinder’s wife and in-laws also got a fake dowry FIR registered against him and his parents with Moga police and alleged that the family demanded an SUV Fortuner from them. It was cancelled as no evidence was found. They also kept all cash and jewellery we gave to the couple during marriage and took another Rs 12 lakhs in the name of getting the couple settled in Canada,” said Sukhwinder Singh, Baljinder’s paternal uncle.

Meanwhile, Baljinder’s father alleged that even after their son’s suicide, his wife’s family had been harassing and threatening them. “We have filed a police complaint today against his wife, her father and uncle. We want proper action against them but neither local police or Canada police have given us any update yet,” said Sukhwinder Singh.

“We want the administration’s help to bring his body back but amid coronavirus travel restrictions, we have no idea if it will be possible,” he added.

Moga Sadar police station SHO said the case will be investigated.

SOURCE: <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/ludhiana/moga-man-commits-suicide-in-canada-kin-claim-harassment-from-wife-in-laws-for-cash-property-6319388/>

18) Thane woman stabs husband to death with help of lover, arrested

Thane: A woman and her paramour were arrested after they killed the woman's husband in Vangani taluka of Thane district.

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The Kulgaon police have arrested Chahat Vishwakarma (32), and her paramour, Viraj Palande (25) from Donegaon in Vangani taluka, for the murder of her husband Vijay Vishwakarma (35)

The deceased Vijay worked as plumber. The accused Chahat is a housewife. The couple got married eight years ago and had a child. They are natives of Gonda district in Uttar Pradesh. Viraj works as driver and he was Chahat's neighbour.

The incident happened at Vishwakarma room situated Donegaon in Vangani taluka on Monday.

According to police, Chahat and Viraj were in a relationship for the past eight months. Vijay had found out about their relationship and objected Chahat illicit relationships with Viraj. However, she refused to listen to her husband.

Chahat and Viraj had planned to kill Vijay because he opposed their relationship. On Sunday night, Chahat mixed some sedative in Vijay drinks and he fell asleep. She called Viraj and asked him to come home. They tied Vijay's hands with a 'dupatta' and slit his throat with a knife. Later, they packed the body in a blanket, put it in the scooter and dumped the body at Ulhas river in Donegaon village in Vangani.

Sandeep Bigade, Assistant Police Inspector from Thane rural crime branch said, "The body was found at Ulhas river in Vangani taluka. We identify him through local informers. We rushed to his resident and questioned his wife and her answers were suspicious. We strictly interrogated her and she confessed the crime along with Viraj".

A case was registered against them under section 302, 201 of Indian Penal Code.

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SOURCE: <https://m.freepressjournal.in/article/mumbai/thane-woman-stabs-husband-to-death-with-help-of-lover-arrested/f7642fc5-d746-4790-90ed-a44160d9ba18>

19) Agra: MCD junior engineer, woman arrested for murder of her husband

AGRA: A 39-year-old woman and her paramour, a junior engineer with MCD South Zone, were arrested by Agra police on Tuesday for alleged murder of her husband two days ago. The two came to know each other through social media and were desperate to get married, cops say.

According to police, BSNL junior technical officer Virender Kumar, 45, was found murdered some 400 meters away from his home near Deep Inter College of Shahganj police jurisdiction in Agra on Sunday morning. Virendra was married to Bhawna for nearly eight years and had two children. The family was living in Panchsheel colony of the city.

Agra SSP Babloo Kumar said: “Within 48 hours of murder, three persons, including the victim’s wife, her paramour 31-year-old Kapil Kumar and his associate Manish Kumar Singh were arrested.”

“During the probe, our team came to know about the illicit affair between Bhawna and Kapil. They came to know each other through Facebook and later decided to get settled. A month back, the two accused along with Kapil’s associate Manish hatched a plan to eliminate Virender Kumar. On January 4 evening, Kapil borrowed his colleague Deepak’s car and drove Agra along with Manish. At around midnight, the two entered into Virender’s house with the help of Bhawna and murdered him,” the SSP said.

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Speaking to TOI, Shahganj SHO Arvind Kumar Singh said: “The deceased Virender Kumar was heavily drunk. The three accused strangulated the victim with the help of mobile phone’s USB cable and also rained kicks and punches to ensure that he dies of internal bleeding. Later Kapil and Manish carried his body in the and dumped it near Deep Inter College. The two then went back to Delhi.”

“In order to misguide the police and family, accused Bhawna claimed that Virender left home with Rs 7000 cash after he received a call on late Saturday night and did not return home. Examinations of phone call records of the victim and his wife revealed that Bhawna was lying and later confessed to her crime,” the SHO added.

Kapil Kumar hails from Ashok Vihar Colony of Agra which is close to the victim’s house, while co-accused Manish is immediate neighbour of Virender. According to police, Manish was preparing for government job while Bhawna has done MSc in zoology.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/agra/mcd-je-woman-arrested-for-murder-of-her-husband-in-agra/amp_articleshow/73145078\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/agra/mcd-je-woman-arrested-for-murder-of-her-husband-in-agra/amp_articleshow/73145078) cms)

20) Bhopal: Woman throws hubby, three kids out of house in bone-chilling night

BHOPAL: Two girls - aged 11 and 15 - were shifted to a shelter home in Bhopal at 1am on Sunday. The move came after their father reached Ashoka Garden police station around 11 pm on Saturday after his wife threw him and his three children out of the house following a spat.

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The police arranged for the man and his 13-year-old son to stay in a night-shelter while the girls were handed over to a shelter home through the City Childline.

Director of City Childline, Archana Sahaye, told TOI that the couple had a dispute following which the woman threw her children and husband out of the house and locked the door. Despite several attempts, she did not open the door.

"The man reached the Ashoka Garden police station around 11 pm and they tried to call up the wife to help the two reconcile. When the wife did not budge, the husband asked the police officers to help him arrange for a safe place for his daughters while the boy stayed with him at a nearby Rain basera," said Sahaye.

The Childline team coordinated with the Ashoka Garden police and got a shelter home in the city to help the two.

"It was freezing and after all the efforts by the police and the husband to make the wife take them back proved futile, the girls were sent to a shelter home at 1 am. They will be kept there till such time the couple sort out their differences," Sahaye added.

Ashoka Garden station house officer Umesh Yadav said that cops have called the wife to the police station on Monday and as they did not file an FIR, because it was the couple's personal issue, the man and his wife will be sent for counselling.

"The girls are safe in the shelter home and the boy is with his father. We will try to provide the couple with proper counselling and make the wife take her family back. We could not talk to the girls on Sunday, but will record their statement if the need arises. So

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far, an FIR has not been lodged and we are hoping that the couple will sort out their differences for the sake of the children," said Yadav.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/bhopal/bhopal-woman-throws-hubby-three-kids-out-of-house-in-bone-chilling-night/amp_articleshow/73115230.cms

21) Madhya Pradesh: Man in quarantine, wife ‘elopes’ with lover

BHOPAL: A quarantined migrant worker in MP’s Chhatarpur district has complained to police that his 46-year-old wife has eloped with her lover.

Police have registered a missing person’s report and are looking for the mother of three.

The 50-year-old migrant, returned to Munderi village on May 19. He worked at construction sites in Delhi and his family lived with him till around one and a half years ago, when his wife returned home with the children.

He came back on a Shramik Special and was in the middle of his 14-day home quarantine when he had to go around looking for his wife.

He says he had quarantined himself on the first floor of his house and his wife and kids lived on the ground floor. On May 24, he woke up to find his room locked from outside. When he managed to get out, his wife was nowhere to be seen and the kids didn’t have a clue, either, says his complaint.

Wrapping a gamccha around his face, he went house to house, knocking on the doors of relatives and acquaintances, to inquire if they had seen his wife.

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SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/bhopal/man-in-quarantine-wife-elopes-with-lover/amp_articleshow/75991048\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/bhopal/man-in-quarantine-wife-elopes-with-lover/amp_articleshow/75991048) cms)

22) Punjab: Man facing dowry charges commits suicide

PATIALA: A 52-two-year-old man on Sunday allegedly committed suicide in Patiala by consuming some poisonous substance two days after he appeared in the police station to join the investigation in a case related to dowry and breach of trust.

The deceased has been identified as Jagdish Singh. The police have booked Jagdish's distant relative Lalit Kumar, 38, of Dhamoli village, an employee in private industry, under sections of abetment to suicide at Banur police station.

Deceased's family alleged that Lalit Kumar somehow developed an extramarital affair with Jagdish's 21-year-old unmarried daughter. They added that around six months ago Lalit's wife came to know about the illicit relations and got annoyed and then she managed to get registered a case of dowry against her husband Lalit, his family members and Lalit's relatives including Jagdish and his 21-year-old daughter.

“Only two days before committing suicide Jagdish has appeared before the court and also visited the police station as he joined the investigation in a case registered against him under sections of dowry. He was a distant relative of the complainant and it seems that he was wrongly implicated in this case by my predecessors but we are investigating into the matter thoroughly,” Banur police station SHO Subash Kumar said.

“Lalit's wife earlier also landed in a mutual compromise in dowry case after both Lalit and Jagdish's daughter had assured her not to continue their illicit relations. However,

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both of them allegedly continued their affair and this remained the bone of contention between the Lalit's wife and Jagdish and his family. Jagdish appeared before the court in this case and I had assured him to get him justice. He has written this in his suicide note too. We are verifying all the facts and will also probe that how a case of dowry was registered against him despite the fact that his involvement does not seem to be", said Subash Kumar.

Deceased's relative Amarjit Singh, who lodged the complaint, said, "I was stunned how the police had falsely implicated Jagdish and his daughter in a dowry case. He was already facing economic distress. Jagdish was twice married and both his wives died in the past."

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/chandigarh/man-facing-dowry-charges-commits-suicide/amp_articleshow/74052004.cms

23) Mohali: 27-year-old married man commits suicide at Balongi

MOHALI: A 27-year-old man allegedly committed suicide by hanging himself from a ceiling fan in his rented accommodation at Balongi late on Monday. No suicide note was found from the crime spot. However, the police have found a copy of a complaint which had been lodged by the victim against his wife and mother-in-law at a police station in Chandigarh some days back.

The victim in the complaint had accused his wife and mother-in-law of harassing him. According to the police, the deceased has been identified as Anil Kumar (27), a resident of Chandigarh and presently living in a rented accommodation at Balongi. He was working in a shopping mall located in Mohali.

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On Monday, the victim hanged himself from a ceiling fan and somebody informed the police about it. After receiving information, a team of Balongi police station reached the spot and took the victim to Kharar civil hospital, where doctors declared him brought dead. Sources said in his complaint he had stated that he got married a few years ago and his wife had lived with him for only 20 days. Later, his wife and his mother-in-law started harassing him.

Yogesh Kumar, Balongi station house officer (SHO), said, "We did not find any suicide note from the spot. We have received an old complaint, which had been lodged by the victim against his wife and mother-in-law. We have initiated inquest proceedings under Section 174 of the CrPC at Balongi police station."

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/chandigarh/mohali-27-year-old-married-man-commits-suicide-at-balongi/amp_articleshow/68807049.cms

24) Chennai: 'Missing electrician killed by ex-girlfriend, hubby'

CHENNAI: An electrician from the city who went missing more than 10 days ago was lured by his former girlfriend to her home in Chittoor, Andhra Pradesh, where she and her husband beat him to death, police said. The body was buried in a vacant plot.

A team of the city police on Thursday arrested Sivakumar, 38, and Madheswari, 34, and charged them with the murder of Karthikeyan, 40, of Sankar Nagar in Pallavaram. After the body of Karthikeyan is found, the arrested couple will be brought to the city, a police officer said. Karthikeyan, also a social activist, was married when he began an affair with Madheswari two years ago, the officer said. She and her husband then lived near his

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house. Sivakumar learned of the affair and the couple went back to Chittoor, the officer said, quoting from the couple's statement.

But, Karthikeyan kept calling her and she complained to her husband. The couple hatched a plan and Madheswari invited him home, saying her husband would be out of station. On December 18, the officer said, Karthikeyan left home without informing his family. At Madheshwari's home, she and her husband hit him with iron rods and logs and buried the body in a vacant plot.

When he did not return home, his family members first thought he may have left on a trip with friends as he sometimes did. But his mobile phone too was switched off and they lodged a complaint with the Shankar Nagar police on December 30. Police found he had spoken to Sivakumar in Chittoor on the day he went missing and that he often spoke to Madheswari. Police rushed to Chittoor and detained the couple who initially said Karthikeyan did not come there.

However, when a neighbor of the couple said he saw a stranger entering their house at night and that he did not see him leaving, police again confronted the couple who admitted to the crime.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/chennai/chennai-missing-electrician-killed-by-ex-girlfriend-hubby/amp_articleshow/73094529.cms

25) Coimbatore child murder case accused surrenders before officials, fractures leg ‘while trying to escape from cops’

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COIMBATORE: A 24-year-old man, who is accused of murdering a three-year-old girl, fractured his right leg when he “tried to escape from police” at Karattumedu in Coimbatore on Tuesday evening.

The accused – Tamil alias Sargunam – was admitted to the prison ward in Coimbatore Medical College Hospital (CMCH)

The body of Devasree was found from near a temple at Karattumedu around five months ago. The body had multiple injuries. Investigations revealed that the girl had been assaulted before being poisoned. The Saravanampatti police registered a case under the Section 302 (murder) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC)

Investigations revealed that the victim’s mother, P Rubini, who had separated from her husband over a year ago, had developed an affair with Tamil. They decided to murder her daughter as she was considered a hindrance to their relationship. The duo had fed the girl with poison-laced biscuits and dumped her body near the temple, said a police official.

While the police managed to arrest Rubini, her boyfriend had remained absconding for nearly five months. A special team was formed to nab the accused. Based on the tip-off that the accused had been roaming in Karnataka, the team visited the spot multiple times but of no avail.

The accused surrendered before officials at the office of the village administrative officer at Karattumedu on Tuesday morning. They handed him over to the Saravanampatty police.

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“After questioning the accused, the police took taken him to Karattumedu government elementary school where the victim was murdered. The man tried to run away from the police. He climbed the compound wall of the school, fell down from there and fractured his right leg,” the official added.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/coimbatore/coimbatore-child-murder-case-accused-surrenders-before-officials-fractures-leg-while-trying-to-escape-from-cops/amp_articleshow/73057913.cms

26) Coimbatore: Drunk woman kills husband following scuffle, arrested

COIMBATORE: A 32-year-old woman and her brother-in-law were arrested on Tuesday for killing her husband in a state of drunken stupor at Periyakuyili near Chettipalayam in Coimbatore district.

The deceased, M Annamalai, 35, from Naduvaneri village in Salem was living in a rented house with his wife A Priya, 32, and two children at Periyakuyili. The couple were daily wage labourers and were used to drinking liquor after work. On many occasions, the couple fought with each other after getting drunk, police said.

On Sunday evening, the couple got involved in a heated argument after consuming liquor at their residence. In a fit of rage, Priya assaulted Annamalai with a stone. Annamalai suffered severe head injuries and died instantly. Police said she killed her husband in the presence of her minor daughter.

A few hours later, Priya became normal and found her husband lying dead in a pool of blood. She rang up her elder sister’s husband K Selvaraj, 35, from Jalikottai near

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Kanavaipudur in Salem district, who hired an ambulance and travelled to Coimbatore the same night.

The duo then took Annamalai's body to his native place at Naduvaneri in Salem early on Monday and told the relatives that her husband had died after a fall under the influence of alcohol.

However, M Sengodan, 40, the elder brother of the deceased, refused to believe their version and informed Magudanchavadi police that there was something amiss. Police took the body to Salem government hospital for a postmortem, which revealed that Annamalai had died of head injuries.

Following the report, Chettipalayam police registered a case against Priya under IPC section 302 (murder) and section 201 (causing disappearance of evidence of offence, or giving false information) against Selvaraj. Both were arrested on Tuesday and remanded to judicial custody.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/coimbatore/drunk-woman-kills-husband-following-scuffle-arrested/amp_articleshow/75836061.cms

27) Day after Haldwani murder, woman accompanying victim held for plotting crime

Nainital: Police on Friday claimed to have solved the murder of 31-year-old Nazim Khan who was shot dead in broad daylight in Chanda Devi forest area in Haldwani by unidentified men on Thursday.

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Addressing a press conference in Bhimtal, police said that the woman accompanying the victim plotted the murder as she was miffed by the fact that he had married another girl despite promising to marry her. “Though both Nazim and the woman are married, they had a relationship for several years and Nazim had even promised to marry her. However, he got married to another girl a few months ago. This miffed the woman who then conspired to kill him,” said Bhowali circle officer (CO), Anusha Badola. The woman had earlier told police that she and Nazim were sitting along the road when three men came and started passing comments at her. This led to a fight and then they shot him. However, police rubbished the statement saying that the woman was trying to deceive them by concocting stories. “We have arrested the accused, identified as Radheshyam, after watching CCTV footages of the area. He has confessed to the crime. We have also seized from him the country pistol which was used in the murder,” Badola said.

Police added that to evade arrest, Radheshyam had got himself admitted to Haldwani hospital after shooting Nazim. “We have also taken into custody the woman who was with Nazim,” Badola said.

Police added that the woman is married and has two daughters. However, her husband is paralysed and lives in Rampur district of Uttar Pradesh.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/dehradun/day-after-haldwani-murder-woman-accompanying-victim-held-for-plotting-crime/amp_articleshow/73088983.cms

28) Haryana: Man commits suicide, in-laws booked in Kurukshetra district

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KURUKSHETRA: Kurukshetra police on Monday registered a case against the wife and in-laws of a man of Sonti village in Haryana's Kurukshetra district for abetment of suicide after he ended his life by consuming poison.

Satpal Singh - father of the deceased Prinkash (22) - has accused his daughter-in-law and his son's in-laws of harassing his son over his income, alleging, his wife even slapped him in front of the family members following which he took the extreme step.

"On February 12, 2018, my son Prinkash got married to Ritu of Indri in the Karnal district. But Ritu never respected her husband due to his meagre income. We had even talked to her family members and a meeting was scheduled for September 29, 2019). During the meeting, they threatened to implicate us in a dowry case and Ritu also slapped Prinkash in front of the relatives. Prinkash later ended his life by consuming poison due to harassment by his wife and in-laws," Satpal alleged. A case against Ritu, her mother Paramjit and her brother Sonu has been registered under Section 306 (abetment of suicide) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) at Ladwa police station.

"We have booked the wife of the deceased and his in-laws for abetment of suicide. The post-mortem of the deceased has been conducted and his body has been handed over to family members for last rites. So far, no arrest has been made," said inspector Om Prakash, SHO, Ladwa police station.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/gurgaon/ladwa-man-commits-suicide-after-consuming-poison-in-laws-booked-under-abetment-charges/amp_articleshow/71395384\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/gurgaon/ladwa-man-commits-suicide-after-consuming-poison-in-laws-booked-under-abetment-charges/amp_articleshow/71395384.cms)

29) Gurugram: Woman gets 5-year jail for snatching cellphone, Rs 1,000

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GURUGRAM: A woman from Badshapur was sentenced to five years in jail by a city court on Friday for snatching a mobile phone and Rs 1,000). The accused had snatched a handbag from an elderly woman in Sadar Bazar in March last year. This is the second time under the Act that a woman is awarded five years of imprisonment in a snatching case in Gurugram. On March 3 last year, Vikash — an Indian Air Force personnel — had gone to Sadar Bazar for shopping with his mother-in-law when a woman snatched her handbag before fleeing. The handbag had mobile phone, Rs 1,000 and some documents.

Vikash tried to chase the woman but taking advantage of the crowd, she managed to escape from the spot. A case was registered at City police station under section 379A (snatching) of IPC. Within a few days, police arrested Poonam (25) who is from Uttar Pradesh. She is staying in Badshapur area, according to the police. After filing the case, investigators put the phone under surveillance. “Soon after snatching the bag, the accused had switched off the phone and removed its SIM card. But after a few days, phone became active with a new number. We tracked the phone using its IMEI number,” said a police officer. He said it was found that the accused bought a new SIM card in her father’s name and was using it in the stolen phone. In a few days, she was tracked and arrested.

Vikash and his mother-in-law could identify the accused in the court. On the basis of the probe findings and the witnesses’ statements, district and sessions judge Man Mohan Dhonchak held her guilty and awarded five years of rigorous imprisonment. She was also fined Rs 25,000). In 2015, Haryana became the first in the country to make the law against snatching harsher. A person convicted of snatching could be sentenced for a maximum of 10 years of jail, as per the amended law. Two new clauses of the law —

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379A and 379B — have been added to Section 379 (theft) of IPC. By doing this, the government has defined snatching is a non-bailable crime.

Earlier, Section 379 of IPC (theft) carried a maximum punishment of three years or a fine, or both. According to 379A (snatching), the convict will be punished with rigorous imprisonment for not less than five years, but this may extend up to 10 years and the convict will be also liable to pay Rs 25,000). As per 379B (snatching and use of force), the offender will be punished with imprisonment for not less than 10 years. This may extend up to 14 years, and the convict will be liable to pay a fine of Rs 25,000)

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/gurgaon/woman-gets-5-year-jail-for-snatching-cellphone-rs-1000/amp_articleshow/73341903\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/gurgaon/woman-gets-5-year-jail-for-snatching-cellphone-rs-1000/amp_articleshow/73341903) cms)

30) Woman murders husband after tiff

Hyderabad: A woman strangled her husband while he was sleeping after he allegedly repeatedly accused her of having an affair. The victim, Mahankali Krishna (36), a welder, was found dead by his brother at his house in Akbarjapet on Thursday. When his family confronted Laxmi, Krishna's wife, she told them he had been behaving strangely for the past 10 days due to unavailability of alcohol. According to police, the victim allegedly suspected that someone had been waiting for his wife outside.

Vexed with her husband's behavior, Laxmi strangled him while he was sleeping, with an iron box wire and killed him. A murder case was registered, while the wife was taken into custody. TNN

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SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/hyderabad/woman-murders-husband-after-tiff/amp_articleshow/75074212\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/hyderabad/woman-murders-husband-after-tiff/amp_articleshow/75074212) cms)

31) Rajasthan: Wife, paramour saw online videos for tips to kill accountant

JAIPUR: The murder of the accountant in Bagru last week planned by his wife and the man that she was in relationship with has unveiled startling revelations including the fact that the couple looked at YouTube videos to find the ideal way to kill the woman's husband. The two planned the murder during the lockdown as they were unable to meet. The two accused knew each other since 1998 and rekindled their relationship couple of years back. The accused admitted that they were inspired by television shows.

Suresh Sharma's (43) body was found dumped on the roadside under Bagru police station area on Tuesday night. The deceased had multiple injuries on upper part of his body. Cops arrested his wife Kusum Sharma (35) and her paramour Puran Mahavar (40) who are currently in judicial custody. During interrogation, cops found that the two accused had known each other since 1998 when and after Kusum got married, they got in touch again through social media.

“Kusum and Puran rekindled their relationship and during the lockdown started planning Suresh's murder. On the day of the incident, Puran called the victim and claimed that he had some information about Kusum. When Suresh reached the decided spot, Puran first thrashed him and then ran him over with his vehicle to ensure that he died,” said Brij Bhushan, SHO, Bagru police station.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/jaipur/wife-paramour-saw-online-videos-for-tips-to-kill-accountant/amp_articleshow/76126430\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/jaipur/wife-paramour-saw-online-videos-for-tips-to-kill-accountant/amp_articleshow/76126430) cms)

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32) Man kills estranged wife in Bengaluru, mom-in-law in Kolkata, shoots self

KOLKATA/BENGALURU: A city-chartered accountant flew to Bengaluru last weekend, murdered his estranged wife at her Whitefield home and then returned to Kolkata, where he shot dead his mother-in-law and then killed himself at an upscale residential complex in Phoolbagan on Monday evening.

The murder-murder-suicide came in the middle of acrimonious divorce proceedings that might have involved a dispute over property, cops said after an initial probe. Both Amit and Shilpi Agarwal were chartered accountants and were living separately — husband in Kolkata and wife in Bengaluru — for the last two years after the marriage turned sour. A 10-year-old son survived the grisly events of the past three days; Amit brought him back from Bengaluru on Monday and left him at his brother's residence in Kolkata before heading to Phoolbagan, cops said.

Amit knocked on his in-laws' door, on the second floor of Tower B of Rameshwaram Apartments — a residential complex on Ramakrishna Samadhi Road — around 5) 30pm on Monday. Shilpi's parents, 70-year-old Subhas and 62-year-old Lalita Dhandhanias, were there and allowed Amit in, cops learnt from their neighbours.

Sometime later, however, neighbors heard heated arguments that continued for some time. Neighbors later told cops that the debate “appeared to be” over some property documents that Amit wanted the Dhandhanias to sign.

Neighbors heard the first gunshot a little before 6) 30pm, following which Subhas ran out of his flat, bolted the door from outside and took refuge inside his next-door neighbor's apartment. Cops were called and they arrived a few minutes later and entered the

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Dhandhanias' home, where they found Lalita's and Amit's lifeless bodies. "The mother-in-law's body was lying on the floor and Amit's body was on a bed," a senior police officer said, adding that cops had recovered the revolver that Amit had used to kill his mother-in-law and himself.

"We recovered a suicide note from the flat," joint commissioner of police (crime) Murlidhar Sharma said. "It said that he had killed his wife in Bengaluru. We contacted cops there and the Whitefield deputy commissioner of police confirmed that Shilpi's decomposed body was recovered from her home," he added.

Cops in Bengaluru told TOI that Shilpi's body was recovered from Brigade Metropolis apartment in Mahadevapura, Whitefield Road, around 9pm on Monday. The flat bore the signs of a fight, officials said, adding that many items were scattered in the hall. "It indicates that Shilpi had opposed Amit's entry and there seemed to have been a fight near the entrance itself. There seems to have been another scuffle near the kitchen, with smashed glass tumblers and damaged utensils lying around. The murder occurred near the bedroom," an investigating officer said. Amit would visit Bengaluru when there were court hearings, cops said quoting neighbors, and most of these visits would end in fights. Deputy commissioner of police (Whitefield) MN Anuchet said investigators would speak to neighbors to learn more about the couple.

Officials in Kolkata said Amit returned from Bengaluru with his son on Monday. "He went to his brother's residence and left his 10-year-old son with him before starting out for Phoolbagan," an officer said, adding that Amit and Shilpi had married in 2005)

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Cops in Kolkata have got in touch with Shilpi's brother to help the probe. "It is important to find out what transpired immediately before the murder-suicide at the Phoolbagan flat. Did Amit divulge anything there? We are trying to get these details from Subhas," an official said.

A police team has left for Uttarpara Station Road to question Amit's relatives. Cops are also probing from where Amit got the six-chamber revolver.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolkata/man-kills-estranged-wife-in-bluru-mom-in-law-in-kol-shoots-self/amp_articleshow/76519987\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolkata/man-kills-estranged-wife-in-bluru-mom-in-law-in-kol-shoots-self/amp_articleshow/76519987) cms)

33) Mumbai: Woman held for killing hubby jobless due to lockdown

MUMBAI: A Boisar woman was arrested for allegedly killing her husband who was jobless following the lockdown. When Arun Maurya (29), a technician in a Goregaon factory, vomited blood on May 18, Kavita (22) called neighbors and took him to hospital, where he died. Boisar MIDC police registered an accidental case after Kavita told them that he was unwell for some days. But the autopsy report revealed he had died of injuries on his abdomen. When police seized Arun's cellphone, they found video clips of her assaulting him since May 14)

Kavita used to torture him mentally for being jobless and accused him of having extra-marital affairs. Arun kept his phone video on and left it on the window on May 14)

Kavita's assaults since then, including on May 18, when he died, were all recorded.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/mumbai/mumbai-woman-held-for-killing-hubby-jobless-due-to-lockdown/amp_articleshow/75860302\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/mumbai/mumbai-woman-held-for-killing-hubby-jobless-due-to-lockdown/amp_articleshow/75860302) cms)

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34) Woman kills husband over his drinking habit

Nagpur: A 41-year-old woman surrendered before Ajni police on Thursday night after allegedly bludgeoning her husband to death with a hammer at Jaywant Nagar. The accused has been identified as Mamta Porandwar, a resident of Bhagwan Nagar. She took the drastic step allegedly due to her husband's drinking habit and relations with other women.

Sources said the deceased Mahesh, a transporter-turned-moneylender, had been living away from Mamta and his son for the last four months and did not give any money to them for daily expenses forcing Mamta to take up a job as a caretaker. She is learnt to have gone to the rented house of Mahesh on Thursday to ask him for money for their son's college admission.

Mamta's son Manthan, a BCCA second year student, told TOI, "My father did not used to give any money. Whenever we went to speak with him he would abuse us. Some days back when we had gone to speak with him, he and his neighbours attacked us. My mother had sustained injuries on her face but when we went to the police to file a complaint we saw my father filing a complaint against her for assault."

Manthan claimed that his mother was suffering from severe depression and migraine. "She was undergoing treatment at GMCH," he said. It is learnt that Mamta had taken several pills before going to meet Mahesh at his house in Jaywant Nagar. "I later found several empty packets of pills at the home," Manthan said.

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Police said a fight broke out between husband and wife. In the fit of anger Mamta picked up a hammer and hit Mahesh on the head. He fell down. Mamta feared that if he got up, he would beat her up, so she continued to hit him with the hammer.

Mamta later approached Ajni police station and confessed her crime. Cops rushed to the spot and sent the body to GMCH where Mahesh's post mortem was conducted on Friday. Police registered a case of murder against Mamta and arrested her. She was produced before the court on Friday and remanded to police custody till January 6)

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/nagpur/woman-kills-husband-over-his-drinking-habit/amp_articleshow/73091805\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/nagpur/woman-kills-husband-over-his-drinking-habit/amp_articleshow/73091805) cms)

35) Notorious woman goon booked under Goondas Act

Puducherry: The Karaikal police on Thursday arrested notorious woman goon R Ezhilarasi alias Meera, who was booked in three murder cases, including the murder of former speaker and minister V M C Sivakumar, under the Goondas Act. The action came after the Karaikal collector issued an order to detain her under the Goondas Act following recommendations from the district police.

A police team, which reached the goon's house, arrested her and took her to the SP's office for preliminary inquiries. This is the second time she has been booked under the act. She was set free by the Madras high court after she was detained under the Goondas Act earlier.

The second wife of slain liquor merchant Ramu alias Radhakrishnan, Ezhilarasi was involved in a series of murders and attempt to murder cases. She murdered her husband's

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first wife R Vinodha in 2015 and a travel agent Iyyappan in 2014 to avenge the murder of her husband. She engaged goons to murder the former minister in 2017 following a dispute over the properties of her husband. The former minister and her husband were close friends but turned foes after her husband abandoned his first wife and married her.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/puducherry/notorious-woman-goon-booked-under-goondas-act/amp_articleshow/73562893\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/puducherry/notorious-woman-goon-booked-under-goondas-act/amp_articleshow/73562893) cms)

36) Woman, 4 others held for killing her husband

Rajkot: A woman, her paramour and three of their accomplices were arrested on Sunday for the alleged murder of the woman's husband in Akolvadi village of Talala taluka in Gir Somnath district.

Police said the accused, Nadeem Baloch (30) was in love with Varsha (32), wife of the deceased, Sameer Solanki (35). At her insistence, Nadeem, Ramij Baloch (27) Sagar Gadhia (28), Nahishad Patel (25) and Ajay Koli had allegedly strangled Sameer on April 22 night.

According to the police, Sameer was a habitual drunkard and would go to a farmhouse in his SUV to booze. On the night of the crime, when Sameer was driving out of the farmhouse, he saw the accused walking on the road. “Nadeem, Ramiz, Sagar and Ajay were walking down the road. When Sameer, who knew them, stopped to ask them what happened, they said their bikes had developed snags and so they were walking home. At this, Sameer offered them a lift in his SUV. Once they got inside, one of the accused sitting behind Sameer strangled him with a wire,” said H S Bhuvra, sub-inspector with Talala police station.

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After killing Sameer, the accused drove the SUV to the farmhouse of Patel's uncle on the outskirts of Vadal village of Talala taluka, where they cut the body into pieces and threw his hands and feet, the wire, and the deceased's clothes in a borewell. They then took Sameer's head and torso to a pond in Akolvadi and buried it on the banks of the pond.

After this Nadeem drove the SUV to Sameer's house and told Varsha that the job was done. On April 23 morning, Varsha declared that Sameer had gone missing after going for a morning walk.

“Meanwhile, Sameer’s elder brother Bipin Solanki approached us. He told us that Varsha had an affair with Nadeem and that he suspected a foul play. We rounded up Varsha, who, when interrogated, confessed to the crime, leading to the arrests of the accused,” said Bhuva.

Cops have launched a manhunt for Koli, who is still at large.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/rajkot/woman-4-others-held-for-killing-her-husband/amp_articleshow/75414930\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/rajkot/woman-4-others-held-for-killing-her-husband/amp_articleshow/75414930) cms)

37) Woman lands in police net for killing husband

The Commissioner of Police, Gurpreet Singh Bhullar, said on Thursday that Babu Lal, whose beheaded body was found abandoned in a plot at Transport Nagar, was murdered by his wife along with her paramour.

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The mystery behind the killing was resolved after a police team recovered the chopped off head of the deceased. Bhullar said the wife of the deceased along with her paramour had murdered him and severed the head later.

The accused have been identified as Prabhawati, a native of Jhajjor village and her paramour Radheshayam of Kollian village in Sultanpur district of Uttar Pradesh. While Prabhawati was arrested on Thursday, Radheshayam is still absconding. A police team has been sent to Sultanpur to locate his whereabouts. The police reportedly recovered the severed head near canal distributary in Randhawa Masanda locality. The accused had first used sharp-edged weapons to kill the victim before chopping his head off.

A panic was created in Transport Nagar on February 28 last month, after some locals informed the police about a headless body dumped near Sarb Multiplex.

A case under Sections 302, 201 and 34 of the IPC has been registered against both the accused at police station division No.8)

Bhullar added during preliminary interrogation Prabhawati told that she was married to Babu Lal about 21 years ago and have three teenage children; one son and two daughters.

SOURCE: <https://m.tribuneindia.com/news/jalandhar/woman-lands-in-police-net-for-killing-husband-58331>

38) Wife booked for man's murder

The police booked three persons, including a woman and her paramour, for allegedly killing the former's husband, Ramesh Kumar Mustafa (36) of cantonment area.

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Kirpal Singh, SHO, said Kirandeep had allegedly developed illicit relations with Japan Singh, a resident of Rukna Begu village. On May 21, Ramesh went out with Japan and did not return. Kirandeep, her paramour Japan and his friend Akash were booked following a complaint by Bunty, victim's cousin

SOURCE: <https://m.tribuneindia.com/news/punjab/wife-booked-for-mans-murder-90827>

39) Case against wife, in-laws for abetting man's suicide

A case of abetment of suicide has been registered against a woman and her parents after her husband hanged himself earlier this month. DD Tribhuvan, the deceased, had allegedly informed his mother before his death that his wife and in-laws used to harass him and 'treated him like a servant'.

Tribhuvan's mother Shobha lodged an FIR after his death on February 1, based on which the Rabale MIDC police in Navi Mumbai started their investigation. According to the FIR, Jalgaon resident Tribhuvan met Ashwini, a resident of Navi Mumbai, through Facebook and they got married in May 2019, against the wishes of the girl's family. The couple then settled in Jalgaon. As per the complaint, the couple used to quarrel as Ashwini wanted them to move to Navi Mumbai.

During Diwali last year, the couple visited Ashwini's residence, after which they started living there. The FIR also states that later, Tribhuvan rented a flat near his in-laws' place. Tribhuvan also got a job in a security company.

According to Shobha's complaint, when she had visited Tribhuvan's place in December last year, her son had told her that during his stay at his in-law's place, he was made to

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work as a cook and a servant. On January 31, Shobha received a call from Ashwini's mother, who informed her that Ashwini had returned to her maternal home after a quarrel with her husband during which Tribhuvan had hit her. When Shobha spoke to Tribhuvan about it, he said that it was Ashwini who had slapped him twice during the quarrel. "Tribhuvan also informed his mother that he had noted down all the information about the harassment in his phone," said a police officer. The next day, Tribhuvan hanged himself.

Senior inspector Nitin Gite said a case was registered under sections 306 (abetment of suicide) and 34 (common intention) of the Indian Penal Code against Ashwini and her parents. No arrests have been made so far. "We have also found a note in Tribhuvan's phone in which he had written about the ill-treatment he got from his in-laws and that he was stressed since he was jobless and that he was going to end his life," said Gite.

SOURCE: [https://mumbaimirror.indiatimes.com/mumbai/crime/case-against-wife-in-laws-for-abetting-mans-suicide/articleshow/74182621\) cms](https://mumbaimirror.indiatimes.com/mumbai/crime/case-against-wife-in-laws-for-abetting-mans-suicide/articleshow/74182621) cms)

40) EMPLOYEE DUPES JP MORGAN OF RS 3) 5 CR IN GIFT VOUCHER SCAM

JP Morgan, the American multinational, has filed a case of cheating against one of its employees for allegedly embezzling Rs 3) 5 crores under the pretext of ordering gift vouchers meant for the outperforming workers.

The case was registered in Powai police station by the senior vice president of the company against the employee identified as Preet Saani on January 18)

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According to the complainant, the company deals in providing IT inbuilt services and has around 15,000 people working in Mumbai. In order to incentivize well-performing employees, the company gives them a gift voucher worth Rs 1,000 as a token of appreciation.

The source said the accused, who worked as an assistant to a business managing director of the company, would get the requests from the team leaders of the company for gift vouchers, and accordingly she was supposed to place the order from authorized vendors.

In January 2019, an employee working in the CEO's office found a few boxes in Saani's office. On checking, 2,600 gift vouchers (of zero value) were found in them. This raised the suspicion of the office staff and an inquiry was initiated, suspecting irregularities in the procurement of gift vouchers. Meanwhile, Saani went on sick leave for three months and did not resume office.

The company in its internal investigation found that from February 2016 to November 2018, Saani had ordered gift vouchers worth Rs 3) 5 crores. Interestingly, in the year 2018, the team leaders had asked for only 242 gift vouchers while Saani allegedly ordered 1,7000 vouchers worth Rs 1) 96 crores.

“It has been revealed in the company's inquiry that Saani ordered the excessive gift vouchers without having any requirement for it. She took the delivery of the vouchers outside the office, and used them for her personal benefit. She also used the 2,600 vouchers which were of zero value to cheat the company by showing them as original vouchers – having a value of Rs 1,000 each,” said a police officer.

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The officer said that Saani has been booked under relevant sections of Indian Penal Code for cheating and criminal breach of trust by clerk or servant.

Another officer said, "She used to order the vouchers from the authorized vendor and would get the payments approved from her seniors. However, there is a huge difference between the actual requirement of the vouchers by team leaders and the number of the vouchers ordered by her."

SOURCE: [https://mumbaimirror.indiatimes.com/mumbai/crime/employee-dupes-jp-morgan-of-rs-3-5-cr-in-gift-voucher-scam/amp_articleshow/73535646\) cms](https://mumbaimirror.indiatimes.com/mumbai/crime/employee-dupes-jp-morgan-of-rs-3-5-cr-in-gift-voucher-scam/amp_articleshow/73535646) cms)

41) Mumbai Police Bust "High-Profile" Sex Racket, Rescue Actress, A Minor

The Social Service branch of the city police conducted the raid at the hotel at Andheri East on Thursday, an official said.

Mumbai: Police have busted a "high-profile" sex racket operating in a three-star hotel in Mumbai's suburban Andheri and arrested a 29-year-old woman and rescued three female artistes, including a minor, an official said on Thursday.

The Social Service (SS) branch of the city police conducted the raid at the hotel at Andheri East on Thursday, the official said.

"During the raid, three females, including a minor, were found to have been forced into prostitution. They were rescued and a woman, identified as Priya Sharma, who was operating the racket, was arrested," he said.

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"Priya Sharma was running a tours and travel agency in Kandivali East. However, she was involved in immoral activities," senior inspector of SS branch Sandesh Revale said.

While one of the rescued is a woman actor and singer, who has worked in "Savdhaan India" TV crime show, he said, another one has worked in a Marathi movie and serials.

The minor has worked in a web series, Mr Revale added. The offence was being registered against Priya Sharma, he said.

SOURCE: <https://www.ndtv.com/mumbai-news/mumbai-police-bust-high-profile-sex-racket-in-andheri-rescue-minor-actress-2165244>

42) Man commits suicide after fight with wife in Gurugram, posts video on net

Amit Chauhan streamed his suicide on Facebook live after his wife Preeti left to her parents' home after a tiff with her husband.

GURUGRAM: A 28-year-old married man committed suicide by hanging himself from the ceiling fan in his house here and posted the live video of his final moments on Facebook, police said on Tuesday.

The deceased was identified as Amit Chauhan, a resident of Haily Mandi near Pataudi, 28 km from Gugugram city.

Police said Chauhan and his wife Preeti had differences over some family issue.

"Preeti left her in-laws home on Monday after a tiff with her husband and called her parents, who took her to their house in a village near Sohna," police officer Subhash Boken said.

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"Anguished, Chauhan hanged himself and the posted a video of the suicide on Facebook," Boken said.

Chauhan requested his friends on the social site to further share his suicide video.

"The deceased posted two videos... He was also in depression and was being treated at PGIMS Rohtak for the last few months," Boken added.

"Family members of the deceased on Tuesday cremated the body without informing the police. We are investigating the case," he added.

The couple have two girl children. No one was arrested for the suicide.

SOURCE: [https://www.newindianexpress.com/nation/2018/jul/31/man-commits-suicide-after-fight-with-wife-in-gurugram-posts-video-on-net-1851201\) html](https://www.newindianexpress.com/nation/2018/jul/31/man-commits-suicide-after-fight-with-wife-in-gurugram-posts-video-on-net-1851201) html)

43) Woman, two friends booked for abetting husband's suicide in Maharashtra

Before taking the extreme step, the victim, on November 18, recorded a video in which he purportedly stated that he was fed up of harassment by his wife and her two friends, including a man.

THANE: A woman and two of her friends have been booked for allegedly abetting her husband's suicide in Thane city of Maharashtra, police said on Sunday.

The main accused, Suvarna Sontakke, got married to Gajanan Sontakke (32), a resident of Ambewadi locality here, in 2013 and the couple had two children.

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The woman started working since July this year and developed friendship with a man in her office, to which her husband objected, a police spokesperson said.

This led to frequent quarrels between the couple following which the husband allegedly committed suicide by hanging himself at their home on November 22, she said.

Before taking the extreme step, the victim, on November 18, recorded a video in which he purportedly stated that he was fed up of harassment by his wife and her two friends, including a man, and was planning to commit suicide.

He then circulated the video through social media to his relatives who even tried to convince him not to end his life, the official said.

The victim's mother lodged a police complaint in this connection on Friday.

Based on the complaint, the police on Saturday registered an FIR against the main accused and her two friends - Shakira Banu Shaikh and Lakhan Kasbe, the official said.

The accused have been booked under Indian Penal Code Sections 306 (abetment of suicide) and 34 (common intention), she said, adding that no arrest has been made so far.

SOURCE: [https://www.newindianexpress.com/nation/2019/dec/15/woman-two-friends-booked-for-abetting-husbands-suicide-in-maharashtra-2076478\) html](https://www.newindianexpress.com/nation/2019/dec/15/woman-two-friends-booked-for-abetting-husbands-suicide-in-maharashtra-2076478) html)

44) Woman kills infant daughter four hours after birth in Gujarat

VADODARA: A 26-year-old woman allegedly strangled her newborn daughter to death four hours after giving birth to her at a referral hospital in Umbergoan of Gujarat's Valsad district, police said on Tuesday.

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The incident took place on December 27 when Anitadevi Dimple Bind, who hails from Jaunpur in Uttar Pradesh, allegedly strangled her daughter who was born at around 4 pm on the same day, inspector J J Dabhi of Umbergaon police said.

The matter came to light after the woman's husband approached the on-duty doctor at around 8 pm saying his wife was finding it difficult to breastfeed the infant, who weighed 2) 7 kg, he added.

On examination, the doctor found that the infant had died, following which a post-mortem was conducted at a hospital in Surat, the official said.

The post-mortem report indicated that the newborn had been strangled to death and marks were found on her face and neck, the inspector said.

The couple, who is staying in the Saket Nagar locality of Umbergaon, already have three daughters, the official said, adding that the alleged accused's husband works in a factory at Gujarat Industrial Development Corporation.

"A case under section 302 (murder) of the Indian Penal Code has been registered against the woman, and an arrest will be made after gathering more conclusive evidence," Dabhi said.

SOURCE: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/nation/2019/dec/31/woman-kills-infant-daughter-four-hours-after-birth-in-gujarat-2083206>) amp

45) Woman held for murdering hubby with lover's help

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BERHAMPUR: Sadar police on Thursday arrested a woman and her alleged lover on charges of killing her husband in Sukunda village here. The deceased is Prafulla Sahu (32). According to IIC S Oram, the accused woman Mita Sahu (25) had filed a complaint with police on Tuesday, stating that Prafulla, a mason, had returned home in an inebriated condition and had suffered head injuries.

While the latter was immediately taken to the hospital, doctors declared him brought dead. Police, on registering a case of un-natural death, sent the body for autopsy and started investigating.

On Wednesday, when Prafulla's cousin lodged a police complaint, alleging that his brother was murdered, police nabbed Mita and her paramour, identified as Saroj Moharana (31), who too was present in the house when the incident took place.

Meanwhile, the post-mortem report confirmed that Prafulla was strangled to death after being hit by a hard material. During investigation, the crime was established after the two reportedly confessed to it. The accused duo was forwarded to court on the day.

SOURCE: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/odisha/2020/jan/24/woman-held-for-murdering-hubby-with-lovers-help-2093762>) amp

46) Woman, paramour held for killing 5-year-old boy

MADURAI: Investigation into the 'unnatural death' of a five-year-old boy shed light on the alleged involvement of his mother and her paramour. The duo reportedly strangled the boy to death. Police on Saturday arrested R Anandha Jothi (25), the mother, and her paramour P Maruthupandi (20)

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The police said that Jothi on Friday called up her husband S Ramkumar (28), a farmhand in V Kuchampatti in Peraiyur, and informed that their son R Jeeva (5) had fallen unconscious due to insect bite. He rushed the unconscious Jeeva to a hospital, where the boy was pronounced dead. However, Ramkumar became suspicious after noticing scratches and strangulation marks around his son's neck and alerted the police.

During the investigation, the police reportedly found out about Jothi's extramarital affair. Police said, on the day of the incident, the boy came to know about his mother's affair, and fearing that her child would inform her husband, Jothi, along with her paramour, allegedly strangled the boy to death.

The V Chatrapatti police altered the initially registered case under Section 174 of the CrPC to Section 302 (murder) of the IPC.

SOURCE: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/tamil-nadu/2020/jan/13/woman-paramour-held-for-killing-5-year-old-boy-2088943>) amp

47) Woman, lover arrested for killing husband one-and-a-half years ago

Malappuram: The police have arrested a 42-year-old woman and her lover for allegedly killing her husband at Kalikavu in Kerala's Malappuram district one-and-a-half years ago.

A native of Kalikavu, Muhammedali, 50, was allegedly poisoned by his wife Ummul Sahira and lover Jaimon, 37, a Pathanamthitta native. Muhammedali died on September 21, 2018). Heart attack was believed to have been the cause of the death and his funeral was held the next day.

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Soon after Sahira eloped with Jaimon and also took along her children. The relatives then got suspicious and filed a complaint with the police.

Then the victim's body was exhumed and a post-mortem was held. The autopsy revealed traces of poison in his internal organs.

The Malappuram District Crime Branch arrested Ummul Sahira from Sivakasi in Tamil Nadu on Monday and Jaimon was nabbed from Dindigul, also in the neighbouring state, on Tuesday.

The Malappuram police reached Sivakasi after getting a tip-off on their location. The cops were able to locate Ummul Sahira and her two children. But Jaimon managed to give them the slip.

Finally, Jaimon was arrested from Dindigul on Tuesday.

Recently, the Crime Branch had solved some sensational murder mysteries after exhuming the bodies of victims.

Last year, the Crime Branch arrested a 47-year-old woman, Jolly Joseph, who allegedly killed her husband and five other family members at Koodathayi in Kozhikode district by giving them cyanide-laced food or drink. The victims were killed one after the other over a period of 14 years. The bodies were exhumed, helping the police find leads to solve the case.

In another case, the body of a 14-year-old boy, Adharsh Vijayan who was found dead under mysterious circumstances in a pond in Thiruvananthapuram district 11 years ago, was also exhumed in October last year for further examinations.

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SOURCE: <https://www.onmanorama.com/news/kerala/2020/01/21/malappuram-woman-lover-arrested-for-poisoning-husband.amp.html>

48) Poured poison instead of alcohol: How Malappuram woman and lover killed her husband

Malappuram: A 42-year-old woman and her lover have confessed that they plotted for months to carry out the murder of her husband, Mohammedali, at Kalikavu in Kerala's Malappuram district in 2018).

In their statements to the police, Ummul Shahira and Jaimon admitted that they poisoned Mohammedali to lead a life together.

The accused have been arrested from Tamil Nadu.

Ummul Shahira is the second wife of Mohammedali. The couple along with their two children lived at a rented quarter at Moochikal. Mohammedali died on September 21, 2018)

Mohammedali and Jaimon had drinks together on the terrace of the house on that night. Jaimon told the police that he had poured poison into the glass instead of alcohol and gave it to Mohammedali. After ensuring that he was dead, Jaimon cleaned his body and clothes, and laid down the body on the cot and left. The couple also hid the liquor bottles and destroyed all evidence.

Poured poison instead of alcohol: How Malappuram woman and lover killed her husband

Mohammedali died on September 21, 2018)

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Early next day, Shahira called her relatives, who lived nearby, and told them that Mohammedali died after he suffered a heart attack while sleeping. The relatives too believed it to be a natural death.

Shahira also convinced the relatives not to take him to hospital as he had been drinking.

Four days after his demise, Ummul Shahira and her children went missing, and the relatives got suspicious.

After it came to be known that Jaimon too had gone missing, news spread that the duo had eloped. Soon Mohammedali's son from the first wife, filed a complaint with the police, raising suspicion about the death.

The victim's body was exhumed and a post-mortem held. After traces of poison were found in the body, the internal organs were sent for chemical tests. After the test results got delayed, the probe into the death slackened.

Villagers then formed an action council, seeking to unravel the mystery and nab the culprits at the earliest. Complaints were also filed with the Chief Minister and the DGP.

Then the district Crime Branch took over the case.

The cops were able to locate an old mobile number of Jaimon, that proved to be crucial to the case. With the help of the cyber cell, the mobile signal was checked and found that he was in Sivakasi and Dindigul in Tamil Nadu.

The police reached Sivakasi on Monday and located Shahira and her two children. Though Jaimon managed to give the cops a slip, he was nabbed from Dindigul on

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Tuesday. Ummul Shahira was presented in court and remanded. The children have been moved to safe centres. Malappuram SP U Abdul Karim said that Jaimon would be presented in court on Wednesday.

Jaimon accused in 20 cases.

Jaimon, a native of Unnakavu in Pathanamthitta, is an accused in 20-odd cases at various police stations in the state. Cases have been registered against him at the stations in Kannur, Idukki, and Kottayam districts. Three of these are abuse cases. He had also undergone prison term for molesting a girl in Idukki.

Jaimon got acquainted to a Kalikavu native at the Kozhikode Medical College two years ago. That's how he reached this Malappuram village and stayed for rent near Mohammedali's house. He also became friends with Mohammedali and the duo started drinking together. He became close to Ummul Shahira around six months before the murder.

The couple told the police that they had been plotting the murder for months.

SOURCE: <https://www.onmanorama.com/news/kerala/2020/01/22/malappuram-murder-woman-lover-poisoned-husband.amp.html>

49) Maha: Woman held for killing husband

Palghar, May 20 (PTI) A 22-year-old woman was arrested at Boisar in Palghar district of Maharashtra on Wednesday for allegedly killing her husband over the suspicion of illicit relationship, an official said.

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According to police, the woman, Kavita Mourya, resided with her husband Arun (29) at Sai Lok Nagar in Boisar. He worked at a company.

"The woman suspected that her husband was in an extra-marital relationship. The husband-wife duo used to argue over this issue frequently," Palghar police spokesperson Hemant Katkar said.

On Monday, the accused woman attacked him with a metal rod and also kicked him in the stomach. He suffered serious injuries and was taken to a hospital, where he was declared dead, he said.

The police initially registered a case of accidental death. However, during the probe it came to light that the victim's wife was involved the crime, he said.

"Accordingly, a case was registered against her under IPC section 302 (murder) at Boisar police station on Tuesday evening, following which she was arrested," Katkar said.

SOURCE: <https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/amp/maha-woman-held-for-killing-husband/1840534>

50) Woman, lover arrested for killing husband

New Delhi, May 6 (PTI) A woman and a man were arrested for allegedly killing her husband in northwest Delhi, police said on Wednesday.

On the intervening night of Friday and Saturday when Sharat Dass (46) was asleep at his house in Jelarwala Bagh, Anita called Sanjay to her house and they smothered Dass to death with the help of a blanket, the officer added.

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After receiving information, police grew suspicious about the cause of the death and later sent the body for post-mortem, an officer said.

The autopsy was conducted on Monday and it revealed asphyxia due to antemortem smothering as the cause of death, following which a case of murder was registered, the officer said.

During investigation, Anita was interrogated and she broke down, confessing that she was in relationship with Sanjay, who lives in the same locality. Due to that, her marital relationship got strained and they planned to get rid of Dass, police said.

SOURCE: <https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/amp/woman-lover-arrested-for-killing-husband/1826161>

51) Woman, three others, arrested for killing husband

New Delhi, Jan 23 (PTI) A woman was arrested along with three accomplices for allegedly killing her husband in northwest Delhi's Shalimar Bagh, police said on Thursday.

The matter came to light on January 4 after a man filed a complaint that his brother Satyanarayan (35), a resident of Pitampura village, was missing, they said.

After the family raised suspicion, police registered a kidnapping case at Shalimar Bagh police station on January 12)

The man's body had been recovered in Sahabad Dairy area on January 4 and the complainant later identified it to be Satyanarayan. He also raised suspicion that the

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deceased's wife and her male friend were responsible for his death, said Deputy Commissioner of Police (Northwest) Vijayanta Arya.

Police analysed the call details of the suspected persons and Satyanarayan and found that there was a relationship between his wife and her friend Ajay, the officer said.

During investigation, the wife confessed to her involvement in the killing.

She disclosed that she was in a relationship with her husband's friend. Her husband restricted her from meeting him due to which she provoked her friend to kill him so that they could live together, the officer added.

"It was found that Sonu and Suresh, friends of Ajay, helped him in the murder. Police conducted raids but all of them were absconding. After getting a tip off about their location, a police team was sent to Satna district in Madhya Pradesh. All of them were held with the help of local police and brought to Delhi," Arya said.

Ajay conspired to kill Satyanarayan, the officer said. On January 4, Ajay consumed liquor with him and then killed him with the help of his friends, he said.

SOURCE: <https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/amp/woman-three-others-arrested-for-killing-husband/1716143>

52) Nizamabad: Man murdered by wife, paramour

Nizamabad: An incident where a woman along with paramour killed her husband in Mandharna village of Bodhan mandal, came to light late. According to the police, Ganga Sagar along with her husband Sinigiri Sairam lives in Mandharna village and she has

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extra marital affair with Subhash Patel. Ganga with the help of Subhash and father Naguram had killed her husband Sairam on Friday.

The siblings of the deceased complained to the police that Sairam was missing for the last two days. During the investigation, the police found out the extra marital affair between Ganga Sagar and Subhash Patel and interrogated them. Both confessed their crime.

Bodhan ACP Jayapal said Ganga Sagar's father also helped the duo in burying the body at Manjira riverbed. CI Shakir Ali registered a case and dug the body in the presence of Tahsildar. Police arrested Ganga Sagar and her paramour Subhash Patel and searching for her father, who is absconding.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/andhra-pradesh/nizamabad-man-murdered-by-wife-paramour-622018>

53) Mother killed her two-year-old daughter for third marriage in Vellore

In a horrific incident, a mother has killed her two-year-old daughter as she thought that the child is an obstacle for her third marriage. This incident has happened at Kammavanpettai village near Vellore in Tamil Nadu.

Going into details, the Murugan temple construction works are going on at Mettamalai hill in Kammavanpettai and due to the foul smell, the workers searched in the surrounding areas and found a two-year-old child's dead body under the decomposed stage. With this, they immediately informed the police.

On receiving the information, the police reached the spot, initiated the investigation and examined the body. In this context, the police have received a missing complaint of a

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child and the person has expressed suspicion on the mother. With this, the police reached Thayanur village and took Manjula (22) into their custody and interrogated in their style, where she revealed shocking facts.

In the investigation, the police found that she got third marriage to a man by name Rajamani just a few days ago. She thought that her daughter was an obstacle in her relationship, killed and thrown her on the hillside.

Manjula first married her uncle and later got a second marriage to Pandiya and gave birth to a girl child. She again left the second husband and was living alone with her daughter at Thayanur.

Here she met with Rajamani and decided to get married. With this, they thought that the child as an obstruction for their wedding and killed her on December 22nd and dumped the body at Kammavanpettai hilly area. On the incident, the police registered a case and arrested the accused Manjula and her third husband Rajamani.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/news/crime/mother-killed-her-two-year-old-daughter-for-third-marriage-in-vellore-594054>

54) Woman attempt to kill husband with help of boyfriend in Chittoor district

Chittoor: A married woman has attempted to murder her husband with the help of her husband in the Chittoor district. In the incident, the victim suffered severe injuries. The locals noticed him and rushed to the hospital.

According to the sources, Gopal of Kalepalle village at Gangadhara Nellore mandal has got married to Bharati a few years ago. The couple lived happily for some time.

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In this context, Bharati made friendship with a man named Dinakar of the same village, which later developed into an illegal affair. Both became intimate in the absence of her husband.

On knowing about the affair, Gopal warned his wife to stay away from Dinakar. With this, Bharati decided to murder her husband with the help of the boyfriend. As per the sketch, both attacked Gopal and tried to slit his throat with a knife on Sunday night.

At the last moment, somehow the victim managed to escape from them. The locals who noticed him with injuries and immediately rushed to the hospital. On receiving the information, the police have registered a case and arrested Bharati and search is going on to trace her boyfriend Dinakar.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/news/crime/woman-attempt-to-kill-husband-with-help-of-boyfriend-in-chittoor-district-595302>

55) Woman killed husband with her boyfriend in Karnataka

Bangalore: In an incident, a woman has killed her husband with the help of the boyfriend and in order to escape from the case she developed an illicit affair with ASI. Finally, the accused, who were hiding from the police for the past three years were arrested by Maddur police in Mandya district of Karnataka.

Going into details, Rangaswamy of Kollegala taluk in Chamarajanagara district works as a tipper driver at a stone quarry. He got married to Rupa a native of Bhimanakere village a few years ago. the couple has three children.

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In this context, Rupa came into contact with Mudde Gowda who is a fellow driver with Rangaswamy, which later developed into an extramarital affair. Over knowing about their affair, Rangaswamy warned his wife to change her way. With this, Rupa and her boyfriend decided to murder Rangaswamy.

On July 4, 2017, both killed Rangaswamy by hitting him with sticks while he was sleeping at home and dumped the body at Chandahallidoddi cheruvu. Later, Rupa lodged a missing complaint of her husband.

Rangaswamy family members who felt suspicious over Rupa's activities filed a complaint against her. On learning about the police complaint, Rupa and Mudde Gowda flew away from the town.

They were hiding from the police for a long time and finally got arrested on Tuesday. In the interrogation, the accused admitted the crime. The police recovered the body of Rangaswamy and shifted it for post-mortem.

During the investigation, the police found another twist in the case. In order to escape from the murder case, Rupa developed an illegal relationship with ASI Siddaraju who is working at Maddur police station. As the matter came to the notice of district SP, he ordered to file a case against ASI Siddaraju.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/news/crime/woman-killed-husband-with-her-boyfriend-in-karnataka-597429>

56) Woman kills husband with boyfriend's help, held in Madanapalle

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The police have arrested a woman who killed her husband by crushing him with a lorry with the help of her boyfriend. This crime has taken place at Madanapalle town in Chittoor district on Saturday night.

Going into the details, Balasubrahmanyam (35), a native of Siddavaram panchayat in Peddamandyam mandal got love marriage to Renuka of Neerugattuvaripalle 11 years ago. The couple has three children.

Balasubrahmanyam runs a bookstall near Kadiri road here in the town, and later he got loss in the business. After which, he moved to Tirupati and started travels business two years ago. His wife Renuka and children remained at Madanapalle.

In this context, Renuka met a person named Nagi Reddy, who was a political leader, which later developed into an illegal affair. Then, she also joined the political party and became intimate with him.

Recently, Balasubrahmanyam left the travels business in Tirupati and returned back to Madanapalle and started other business here. With Balasubrahmanyam came back, Renuka couldn't have time to spend with her boyfriend. However, she managed to meet Nagi Reddy in the name of party activities.

Somehow, Subrahmanyam came to know about his wife's affair and warned to change her behaviour, but she continued the relationship with her boyfriend.

She thought that Subrahmanyam has become a block to her illegal affair and decided to murder him. With this, she made a murder plan with her boyfriend, where Nagi Reddy sketched to kill Subrahmanyam by crashing him with a lorry.

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On Saturday night, Subrahmanyam came out of the house to buy medicine as he was suffering from cold. Taking advantage of this, Renuka phoned her boyfriend to implement the plan.

While Subrahmanyam was riding on his bike, Nagi Reddy collided him with a lorry. In the accident, Subrahmanyam died on the spot. On receiving the information from the deceased's brother, the police registered a case and initiated the investigation.

The investigation revealed the illegal affair between Renuka and Nagi Reddy. The police got the calls data of Renuka and found that she called Nagi Reddy when Subrahmanyam went out for medicine. With this, the police took both into their custody and interrogated in their style. The police seized the lorry which was used for the murder at Valmikipuram, registered a case against the accused and sent them to remand.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/news/crime/woman-kills-husband-with-boyfriends-help-held-in-madanapalle-615915>

57) Wife kills husband by slitting his throat in Nagarkurnool

A petty quarrel between a couple ensued to the wife killing her husband by slitting his throat while the latter was asleep.

According to reports, Ganji Sreenu, a resident of Manganur village in Bijinepally mandal of Nagarkurnool district used have frequent quarrels with his wife after returning home in drunk state. On Sunday night, a dispute between husband and wife erupted which led to a big fight between the two. However, when everything got settled after a while, the woman planned to kill her husband.

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Fed up with the harassment, the woman slit her husband's throat with a knife at night and killed him. The Bijinepally police have started investigating the matter and have registered a murder case against the victim's wife.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/telegana/wife-kills-husband-by-slitting-his-throat-in-nagarkurnool-621882>

58) Kurnool: Wife hires killers to murder hubby

Kurnool: A woman got her husband killed by hired killer at Chinna Gummadapuram village under Kothapalli police station limits in the district on Monday. The victim was identified as Gangaiah, 35, of Shivapuram village. The contract was agreed for Rs.3) 50 lakhs and one lakh was given in advance.

According to Atmakur CI B R Krishnaiah, the Gangaiah married Durgamma of Chinna Gummadapuram 18 years ago and have two children. The wife had been pressuring Gangaiah to leave the joint family so that she and children can have some freedom.

This led to frequent arguments between the couple. Miffed over her husband's refusal to come out of joint family, she occasionally went to her maternal home at Chinna Gummadaopuram but returned intervention of elders. A week ago, she demanded her husband to get his share of property or she would desert him. Accordingly, she left Gangaiah and went to her parents.

Gangaiah went to his in-law's village on September 28 asked them to send his wife with him. An altercation took place there when his in-laws said to have warned him to see his end. On the evening of the same day, three members of hired killers' gang, took Gangaiah

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out from his in-law's house on the pretext of talking over the issue. They hacked him to death and left the body in the deep Nallamalla forest.

As Gangaiah did not return home, his brother Ganga Mahesh went to his siter-in-laws village and enquired about him. Her parents threatened to kill him too like his brother. On the the information given by them, Ganga Mahesh found the spot where his brothers body was thrown. He immediately informed Kothapalli police station, said Krishnaiah.

Police shifted the body to Atmakur government general hospital for post-mortem. A case under Section 302 IPC was registered against Durgamma and three others. Accused are yet to be arrested, he said.

He further said that the hired killers had acted upon the direction of a political leader. The facts would come to light after thorough investigation, Krishnaiah added.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/andhra-pradesh/kurnool-wife-hires-killers-to-murder-hubby-648661>

59) Warangal: Home guard killed by wife and her paramour

Warangal: A woman with the help of her paramour killed her husband on Wednesday here at Nekkonda mandal of Warangal Rural district. The victim, Dharyavath Singh (42), was working as a home guard at Warangal traffic police station.

Singh who was on a holiday was residing at home from the past 21 days which made difficult to his wife, Jyothi to meet her paramour. Jyothi was in a relationship with one Sambaraju and used to meet him frequently when her husband was not at home.

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However, Singh learned Jyothi's affair with Sambaraju who started harassing her. Unable to bear the harassment, Jyothi and Sambaraju planned to get rid of Singh to continue their affair. On September 14, Jyothi called up Sambaraju to come home in order to kill her husband.

The duo strangled Singh to death when he was asleep and shifted the dead body in an auto-rickshaw to an isolated place. Sambaraju, his brother Suresh and father Yakaiah burnt the dead body and left the place. They visited the spot the next day and found the body was partially burnt. The trio burnt the dead body again and mixed the ashes in the river.

The incident came to light when the victim's brother lodged a complaint with the police on his brother missing. Based on the call data of Jyothi, the police found that the home guard has been murdered and took Jyothi and her paramour into custody. Efforts are on to nab two others who have gone absconding.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/news/cities/warangal/home-guard-killed-by-wife-and-her-paramour-in-warangal-647554>

60) Newly-wed woman bludgeons husband to death in Hyderabad

A 22-year-old woman bludgeoned her husband to death after a heated argument on Friday night. The incident took place under Tappachabutra police station limits in Hyderabad.

Getting into details, the accused, Samreen was got married to Mohammad Aslam, who was working in a furniture shop and is a resident of Mujahidnagar two days ago. On

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Friday night, the couple had a quarrel following which Samreen hit her husband with a heavy object who sustained serious head injuries.

Aslam was then shifted to a hospital where he died while undergoing treatment. The Tappachabutra police registered a case and took Samreen into custody. An investigation is underway.

In a similar case, a 32-year-old woman identified as Sukanya allegedly killed her husband Prabhakar as she could not tolerate her husband staying with another woman. The incident occurred in Andal Nagar in Moula Ali on June 20). She told the police that she was unable to bear the harassment and also angry over him for living with another woman following which she killed him.

The woman confessed that she smothered her husband to death and tried to portray it as a suicide, the police said. A case of murder has been registered and she was sent to remand.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/tehangana/newly-wed-woman-bludgeons-husband-to-death-in-hyderabad-645134>

61) Hyderabad: Woman's extramarital affair with two men results in daughter's death

Hyderabad: A woman's extramarital affair with two men resulted in her six-year-old daughter's death. The incident occurred at Ismailkhaguda in Medchal.

Getting into details, Anusha who was residing at Vihari Homes along with her husband and daughter has developed an extramarital affair with two men. She befriended Karunkar on Facebook who then exchanged their numbers and entered to the illicit

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relationship. Meanwhile, Karunakar was enraged after noticing Anusha with another man, Ramesh.

On Thursday, Karunakar went to Anusha's home after learning she was with Ramesh. On noticing Karunakar, Ramesh rushed into the bathroom to hide from him. Karunakar who knew the presence of Ramesh asked him to come out and threatened to kill Anusha's daughter Aadhya.

As Ramesh did not come out, Karunakar slit Aadhya's throat and killed her. Locals alerted the police who rushed to the place and took the accused into custody. An investigation is underway.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/tehrangana/hyderabad-womans-extramarital-affair-with-two-men-results-in-daughters-death-631376>

62) Man found dead in Nagarkurnool, extramarital affair suspected

A man was found dead at a married woman's house here at Nagarkurnool on Thursday.

According to SI Madhava Reddy, Sharath Kumar Reddy (25), a native of Nallavelli in Nagarkurnool district was working in a private firm in Hyderabad. He has gone to his native place for Sankranti festival and was found dead in a married woman's home in Raghavendra colony.

On learning his son's condition, Sharath's father Chandra Reddy rushed to the place and shifted him to a hospital where he was declared brought dead. Meanwhile, the police enquired about the incident and shifted the body to the government hospital.

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The preliminary investigation revealed that Sharath was in an affair with a married woman, the SI said.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/telangana/man-found-dead-in-nagarkurnool-extramarital-affair-suspected-597793>

63) Woman and her two boyfriends held for trying to kill husband in Karimnagar

woman and her two boyfriends were arrested on Sunday for trying to kill her husband in Karimnagar. The incident took place on December 14 but came to light with the arrest of the two youth who went absconding.

The woman, Kaveri was married to Krishnavamsi few years ago and the couple is residing at Karimnagar. She befriended Samanvith and Ganesh when her husband went out for office. Later, her friendship with the two turned into extramarital affair.

Kaveri has been continuing affair with two for the past two years which was learned by her husband. Krishnavamsi warned his wife and asked her to stay away from them.

Upset over ending her relationship, Kaveri decided to get rid of her husband and hatched a plan to kill him with the help of her lovers.

Samanvith and Ganesh along with Kaveri tried to kill Krishnavamsi by smothering him to death. However, he managed to escape from them and lodged a complaint with the police. The police arrested the accused on Saturday and recovered their mobile phones.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/telangana/woman-and-her-two-boyfriends-held-for-trying-to-kill-husband-in-karimnagar-592029>

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64) Woman kills mother in Hyderabad to continue extra marital affair, held

An unmarried woman killed her mother here under Rachakonda police station limits to continue her extramarital affair. The incident came to light on Monday with the woman's arrest.

Getting into details, the victim, Rajitha who learned about daughter's affair chided her and asked to stay away from his lover. Fumed over her mother's behaviour, the woman identified as Keerthi along with her lover Shashi killed her mother and tossed the body on a railway track near Munaganur village under Hayatnagar police station limits.

Meanwhile, the woman's father Srinivas Reddy who is unaware about the incident lodged a complaint with Hayathnagar police along with her daughter.

The police who investigated the case nabbed the woman for killing her mother and are looking out for her lover who has gone absconding.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/tehangana/woman-kills-mother-in-hyderabad-to-continue-extra-marital-affair-held-576241>

65) Woman thrashes husband for extramarital affair

Hyderabad: Tension prevailed at Pragathinagar on Thursday when a woman thrashed her husband for leaving his family and staying with another woman under Bachupally police station limits.

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According to police, one Soujanya got married with Lakshman and few days after their marriage, Lakshman left his wife and started a live-in relationship with another woman Anusha. He took a flat on rent at Pragathi Nagar and started living with her.

When Soujanya came to know about her husband's extra marital relation she asked for divorce with him. Lakshman did not bother her and continued his relation with Anusha.

On Thursday Soujanya along with her supporters rushed to Lakshman's house and assaulted him.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/telangana/woman-thrashes-husband-for-extramarital-affair-549581>

66) Woman kills husband for opposing extramarital affair in Jadcherla

A woman killed her husband on in Jadcherla after he opposed her extra marital affair. She also thought of getting her husband's job and property after his death.

The accused Lakshmi Devi left his husband Narasimha and was in a live-in relationship with her paramour Sekhar for the last one year. Devi came to her husband a few days ago and planned to kill him with the help of her paramour Sekhar.

On March 3, when Sekhar and Narasimha consuming alcohol, Lakshmi hit her husband with a beer bottle. Narasimha suffered serious head injuries and was dead.

An investigation is underway.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/telangana/woman-kills-husband-for-opposing-extramarital-affair-in-jadcherla-512778>

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67) Chittoor youth butchered in a suspected extramarital affair

Body parts of a 19-year-old youth found in a forest in Chittoor district on Saturday has sent shock waves in the area. The deceased identified as Vamsi had worked as JCB operator at Triveni Crusher.

Vamsi who went missing on Thursday morning was found butchered in a forest area by the people of a nearby village who traced the body parts with a foul smell emanating from the area. The parents of Vamsi recognized him by his cell phone found at the spot.

The police sent the body to Srikalahasti area hospital for post-mortem. However, the relatives of Vamsi alleged that he was in an extramarital relationship with a woman who is suspected to have killed Vamsi.

SOURCE: <https://www.thehansindia.com/amp/posts/index/Latest-News/2019-02-10/Chittoor-youth-butchered-in-a-suspected-extramarital-affair/492197>

68) Woman bludgeons husband to death

A 32-year-old woman who took the body of her husband, whom she allegedly bludgeoned to death, to her native place in Salem district for burial was arrested by the police. Her brother-in-law who assisted her was also arrested.

A. Priya, a daily wage worker, murdered her husband Annamalai (35) following a quarrel under the influence of alcohol at their house at Periyakuyili near Chettipalayam on Sunday evening. The police said that the woman bludgeoned her husband using a stone. She then sought the help of her sister's husband K. Selvaraj (35) and the two took the body to Salem district for burial, making everyone believe that the man died of natural

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causes. Some of the relatives who found injuries on the body raised suspicions about the man's death. They informed the incident to Magudanchavadi police station.

Magudanchavadi police questioned Priya and Selvaraj and found that Annamalai was murdered. On being informed by the Magudanchavadi police, Chettipalayam police went to Salem and arrested the two.

SOURCE: [https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/Coimbatore/woman-bludgeons-husband-to-death/article31626669\) ece/amp/](https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/Coimbatore/woman-bludgeons-husband-to-death/article31626669) ece/amp/)

69) Man live streams suicide on Facebook

Had altercation with wife before taking step; was mentally disturbed: police

A married man committed suicide in a live video on Facebook by hanging himself from the ceiling fan at his house in Jatoli village here on Monday. He was mentally disturbed and under treatment, the police said.

Amit Chauhan (26) hanged himself in the evening after his wife Preeti left home with their two children following a minor altercation between them.

No one was at home when Amit took the extreme step.

SOURCE: [https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/Delhi/man-live-streams-suicide-on-facebook/article24567463\) ece](https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/Delhi/man-live-streams-suicide-on-facebook/article24567463) ece)

70) Newly-wed man commits suicide

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A 25-year-old newly married man allegedly committed suicide in the early hours of Monday after his wife complained to the police that she was forced to marry him in Hallada Hosahalli in Turuvekere taluk of Tumakuru district.

The police said that he has been identified as Mohan Gowda. He locked the cow shed from inside and allegedly hanged himself from the beam with a plastic wire. His grandmother Jayamma found him hanging from the window and called his parents. The parents informed the police and alleged that his wife and her family members are responsible for his death.

Mohan Gowda had run away with her and got married one month ago. However, her parents convinced her and took her away from him. The girl had given a complaint to the Turuvekere police that Mohan Gowda forced her to marry him 15 days ago.

This had upset Mohan Gowda. He had written about her on a Facebook page and also had uploaded a video stating that he would commit suicide as his wife had complained against him and left him. He has also written a death note stating the reason for taking the extreme step.

SOURCE: [https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/karnataka/newly-wed-man-commits-suicide/article24678828\) ece](https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/karnataka/newly-wed-man-commits-suicide/article24678828) ece)

71) Woman held on charge of plotting husband's murder

The late-night murder of a businessman that jolted the town took a twist here on Tuesday after investigation revealed that his wife was the main accused in the alleged crime.

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Hours after Bundaram (30) was found murdered at his residence at Vidya Nagara, the police cracked the case by arresting his wife Chandrika. “We are questioning her and investigating the case,” K. Parashuram, Mandya Superintendent of Police, told The Hindu here.

Interrogation of the accused revealed that she had hired killers to eliminate Bundaram as she had developed an acquaintance with another person named Suresh, said another senior police officer.

Suresh’s close relationship with the woman had come to the notice of the businessman recently and he had severely opposed it. This prompted the woman and her friend to eliminate Bundaram, added the officer.

Late on Monday, a group of accused hired by Chandrika visited Bundaram's house and assaulted him with weapons. Initially, the woman told her neighbors/police that the assailants had fastened her and her son in a room before attacking the victim. But detailed interrogation of the woman, following her contradictory statements, helped the police to crack the case. While Chandrika watched the crime, her two daughters were sleeping in a room, added the officer.

Meanwhile, the accused had forgotten a bag containing a pistol, a dagger and other materials in a bus in Hassan district. The Hassan police, following an explosive found at the Mangaluru International Airport on Monday, was conducting special searches at vital installations in their district. Alert public informed the police about the bag found in the bus.

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The police, with the help of KSRTC personnel, arrested the assailants when they came to collect the bag, added the officer.

SOURCE: [https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/karnataka/woman-held-on-charge-of-plotting-husbands-murder/article30615264\) ece/amp/](https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/karnataka/woman-held-on-charge-of-plotting-husbands-murder/article30615264) ece/amp/)

72) Woman, 2 others held for son's murder

MANSEHRA: The police arrested a woman who allegedly killed her son with the help of her father and brother in Barian Shungli village of Oghi tehsil on Tuesday, officials said.

They said the accused Gul Bano, her father Zahid Khan and brother Abdul Qadir were arrested after Gul Raheem, the husband of the woman, booked them in the murder case of his son, Usman, 12) According to first information report lodged with the police under section 302/34 of IPC, the accused woman had taken Usman with her parents' home following filling a marriage dissolution case with her husband in a local court some six months ago. "My in-laws, including my wife, her father and brother hanged my son to death as they had threatened me to do so in the past," Raheem told police. The police after lodging FIR arrested the accused who would be produced before the local court for obtaining physical remand. In another incident, a boy was killed after he fell from the rooftop of his under-construction home here.

SOURCE: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/amp/602503-woman-2-others-held-for-son-s-murder>

73) Woman, accomplices murder man; dump his body in Shahbad Dairy: Delhi Police

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Delhi police are on the lookout for a woman who planned the murder of her 31-year-old husband with help from two accomplices and dumped his body in Shahbad Dairy area earlier this month.

The man's body was found earlier this month but identified only recently. A post-mortem was conducted on his body on Monday, said the Police suspect the role of his wife and her two accomplices in the murder.

New Delhi: Police in the national capital are investigating the murder of a man whose body was recovered from outer Delhi's Shahbad Dairy area in the early hours of Monday. The victim has been identified as 31-year-old Satya Narayan, a resident of Haiderpur who worked as a car sales executive.

Narayan's disappearance first came to light on January 4 when his brother approached Shalimar Bagh police and registered a missing person complaint. An officer familiar with the investigation said that a case of abduction was registered in this regard. During a preliminary investigation, police examined call records of Narayan's wife and found out that she had been in constant touch with someone whose location was traced to the victim's last location.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/delhi-woman-hatches-plan-to-murder-husband-dumps-body-in-shahbad-dairy-area/542841>

74) Coimbatore man murders wife, commits suicide

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COIMBATORE: A 50-year-old man in Coimbatore murdered his wife over a family dispute and committed suicide by consuming cow-dung power (a chemical dye) on Thursday morning.

The deceased have been identified as R Muthuraj, 50, of Kavundampalayam and his wife, M Manimegalai, 40) Muthuraj was a daily wage earner.

Police said the couple had two sons - M Sriramachandran, 22, and M Gopalakrishnan, 21) Both are wall painters. Gopalakrishnan is staying in Udhagamandalam while Sriramachandran, who is married, lived with his parents.

According to police, Muthuraj suspected his wife's character as she often received phone calls from various people while she suspected that her husband had extramarital affair with a young woman in the area. So, the couple often fought with each other.

On late Wednesday night, the couple had a quarrel. Later, they slept. Around 1am on Thursday, Muthuraj murdered Manimegalai by hitting her with a stone. Later, he ended his life by consuming cow dung powder.

Their daughter-in-law, Pavithra, found the dead bodies and alerted the Thudiyalur police.

Inspector of police Balamurali Sundaram and his team rushed to the spot. The police registered two cases under Section 302 (murder) of the Indian Penal Code and Section 174 of the CrPC.

After postmortem, the bodies were handed over to the family members on Thursday afternoon.

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SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/chennai/coimbatore-man-murders-wife-commits-suicide/amp_articleshow/76750863\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/chennai/coimbatore-man-murders-wife-commits-suicide/amp_articleshow/76750863) cms)

75) Man kills estranged wife in Bengaluru, mom-in-law in Kolkata, shoots self

We had inadvertently uploaded a wrong photo in this story. We sincerely apologise for this error.

KOLKATA/BENGALURU: A city-chartered accountant flew to Bengaluru last weekend, murdered his estranged wife at her Whitefield home and then returned to Kolkata, where he shot dead his mother-in-law and then killed himself at an upscale residential complex in Phoolbagan on Monday evening.

The murder-murder-suicide came in the middle of acrimonious divorce proceedings that might have involved a dispute over property, cops said after an initial probe. Both Amit and Shilpi Agarwal were chartered accountants and were living separately — husband in Kolkata and wife in Bengaluru — for the last two years after the marriage turned sour. A 10-year-old son survived the grisly events of the past three days; Amit brought him back from Bengaluru on Monday and left him at his brother's residence in Kolkata before heading to Phoolbagan, cops said.

Amit knocked on his in-law's door, on the second floor of Tower B of Rameshwaram Apartments — a residential complex on Ramakrishna Samadhi Road — around 5:30 PM on Monday. Shilpi's parents, 70-year-old Subhas and 62-year-old Lalita Dhandhanian, were there and allowed Amit in, cops learnt from their neighbors.

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Sometime later, however, neighbors heard heated arguments that continued for some time. Neighbors later told cops that the debate “appeared to be” over some property documents that Amit wanted the Dhandhanias to sign.

Neighbors heard the first gunshot a little before 6) 30pm, following which Subhas ran out of his flat, bolted the door from outside and took refuge inside his next-door neighbor’s apartment. Cops were called and they arrived a few minutes later and entered the Dhandhanias’ home, where they found Lalita’s and Amit’s lifeless bodies. “The mother-in-law’s body was lying on the floor and Amit’s body was on a bed,” a senior police officer said, adding that cops had recovered the revolver that Amit had used to kill his mother-in-law and himself.

“We recovered a suicide note from the flat,” joint commissioner of police (crime) Murlidhar Sharma said. “It said that he had killed his wife in Bengaluru. We contacted cops there and the Whitefield deputy commissioner of police confirmed that Shilpi’s decomposed body was recovered from her home,” he added.

Cops in Bengaluru told TOI that Shilpi’s body was recovered from Brigade Metropolis apartment in Mahadevapura, Whitefield Road, around 9 PM on Monday. The flat bore the signs of a fight, officials said, adding that many items were scattered in the hall. “It indicates that Shilpi had opposed Amit’s entry and there seemed to have been a fight near the entrance itself. There seems to have been another scuffle near the kitchen, with smashed glass tumblers and damaged utensils lying around. The murder occurred near the bedroom,” an investigating officer said.

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Amit would visit Bengaluru when there were court hearings, cops said quoting neighbors, and most of these visits would end in fights. Deputy commissioner of police (Whitefield) MN Anuchet said investigators would speak to neighbors to learn more about the couple.

Officials in Kolkata said Amit returned from Bengaluru with his son on Monday. “He went to his brother’s residence and left his 10-year-old son with him before starting out for Phoolbagan,” an officer said, adding that Amit and Shilpi had married in 2005)

Cops in Kolkata have got in touch with Shilpi’s brother to help the probe. “It is important to find out what transpired immediately before the murder-suicide at the Phoolbagan flat. Did Amit divulge anything there? We are trying to get these details from Subhas,” an official said.

A police team has left for Uttarpara Station Road to question Amit’s relatives. Cops are also probing from where Amit got the six-chamber revolver.

SOURCE: [https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolkata/man-kills-estranged-wife-in-bluru-mom-in-law-in-kol-shoots-self/amp_articleshow/76519987\) cms](https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolkata/man-kills-estranged-wife-in-bluru-mom-in-law-in-kol-shoots-self/amp_articleshow/76519987) cms)

76) Odisha Woman Along with Paramour Killed Husband: Police

Berhampur: Unravelling a murder case that was reported on Tuesday, Ganjam Police on Thursday informed that the victim was killed by his wife, who along with her paramour executed the crime.

According to Berhampur Sadar SDPO, Jayant Mohapatra, one Mita Sahu of Masanipadar Sahi killed her husband Prafulla with help of her paramour Saroj Moharana. Mohapatra

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informed that Saroj visited Prafulla's house frequently. However, when Prafulla protested Saroj's visit and his relationship with Mita, the duo killed him on Tuesday.

Later, to cover up the incident, Mita informed everyone that Prafulla died after falling on the ground accidentally. Besides, she had filed a complaint with the police. However, the post-mortem report revealed that the deceased died due to strangulation. Suspecting some foul play by Mita, Prafulla's family members filed an FIR based on which the local police initiated an investigation into the matter.

Mita was arrested by the cops after interrogation yesterday. Saroj Maharana was also arrested after Mita revealed that they had an affair and killed Prafulla for opposing their relationship.

The accused have been forwarded to the court.

SOURCE: <https://odishatv.in/crime-news/odisha-woman-along-with-paramour-killed-husband-police-430246/amp>

77) Man kills self after being harassed by wife, her lover

A middle-aged man from the city committed suicide by jumping in front of a railway after allegedly being harassed by his wife, her paramour, brother and her mother. The deceased, Mohammed Asgar (40), was living in Kondhwa with his wife Ashma Asgar Shaikh.

The father of the deceased had approached Samarth police station and a case was registered against Ashma Asgar Shaikh, the mother-in-law Rajiya Ansari and brother-in-law Parvez Ansari, and an unknown person who is the lover of Ashma. The four have

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been booked for abetment of suicide under sections 306, 323, 504 and 34 of the Indian Penal Code.

The deceased's father, Mohammed Sharif Ismail Shaikh (67), in his complaint said, "Ashma had fought with us and had asked my son that she wanted to stay in a separate house. So, my son bought a flat in Kondhwa and the two started living there. Fed up of harassment by her, my son left and was living with us for about 10 months."

Shaikh has alleged that Ashma had beaten his wife and had her lover physically attack his son Asgar. He said Ashma was torturing his son and compelling him to name the flat on her name. "On April 2, my son told me he was going out for some work and left the house. After some time, I received a call from the Pune railway police who told me that they had found my son's body near Sangam bridge."

Police said they had found a suicide note in which Asgar blamed harassment from his wife, her brother, mother and her lover. Sub-inspector Parvej Shikalgar from Samarth police station is investigating the case.

Woman extorts lakhs from man, threatening to frame him in a 'rape case'

A 22-year-old woman was arrested for allegedly starting an affair with a married man and extorting Rs 4 lakhs and other valuables from him by threatening to file a rape case against him.

The duo came in contact after she allegedly sent him a Facebook request last year. Chikhali police have registered a case based on the complaint filed by the wife of the

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male victim. The accused has been identified as Sonia Uddesh Mehra (22 years), a resident of Vishrantwadi.

As per the complaint, Mehra had been extorting money from the victim for the past eight months. The victim, who is in his early 30s, runs an event management firm.

Mehra, who befriended him over Facebook told that her father had passed away and she was in deep financial problems.

A few months back, she invited him to a lodge in Chikhali's Gharkul Yojana and established sexual relations with him. She allegedly clicked his picture without his knowledge and started blackmailing him. She then took between Rs 3-4 lakhs from the victim in instalments, threatening to file a rape case.

Meanwhile, the victim's wife happened to see a message written by the suspects in Marathi to her husband.

"When questioned, he spilled the beans and said that he was due to pay her more money. The wife approached us on Saturday. Some of the transactions were done using online platforms and we have those records," said sub-inspector Ratna Sawant from Chikhali police station.

Cops suspect that Mehra has extorted money from other men too in a similar fashion. She has been booked for extortion under section 384 of the Indian Penal Code.

SOURCE: <https://punemirror.indiatimes.com/pune/crime/man-kills-self-after-being-harassed-by-wife-her-lover/articleshow/68982225.cms>

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78) Man murders wife, hangs self from fan

He left behind a brief suicide note, saying that he has sent his wife to her deceased mother

On Tuesday morning, a gruesome case came to light in Bhosari, where a man murdered his wife and then committed suicide. They had been married for 10 years and had a seven yearold daughter. The man wrote a brief suicide note before killing self, which mentions that he was sending his wife to her mother (who is no more) — thus confessing that he had murdered his wife before hanging self. A case has been registered by Bhosari police.

The deceased have been identified as Priyanka and Nilesh Deshmukh. Nilesh hails from Indore, whereas Priyanka hails from Amravati. They had settled in Bhosari a few years ago.

On Monday, Priyanka had sent her daughter to a friend's home. Around 9 pm, the friend called up Priyanka so that she could take her daughter home. However, she did not receive her phone. The friend then deemed it appropriate to keep Priyanka's daughter at her place overnight.

On Tuesday morning, the friend again called her. The call went unanswered. So, she went to Deshmukh's residence, where knocking on the door elicited no response. In a state of doubt, the friend called up the police, who entered the house after breaking the door. They found Nilesh's body hanging from the ceiling fan and Priyanka was lying on the bed. She was strangulated to death.

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Police inspector Shankar Avtade, attached to Bhosari police station, told Mirror, “The couple had a love marriage ten years ago. They would quarrel daily Nilesh had been unemployed for the last two years and Priyanka worked with a Tata showroom.”

He then confirmed the ordeal, involving Priyanka’s friend who dialed the cops upon receiving no response to multiple calls. “Priyanka’s friend had reached the house at 10 am on Tuesday. She knocked on the door persistently before calling the police. The door was later opened with help from locals,” he added.

Both the bodies have been sent to Yashwantrao Chavan Memorial Hospital for post-mortem. Their daughter has been handed over to Nilesh’s brother. At present, a case of accidental death has been registered, following which a murder case will be registered.

SOURCE: <https://punemirror.indiatimes.com/pune/crime/man-murders-wife-hangs-self-from-fan/articleshow/73257323.cms>

79) Medak: Wife, paramour kill husband

Medak: A woman allegedly killed her husband with the help of her paramour on the outskirts of Annaram village of Papannapet Mandal in Medak district during the intervening hours of Monday and Tuesday. The victim was identified as Janumula Devadas (36), a resident of Annaram village. He was strangled to death with a wire. In a written complaint from Latchamma, mother of Devadas, she has suspected the role of Devadas’s wife Parvathi and her paramour Gaddam Babu. Latchamma said that Parvathi and Devadas had an argument even on Monday late night. The villagers say the couple used to fight quite frequently over her relationship with Babu. Sub-inspector of Police,

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Medak Rural Police Station, Rajashekar has said that they have registered a case and the investigation is on.

SOURCE: <https://telanganatoday.com/medak-wife-paramour-kill-husband/amp>

80) Woman, paramour arrested for killing husband

SRINAGAR, Jan 21: Police today solved a murder case in which a woman along with her paramour had killed her husband in Pariswani village of Tangmarg in North Kashmir's Baramulla district.

One Mudasir Ahmad Reshi son of Kahzir Mohammad Reshi resident of Pariswani Tangmarg was missing from his home since 15th of January. A day after his missing, the family had registered a missing report in Police Station Kunzer and Police started investigations into his missing. On 18th January the body of deceased was recovered Reram Nallah in Tangmarg.

The SSP Baramulla Abdul Qayoom told a press conference in Baramulla that on 16th of January Police station Kunzer received a written complaint that one person Mudasir Ahmad Reshi Son of Khazir Mohammad Reshi resident of Pariswani is missing.

He said searches were launched to trace the missing man. He said that on today they solved the murder case within in 3 days and have arrested accused duo involved in the killing.

He said during the course of proceeding, the officer investigating the case learnt that two suspects identified as Sumira Begum wife of Mudasir Ahmad and Waseem Ah Reshi resident of Pariswani had hatched a conspiracy to murder the Mudasir.

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“During the investigation, the wife of deceased Mudasir Ahmed admitted that she called her husband to reach Reram Nallah where the duo first hit him with stick and later Waseem Ahmad stabbed him with knife”, she said.

The officer said according to case FIR No, 04/2020 under Section 302 IPC was registered at Police station Kunzer and investigation was taken up. He further added that both the accused were taken to custody have admitted of killing him.

SOURCE: <https://www.dailyexcelsior.com/woman-paramour-arrested-for-killing-husband-2/>

81) Dislike for husband drives woman to stab him to death as poisoning proves ineffective

Police said the woman first poisoned her husband and when it did not prove effective, she stabbed the victim Vakji Patel to death at their residence in Sector 6 Gandhinagar.

The victim has been identified as 23-year-old Vakji Patel. The incident took place at Sector 6 in Gandhinagar on Tuesday evening. Police: The woman stabbed her husband after the poison she gave him proved ineffective.

Ahmedabad: In a shocking incident reported from Gujarat capital Gandhinagar, a woman first poisoned her husband and then stabbed him to death as she did not 'like' him.

The victim has been identified as 23-year-old Vakji Patel. The incident took place at Sector 6 in Gandhinagar on Tuesday evening.

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According to a report in Times of India, the accused woman initially told police that her husband poisoned himself before she stabbed him. The accused has been identified as Umiya Patel.

"During the course of interrogation, we found out that the woman stabbed her husband after the poison she gave him proved ineffective. The woman has been sent for COVID-19 test before her arrest," said Mayur Chavda, Superintendent of Police (SP), Gandhinagar.

The couple was married for two years but somehow did not like each other.

"The accused woman used to live with her parents at Mangrol village of Banaskantha district. The woman would occasionally stay at her husband's house in Tharad. The victim used to work at a printing press in Gandhinagar," the report quoted Inspector Amarsinh Chauhan from Sector 21 police station as saying.

The inspector added that the couple was staying at a rented accommodation in Gandhinagar for the last few days. The victim's father Narbat Patel has filed a police complaint against the woman on Tuesday night.

According to the FIR, the woman's father Premabhai called Vakji and told him that his wife had called him to the place and murdered him.

SOURCE: <https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/dislike-for-husband-drives-woman-to-stab-him-to-death-as-poisoning-proves-ineffective/622572>

82) Indian Stepmother strangled Husband's Son aged 4

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An Indian stepmother from a village in Jharkhand carried out a heinous crime in which she strangled her husband's four-year-old son.

an Indian stepmother has been arrested after she killed her husband's four-year-old son.

The shocking crime happened on May 17, 2020, in the village of Baniyadih, Jharkhand.

Villagers heard about the incident and went to the house. They found out that the child's stepmother was responsible for the killing. Meanwhile, the father called the police.

Police identified the victim as Rohit Kumar. When officers arrived at the scene, they found bruises and nail marks around the boy's neck.

During questioning, she admitted killing the child, saying that the constant arguments with her husband had angered her to a point that she killed the boy.

The father, Teklal Das, filed a police complaint, accusing his second wife Sarita Devi of killing his son.

He said that he earned a living by driving a tractor. On the day of the murder, Teklal returned home at 3 pm to have food with his son.

Teklal then went back out to work and did not return home until 7 PM. When he did not see his son, he asked Sarita who claimed that she put him to bed.

The boy did not wake and at 9 PM, Teklal tried to wake his son but was unsuccessful. The concerned father and a neighbour took the child to the hospital where doctors declared him dead.

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He immediately suspected his wife as she was the only person who was with his son.

On returning from the hospital, Teklal asked her what happened. Sarita confessed to killing Rohit, saying she strangled him to death.

Teklal then called the police while neighbors gathered near the house after hearing about what happened.

It was revealed that Teklal's first wife died during childbirth. After his wife's death, Rohit went live with his aunt while Teklal lived with his father.

He decided that he would get married again. With the support of relatives, he got married to Sarita in December 2019.

Sarita was a mother to a one-year-old daughter. Her first husband had separated from her.

After the marriage, Rohit returned to live with his father. It was reported that the Indian stepmother was jealous of the four-year-old child.

Sarita has been arrested and has been remanded in custody following her confession.

Meanwhile, the victim's body was sent to Sadar Hospital for a post-mortem. Police are awaiting the results so that they can carry on with the investigation.

SOURCE: <https://www.desiblitz.com/content/indian-stepmother-strangled-husbands-son-aged-4>

83) NRI attempts suicide, wife, ex-wife among 11 booked

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Ex-wife was hindering visa application process of 36-year-old's wife; victim also came to know that the latter was twice divorced before getting married to him

A 36-year-old non-resident Indian (NRI) man tried to commit suicide by consuming a poisonous substance at a village in Ludhiana.

Police said the victim was admitted to Satguru Partap Singh Hospital at Sherpur Chowk of Ludhiana, and his condition is serious.

Based on the suicide note recovered from his pocket and statement of his elder brother, the Meharban police on Wednesday booked 11 people, including the victim's wife, ex-wife and their relatives.

The complainant said the victim, who is settled in Canada, had got married in 2010 and migrated to Canada with his wife. He said the woman had lodged a complaint against her husband at the Doraha police station in 2013 for dowry harassment. While the case was in court, the couple got divorced and the woman solemnized marriage her marriage with a Moga man.

The complainant said the victim also got married to another woman in January this year, adding that the woman and her parents were forcing him to take her to Canada. When he applied for her visa, the victim's ex-wife and her father complained against it to the embassy.

The complainant also alleged that they came to know that his current wife was already twice divorced before her marriage to the victim. He said the couple had an argument

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over it on Tuesday, following which the victim consumed poison at home, and was rushed to the hospital.

ASI Gurmukh Singh, who is investigating the case, said the accused were booked under Sections 306 (abetment to suicide) and 511 (attempting to commit offences) of the Indian Penal Code. “The condition of victim is serious. A hunt is on for the arrest of the accused.”

SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/chandigarh/nri-attempts-suicide-wife-ex-wife-among-11-booked/story-pPk1ezhuH1W5YOYt5qFBO.html>

84) IIT-IIM alumnus engineer commits suicide in Noida, wife booked for abetment

Even though no suicide note was recovered from the spot, the family suspects that his ongoing marital discord and financial trouble pushed him to suicide.

The family of a 39-year-old software engineer, who allegedly took his life on Monday morning by jumping from the balcony of his 10th floor apartment in Sector 128, has filed a case of abetment to suicide against his wife and in-laws.

Even though no suicide note was recovered from the spot, the family suspects that his ongoing marital discord and financial trouble pushed him to suicide.

The family said they first got a call around 10 AM from a security guard of the society who said the man, an alumnus of IIT-Kanpur and IIM-Ahmedabad, had “burnt down his house and was admitted to a private hospital nearby”.

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“When we reached the society, we found that he had jumped from his balcony and was dead,” the father, a resident of Delhi, said in his police complaint.

The family blames his wife for him ending his life. The couple had got married in 2014. According to family members, she was posted in a PSU in Haridwar at that time and he was working with a private firm in Gurugram.

“After a while, they both got transfers to Noida and moved to Sector 45. Soon afterwards, they started facing problems and my son ended up losing his job. He started his own venture but that also failed to take off. He was being constantly pressured by her family and one day, he told me that his father-in-law and two brothers-in-law had assaulted him and threatened to harm him. He had moved to the Sector 128 house after he filed for separation,” said the father in his complaint.

The wife had also filed a case against him, accusing him of subjecting her to cruelty, almost two years ago, when they separated. “He was under a lot of pressure and told us that her family was asking for Rs 50 lakhs and a flat to withdraw that case. We are convinced that it was the physical and mental harassment that led my son to take this step,” he said.

Based on the father’s complaint, a case was registered at the Expressway police station under IPC Section 306 against the wife, her parents and two brothers.

Police said the wife is working now in Noida. “So far, the family has not been able to provide her exact address. We are working on this. A probe in the matter is underway. Due legal action will be taken soon,” Bhuvnesh Kumar, station house officer, Expressway police station, said.

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The body was handed over to the family following an autopsy.

SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/iim-iit-grad-suicide-wife-in-laws-booked-for-abetment/story-0EbrW59dP53NcDaYh0VRJJ.html>

85) 62-yr-old Delhi doctor shoots woman dead over affair, then kills himself: Cops

Rajneesh Gupta, deputy commissioner of police (Rohini), identified the dead doctor as a general physician of a hospital in Rohini and the woman he allegedly shot dead as the managing director (MD) of a nursing home associated with the same hospital.

A 62-year-old doctor shot dead a 55-year-old woman in a car in Delhi's Rohini area before using the licensed revolver to shoot himself, police said after finding two dead bodies in a white Volkswagen Vento car on Wednesday morning.

SD Mishra, deputy commissioner of police (Rohini), identified the dead doctor as a general physician of a hospital in Rohini and the woman he allegedly shot dead as the managing director (MD) of a nursing home associated with the same hospital.

“The doctor and the MD were in a relationship. The woman wanted the doctor to marry him. That demand led to the murder and suicide,” the DCP said based on the initial probe.

While the police are yet to verify the family background of the woman, the doctor was a married man with two children, said the DCP. His son is a doctor in another state while his daughter is a doctor in another part of the city, the DCP added.

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The bodies were found by a passerby around 7.45 am on an isolated stretch of a road in Rohini Sector 13, the DCP said. “The car’s ignition was on and the doors were locked from inside. We had to break open a window to gain access to the bodies,” said the DCP.

The woman was shot in her chest while the doctor had shot himself in his head, the officer said.

SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/delhi-news/62-yr-old-delhi-doctor-shoots-woman-dead-over-affair-then-kills-himself-cops/story-anOV4wG7EWdg8tpaEB8vjL.html>

86) Man hangs to death in Gurugram

Kuldeep, investigating officer, Sadar police station, said, “We found a suicide note at the spot. The persons mentioned in the suicide note are yet to be arrested.”

A man, in his late twenties, allegedly committed suicide by hanging himself at his house in Sector 33 on Friday. The police said that in his suicide note, the man has alleged that his wife, mother-in-law and a relative were harassing him.

“My brother got married in April 2018. He was under stress because of his wife, mother-in-law and a relative,” the deceased’s younger brother stated in his FIR. However, the family members of the deceased’s widow have denied the allegations of harassment. “He used to beat her (his wife) and was depressed even before they got married,” a relative of the man’s widow said.

Kuldeep, investigating officer, Sadar police station, said, “We found a suicide note at the spot. The persons mentioned in the suicide note are yet to be arrested.”

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SOURCE:

<https://www.hindustantimes.com/gurgaon/man-hangs-to-death-in-gurugram/story-pKizpqTGCUBP4dXpQbhZLJ.html>

87) Dalit man commits suicide in Hyderabad, blames in-laws for separating him from OBC wife

Srikanth's family members told police that he had married Gadagoju Sriharsha who belonged to an Other Backward Caste, much against the wishes of her parents.

A Dalit man committed suicide by setting himself ablaze in Hyderabad in the early hours of Thursday after recording a video blaming his in-laws for taking away his wife and turning her against him, police said.

Chittipaka Srikanth (24) doused himself with kerosene and set himself ablaze at his residence in Santoshnagar area of the old city in yet another tragic end to an inter-caste marriage. He was rushed to Osmania General Hospital immediately, where he succumbed to his injuries in the afternoon.

Srikanth's family members told the Santoshnagar police that he had married Gadagoju Sriharsha (23), who belonged to an Other Backward Caste, from Nakirekal town in Nalgonda district, at an Arya Samaj temple in Hyderabad in 2015, much against the wishes of her parents.

“A few months ago, Sriharsha became pregnant and her parents forcibly took her away to their home. Since then, they had not been allowing Srikanth to meet her,” the police quoted the relatives as saying.

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In a video he shot on his mobile phone before he set himself on fire, Srikanth blamed his wife Sriharsha who is presently pursuing her MBBS, her father G Shanmukha Chary, other family members and a police constable for his suicide.

He alleged that Chary, who converted to Christianity, had brainwashed Sriharsha, forced her to undergo abortion and was looking for fresh alliances for her. “When I confronted them, my father-in-law started torturing me and harassing me by foisting cases against me and my family members. We were arrested and jailed for some time, before we came out on bail,” he said.

He said his wife had stopped talking to him. “I ran from pillar to post, including local politicians, seeking justice, but nobody came to my rescue,” he said.

The Santosh Nagar police are investigating the case.

Srikanth’s father Ch Muttaiah told reporters outside the hospital that his family had borne the entire expenditure for his daughter-in-law’s MBBS course and other needs, but her parents had forcibly separated the couple, after she got pregnant. “My son was madly in love with the girl and he could not forget her,” he said.

This is the third incident of trouble in inter-caste marriages in Telangana in less than a week. Pranay Perumalla, a Dalit engineering graduate was brutally murdered by a professional killer hired by his upper caste father-in-law T Maruthi Rao, who did not approve of Pranay’s marriage with his only daughter Amrutha Varshni in Miryalaguda town of Nalgonda district. The police arrested seven people including Amrutha’s father T Maruthi Rao on Tuesday.

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SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/dalit-man-commits-suicide-in-hyderabad-blames-in-laws-for-separating-him-from-obc-wife/story-rf6G8fPIUwPHkx2uxwg5SN.html>

88) Woman booked for driving husband to commit suicide in Pune

The deceased's mother told the police in the complaint that the accused woman made her husband do the household chores, which led him to commit suicide

A woman has been booked by the Hadapsar police for abetment of suicide of her husband at their residence in Magarpatta, Hadapsar.

The deceased man has been identified as Pranay Milind Khutal, 29, a resident of Zinnia building in Magarpatta. He is suspected to have committed suicide, by hanging himself, on the night intermediate of December 6 and December 7.

The complaint was lodged by Sangita Khutal, 49 years, the mother of the deceased man.

Khutal lives in Limboda village of Hatod taluka in Indore, Madhya Pradesh. The deceased's mother told the police in the complaint that the accused woman made Pranay do the household chores, which led him to commit suicide.

The complainant told the police that the wife would beat Pranay up, force him to wash clothes and utensils and make tea, according to the police.

The accused woman has been identified as Kanika Khutal, who is in her late 20s. While the deceased man was an employee at a private company, the accused woman is a housewife, according to the police.

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“They have been married since 2015. They have lived in various places, including Bhopal and Indore, before moving to Magarpatta six months ago,” said assistant police inspector (API) VO Bhabad of Hadapsar police station, who is investigating the case.

When the man was found hanging, a case of accidental death was registered at the Hadapsar police station.

A case under Sections 306 (abetment of suicide) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) has now been registered at the Hadapsar police station.

SOURCE: <https://www.hindustantimes.com/pune-news/woman-booked-for-driving-husband-to-commit-suicide-in-pune/story-EaUFQm1qIpfRgaXdYJf9qN.html>

89) Woman Strangles Newborn Daughter to Death in Hospital, 4 Hours After Giving Birth

A woman killed her newborn daughter, hours after giving birth to the girl. The incident took place at a hospital in the western Indian state of Gujarat on Saturday.

Speaking to local media Tuesday, police said the woman gave birth to the child around 4 in the afternoon. Four hours later, the husband of the unidentified woman approached the doctor and said his wife was finding it difficult to breastfeed the baby.

The doctor examined the baby and declared her dead. An autopsy was conducted Sunday, the results of which indicated that the newborn was strangled to death. The report also said there were marks on the baby’s face and neck. Investigation was ongoing to find out the reason behind the crime. Meanwhile, police said the couple already had three daughters.

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"A case under section 302 (murder) of the Indian Penal Code has been registered against the woman, and an arrest will be made after gathering more conclusive evidence," police said.

The incident comes a month after a woman in the Indian state of Maharashtra flung her newborn to death from the 17th floor of a building. Residents of the apartment complex alerted the police after finding the baby dead. Investigation revealed the woman had delivered the girl in the bathroom before throwing her from the window a few minutes later.

"The accused told us that she suspected that the husband was having an affair and was not giving money to take care of expenses and so she was struggling to take care of their two children," police said, adding that a case of murder was registered against the unidentified accused.

SOURCE: <https://www.ibtimes.com/woman-strangles-newborn-daughter-death-hospital-4-hours-after-giving-birth-2895734>

90) Newborn girl stolen from West Bengal hospital

A newborn girl was stolen from a government hospital in Purba Bardhaman district of West Bengal on Sunday by a woman who lured her parents with the promise of getting them money from a scheme.

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The accused woman was identified through CCTV footage of the hospital and efforts are on to nab her and rescue the baby, police said.

The girl was born in the maternity ward of the Barddhaman Medical College and Hospital on Friday and the baby and her mother, Rima Malik, were released on Sunday, Deputy Superintendent of the hospital Dr Amitabha Saha said.

When the family members were leaving the hospital, a woman came to them claiming to be a social worker. She told them that the government provides Rs 6,000 to all girl child born in hospitals, Saha said.

The accused woman took the family to another government hospital and sent the newborn's parents on errands and fled with the baby.

Police said they have started an investigation.

Newborn girl stolen from West Bengal hospital

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SOURCE: <https://www.indiatoday.in/amp/crime/story/newborn-girl-stolen-from-west-bengal-hospital-1638336-2020-01-20>

92) Ghaziabad: Wife, mother-in-law among three arrested for killing husband

Three people have been arrested for allegedly killing a railway carpenter, said police on Tuesday. The accused have been identified as the victim's wife Rishika, mother-in-law Rama Devi and her paramour Davendra, alias Kansa. The victim, identified as Surjeet, was a resident of the Punjab Lines colony. He lived there with his wife and a four-year-old son.

DSP Dharmendra Chauhan said the accused have confessed to their crime. During investigation, police found discrepancies in their statements after which they were arrested.

Police said they admitted that Surjeet was opposing his mother-in-law Rama's illicit relationship with Kansa.

Rishika knew about it but never objected to the relationship. Surjeet often had an argument with them over the issue.

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On Monday, he again had an argument with them after which the accused allegedly made a plan to eliminate him.

Police said Rama invited the victim for a dinner at her residence.

According to the plan, they hit him on his head with an iron rod and strangled him to death.

They threw the body in a nearby vacant dilapidated house. The body was found in a pool of blood by police, the DSP said.

SOURCE: <https://www.indiatvnews.com/amp/crime/ghaziabad-murder-case-wife-mother-in-law-arrested-for-killing-husband-612312>

93) 42-year-old man killed by wife, son over domestic feud; decomposed body recovered

The police questioned Ghuge, who allegedly admitted that he alongwith and his mother Jayashree killed Angadrao Ghuge, his father, as the deceased often quarelled with them over domestic issues.

A woman and her son were arrested after her husband was found dead in Maharashtra's Solapur district. According to the police, the woman took the help of her son's friend to plot the murder of her own husband, over a domestic feud. The deceased was identified as 42-year-old Angadrao Suresh Ghuge, who was a resident of Bhalgaon in Barshi tehsil.

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The incident came to light on last Friday when the police found the decomposed body of a man at Laul village in Madha tehsil, an official said. There were deep injuries on the body and it had been set on fire.

The police later found an abandoned Scorpio car with blood stains inside in Barshi. DNA samples from the unidentified body found in Laul matched with the blood.

The owner of the Scorpio, Sonu Pawar, told police that he had given the car on January 11 to Vishal Ghuge (19), and Ghuge had not returned the car even after a week.

The police questioned Ghuge, who allegedly admitted that he along with his mother Jayashree killed Angadrao Ghuge, his father, as the deceased often quarreled with them over domestic issues.

Fed up with his behavior, Vishal, his mother and three of his friends killed Angadrao, he allegedly told police.

The police arrested Vishal and his mother while a search was on for the remaining three accused, the officer said.

SOURCE: <https://www.indiatvnews.com/amp/crime/solapur-man-murdered-by-wife-son-maharashtra-582472>

94) Woman Stabs Husband to Death, Tries to Fake it as Accident in Coimbatore

However, she cracked during sustained interrogation and confessed that she had stabbed her husband during an argument over getting back her gold necklace (mangalsutra) pledged with the pawn broker, the sources added.

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A woman was arrested in Coimbatore on Tuesday on charges of killing her husband with a knife, police said. Franklin Britto, working as a salesman in a private firm here, was brought to the Government Hospital with bleeding injuries on the neck and abdomen by his wife, Carolyn, late last Monday.

However, doctors declared him brought dead, police sources said. On inquiry, Carolyn told police that her husband sustained the injuries accidentally as the knife pierced his stomach when she suddenly turned after slicing vegetables in the kitchen, they said.

However, she cracked during sustained interrogation and confessed that she had stabbed her husband during an argument over getting back her gold necklace (mangalsutra) pledged with the pawn broker, the sources added.

SOURCE: <https://www.news18.com/amp/news/india/woman-stabs-husband-to-death-tries-to-fake-it-as-accident-in-coimbatore-2919337.html>

95) Woman, lover held for killing husband in Bengaluru

BENGALURU: A 27-year-old woman, who allegedly got her husband murdered and tried to show it as a robbery bid, has been arrested with five others, including her lover. The arrested are Gayathri of Hegganahalli; Irfan Pasha, 23, Saddam, 23, from Anandanagar; Nayaz Pasha, 20, of Sompura; Kaleemullah, 26, of Vajarahalli and Ram Prashant M, 27, of Hegganahalli Cross. The deceased, Ravikumar was working in the APMC market.

Madanayakanahalli police said Gayathri had an affair with Sathish and her husband had warned her against it. But Gayathri and Satish decided to get rid of Kumar. On July 17 at

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10pm, a seven-member gang intercepted Kumar and his friend Basavaraj, assaulted him and made away with valuables. Initially, police suspected it to be murder for gain, but probe revealed it was a well-planned operation. Police are on the lookout for Satish.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/bengaluru/woman-lover-held-for-killing-husband-in-bengaluru/amp_articleshow/77232090.cms

96) Mumbai: Wife held for conspiracy in husband murder case

MUMBAI: Shivaji Nagar police on Wednesday arrested a 35-year-old woman in connection with the orchestrated murder of her husband.

Police arrested Yasmin, the wife of deceased Ahadullah who was found dead in Navi Mumbai early last month. The circumstances under which Ahadullah was found dead in the pool of blood with his skull crushed on the road, was considered an accident case and Turbhe police closed the case as an accidental death report (ADR) On June 18, Ahadullah 's wife Yasmin lodged a complaint with Shivaji Nagar police that her husband was missing for two days and did not return home. Police registered a missing complaint and circulated his pictures to adjoining police stations. Deceased Ahadullah Khan a resident of Govandi was a civil painter and used to take contracts of painting buildings.

During the investigations deceased Ahadullah's brother Sajid alleged that he suspected foul play and pinpointed one Naushad Khan's involvement. Police picked up Khan and inquired. At the same time Yasmin secretly shifted to Kajupada in Kurla west. After interrogations Khan spilled the beans on the murder conspiracy and named his accomplices and Yasmin.

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Police then arrested Ram Kumar alias Devraj Nirmal (28), Noor Alam Khan (38) and Mohammed Taqi Ahmed Shaikh (28) Khan told the cops that he was having illicit affairs with Yasmin and secondly deceased had taken a loan of Rs 2 lakhs from him on interest which he had failed to return even after two years. Hence Khan under pretext of availing a painting contract took him to Navi Mumbai and killed him with an iron rod and then moved a jeep over his head to look like an accident.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/mumbai/mumbai-wife-held-for-conspiracy-in-husband-murder-case/amp_articleshow/77269155.cms

97) Woman sentenced for killing husband

Kolhapur: Satara court has sentenced a 37-year-old woman to two and a half years of rigorous imprisonment for murdering her husband. The woman killed her husband by setting him ablaze, suspecting his character. District and session judge A A A R Auti sentenced the accused Seeta Balu Rokade, a resident of Riswad village in Patan tehsil of Satara district, after considering witnessES and circumstantial evidence. Nine witnesses appeared in the hearing.

Milind Kulkarni, the assistant public prosecutor, said the incident took place on December 20, 2017. According to the prosecution, Seeta suspected her husband's character. She used to feel that her husband, Balu Rokade, was in a relationship with another woman of the village. The couple used to frequently fight over the issue.

After a heated argument about the issue one day, the accused poured petrol on her husband and set him ablaze. The victim ran to his relative and told them his wife had set

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him on fire. The relatives rushed him to the nearest primary health centre. He was shifted to the Satara civil hospital, however, he died while undergoing treatment.

SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolhapur/woman-sentenced-for-killing-husband/amp_articleshow/77136341.cms

98) Wife arrested for killing husband with help of paramour in Pimpri-Chinchwad

The woman said that she wanted to marry her cousin brother who lives in Mumbai but since her parents and her husband's parents were not ready to listen, she took the extreme step

The Pimpri-Chinchwad police arrested a 20-year-old woman for allegedly murdering her 28-year-old husband with the help of a man, who is believed to be her boyfriend. The accused woman was identified as Ritu Gaikwad, while her deceased husband was identified as Mayur Gaikwad, both residents of Dahivade Mamurdi.

According to a report in Hindustan Times, the woman was remanded to police custody and the cops are on the lookout for the man who helped her in the murder. The incident came to light after the deceased's younger brother received a call from his neighbour at 9:30 am on Tuesday, who said that his brother was lying in a pool of blood in their house.

After receiving the news, the deceased's younger brother Omkar Gaikwad (25 years), who works in a local hospital, along with his mother filed a police complaint. While the complainant's mother was working in night shift, he was with a friend at the time of the alleged murder.

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In his complaint, Omkar said that the two pet dogs of the family were locked in another room of the house when he returned and found his brother dead. Acting on Omkar's complaint, the police registered a case under Sections 302 (murder) and 34 (common intention) of the Indian Penal Code at Dehuroad police station against the woman.

Manish Kalyankar, senior police inspector of Dehuroad police station, said, "We have arrested her today. She said her phone was taken away for the past few months and nobody was listening to her requests of not staying married to him. She wanted to marry her cousin brother who lives in Mumbai. But since her parents and his parents were not ready to listen, so she took this step."

SOURCE: <https://m.mid-day.com/amp/articles/pune-crime-wife-arrested-for-killing-husband-with-help-of-paramour-in-pimpri-chinchwad/23021283>

99) Wife, minor daughter among four held for husband's killing in south Delhi

NEW DELHI: A 36-year-old woman, her minor daughter and two other persons were apprehended for allegedly killing her husband in south Delhi's Maidan Garhi area, police said on Saturday.

The accused have been identified as Sarita Tawar, a resident of Dera village and her friend Manoj (22 years), a resident of Loni in Ghaziabad.

Sarita's minor daughter and the girl's school friend were also apprehended, they said. All four persons were involved in the incident, police said.

On July 2, a decomposed body of a man was recovered from a drain at Mahabali Puram near Bhati village.

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Police saw a tattoo with the initials 'ST' on the body, they said. An abandoned car was also found around one kilometer from the spot.

Based on the ownership of the car, the deceased was identified as Mahender alias Sanjay, a resident of Dera village, a senior police officer said.

During investigation, the brother of the deceased said that Mahender used to drive a taxi.

He went out to pick up a booking but did not return, the officer said.

When the officer asked Mahender's wife, she said that his phone was switched off and he had not returned since July 1. Mahender's brother also informed that one Manoj used to visit his house and the couple used to fight over this issue, the officer said.

"Police questioned Manoj who confessed to his crime. On his instance, Sarita was nabbed. The daughter of the deceased and her school friend, were also apprehended," Deputy Commissioner of Police (South) Atul Kumar Thakur said.

Interrogation revealed that Manoj was a close friend of Sarita for the past eight to nine months.

They used to meet and Mahender knew about it, police said.

The deceased allegedly used to beat his wife and daughter. Manoj was annoyed with it and planned to kill him, they said. On June 30, Mahender was drunk when Manoj reached his house. The accused persons overpowered Mahender and strangulated him.

Later, they loaded the body in Mahender's car and dumped in the drain, the DCP added.

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SOURCE: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/delhi/2020/jul/11/wife-minor-daughter-among-four-held-for-husbands-killing-in-south-delhi-2168425.amp>

100) Woman among 3 arrested for killing spouse

The Sonapat police claimed to have solved a murder case of a 26-year-old man by arresting three persons, including the deceased's wife.

Sandeep of district's Guhna village was found dead in his fields on Sunday. The autopsy revealed that he was strangled.

The police booked a youth of Bhatgaon village and members of his family in connection with the murder. But during probe, it came to fore that the deceased's wife, Nirmal, was behind the murder as she was reportedly in a relationship with one of the accused, Sandeep, alias Boda.

Subsequently, Nirmal was nabbed. During interrogation, she admitted to have asked Boda to kill her husband.

Boda was arrested on Sunday and he reportedly admitted to have killed Sandeep. He disclosed his friend Asha of Gohana was also involved.

Nirmal and Asha have been sent to judicial custody, while Boda remanded to a two-day police custody.

SOURCE: <https://m.tribuneindia.com/news/haryana/woman-among-3-arrested-for-killing-spouse-109704>

101) Wife poisons, stabs man to death in Gandhinagar

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AHMEDABAD: A 21-year-old woman, Umiya Patel, allegedly poisoned and stabbed her 23-year-old husband Vakji Patel, killing him, at Sector 6 in Gandhinagar on Tuesday evening. She had initially told investigators that her husband had poisoned himself before she stabbed him.

SP Gandhinagar, Mayur Chavda, said during her interrogation it emerged that she had poisoned him and later stabbed him because the poison was proving ineffective. Chavda said the accused was sent for a pre-arrest Covid test.

Inspector Amarsinh Chauhan of Sector 21 police station said the couple married about two years ago, but apparently did not like each other. “The woman lived at her parents’ house at Mangrol village in Tharad taluka of Banaskantha district. They would occasionally stay together at the house of Vakji’s father, Narbat Patel, in Tharad. Vakji, who had passed Class XII, worked at a printing press owned by one Vashram Patel in Gandhinagar. For the last few days, the couple were staying at a rented house in Gandhinagar,” added Chauhan.

According to the FIR lodged by the victim’s father Narbat Patel (Chaudhary), on Tuesday night, Umiya’s father, Premabhai, had called him and told him that Umiya had called him and said that something had happened to Vakji and he was unable to speak now. Police sources said they called a relative in the police, Jebhai Patel, and asked him to go to Vakji’s house while they left for Gandhinagar.

“According to the FIR, when they reach Vakji’s house, they saw policemen there and Vakji’s body in a pool of blood on the floor of the house. Umiya was sitting on the staircase weeping,” said a police official.

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SOURCE: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/ahmedabad/wife-poisons-stabs-man-to-death/amp_articleshow/76987533.cms

This study Article / Report is based on news media coverage published in India in the first six months of 2020, and is not as collected by Women organizations using Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories which have no valid backing or proof.

There is a woman behind every crime listed above, either she is involved directly abusing/abetting or killing a man or is the reason for the crime. In India Women is empowered to kill anyone and most of the time she escapes punishment because of the biased Indian laws which are favorable to Women and encourage them to take the lead in a crime. She will get away even though she is abetting the suicide of a man and even if she is charged, she will hardly be sentenced for 2/3 years. But if a man is convicted, he will get a life in prison which shows how the Indian Judiciary is biased.

All the above news stories show why men are committing suicide or sometimes even taking extreme steps like killing the wife and her family who harassed him throughout his married life. Most of the suicides are because of family problems, threats from wives to file fake cases, financial commitment towards the family, one sided laws, Reservation and Schemes meant only for females, zero support from Government, zero protection from current laws against false accusations and fake cases.

Recently feminists and Minister of NCW mentioned that women are harassed and abused during the COVID-19 Pandemic. There are many reports covered in the above news section of Men murdered during Lockdown, but there are no reports of Women killed by husband during the lockdown.

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We agree with Maneka Gandhi's statement "*all the violence is male-generated*" but it's an incomplete sentence, it should be "***All the violence is male-generated, for the women, by the women.***" If you see news listed above, most of the time women is the master mind behind the murder, harassment and abuse of the husband, but her vicious plan was executed by her lover/paramour or male member of her family.

We collected above news from the major news media houses published in English language only, if we cover all crimes done by women and published in India's vernacular languages news media and Police investigations then this crime count will be 10 times more than what we have collected. In this article we published 101 news reports only and we have more than 1000 plus more news articles.

There will be No wonder that once this article is published exposing the feminist agenda, the women wing sponsored and promoted by WCD/NCW may request Government of India to issue executive order to the puppet media, not to cover any such news of Crime by Women, because it's against their vested interests.

WE HEREBY REQUEST THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA AND NEWS MEDIA TO STOP PORTRAYING WOMEN AS ABLA, INNOCENT AND VICTIM OF MEN. CRIME HAS NO GENDER; WOMEN ARE CAPABLE ENOUGH TO COMMIT THE SAME CRIME AS MEN. CRIME IS CRIME AND PUNISHMENT SHOULD BE EQUAL TO ALL.

Above all news links sourced from https://twitter.com/Mynation_BH or tweeted with a hash tag #CrimeByBharatkiLaxmi #CrimeByWomen #CrimeByAblaNari

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Chapter 10:

Study on Men's Health – Effects of Legal Terrorism on Men's Health

TRUTH IS OUT HERE

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Summary:

Study on Men's Health covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. What causes men to die young? How do false cases which Supreme Court of India has called "legal terrorism", daily abuse and harassment by women against her male partner by using "women centric" laws in India effect men's mental health and overall health. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India.

The exact numbers of such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported. It is even tougher to figure out with exactitude how many men are suffering because of "legal terrorism"!

Key Findings:

Majority men feel shy to come forward to report abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body, and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology:

Information for this report is sourced from various secondary sources, medical journals and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics etc.

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Introduction:

Analysis report on Study on Men's Health address following questions: How men are harassed? How legal terrorism is impacting their health? How do they suffer in silence? Why do they suffer in silence? How stressful life they lead, when they face abuse and humiliation at the hands of their beloved ones. Most of the literature collected by MyNation demonstrates that there is a dearth of research on men's mental health or overall health when someone is reported to be depressed due to marital distress or stressful relationship. There is no government body or agency for men in distress to consult with, no funding earmarked to encourage any organization (governmental or non-governmental) to work for men's health issues or address their socio-economic problems or to support men in distress. This study article / report is based on review of literature obtained from legal journals, medical journals and reference from other study reports.

Psychological research has found that relationships have "direct influences" on physiological, immune, neurosensory, and other cardiovascular mechanisms. So, bad relationship leads to depression and stress in people. According to the American Psychological Association, men aren't reporting emotional and physical symptoms of stress because of societal pressure and hence men try to hide their stress and suffer in silence.

A simple online search for "depression due to toxic relationships", leads to hundreds of articles only on women. Most of the readers and writers are women and they are very good in glorifying problems of women alone and showcasing as if men are immune to depression or stress. Very Few research or articles are available on addressing the alarming issue of men's health. The present study aims to highlight this gap in research.

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What Is Stress?

Stress is the human body's reaction to unhealthy, painful damaging situations. When a person feels threatened, a chemical reaction occurs in their body that allows them to act in a way to prevent damaging injury psychologically or physically. As a response or reaction to stress, breathing quickens, muscles tighten, heart rate increases and blood pressure (BP) rises.

Stress doesn't discriminate anyone. While mostly similar stress symptoms are experienced by men and women both, there are a few that are exclusive or more common in men. Stress can affect anyone at any time, regardless of sex. And it all depends on how we manage stress which differs between men and women. Some handle any stress better than others. Not all type of stress is bad. In small doses, stress can help you accomplish tasks and prevent you from getting hurt and stop you from drifting to depression. It is said that when relationship fails, men take it to heart and corner themselves or withdraw from the society.

Evidence suggests that women handle stress better than men, whereas men are most likely to succumb to major depression brought in by family related and financial issues. Men are also more likely to withdraw from society while dealing with stressful relationships. Studies have also shown that stressful relationships are leading cause of psychological impotence and ill health. There are numerous causes of stress in romantic relationships, married or otherwise. When couples are constantly under pressure to fulfil their duties and roles, the relationship could be at risk of failure. The stress men experience from these relationships can affect their physical as well as mental health.

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Men's bodies are designed to handle small doses of stress or short-term shocks. But they are not equipped to handle long-term, prolonged chronic stress without proper attention leading to deadly consequences.

Ongoing chronic, prolonged stress, can cause many serious health problems including:

1. Mental health problems such as depression, anxiety, behavioral problems, being pessimistic, poor judgment, forgetfulness and disorganization, inability to focus, personality disorders, nervousness, shaking, getting easily agitated, frustrated, and moody.
2. Physical health problems like cardiovascular disease, including chronic heart disease, chest pain and rapid heartbeat, high blood pressure, abnormal heart rhythms, heart attacks, Headaches, stroke, insomnia, diarrhea, constipation, nausea, aches, pains, tense muscle, obesity and other eating disorders
3. Sexual dysfunction such as impotence and premature ejaculation in men and loss of sexual desire in men
4. Skin and hair problems such as acne, psoriasis, and eczema, premature greying of hair, and permanent hair loss

Signs and Symptoms of stress in men

Stress in men can manifest as psychological signs like depression, anxiety, anger, sadness and restlessness; behavioral changes like less sleep or over sleeping, drugs or alcohol abuse in order to forget events of stress, overeating or under eating, isolating oneself, social withdrawal, excessive smoking, carelessness or compulsive behaviors and physical signs like muscle tension, chest pain or body pain, lack of interest in sex or achieving or maintaining an erection, rapid heartbeats, fatigue and difficulty in concentrating.

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Evidence suggests that people in toxic relationships or with an abusive wife who filed false cases to harass men, are three times as likely to experience depression as compared to others. Unhappy or broken marriage relationships are a risk factor for depression. Some studies have found that over 60% of those with depression consider relationship problems to be the main cause of their illness.

Main Causes for Depression in Indian men.

Stress leads to depression. Stress from family or relationships is the main cause for depression among men.

Strained relationship or broken marriage: Many articles can be found which supports the theory of depression leading to divorce, without assessing why men are depressed? For a woman, marriage is protective against depression. Many women who were depressed pre-marriage, get someone to blame for their situation. Women are comparatively less depressed than men and it is akin to hitting the jackpot when they are granted a dole of maintenance by the court while going through divorce process. Many men are forced to live together with an abusive spouse for the sake of children, inability to pay unrealistic maintenance or alimony demands made by wife, for the sake of family reputation or some other personal reasons. Wife's nagging and finding fault in every aspect of life reduces his performance at work and his zeal for participation in other socio-economic and cultural activities. In India most live together as a joint family, but lately as soon as they marry the wife forces the man to separate from his family and keep distance from his aged parents. There are even news reports with instances where a son was forced by the wife to kick out his parents. Isolating a man from his parents is the first sign of future abuse by the wife. Men are adjusting with an abusive wife because of his children. Indian

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law system is biased towards men and so she can take away the children and prevent the man from meeting them by just filing a domestic violence case misusing the provision of “protection order” available at her disposal in the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 which fails to recognize ‘men’ as a ‘victim’ of domestic violence. Even if the wife is abusive or tortures her husband and in-laws, the man has no option to file a case or report to the police or court.

False accusations and false cases: In India every word of a woman is Gospel truth, for society or legal system, she is treated as Abla Nari i.e., innocent and a victim. She can accuse anyone, harass or kill and get away with it (Ref: <https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3673754> - *Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment* and <https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3704275> - *CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN*) there are many reports of false accusations of rape, outraging modesty of women, false cases like dowry demand and domestic violence. These cases and accusations not only push men to depression but many also commit suicide because of depression and stress. Even if men who survive the long legal battle are acquitted of any such false accusations, regaining their pride and status in the conservative Indian society is very difficult. This in turn leads them to deep depression and forces them to take drastic step of committing suicide.

How Depression / Stress affects men’s health

Stress / Depression can actually make you sick and disturb peace of mind. A national study reported that 60 to 80 percent of doctor’s visits may have a stress-related component. Stress has also been linked to a higher risk for disease, including cardiovascular disease, neurological imbalance and certain cancers.

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The following are problems and complications of stress and how they affect men's health.

Cardiovascular disease

All types of stress have shown to increase the risk of heart related issues and disease. Researchers have found that stressed people have a higher risk of high blood pressure and heart problems. Stress can directly increase blood flow, heart rate and causes the release of cholesterol and triglycerides into the bloodstream. Stress increases blood pressure and cholesterol, which are the major risk factors in the development of heart disease. Repeated and prolonged events of stress also cause inflammation in the coronary arteries, increasing the risk for a heart attack.

Male infertility

Testosterone levels will reduce because chronic stress on men result in loss of libido or reduced sex drive. Sperm production, and sperm quality increases the risk of infertility. Chronic prolonged stress also impairs testosterone production which can cause impotence.

Prostate cancer

A study found that stress on nervous system promotes tumor growth and spread and ultimately increases the risk of prostate cancer. Sympathetic nervous system (SNS) regulates the body's immune system to fight-or-flight response to depression because of stress. Stress causes SNS to release the chemical noradrenaline, which was found to trigger a cancer-stimulating response. Parasympathetic nervous system (PNS) nerve

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fibers release another chemical that helps cancer cells break away and spread to other parts of the body.

Erectile dysfunction

Depression because of Stress can cause erectile dysfunction (ED) in men, and relationship stress is the leading cause of ED in middle-aged men. Abuse and humiliation lower performance in bed by the partner further leading to stress and strain in the relationship. Stress affects the brain signals to the penis that reduces the blood flow needed for an erection.

Emotional effects of stress combined with stress and anxiety about erectile dysfunction also contributes to an ongoing cycle of ED.

Obesity.

Stress causes higher levels of the hormone cortisol, which store excess fat in the belly which pose greater health risks than fat on the legs or hips and turn person more obese

Diabetes.

Stress can worsen diabetes, also raise the glucose levels of people with type 2 diabetes directly.

Social and Other health issues

Most men with prolonged events of stress withdraw from society, they isolate themselves and fall into depression. Ongoing stress can create severe problems on your gastrointestinal system. Even brief episodes of stress can cause stomach upset and pain, chronic pain, chronic constipation, stomach ulcers, diarrhea and heartburn

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Stress is also a common cause of headache and trigger for migraine. Stress causes muscles to tense, which can lead to ongoing pain in your whole body or neck, back and shoulders. Numbness in touch or bottom of the foot or has been linked to increased pain sensitivity too. Living with chronic pain also increases your stress and anxiety which leads to depression.

Abuse, control and ‘power play’ in the relationship, results in toxic relationships or broken marriage making it a reason for stress which leads to depression. In India most of the time women separate children from fathers and our legal system stands biased against men, with inherent prejudice they term all men as ‘permanent potential abuser and child molester’. A simple online search for the phrase “all men are rapist” will fetch a plenty of “feminist” articles and quotes spreading this prejudiced misinformation. As per statistics of Indian judiciary only 2% fathers get custody of their children and 5% fathers get visitation rights and rest all only have to keep paying maintenance that leads to emotional problems (depression, anxiety, anger, grief, guilt, low self-esteem) resulting from parental-child alienation.

Most of the Indian women are control freak and after recent law reforms women has one sided laws in favor of then that make them empowered to abuse their husband and that leads to less interest in Intimacy and no sex marriage which is another cause for health problems, if your partner is thinking about or marriage is on the brink of divorce, many men take refuge of alcohol or start using drugs. The signs of stress related to personal relationships are similar to normal symptoms of general stress and may include physical health and sleep problems, depression, and anxiety. For men, losing a child is the deadliest stress, they suffer silently and suffer from inside thinking about children. This

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stress comes from inside, rather than outside. You can stress yourself out just by worrying or thinking about problems or things. All of these factors can lead to more stress, depression and ultimately drive men to grave.

Such men unless counseled and treated for such drastic situation, start to lose hair, turn obsess, neglect themselves, loose interest in keeping themselves fit and fall sick now and then in cyclic manner. They perform poorly at work and many times lost job and go bankrupt coz they are forced to pay child maintenance without allowing him to meet his children. In Indian judicial system there is no mechanism nor all law to share child access equally. Indian laws designed only for women in child custody matters, mother take the child custody by default. Even though law book says that father is a natural guardian, but that is only in law books seem to be there only with a purpose to shed out money from his pocket in absence of any provision for default 50-50% custody. Custody Judgments statistics says 95% mother are getting custody, because it is one more way to hand over the dole of maintenance in the hands of woman “in the name of child’s maintenance” while at the same time excluding the man from the company of the child.

When you are passing through a stressful situation, your body launches a physical response, that’s called a stress system. When your nervous system springs into action, the stress system releases hormones that prepare the body and mind to fight the stress, when you're in a stressful situation, you may notice that your breathing gets faster, your muscles tense, your heartbeat speeds up, and you start to sweat. This kind of stress is temporary and short-term (acute stress), and your body usually recovers quickly from it.

But if your stress system stays activated over a prolonged period which is also called chronic stress, it can lead to or aggravate more serious health issues and problems. The

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constant rush of stress hormones can create problems and put a lot of wear and tear on your body, causing it to age more quickly and making it more prone to illness and early death. Stress can affect all aspects of your life, including your emotions, behaviors, thinking ability, and physical health resulting in low self-esteem and poor performance in day to day life. No part of the body is immune.

What is LEGAL TERRORISM how it will affect Men's Health.

What Is Legal Terrorism?

A harassment by the legitimized agency of the state with the help of laws as a tool, channelized through judicial court or police by vexatious litigation, or by the individuals or unscrupulous persons to wreak personal vendetta or unleash harassment by filing of lawsuits to extort money/ assets or force to admit for their demands is “legal terrorism”.

In India, for a woman, the best way to harass her husband to get divorce or maintenance is filing false cases against his aged parents along with him. Even though they never stayed with them or are staying far away, police will add their name by default. It all depends on how the police have been bribed with and how influential the women's family is. Police even include brothers/sisters even breast fed 2/3 months old child of husband sisters have been included in many reports.

In India, it is very easy for a woman to file a complaint with police. Anyone can go to the police station, shed some crocodile tears, cry loudly and police are bound to register her complaint without verifying any of her claim or evidence. Height of all! Some claimed to be raped by a person who was miles away in another city or even if she claims she was

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raped in her dream. Police will register her complaint and start arresting whoever she names.

False case of matrimonial issue which not only is enough to tarnish the image of a familial man, or person, or a family in the eyes of the society but often drive people to other extreme measure as harming themselves, creating depression and even driving many to end their precious God given life.

(Ref: **Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism** - <https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3699991>)

Men are always neglected by international organizations and government bodies. None of the survey data study institutes or media is not ready to publish domestic violence/ abuse experienced by men or their mental health resulting from such abuse.

According to the research, 40 per cent of Indian wives admitted to having had an intimate relationship outside their marriage (Ref: <https://supari.org/40-percent>) she can have sex in front of her husband at his home, but he cannot do anything legally as Section 497 IPC scrapped by Indian judiciary. Value system of the Indian society, founded on 'truth and non-violence' has already been tossed in the name of clash between 'morality' v/s 'liberty' (absolute) and 'justice' (gendered) While constitutional legality is being talked about, the constitutional ethics and constitutional morality has completely been forgotten. Thereby making us think, whether the makers of a lengthy Modern Indian Constitution and the Modern India desired an 'adulterous future' for its citizens, while penning down the 'equality and liberty' along with 'fraternity' among its citizens? Whether polygamy/ polyandry or adultery will lead to retention or disruption of 'peace and fraternity'! It needs to be well thought about by the legislature and judiciary.

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Today, legally any woman can file a case on man and all her allegations are assumed "possible" as they stayed under one roof and closed walls. These baseless allegations can be shattered through proper investigation, but India has investigation officers and protection officers who do not even know the basics of the complaint verification process. There are scenarios, where the bride has come back after a year of eloping with someone, but the groom's family had spent that one year in jail on charges of bride's murder. Corruption also plays a major role in the misuse of these gender biased laws.

The latest health statistics paint a grim picture of India's mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health Profile 2018 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths-a whopping 1, 33,623 in a year.

This translates into 366 suicide deaths every day and 15 an hour.

The following data also show increasing vulnerability of Indian men vis-à-vis women.

Nearly 70 per cent of all suicide deaths in India involve males. Of the 1, 33,623 people who killed themselves, 68.49 per cent (91,528) were men as against 42,088 women.

The number of suicides by men has risen from 66,032 in 2000 and 80,544 in 2008 to 91,528 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

According to the latest data, the highest suicide burden is in Maharashtra (16,970 deaths), followed by Tamil Nadu (15,777) and Bengal (14,602)

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Health data also reveal that suicides are the highest in the productive age group of 30 to 45.

Data from the Survey show that men made up about 45% of Domestic Violence victims each year between 2018-19 and last year for which figures are unavailable. In 2016-17 men made up 43.4% of all those who had suffered partner abuse in the previous year, which rose to 45.5% in 2017-18.

Violence on men can range from anything like - physical violence including slapping, pushing, hitting by wife, her parents and her relatives; emotional violence with wife threatening suicide to intimidate and control the husband; verbal abuse if husband remains in contact with his parents or comes home late from work; throwing objects like utensils, mobile phones and crockery at the husband; sexual abuse if husband denies sex to mental abuse by constant threats of implicating the husband and his family under false case of dowry and domestic violence.

(Ref: **Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health** - <https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3665274>)

Above article talks in detail about abuse of men by his partner/wife but there is not a single survey conducted by the Indian government or any other organization which would capture exact data on male abuse in domestic relationships. There are more and more men who are being pushed to suicide because of strain in marriage and abuse by wife. Suicidal tendencies do not come to men by birth, it's because of stress men face at home and outside which push them to such extremes. When there is no helping hand available then they have no choice for them.

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Psychological Impact on MEN Due to Biased Women Centric Laws

In India MEN Are presumed to be guilty until proven innocent. And based on verbal complaint to police, innocent man and his entire family gets arrested.

Once the false complaint is filed; all relatives, friends, neighbors, acquaintances and other known people immediately cut-off relationship with such accused MEN and their family members who are involved in such false cases. Once trapped in these fake cases, it becomes a social taboo which assumes that “all accused are criminals”. Therefore, in a society no one wants to keep a contact with such people. Hence Indian criminal justice system and society’s prejudice against accused men create immense trauma and mental abuse to them.

Implicating MEN in False cases (Legal Terrorism) is enough for social Ostracization which create tremendous depression among MEN

Office employees/colleagues, managers or even subordinates stops respecting such people as soon as they come to know about false cases/proceeding against these MEN. Their professional growth such as promotion, salary increment is completely stalled or seriously affected since employers start perceiving and treating such employees in an extremely prejudice and biased way. This negative environment and behavior would directly affect to MEN’s health, wellbeing, productivity and efficiency.

In this immense and cut-throat competitive job market, no company would like to keep any person in a job who is involved in such criminal cases (even they are not proven) – Hence the resultant impact of such legal terrorism forces men to commit

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suicide or take other drastic steps including various addiction, abuse their own health through drugs, alcohol, smoking etc.

From police stations to lawyers everyone will squeeze them financially. In order to do so police in connivance with cunning women arrest men, ill-treat and mentally torture them through their vast legal power.

MEN live in constant fear of losing their jobs i.e. livelihood, frightened of being arrested, horrified that any time their family members may be harassed, tortured and incarcerated. MEN are at the mercy of unscrupulous Indian Women who filed false cases which is nothing but MEN becoming slave of Legal Terrorism Mafia (Women, Police, Biased Laws, Judiciary, Women Cell, Media and other Feminists organizations/NGOs). These innocent MEN are tortured by police in Jail so that they would give up the legal extortion demand by false accuser women. Hence This kind of treatment not only affect MEN's health and mental state but it also impacts them physically and mentally.

MEN and their family will have permanent seal of "criminal character" stamped on their life. Even if they are acquitted by court. Their life's previous years get wasted. They have to live their life with this social taboo being treated as criminal. This kind of treatment to MEN is nothing but the psychological, emotional, mental and economical abuse

When there are various schemes / support and funding for women why nothing for men?

Can anyone show us, like PINK RIBBON or whatever color ribbons planned for women and similar for men?

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Can someone show us support and funding for reproductive health of men, men's prostate cancer or any other cancer like cervical cancer or breast cancer, reproductive health, maternal health etc. programs earmarked for women?

There is so much support for #MeToo Why not one for #MenToo?

Why all law support / free legal-aid services only women, why not similar laws for #MenToo?

In India men are neither allowed to talk about their problems nor they can officially report it anywhere. For stressed men there is only one option that's ending his 'dear life'. Indian government and gender biased organizations like Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD) / National Commission for Women (NCW) by encouraging legal terrorism are further contribution to each and every suicide which Indian men are committing.

40% of Indian married women have regular Sexual intercourse with Lovers outside marriage - <https://supari.org/40-percent>

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Chapter 11:

Sacrificing Children to Empower Women

Vicious Feminists Agenda

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This study Article / Report is based on Legal Journals, Indian Penal code, Code of Criminal Procedure of India, Valid Statistics from National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reference from other study reports, Media coverage or testimonials from the victims.

Summary:

The term "SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN" covers a broad range of tactics, false litigations, abuse of children and murders of the children in the hands of their most trusted person and violent acts committed on them with the help of law, by women / Mother by using Women centric laws of India. These laws are biased against men and specially designed only for women and favor only young women.

As per National Crime Bureau (NCRB), reports and statistics almost 95% Child custody cases settled in favor of women and Fathers are forced admit and deny Custody on the threat of False Rape or other LEGAL TERRORISM cases. The exact numbers such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men / fathers are suffering abuse and face LEGAL TERRORISM which stops them from meeting their children or claim custody.

Key Findings:

Majority men / Fathers are not getting Custody of their children. Their request for even a visitation is denied, but they are forced to pay Maintenance. Section 17 of The Guardians and Wards Act, 1890 says "Father is the natural guardian of the minor" but that's only in Law books but not followed practically. Most Fathers are afraid to file for child custody or child visitation because it will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A of Indian Penal Code / Protection of Women from Domestic

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Violence Act, 2005, false rape, out raging modesty of women or any other 50 women centric laws existing in India.

Methodology:

Information for this report is sourced from various secondary sources, various News publications, testimonies, and Survey statistics etc. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to not only highlight the plight of Men, but also about how the law is misused in India to violate rights of Children who are neglected by World Organizations and Government bodies.

Introduction:

The Hague Convention is a multi-national treaty that seeks to protect children wrongfully taken away by one of the parents from the custody of the other parent.

To support Indian Women, promoted by WCD/NCW directs Government of India not to sign any such treaty as most of the time such cases of running away with children pertain to women instead of men. India is not ready to sign Hague Convention even though other countries accuse India of not adhering to any protocol with respect to international parental child abduction. 90 per cent of requests for the return of “abducted children” from other countries remained unresolved for over a year.

Indian women abduct children from lawful custody from a foreign country and come back to India and file some women centric case and manage to get LOOKOUT NOTICE (LOC) to prevent man/father from entering India to contest child custody to get access to foreign born, foreign citizen child.

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But Indian Feminists twist Hague conventions terms in their own version to show it's against women / mother *“The terminology of the Convention is very offensive, labeling the removal of young kids from a country of their birth and citizen by their own parents as “abduction”. This misrepresents things when a parent (usually the mother) leaves the country taking children following breakup, divorce or separation from the opposite parent, mostly husband. The abducting parent in most cases moves to a different / home country to either protect themselves, the child, or both.*

This is the truth where India is being asked under The Hague Convention to return children from their Indian women / mother and family, and send them back to foreign-domiciled parents, or child protection agencies (cf. Article 8 of The Hague Convention, giving “any person, institution or other body” the right to claim abducted child in a member country)”. Terming that only mother is protector and all Men / fathers are abusive and rapists.

Under the UN convention, there is no Scope for Fathers who fight for Child custody and the protection of Children and Young people from the abuse and neglect. It was formed by the child welfare / protection professionals, advocates for children, children's lawyers, researchers, academics, and parents to promote the Rights of the Children. United Nations has UN_WOMEN agency but no UN_MEN or nothing for Men.

In 2007, Ministry of Women and Child Welfare (WCD) supported by United Nations Children's Fund, conducted a study to understand the immensity of child abuse in India, the result they found that 53.22% children faced one or more forms of sexual abuse; among them, **52.94%** of abused children are boys.

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Child sexual abuse is a horrific, traumatic event in the life of a child. According to the WHO (1999), it results in real or potential harm to a child's health, development, trust, dignity in the context of a relationship of responsibility and survival.

In India out of its total population, 40% are children, and India is ranked as the sixth most unsafe country for children. Among them, 47.06% are of girls, and boys are 52.94%, and among them 69% of physically abused, 88.6% were physically abused by parents. 65% of school going children reported facing corporal punishment; 50.2% of children worked all 7 days in a week and they never reported abuse to anyone. Homeless street children, poor young age working children, and children in institutional care or orphanage reported highest incidence of sexual assault.

In authors own words *"I have been consulting/Advising and talking to men and his Family since 2000. I predominantly discuss in the Criminal field of Law. Until, in 2007, when I was asked to talk to a Father who was appearing in the Family Court in Bangalore. He alleged that his 3-year-old son had been brutally assaulted by the child's mother because she was angry with father of the child, when he caught her red handed with her lover. This case made me to look into a new pathway in law.*

From that time onward, my life took on a new direction. I joined the Fathers rights along with Men's rights where I was asked to assist a number of fathers who had their children taken from them by the Family Court after reporting that their children had been sexually abused by their father or partner and handed to the abusive mother. I was asked to assist fathers in all States of India. For the following ten years I did my duty mostly pro-bono. It was during these Court cases that I noticed a distinct pattern of corrupt conduct of the Family Court whereby the fathers were treated with abuse and disrespect. They were

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called Alcoholic / Womanizers / liars / Cheaters / Rapists / jobless, and accused them of coaching their children to lie. The fact that very young children suffering did not move police or Child Protection Authorities into doing proper investigations into the complaint of child sexual abuse. The Family Court Judges, were more concerned with discrediting the fathers and supporting the abuser. The conduct of the court and judges in most of the cases in which I had appeared, were abominable.

*I was shocked to realize that conduct of the Family Court '**Step Mother Policy**' was an orchestrated corrupt system that was designed to discredit fathers and remove their children from them. Question is, what motivates them to act against Fathers in such an inhumane manner. Family court judges make all efforts to avoid custody to father, it's my own experience where judge asked me "**You filed custody case just to harass her right?**" My son was left with her old Parents and she went abroad. When I asked for custody, judge asked "Who is at home to look after the Child?" I replied my mother, the Judge replied back as if he is paid for it or it's his own case, "Your mother is old she can't raise a child at this age". Even her mother was also of the same age, but as per the judge that's ok. This is the bias men face in Family Court.*

*Later in same case when I approached High court of Karnataka, at Bangalore; Judge ordered Visitation on condition that I have to deposit my Passport as well as 10 Lakhs (**ONE MILLION RUPEES**) in mother's name, as I was fighting for visitation for 13 years, and have not seen my son for 13 years.*

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Learned counsel for the appellant undertakes that for the period of appellant's stay in India, he shall surrender his Passport with the jurisdictional Police Station, who shall return the same in time so as to enable the appellant, to return to his place of work.

fen

ORDER COPY PASSPORT DEPOSIT AND 10 LAKHS DEPOSIT SCREEN SHOT

This shows how the family court judges are biased, asked to deposit passport as if I am a notorious absconding terrorist and one Million is impossible for a normal person. But judge wanted to stop me at any cost, so he ordered 10 Lakhs and I deposited it within a day.

A sum of Rs.10 lakhs has been set apart and placed in Fixed Deposit in Vijaya Bank, Karkala Branch, Karnataka.

Learned counsel for the appellant states that the nominee shall be changed to Mrs. [redacted] i.e. the mother of [redacted]. He is directed to do so in order to remove any likelihood of this amount being misused by any other person. The appellant is directed to place this amount in a Cumulative Deposit for an initial period of 8 years. However, if any amount is needed for the education of

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Even that did not melt the judges stony heart, even after knowing how eager the father is to meet his son - [News details here [CLICK HERE - https://mynation.net/abio/news/](https://mynation.net/abio/news/)]

*Most of the time Mother takes the child. If father files visitation/Custody appeal, visitation itself takes not less than four / five years and by then child is totally brainwashed. Once the child is no longer able to remember the father, Child is called to the court and asked, "**YOU WANT TO STAY WITH MOTHER RIGHT?**" The confused child will just nod with whatever the judge says because child has no option to choose with whom they can stay. This is how Visitation / custody in India is decided in the favor of the mother."*

If mother fails to take the child when she leaves her husband's home, she will report to police that her child is abducted. She will not inform that the child was born and staying in father's house. She will report that the child was kidnapped by the father and kept in his house. Police will register her complaint as is and arrest the father and snatch the child and handover to the mother. Recently one of our members was also arrested by PS NIT Faridabad Haryana Police, without any verification. If father reports a similar complaint stating the mother has taken away his child, police will say that she is the mother and entitled to take her child and so no action is taken. Above this, they will mention to file an appeal for custody in the court.

In few cases, even after the father has proved that the child is not his with the help of a DNA test, the court ordered him to pay for child support. Mother can even deny Parentage testing. No family court dares to order DNA test on child so as to shield the mother.

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The fathers that I have counseled are only the tip of a very large iceberg. Over the years we are talking of thousands of fathers who have been described by the Judiciary as child abuser or molesters. Many times, judiciary forcibly removed a father from his child for the crime of reporting sexual abuse of his child by his wife or her partner and in some cases the grandfather. It took me some time to realize that the fathers had lost their children from the moment they filed application reporting sexual abuse. I endeavored to report the conduct of the Family Court to friends and acquaintances, but was met with disbelief and their belief that fathers lie, to stop their wife from seeing their children. I was accused of being obsessed and crazy. The Myth of lying fathers was deeply entrenched in the community.

Not only Indian Family courts but Indian government too is against fathers. So far India has refused to sign The Hague Convention in Child Abduction.

The Hague Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction is a multilateral treaty developed by the Hague Conference on Private International Law (HCCP) that provides an expeditious method to send back a child internationally abducted by a parent from one signatory member country to another.

Suppose if an Indian woman marries a NRI person and settles in some country, and somehow marriage goes wrong and woman returns to India with her child, here Hague convention will enter into picture and in such cases, the mother will be a “child abductor”. An application can be made to the authority in India for the return of the child to the place of “habitual residence”, that is the any other reciprocal country who has signed the convention.

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One of the fathers approached me, who is an Australian citizen, his wife is also Indian origin Australian citizen. He found out that she is meeting another man, when questioned she took her Australian born Son and came back to India. She filed a false IPC 498A, domestic violence hiding her Citizenship status as Australian. She registered a complaint for an attempt to murder in Lucknow 5 years ago. She even named her husband's brother though he had not visited India for the last 5 years. However, Lucknow Police registered a case on all of them without any verification. She also managed to get LOC issued, so as to stop the father from entering India to claim his Australian born son. As India has not signed Hague, he could not approach them. India is shielding such Women abductors. (Case details can be shared on request)

It is reasonable for the community at large to ask if what I am saying is correct, why is there no news about the forcible removal of fathers from their children and the children handed to their sexual abusers (Mothers Lovers)? Why is not published by newspapers / magazines or on TV? The reason is that the Family court has a complete gag order which can punish anyone who breaches this order of silence with 6 months' jail. It is criminal contempt of the Section 12 of Contempt of Court Act, 1971.

The Chief justice of All the Family Courts, maintains that these draconian orders are to protect children. Nothing could be further from the truth. Section 12 of Contempt of Court Act, 1971 is for the protection of Judges, select employed psychologists, and the so-called Independent Child Lawyers in their immoral and illegal conduct in separating children from their fathers. Unfortunately, it has been difficult to raise or expose these issues of this corrupt and biased system because of a gag order in preventing them from doing so. So, their conduct, favoritism towards women cannot be revealed to the general

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public. No radio station will report it, no newspaper / media will write / publish about it, and no TV program will cover it. They are warned off. Failure to comply can result in a jail sentence citing contempt of court. However, independent articles have started to appear about the dysfunction of the Family Court and fake complaints, false allegation by women / mothers and ill treatment of Fathers.

The NCPCR hardly presents any case against the Family Court of India or on behalf of literally thousands of fathers and children around India who have suffered no less than war crimes against humanity. You will read a number of claims against the Family Court which include: Breaches of the United Nations Rights of the Child, Denial of Natural Justice and Human Rights. The misuse of equal parenting provisions in the Family Law Act to punish fathers and allow sexual abuse by women lovers of their children. The appointment of the Independent Child's Lawyer by the Family Court to be used as a tool in supporting or proceedings against fathers, to support the mother of the child or children. Most of them have never seen the children or the father, but support the separation of the child from the primary care-giver. Even Indian Law books says Father is natural guardian, but it's only in law books.

For those who have had the misfortune of appearing in 'The Step Mother Policy' of the Family Court. The Independent Child's Lawyers obvious bias against fathers during the court's proceedings is patently obvious. In some cases, I would consider their conduct immoral. They cross the floor and openly support the mother. The incestuous relationship between the Independent Child's Lawyers and the Judges in removing of, or, restricting the parenting of children by their fathers, is often quite obvious.

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The Court's selective appointments of psychiatrists or psychologist that are hired for the specific purpose of making false or negative reports against the fathers.

The Fraudulent reports by psychologists or psychiatrist claiming the fathers are suffering from serious mental illnesses or Alcoholic, for the purpose of removing the children from their father and handing them to their abuser. The bias of psychologists that use a template of mental disorders for the purpose of recommending to the court the removal of children from their fathers. The exorbitant fees charged by the selected psychologist as much as Rs.2500 or more for 3 one hourly interviews. It is not unusual for a father to have to find or asked to deposit Rs.10, 00,000 to try and protect their children from sexual abusers, only to find at the end of the day that the result was pre-determined from when the father walked into the Court and filed a restraining order complaining of sexual abuse. It is quite amazing that the Psychologists and the Family Court maintain the fathers are delusional, in addition to every known mental illness known to man, and yet these fathers have provided every last cent in legal fees to protect their children from abuse. Neither would a father lie and go to such lengths to maintain that lie.

The NCPCR charges the Family Court, with consistent breaches of the 'Denial of Natural Justice', 'Breach of human rights', and knowingly and 'consistently committing mental torture, to fathers and children. This is a most serious statement. This claim is not uniquely an Indian problem but a world-wide problem, at least in the UK and the USA, Denmark and Ireland, where children are separated from their fathers for doing what they are mandated to do, care and protect their child.

It is the intention of the NCPCR to provide sufficient evidence to support a Legal Inquiry of the corrupt and inhumane practices of the Family Court that have brutally removed

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children from their fathers and sent their children to live with those who have sexually assaulted, abused or raped them. Unfortunately, it's difficult to convince enough politicians or mandated to do, and serve the people. Unfortunately, many fathers are too scared to put pen to paper to report which attract wrath of the Family Court. Most of the time no Politicians will act against any such Personal matter unless they have VOTE BANK from the large community or some Publicity which benefit them.

We ask how in the name of humanity in the 21st century can a civil court remove a child from its primary care (Father is Natural guardian) and hand that child to the abuser. Some have been convicted of major crimes, extra marital affairs and even her lovers are Pedophiles. Yet the Family Court would prefer the child or children to be in the hands of an abuser than a caring father.

“Most of the time Fathers are allowed for visitation on condition only if they pay Maintenance or child support” says another concerned Father Tanmoy Dutta from Calcutta.

Needless to mention, in default of making payment, any amount as indicated hereinabove, the instant revisional application shall stand automatically dismissed and the petitioner-father shall have no visitation rights to the child.

JUDGMENT COPY OF CALCUTTA HIGH COURT ORDER

All over the world most of the time child custody is granted to mother by default, even if she has criminal records or is a Prostitute. There are many incidents where mother abuse

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or even killed children but law was never changed to grant custody to Father. If any Father is contesting and requesting child visitation or custody, his case is delayed or given date after dates. In India if women are not present in court for long custody battles spanning years, judges will not object but if father is not present they will threaten to dismiss the custody petition because of which the father travels thousands of miles every time just for the sake of the child.

Recently in Tanmoy Dutta of Calcutta case he requested virtual visitation but judge consulted the child's mother and she denied virtual visit. This shows how biased the laws are and judges favor women in custody litigations.

Children need the warmth and surroundings of their parents 24 hours a day. Neither can a mother replace the father nor can a father replace the mother. It is a universal truth that both the parents are required for healthy growth of the child / children. However with forcing equality and equating mother with father and father with mother, the various institutions of law go with very frivolous arguments which become quite illogical.

Here I would like to share incident where child is not ready to leave his father but Police by force handover child to mother. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7mOde3-Dhlo>
(CLICK HERE TO WATCH THE VIDEO)

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With the increase in cases of matrimonial disputes in the courts of India, it has become difficult to give proper and healthy upbringing to the children. For a complete multi-dimensional growth to become level-headed mature adults, a unified-family atmosphere is needed by children. Such issues are further amplified by petty matters like treating one of the parents as some kind of distant relative and asking them to pay for and submit applications for "visitation" rights, "maintenance", etc. does in no way address the real issue of 24-hour parenting. The mere thought of making one parent as basic guardian makes the child's heart deficient due to the other parent's absence in his / her life.

Though there are numerous laws for the betterment of children in Indian society, the ground reality is limited to showing concern only.

Children go through harrowing times seeing their parents fighting and separating. The Institutions make the situation more difficult and rather painful by not having

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professional counseling (for all the family members of both sides) and other means to let the child understand that the family is unified for them. What the child actually sees is the long-drawn custody battle in courtrooms. It affects their view of life and hampers their healthy upbringing. The real issues get side tracked for commercial gain of others. At the end of the day, the very purpose of having a family gets defeated and children are the biggest sufferers.

Not only children suffer because of bias, we demonstrate children are handed over to murders and many such innocent lives lost.

Here is the some of the news where mother killed her own children, killed by person whom they trusted most.

1. Odisha woman strangles infant daughter, attempts suicide

The police have registered a case against the woman for allegedly killing her child.

A woman attempted suicide in Odisha's Ganjam district after killing her 19-month-old daughter because her husband rejected her suggestion to stay separately from her in-laws, police said.

Police said the Sabitri Gouda, wife of Kulamani Gouda from Bhiwanipur village in Ganjam district used to have frequent fights with her husband as she insisted on living away from her in-laws.

Sadar police station inspector Santoshini Oram said the couple had been married for two and a half years. But just weeks after her marriage, Sabitri started pestering Kulamani for staying away from the family. Kulamani, who worked as a mason, ignored her demand.

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After the birth of their daughter last year, Sabitri kept on pressuring her husband to take up separate accommodation for them which led to frequent quarrels.

On Friday morning, when Kulamani and other family members had gone to their farmland Sabitri allegedly strangled her daughter.

“When Kulamani and others returned home at noon only they found Sabitri sobbing with her daughter lying close to her. She confessed to her crime. When she attempted to end her life by slitting her wrist, the family members rescued her and informed the police. A case of murder case has been registered against Sabitri,” said the inspector.

Ref: https://m.hindustantimes.com/india-news/odisha-woman-strangles-infant-daughter-attempts-suicide/story-QRFecF9G9xWRRoHkvd4x3O_amp.html

2. Woman held for dropping month-old daughter into water tank. She wanted a son

The woman was produced before the district court from where she was sent to jail under judicial remand.

A 21-year-old woman was arrested in Bhopal on Friday for allegedly killing her one-month-old daughter since she wanted a male child, according to the police.

The woman, Sarita Mewada, a resident of Dehriya Khajoori village of the district was arrested under Section 302 (murder) of IPC after the police found inconsistencies in her statements. She confessed to the crime later, the police said.

Deputy inspector general (DIG) of police, Bhopal, Irshad Wali said, “The father of the baby, Sachin Mewada, lodged a complaint with the Khajoori police station on Thursday

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about his daughter reported missing from inside his house. A police team recovered the body of the baby from inside a 500 litre water tank kept inside a room of the complainant's house with the lid shut from the top.”

“During the investigation police got to know that the child and her mother Sarita were alone in the house when the child was reported missing by the mother,” he added.

Police interrogated Sarita Mewada and she confessed to having committed the crime.

The DIG said, “In her statement given to the police, Sarita said she married Sachin Mewada a year ago. In August, she gave birth to a girl child but she was not happy as she wanted a boy. Sarita said her in-laws were also unhappy over the birth of the girl child. On Thursday, the baby was crying when she got upset and dropped her in the water tank. Then, she closed the lid of the tank.”

The woman was produced before the district court from where she was sent to jail under judicial remand.

Ref: https://m.hindustantimes.com/india-news/woman-held-for-dropping-month-old-daughter-into-water-tank-she-wanted-a-son/story-mztZvLwv3LSOZi2DRuP6nJ_amp.html

3. Superstitious Kalyugi mother arrested for killing 8-year-old daughter

Police have arrested a superstitious mother who strangled her eight-year-old girl in Faridabad. On Sunday, the police told that the mother had murdered the 8-year-old girl and threw her on the highway near Bhagola village in Gadwal area of Palwal.

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The case is of Sanjay Colony under Mujesar police station area. An 8-year-old girl went missing under mysterious circumstances on Thursday. During questioning of the girl's parents and family, the police suspected the girl's mother. When the police checked the CCTV camera installed around the house of the complainant Rajesh, it was found that his mother was seen carrying him. After this, the suspicion of the police was deepened.

The investigation of the case was handed over to Crime Branch DLF. When the crime branch team questioned the girl's mother, she started talking like chandeliers, sorcery and sorcery. On which the suspicion of the police began to change with confidence and the police questioned the woman strictly, then the woman told that she was the one who took her child to village Bhagola in Gadwali area of Palwal and strangled her to death. She left and came home. On inquiry, the mother of the deceased 8-year-old girl told that she believes in flickering. Since 2001, he has a ghost and he has killed his daughter due to superstition.

Ref: <https://m.livehindustan.com/ncr/story-superstitious-mother-killed-8-year-old-daughter-arrested-by-police-in-faridabad-3487107.amp.html>

4. Mom killed daughter in Anandapur: Police

KOLKATA: Six months after the death of a three-day-old girl child at Nonadanga in Anandapur, cops arrested her mother, Sonia Sen, on Sunday on charges of killing her. The autopsy report, which took five months to come due to the COVID pandemic, found light marks on the child's neck, suggesting that she might have been throttled to death.

This is the second incident in a year, in which a mother killed her newborn. The first such incident had been reported from Beliaghata.

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The girl child was found dead on February 5 this year and initially, her mother claimed to have gone to the bathroom, locking the girl and her one-and-a-half-year-old boy in a room. She told cops that her daughter might have died when her son was playing with her. On Sunday, the woman broke down before the police and confessed to have killed her daughter. She was afraid that her husband, who had an illicit affair, would not support the upbringing of the girl child, said the police. “We arrested the woman after a forensic report failed to establish her accidental death theory,” said joint CP (crime) Murlidhar Sharma.

Cops have registered a murder case and they will recreate the crime scene based on the woman’s statement. “We need to depend on crucial forensic evidence as we do not have too much circumstantial evidence. We may seek the help of a psychiatrist to speak to the accused,” said an officer.

Ref: https://m.timesofindia.com/city/kolkata/mom-killed-daughter-police/amp_articleshow/77471762.cms

5. Adampur woman held for murdering 12-year-old son

The Jalandhar rural police on Friday arrested Gurmeet Kaur, an Adampur resident, on the charge of murdering her 12-year-old son, whose body was found in the fields of Padhiana village in Adampur on September 17. A case under Section 302 of the IPC has been registered against the woman.

On the complaint of the victim’s mother the police started investigation of the case. On September 24, Gurmeet’s father-in-law (boy’s grandfather) alleged that his daughter-in-law had murdered the boy and sought detailed investigation.

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The police said during investigation the woman confessed her crime. Gurmeet lived with her three children at Padhiana village, while her in-laws lived next door in another house. Her husband Amarpreet Singh lives in Dubai. The police said the boy had seen his mother with her paramour. The boy threatened to inform his father about his mother's affair. Enraged over this, the woman killed the child. DSP Harinder Singh said, "During interrogation, her replies did not satisfy the police. She took her son to the fields, mixed sulphas tablets in the drink and hit his head with a brick."

Ref: <https://m.tribuneindia.com/news/punjab/adampur-woman-held-for-murdering-12-year-old-son-146843>

6. Shocking: Woman Took Her Own Innocent Son for Fourth Marriage, Arrested

Bihar News: Police officer told that Arun and Dharmashila got married about five years ago. But after a year she was separated from Arun. During this, Arun had demanded to keep his son Saajan with him, despite this, his devout woman separated with his child. Now the woman is accused of his murder.

In Patna, Bihar's capital, a very serious Murder in Patna case has come to light, where a mother is accused of taking the life of her own four-year-old innocent son (Mother kills her son) for her fourth marriage. The accused woman was sent to judicial custody on Saturday. The 23-year-old woman is accused of drowning her partially blind and speech-impaired minor son in deep water. SHO of Shahjahanpur Police (Patna Police) station in Patna district, Amarendra Kumar said that the arrested woman has been identified as Dharmasheela Devi.

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Woman of only four-year-old innocent son killed

The whole matter is of Hasanpur Khandah village of Shahjahanpur police station area located in Fatuha on Friday. Police said the accused Dharmasheela Devi was arrested a few hours after the incident. SHO Amarendra Kumar said that the woman's son Sajan was barely four years old. She was born to the woman's first husband Arun Chaudhary after her marriage. Arun was a resident of Hilsa police station area of Nalanda.

The police officer said that Arun and Dharmashila got married about five years ago. But after a year she was separated from Arun. During this, Arun had demanded to keep Saajan with him, despite it, his religious man got separated with his child.

The child was coming in the way of the fourth marriage, so the creepy step was taken by the SHO, that the accused woman later married her second, but her husband died soon. After this, Dharmasheela married Mahesh Chaudhary, living in Mustafabad of Fatuha police station. However, Mahesh also died in a road accident two months ago. After this Dharmasheela planned a fourth marriage. However, her son Saajan was becoming a major obstacle in the person she wanted to marry. In such a situation, the accused woman killed her son. of a confession by a woman, sent to judicial custody

SHO of Shahjahanpur Police Station, Amarendra Kumar further informed that Dharmasheela was currently living in a village with her parents in Nalanda district. Bahadurchak village, which was just some distance away from his house, brought his son there and killed him on Friday morning. Not only this, after being drowned in water, he left his son's dead body there. Around 8 o'clock in the morning, some villagers saw the body of the child and reported the matter to the police. After this, the police started the

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investigation by taking possession of the body. In which the child's family members were found. During interrogation, the woman confessed her crime. After the FIR against him was produced in court on Saturday, from where he has been sent to judicial custody.

Ref: https://navbharattimes.indiatimes.com/state/bihar/patna/23-year-old-woman-allegedly-kill-her-son-for-her-fourth-marriage-patna-district-bihar-sent-to-judicial-custody/amp_articleshow/78345147.cms

7. UP: woman murdered two innocent daughters when husband stopped going to maiden

A shocking incident has come to light in Jalaun district on Friday. Where a mother murdered two of her own innocent daughters due to discord in the house. Later also tried to commit suicide himself. The police have arrested the woman.

A shocking incident has come to light in Jalaun in UP. Where a mother is accused of strangling her 2 innocent daughters. Also, while trying to commit suicide himself, he injured himself by hitting his head on the wall.

After this incident, sensation spread in the whole area. The police reached the spot as soon as the incident was received and got involved in the investigation of the case. At the same time, the accused mother has been taken into custody and admitted to the district hospital for treatment.

This incident is of Chiravali village under Kotra police station area of ??Jalaun. Mahendra Ahirwar, a resident of the village, has accused his wife Pramila that he strangled her 4-year-old innocent daughter Mahi and 10-month-old daughter Roshni in

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the evening. Later, the woman herself attempted suicide and attempted suicide by hitting her head on the wall.

Woman murdered her two daughters

It is being told that the woman had a quarrel with her husband over her maternal uncle. The husband refused, saying that she had just stayed in the maiden for two months. After this quarrel, husband Mahendra went to the buffalo grazing farm and meanwhile the woman strangled and murdered both her innocent daughters and also attempted suicide herself.

At present, the police have taken the woman into custody and she is being treated at the district hospital.

Wife was stubborn to go

The woman's husband Mahendra Ahirwar says that he had quarreled with me about going to Mayke two days ago. That slogan was going on. I along with my father went to the farm to graze the animals and my mother went to get wood. The wife was alone at home when she strangled the two girls and injured herself by hitting them head on in the wall. On getting information from the neighbors, he reached home and informed the police about the whole incident.

Police is investigating the case

The Additional Superintendent of Police, who reached the spot, said that a woman killed her two daughters. When the police reached the spot, both the girls were found dead at

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home. The woman was also found in an injured state and was sent to the hospital for treatment. The matter is being investigated.

Ref: <https://www.aajtak.in/amp/crime/news/story/woman-murder-two-daughter-jalaun-uttar-pradesh-suicide-police-arrest-tstc-1120936-2020-08-29>

8. Tired of domestic discord, first killed the children, then the woman hanged her life

According to the police, just a few days ago the dispute of both came in the police station. Both were compromised, after which this incident has come to light.

First killed the children committed suicide by hanging himself again

In Uttar Pradesh's village Bijnor village in Handari, a woman first killed her two innocent children due to domestic strife, then also hanged herself and committed suicide. The woman's body was found inside the house with children late at night. The woman was found hanging from the fan, while both the children were found dead on the bed. The incident has caused sensation in the area. police are investigating the matter.

On this incident, police say that there was a dispute between Pappu and his wife, a resident of Handari for some days. When the husband went out of the house. At the same time, the woman took this step. He first strangled two innocent children and later committed suicide by hanging them from the fan. Police has not received any suicide note.

Woman commits suicide with two children

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The police have taken the bodies of the three and sent them for postmortem and started questioning the custody of the deceased's husband Pappu. According to the police, just a few days ago the dispute of both came in the police station. Both were compromised, after which this incident has come to light.

Woman commits suicide

Woman's husband detained

SP Bijnor Sanjeev Tyagi says that a woman has committed suicide by killing two of her children in village Handari. The matter is being told about domestic strife. The police is investigating the entire case. The husband of the deceased has been detained for questioning.

Ref: <https://www.aajtak.in/crime/story/suicide-woman-hang-two-children-husband-police-investigation-tstc-1109966-2020-08-08>

9. Killer Woman: Who strangled her husband's 6-year-old son to death

In the headline, instead of the stepmother of the killer, the killer woman is writing only because we do not have the power to write the word killer with the mother, even if she is a stepmother.

To save stepmother, grandparents used to take Sohit to the farm every day, the child remained in the house on Friday.

A shocking incident came to light in Salempur village of Amarapur on Friday evening, where the step-mother strangled the six-year-old son to death. Step mother Suman Devi

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used to harass Sohit Kumar (6), son of husband Balmukund Tanti's first wife. Fearing the untoward, Sohit's grandparents used to take him to the farm, On Friday, the child remained at home due to bad luck and Suman Devi strangled him to death. As soon as the villagers came to know about the incident, people became angry and caught the woman and locked her in the house. Bhudev Tanti, the grandfather of the deceased child, told that the first wife of Balmukund Tanti died of illness two years ago. Balamukund had two twins from his first wife. In this, a child was raised to live in Maharathochak village of Kajraeli police station area. The second child Sohit lived near his grandparents. Balmukund had second marriage to Suman Devi in Binaud Badhari village of Bhagalpur to raise the child. On receiving the information, Banka SDPO Dineshchandra Srivastava, Amarpur Police Station Arvind Kumar Rai, Under Inspector Rajeev Ranjan, Ramashankar Singh, Assistant Under Inspector Jamshed Khan reached the spot and sent the body for post-mortem. The woman was arrested and brought to the police station. Assistant Under Inspector Jamshed Khan reached the spot and sent the body for postmortem. The woman was arrested and brought to the police station. Assistant Under Inspector Jamshed Khan reached the spot and sent the body for postmortem. The woman was arrested and brought to the police station.

Step mother Suman used to prick her thorn

After marriage, Sohit was piercing like a thorn in the eyes of stepmother. The villagers said that their grandparents used to take the child with them to the fields every day. Perhaps his grandfather and grandmother forgot to take the child to the fields on Friday, and the stepmother killed the child by strangulation. Villagers strongly condemned the incident and demanded strict punishment for the killer stepmother. The police station

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officer said that the accused woman has been arrested. An FIR has been lodged on the father's application.

People beating the woman if the police does not arrive soon

There was so much anger among the villagers that if the police administration did not reach without delay, it would have been possible that people would have injured their mother by beating her. Villagers say that when its step mother reached the village after marriage, she did not want to see the child after a few days. So, the grandparents used to take the child along on the farm. After Sohit's murder, the child was left to live with father, grandparents for life.

Ref: <https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/bihar/bhagalpur/amarapur/news/who-strangled-her-husbands-6-year-old-son-to-death-127774724.html>

10. After killing, the mother threw the body of the child into the drain, arrested

In order to be separated from her husband and mother-in-law, a ruthless mother murdered her 9-month-old baby boy and threw the body into a watermill drain. The police have arrested the mother for the murder of the child. On the evening of September 7, Sudha Kujur husband Ravindra Ram, a resident of Jabala, lodged a report in the city Kotwali that in the morning she was going on foot with her 9-month-old baby in her lap. At the same time, the child had defecated near the Panchakki drain at 10 PM. To clean the toilet, she was lying on the side of the drain and washing her hands. Then the child fell into the drain while stirring. Due to not finding the child, she got nervous and reached her maternal home and told her relatives about the child. On receiving the information, the body of the child, who reached near the water mill with Sudha, was found in the drain. In

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the PM report, the doctor said that the child's death was due to a chatter on the head. After the PM report, the police in the case of murder While registering the case, his mother Sudha Kujur is arrested. Sudha told that she took her child out of her home to go to her maternal home and murdered the child by pressing her mouth with a cloth near the water mill. After killing her, she shed the child's body in a watermill drain. However, the police have arrested the mother on charges of murder.

The mother-in-law was suspected of having an illicit relationship. During interrogation, Sudha revealed that she wanted to separate from her mother-in-law and her husband. Sudha's mother-in-law always doubted her relationship with anyone else. On the other hand, susral also believed that the child did not belong to Sudha's husband Ravindra. Rather it belongs to someone else. Sudha got upset about this. Had tried to kill even a day before,

Sudha told the police that she had tried to kill her child a day before the incident. She was beaten up on September 6 with the intention of killing her child. Because of which the baby started crying. Hearing the cry of the child, when the in-laws asked her to silence the child, she had silenced her child.

Ref: <https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/chhattisgarh/raigarh/jashpur/news/after-killing-the-mother-threw-the-body-of-the-child-into-the-drain-arrested-127761270.html>

11. This is the story of a butcher's mother

Penuganchiprolu, Jaggayyapeta village: Usha and Prasad are a couple from Manukonda village near Khammam in Telangana state. They make a living by doing masonry work.

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They have two children, Sukumar (4) and Ankit (18 months). Usha came in contact with Sampangi Sri alias Shiva of Ramanarsanagar, Konijar Mandal, where he was working. He has been married to her in the past. She left her husband and wife and came to Anumanchipalli village in Jaggayyapeta mandal two months ago and rented a house there. Both children stay with them. On the night of the 4th of this month, Gurai beat up Priyudi severely, outraged that the children were rioting. Beyond those blows Ankit fainted and fell and died shortly after. The children got fever. The two left in the car with the children, believing the locals that they were taking them to the hospital.

The owner asked: The two did not return the next day and the landlord became suspicious of them. In addition to the local VRVO, the police were informed. To this extent the case of Chilakallu Essay Venkateswara Rao has been registered and investigated.

Based on the signal: Police who entered the field spotted the two and arrested them at the Suryapeta district backwaters on Wednesday based on the cellphone tower signal. The two said the original thing while interrogating in his daily style. The boy's body was admitted to the ground at Guttala near Chilukur village in Kodada zone. Police pulled out the body and conducted a postmortem. Sukumar was found to have sustained serious injuries after he was shot in the legs.

Heavy movers: Police searched the house where the two were staying and found 40 cell phones. They suspect that the accused Shiva is committing thefts of cell phones and two-wheelers.

Ref: <https://m.eenadu.net/latestnews/general/1600/120118867>

These are the few crimes committed by Mother, killing her own children.

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Rest of these news can be found in below news links. these news links for last 2 months only, there are hundreds of such news where innocent children are killed in the hands of their most trusted person. **Mother**.

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/bihar/patna/news/woman-murdered-her-five-year-old-son-and-threw-the-dead-body-in-a-pit-filled-with-water-having-done-three-marriages-127754470.html>

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/mp/bhopal/news/nine-month-old-girl-murdered-by-a-woman-with-boyfriend-searching-for-accused-went-missing-from-aubedullaganj-3-days-ago-127735769.html>

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/rajasthan/bharatpur/news/step-mother-killed-8-year-old-daughter-with-poison-husband-lodged-case-127732078.html>

<https://www.bhaskar.com/amp/local/rajasthan/bhilwara/chittorgarh/news/after-a-quarrel-in-the-couple-the-mother-jumped-into-the-well-with-her-4-year-old-son-swam-out-on-his-own-the-son-died-127724793.html>

<https://www.india.com/hindi-news/others/women-sell-her-kid-after-husband-leave-house-4110212/amp/>

<https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/vijayawada/2019/feb/24/paramour-killed-minor-with-mothers-help-1942927.html>

<https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/amp/bengal-woman-kills-2yearold-nephew-body-found-in-cupboard/1911912>

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<https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/amp/couple-kills-7yearold-daughter-in-ups-bareilly/1921259>

<https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/india/article/gujarat-6-year-old-boy-abducted-murdered-after-he-saw-mother-in-compromising-position-with-lover/662643>

<https://www.timesnownews.com/amp/mirror-now/crime/article/woman-mother-in-law-resort-to-black-magic-sacrifice-4-year-old-boy-sentenced-to-death/639237>

<https://www.timesnownews.com/pune/article/pune-woman-murders-child-before-killing-self-as-jobless-husband-insists-on-moving-to-native-village/664273>

<https://www.amarujala.com/amp/uttar-pradesh/meerut/up-news-woman-have-arrested-in-love-affair-case-at-meerut>

<https://www.amarujala.com/amp/uttar-pradesh/aligarh/aligarh-stepmother-feeding-daughters-a-stimulant-drug-made-homosexual-relationship-aligarh-news-ali2430578106>

We have hundreds more such news links, if anyone want to verify, we can forward it.

Also refer **CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN** (<https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3704275>), where it explain, all the murders and crimes by Indian women. Most of the time murders of Husband.

The paternal bond is the most beautiful and strong bond in the world. A father provides love, food, shelter and protection to a child, which is very essential for the good upbringing and overall welfare of the child. In return, a father only wants love and respect from his children. The Constitution of India gives many rights to the child and

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women over the property and other resources of the father or husband and also puts an obligation on a father to maintain his children and wife, but it is silent on the rights of the father over his children. Whenever a father requests for custody of his children in the event of divorce or separation, the entire Indian legal system uses all its power to prevent him from getting child custody or even visitation. It is not surprising that every day we hear news about the murder of a child by his or her own mother. In most of these cases, the innocent child was murdered by a vengeful mother to avenge the father or to hide her extramarital affair. Our Indian judiciary instead of punishing such women, frees them by saying that a mother cannot kill her child. On the other hand, our Indian judiciary imposes illogical and irrational terms and conditions on fathers to abstain their rights to meet or to care for their children. It is very difficult for anyone to find a case where an innocent child is killed by his own father.

So here a question arises that why Indian judiciary is biased against fathers?

For men, the Indian Family Court is like *Auschwitz* in India, where there is no option to survive. It is well known that the top government official or judicial officer has given a standing order to all the judges of the country to pass an order in favor of women, irrespective of the matter. As a result, most of the decisions come in favor of women and a woman gets child custody very easily even if she is by nature abusive and violent or has a criminal record. The judges easily pass an order of maintenance or alimony in favor of a woman without looking at the evidence. Even if a father is paying for the child's support, there is no governmental body to monitor the wellbeing of the child and to monitor that the money spent on a child.

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It seems that handing over the child custody to the mother is the only task, for which family courts are set up. It is a misconception that child welfare is better in the hands of the mother only. This kind of thinking person always ignores the abuse and murder of the child by the mother, and it is no surprise that no one is talking about it.

Please refer two external links in support of our claim

Fathers are better Mothers, but Mothers are not - <https://mynation.net/voice/father/>

Fathers are happier parents than mothers, new study shows - <https://medicalxpress.com/news/2019-02-fathers-happier-parents-mothers.html>

Reference:

Fathers being forced to agree not to contest Child custody or else face kidnap or Daughters molestation charges <https://mynation.net/voice/forced/>

SURVEY: Parent Child Access Rights <https://mynation.net/voice/pas/>

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Chapter 12:

Men's Lives Matters – Suicides by Men

STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH

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Summary:

Study on Men's Health and Suicide by Men covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. What causes men to die young or cut short their lives? How do false cases which the Supreme Court of India has called "legal terrorism", daily abuse and harassment by women against her male partner by using "women-centric" laws in India affect men's mental health. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India.

The exact numbers of such cases of suicide are difficult to assess as the majority of cases go unreported. It is even tougher to figure out with exactitude how many men are suffering because of "*legal terrorism*".

Key Findings:

The majority of men feel shy to come forward to report abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports of suicide by men or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body, and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology:

Information for this report is sourced from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) various secondary sources, medical journals, and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics, etc.

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Introduction:

Study on Men's Health and Suicide by Men address the following questions: Why men commit suicide? How men are harassed? How legal terrorism is impacting their health? How do they suffer in silence? Why do they suffer in silence? How stressful life they lead, when they face abuse and humiliation at the hands of their beloved ones. Most of the literature collected by NGO MyNation demonstrates that there is a dearth of research on men's mental health or overall health when someone is reported to be depressed due to marital distress or a stressful relationship. There is no government body or agency for men in distress to consult with, no funding earmarked to encourage any organization (governmental or non-governmental) to work for men's health issues or address their socio-economic problems or to support men in distress. This study article/report is based on a review of literature obtained from legal journals, medical journals, and references from other study reports.

Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that's one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men, and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their death. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was 70.2: 29.8, which is more as compared to the year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate for men is twice than of women, that's 13.9 per 100,000 for men and 6.3 per 100,000 for women

In India, the marital status of suicide victims is observed at 66.7% (92,757 out of 1,39,123) of the suicide victims were married, which shows there is a problem with their marriage and family. As per NCRB 2019 reports, there are two major causes of suicides

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i.e. 'Family Problems' and 'Illness'. They also reported that Family problems and related issues were behind 32.4 percent of suicides, marriage related problems (5.5%), 70.2 were male and 29.8 females for every 100 suicide deaths. The NCRB collects national-level data from various sources. Almost 68.4 per cent of male victims were married.

Suicide Victims by Sex and Age Group during 2019

- As per data provided by States/UTs.

Why are suicides so high amongst Indian men?

The latest health statistics paints a grim picture of India's mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health 2019 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths to 1,39,123 in a year.

This makes it to 381 suicide deaths every day and 16 an hour.

The data also show the increasing vulnerability of Indian men versus Indian women.

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Of the 1,39,123 people who killed themselves, 97,613 were men as against 41,510 women making it nearly 70.1 % of all the suicide deaths in India by men.

The number of suicides in 2000 by men has risen from 66,032 to 80,544 in 2008 and 97,613 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

The survey conducted by the National Family Health Survey which throws light on unprovoked violence against men by women is evident in the face. Notwithstanding the fact that double the numbers of men commit suicide compared to women, it should not be a surprise to ask for a law to protect men as such a law for women already exist. It would be preposterous in this age of gender equality, not to have such a law. Such a law to protect men from domestic violence would act occurs to millions of those men who feel victimized and left out.

These days MEN are becoming victims of domestic violence, abuse against men in the home is on the rise. Suicide in Indian Men is rising after marriage. Suicide is on the rise because violence against men is rising, the Crime Bureau Report of India can be checked for more details.

In India Women is empowered to kill anyone and most of the time she escapes punishment because of the biased Indian laws which are favorable to Women and encourage them to take the lead in a crime. She will get away even though she is abetting the suicide of a man and even if she is charged, she will hardly be sentenced for 2/3 years. But if a man is convicted, he will get a life in prison which shows how the Indian Judiciary is biased.

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(Ref: **CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN** - <http://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3704275>)

Why more men commit suicide than women?

There are many possible reasons why middle-aged married men are more at risk of depression and depressive disorder than other groups in the population. Relationship breakdown can be more devastating for men than women. Women generally tend to be more 'emotionally literate' and can discuss their feelings with others rather than resorting to internalizing their emotions, but most of the time Men are reluctant to say that they are victims of domestic abuse.

As per a study, more than 10,000 patients a year suffer from depressive disorders, and most of them are men. Depression because of stress is far more common than most people think. Almost 20% of adults can be affected by clinically significant depression. Due to ignorance and misunderstanding many of them do not get the help they need, which is often the signs and symptoms. Depressive disorder may not always present with a low mood. Reduced concentration, losing appetite, disturbed sleeping, irritability, diminished libido, an inability to enjoy life, and extreme lethargy can often be the main symptoms and as these can develop incrementally, but most men are not ready to admit that they are depressed and avoid treatment due to their role in the society. Sometimes they even take refuge of alcohol to overcome grief, problems and when they fail, they have no option other than suicide.

Not every attempt at suicide results in completion, taking one's life requires a strong will or the issues are so grave that there is no escape which leads to repeated attempts even after previous failure. Although unsuccessful first attempts are often followed by successful second attempts.

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The most common risk factors for suicide are:

Using drugs and/or alcohol to help cope with relationships, emotions, the pressure of work, or other issues

Social isolation or living alone when wife threatens to take away children with her

Not being able to form or sustain meaningful relationships

Divorce or relationship breakdowns

A history of physical and sexual abuse

Fear or threat of Imprisonment because of false cases like 498A IPC, PWDVA, Rape etc.

Loss of a loved one or losing child custody

Mental illness, particularly where this is related to depression and painful or debilitating illnesses or conditions

Suicide is most strongly associated with depression in older men, physical pain and illness, living alone, and feelings of hopelessness and guilt.

There is a lack of literature on the systemic study of violence against men and the correlates to such domestic violence in society. A few small-scale studies have shown the rates of violence against men to be similar to that of women with a prevalence of emotional violence of 32.8%. Physical violence rates against men are lesser when compared to rates against women with prevalence to be around 25.2% and sexual violence rates being less than 1%. Apart from the violence arising out of matrimonial

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issues, men have been reported to experience physical or psychological abuse from the natal family members of the spouse. Experiences of violence increases the risk of substance addiction, depression, and suicidal risk in men and impair their quality of life and hence the productivity at work leading to economic loss at the national-level

However, there are no laws in India to protect men from any form of domestic violence. Further men are at risk of false allegations and serious legal consequences by misuse of some of the laws present to protect women such as the Dowry Prohibition Act.

Most of the criminal codes (IPC/CrPC) in India are blatantly biased and in favor of women. The real motive behind the enacted of special acts, rules favoring women is to appease the feminist lobby acting in the country. These acts are not targeted for the welfare of the women, rather intimidate men. Quite often such acts are poorly drafted and deliberately kept wide open to misinterpretation, being biased and favoring women in general, thus are tailor-made to abuse and misuse by disgruntled and vindictive women.

These half-baked drafts are publicly supported and intensely lobbied by the feminist mafia and so become the law of the land in double quick time without delving deep into the possible consequences. Most of such acts and amendments are introduced very quickly without taking proper measures for society to adapt to the same. They lack any clarity and appear to be created with the single motive of multiplying litigation in the country and there being little doubt that most regrettably, such a result would always be welcomed by the legal fraternity, police, and supporting departments.

There are strong social prohibitions inhibiting men from being aggressive against women and harsh legal sanctions facing men who dare to transgress but rarely any social

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prohibitions or legal sanctions inhibiting women from being aggressive against men - that is the reason why it is often said that it's a crime being a Male or to be born as a Male Child in India.

The government of India has enacted various one-sided and biased laws against men and favoring only Women. Unlike above-mentioned Schemes for Women, there is not a single scheme to support Men nor any law to protect Men in India.

Men who get trapped in the justice system have experienced severe social, economic, cultural, and political disadvantages. Accordingly, these determinants of well-being are considered to provide a greater understanding of the factors which have permeated and shaped their lived experiences.

Men's experiences from their initial engagement with the police, then their experiences with lawyers, through to orders passed by Courts, clearly reveal that there exist strong perceptions of unconscious bias, unjust practices and an unholy nexus between feminists mafia, Police and Lawyers which the Government has not made any effort to address so far.

Some of the most compelling scientific evidence prove that women are no less violent than men. For more details please refer **CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN** – (<http://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3704275>) But it has been seen that women's groups have threatened and bullied researchers or media or law enforcement agencies even Judges by any means possible to stop them from presenting evidence of the tendencies of women to engage, as much as men, in the perpetration of domestic violence, and additionally to file false reports of sexual harassment, rape or abuse.

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The government of India is over-enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family, and spiritual values that defines this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is visible in the lack of support and help offered to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicides. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to rising numbers of fake cases, ill-treatment by society, and total neglect by the Government.

(Ref: <http://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3710115>)

As reported by NCRB most of the suicide by Men is the result of marital discord. Here are some news links we have collected. Most of the news is not published by mainstream media which are controlled by feminists or anti-men.

Social Worker Dies By Suicide Alleging Demand Of Rs 20 Lakhs Alimony By Wife In Facebook Suicide Post - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/chandan-singh-verma-suicide/>

Man Ends Life Along With Two Children After Wife Left Home Due To Financial Constraints During Lockdown - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/family-suicide-bhavnagar-gujarat/>

45-Year-Old Man Dies By Suicide Due To Illicit Affair Of Wife With Her Nephew - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-cases-india-4/>

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59-Years-Old PWD Worker Dies By Suicide Alleging Constant Blackmail By Woman - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/59-year-old-pwd-worker-dies-by-suicide-delhi/>

Dalit Boy Dies By Suicide As OBC Wife Filed Rape Charges Against Him, Brother, Brother-in-Law After Returning To Her Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/dalit-boy-dies-by-suicide-as-obc-wife-filed-rape-charges/>

NRI Man From Gujarat Ends Life After Constant Harassment By Wife To Buy Property In USA - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/gujarat-nri-dies-by-suicide-due-to-harassment-by-wife/>

Delhi Man Ends Life Alleging Blackmail and Threats Of False Rape Case By Former Business Partner and Haryanvi Singer - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/delhi-businessman-aman-baisla-suicide/>

Ahmedabad Man Ends Life Due To Wife's Affair | Leaves Pen Drive As Evidence With Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-adultery/>

Head Constable Shoots Himself Due To Alleged Ongoing Problems Within Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-india-3/>

Prayagraj Man Shoots Himself Dead After Dispute With Wife, In-Laws - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/uttar-pradesh-man-shoots-himself-dead/>

Man Held Captive By Wife's Family For Six Days; Returns Home and Ends Life - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/suicide/husband-suicide-7/>

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Uttar Pradesh Man Ends Life After Wife Leaves Home with Children -

<https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-6/>

28-Years-Old Man Dies Of Suicide; Leaves Video Blaming Wife, In-Laws of Harassment - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/moradabad-man-suicide-video/>

37-Years-Old Man From Ghatkopar Ends Life; Was Allegedly Upset Over Fights At Home - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/37-year-old-man-suicide-ghatkopar-mumbai/>

Telugu TV Actor Dies Of Suicide | Partner Booked For Abetment To Suicide On Allegations By Girl's Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/sravani-kondapalli-suicide/>

UPSC Aspirant Ends Life After Girlfriend Of Nine Years Backed Out From Marriage - <https://www.mensdayout.com/his-story/justiceforjeet/>

Man Ends Life After Constant Threats From Wife, Family To Transfer Properties On Woman's Name - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/munish-sethi-ludhiana-suicide/>

Aditya Dash Death Case: "Psycho Lady Behind My Son's Death", Alleges Father - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/crime-has-no-gender/aditya-dash-death-case/>

Man Ends Life After Constant Harassment By Daughter-in-Law, Her Sister, Brother; Leaves Whatsapp Note - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/father-in-law-suicide-ahmedabad/>

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Father-in-Law Ends Life With 6-Page Note Alleging Constant Threats Of False Cases By Daughter-in-Law and Her Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/father-in-law-suicide-patiala-punjab/>

“My Parents and Wife Have Constant Tussle; Their Tussle Made My Life Difficult” – IAS Officer Ends Life - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/ias-mukesh-pandey-suicide/>

B. Tech in Electronics (IIT-Kharagpur) and IPS Kanpur Husband Ends Life Within 15-Months Of Marriage - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/surendra-kumar-das-kanpur-ips-suicide/>

“50% Of CISF Jawan Die Because Of Suicide Due To Family Related Issues”: CISF DG (2018) - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/50-cisf-jawans-suicide-due-to-family-problems/>

UP Police Officer Dies Of Suicide After Alleged Fight With Girlfriend - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/kanpur-police-officer-vikas-soni-suicide/>

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Retired Army Man Dies Of Suicide After Dispute With Wife During Lockdown - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicides-india/>

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28-Year-Old IT Professional Commits Suicide After Alleged Strained Relationship With Live-in Girlfriend - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/pune-it-professional-commits-suicide-after-strained-relationship-with-live-in-girlfriend/>

Man Who Was Working Hard To Support His Poor Family, Commits Suicide Due To False Case By Girl's Father - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/man-commits-suicide-due-to-harassment-by-police-in-false-case/>

33-Yr-Old Hyderabad Doctor Commits Suicide As Wife Allegedly Left Him After Marriage and Did Not Return - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/hyderabad-doctor-commits-suicide-due-to-alleged-dispute-with-wife/>

Hyderabad Hospital Doctor and MD Shoots Himself After Alleged Dispute With Wife - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/hyderabad-hospital-md-shoots-himself-after-alleged-dispute-with-wife/>

Troubled With Domestic Problems, Man Jumps Into Netravati River Along With 6-Year-Old Son - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/man-jumps-into-netravati-river-along-with-6-year-old-son-mangaluru/>

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RPF Jawan Shoots Himself On Moving Train; Was Troubled With Family Problems - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/rpf-jawan-shoots-himself-on-moving-train-tirupati/>

UP Minister's Security Cop Found Dead; Was Undergoing Divorce - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/up-ministers-security-cop-commits-suicide-was-undergoing-divorce/>

Army Man Ends Life Accusing Wife Of Adultery and Mother-in-Law For Spoiling His Life - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/army-man-commits-suicide-due-marital-discord-faridabad/>

Kushal Punjabi's Parents Allege Wife Demanded Huge Sum Of Alimony For Divorce - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/kushal-punjabi-suicide-alimony/>

Kota Professor Commits Suicide In Fateh Sagar Lake Due To Humiliation From Wife, Her Mother - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/kota-professor-commits-suicide-due-to-harassment-by-wife-mother-in-law/>

Fed Up Of Wife's Harassment, Husband Attempts Suicide In Mahila Police Station - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-attempts-suicide-in-mahila-police-station-bihar/>

Software Engineer Commits Suicide Minutes Before Marriage Ceremony - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/hyderabad-man-hangs-himself-before-marriage/>

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Man Commits Suicide After Torture and Constant Threats Of Cases By Girlfriend | No Arrests For Woman Yet - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/man-commits-suicide-in-jhansi-after-threats-of-cases-from-girlfriend/>

Girl Complaints To Police Alleging Boyfriend Took Money On Promise of Marriage | Boy Commits Suicide Fearing Arrest - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/suicide-police-hyderabad-tik-tok/>

MNC Manager Married In January 2019 Commits Suicide; Police Confirms Marital Discord - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-4/>

If women die or commit suicide, by default police will take *suo moto* and arrest husband and his family, but if a man commits suicide, even if he left a suicide note blaming wife and her family, police will not take any action

There is so much support for #MeToo Why not one for #MenToo?

Why do all law support/free legal-aid services only to women, why not similar laws for Men?

In India men are neither allowed to talk about their problems nor can they officially report it. For stressed men there is only one option that's ending his 'dear life'. Indian government and gender biased organizations like Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD) / National Commission for Women (NCW) by encouraging legal terrorism are further contributing to each and every suicide which Indian men are committing.

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United Nations has **UN_WOMEN** body to deal with women related issues but no **UN_MEN**, this shows the bias at top too.

Majority countries around world have special schemes and Funds to empower Women but none for men. No Ministry, no Laws, nor even helpline to counsel men at the critical time. World governments have enough money and funds, In India government allocated 50,000 Cr rupees in its 2019-20 budget for women and none for men. Because for Government and ministers, only **WOMEN LIVES MATTERS**.

WHY SUCH A BIAS?

Why Not **MENS'S LIVES** too.

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Chapter 13:

Gold Diggers – How to Make Easy Money in India

WOMEN SPECIAL.

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Summary

Every girl is looking for well-to-do man who is rich, well-educated and well settled. Has anyone ever seen any matrimonial AD displaying spinster looking for a decent man with good manners and good family values regardless of his financial net worth?

You will always find advertisements along the lines: *“Looking for highly educated man, who has a good job/government job, own house, own car and servants etc.”*. While this may not necessarily be unlawful or even considered discriminatory- it most certainly is HYPOCRITICAL and shows the MINDSET. Many modern women who have been INFECTED BY VIRULENT FEMINISM are ready for Divorce at any time, because with divorce they hit the jackpot – unjustified ALIMONY [*In Legal terms -Alimony can also be called as “unjust enrichment” by abusing gender biased laws when the amount is amicably settled. However, alimony deserves to be classed as “proceeds of crime” - of extortion and blackmail when alimony is obtained after filing false cases*].

Gender biased laws which were initially drafted to support poor uneducated women who had no opportunities in job market are now being OPENLY ABUSED by educated, fundamentally dishonest and unscrupulous women - in collusion with or due to the consent, acquiescence or apathy of custodians of our legal justice system. Marriages of very short duration are also being used as extortion scams and well-educated men and NRIs are usually the targets of such fraudsters. There have been innumerable cases where such unscrupulous women have not only filed false cases and various maintenance cases based on false allegations but also runaway with the gold, cash and various assets of gullible men and his parents at the time of deserting the husband/victim. Although vast majority of such cases go unreported, the authors and their friends are compiling a database of such cases, victims and Gold diggers.

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A Gold digger is a person, typically a woman, who engages by showing fake love in a type of transactional relationship for money. She has no value for relationship or sacrament, her only motive is to make money at any cost. Love, Marriage, Family are all materialistic to her. Her only motive is to make easy money. We collected many reported news articles that shows how married women runaway with all valuables of husband, some even before the first night of the marriage. That shows for women marriage is just a tool to make money.

Key Findings:

Brazenly open misuse of GENDER BIASED LAWS – is a direct consequence of VIRULENT FEMINISM. **Married men have been rendered remediless due to gender biased laws and bad faith interpretations of laws.** The (emasculated) custodians of our system, in their pursuit of vote bank politics or praise/funding from VIRULENT FEMINIST GANGS - have fractured the society, broken the social contract and have laid the foundation for a “war” between the two genders.

Our surveys have found that vast majority of married men who have pending matrimonial cases in courts have been the victims of domestic violence/abuse (Physical, emotional and economical abuse), but there is no statutory law under which they can take shelter or seek reprieve. The only option they have is filing a divorce case which automatically has built in provisions to support the wife who in many cases is the perpetrator of violence/abuse. Any left-over provisions for a man - in general statutory law- have been destroyed by bad faith interpretations in various case laws / Judgements.

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Methodology:

Information for this report is sourced from personal interviews of victims, review of case laws reported in various law journals in India and abroad, various news publications, independent surveys and statistics and records of the government where available etc.

Results of survey

None of the girl's family gives money or financial help to a Man to look after their daughter, nor today's girls are ready to take the responsibility. They always look for a prey, healthy and wealthy boys and are always ready for divorce. These Gold diggers are not ready to take care of their elders. To start, they will separate a man from his family, and once singled out they will loot all his assets. So, the conclusion is many Indian girls marry only to make money, they want to get Rich overnight without any efforts.

Case Studies – Based on Independent News Reports

1. Bride runs away with gold, cash two days after wedding

A woman was arrested in Rajasthan for posing a bride, only to run away with gold, silver and cash after the wedding was solemnized, police said on Tuesday. Four of her accomplices were also held.

Rajasthan Police busted a gang of five persons, who used to allegedly pose as bride, mother-in-law and maternal father-in-law, and two masterminds who trapped innocent families for weddings, and later ran off with gold, silver and cash soon after the marriage. According to Bharatpur Superintendent of Police Anil Kumar Tank, a complaint was lodged by one Biharilal against Riya alias Seema.

In the complaint, he alleged his son Pawan was married to Riya on March 8.

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"Our relatives offered gold and silver jewelry to the bride and cash of Rs 8,000," said the complainant.

However, the bride, on March 10, ran away with the gifted jewels and cash, he alleged.

Police registered a case on the basis of his complaint and started a thorough search for the fake bride and her family members.

A special police team was formed which started search operations for the gang members by collecting and going through their call details. The team also visited Delhi, Fatehabad, Agra and Firozabad in Uttar Pradesh.

On Tuesday, police arrested Riya. She is married to Sanjay Nayak, a resident of Delhi. Her fake mother-in-law, Sanju, the widow of Sanjay Ghiyara, also a resident of Delhi was also arrested.

Police also nabbed the mastermind of the crime, Anil, a resident of Fatehabad, in Agra district and Ramdev, resident of Agra, who played the role of maternal father-in-law in this context.

The gang leader, Gopal, a resident of Firozabad was also arrested, and questioned to find out the details.

A thorough probe revealed some of the gang members were involved in such fake weddings in Dhaulpur in Rajakhedi and Basedi areas in Rajasthan as well.

Investigation was on to collect the stolen jewels and cash.

<https://www.khaleejtimes.com/international/india/bride-runs-away-with-gold-cash-two-days-after-wedding>

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2. Newly-wed Girl in Uttarakhand Runs Away with Jewelry Two Days After Marriage

When the Bollywood film Dolly Ki Doli released, it was classified as a rom-com or a comedy film by the audience. In the film, Sonam Kapoor essays the role of a runaway bride, who cons men and runs away with the jewelry and cash on the first night of the marriage. But what happens when this reel life drama happens in the real life - TRAGEDY! And this is what happened to a man in Uttarakhand. His wife allegedly ran away with the family's gold jewelry barely two days after the marriage and the man is clueless as to why she did this!

Ajay Tyagi, a farmer in Roorkee's Kuvan Hedi village, is the victim of this con and seems like it was a full-proof plan to loot him. Hindustan Times reports that in recent months, a woman from Dehradun put Ajay Tyagi in touch with a prospective bride, whom the family identified as "Kaya". Finding the girl suitable for their son, the family went ahead with the proposal and the marriage took place on November 22, 2017 in Kuvan Hedi, close to Uttar Pradesh. Things seemed fine until Friday, when the bride complained of uneasiness and was taken to the doctor.

This is when the plan seems to be kicking into action. After the doctor prescribed some medicines, the family was returning back home. "Kaya" at this point, said she wanted to have chicken. Non-vegetarian food was however not available in that area, and therefore, Ajay took her to Purqazi, across the state border in Uttar Pradesh. Once they reached the place, Kaya said that she wanted to have a soft drink. "When my brother returned after fetching a bottle from a nearby outlet, she disappeared," Rahul, Ajay's younger brother, told Hindustan Times. Ajay waited at the place for hours and even looked around for his bride, but to no avail. He finally returned home only to see that his bride has disappeared

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with all the gold and silver jewelry that his family had gifted her. "Humari toh dulhan bhi gayi aur zavar bhi (my bride disappeared and so did the jewelry)," said Ajay in the HT article.

Following this incident, the other woman, who had first introduced "Kaya" to the family, has also gone missing, says the family. The Tyagis have reportedly approached the Narsan police in Haridwar district who suspect the women may have been part of a gang that does this regularly. Narsan police chowki in charge Manoj Kumar told HT, "We have received the complaint but since the woman ran away from Purqazi, we have advised the family to report the case there. We are also keeping an eye on the developments and will provide all possible help (to the Purqazi police) in the case."

<https://www.india.com/viral/newly-wed-girl-in-uttarakhand-runs-away-with-jewellery-two-days-after-marriage-2681955/>

3. Bride drugs family, runs away with valuables

In a shocking incident, a newly wed woman fled from her in-law's house with cash and ornaments after giving sedatives in the dinner to the entire family. The incident happened in the Chota Para area in the Badaun district on Friday night.

When the family woke up the following morning, they found the bride missing along with the cash and valuables. Superintendent of Police (City) Jitendra Kumar Srivastava said that according to the complaint lodged by the family Pravin and Ria got married on December 9 and the woman belonged to Azamgarh.

The SP said that the bride fled with Rs 70,000 cash and ornaments worth Rs 3 lakhs. He said the investigation is on and further action will be taken.

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The police are now looking for Tinku, a middleman who had got the marriage arranged. Tinku had accompanied the bride to her new home after marriage and he is also missing with the bride.

Groom's father Ram Ladete said: "We had spent Rs four lakhs in the marriage of Praveen. The marriage was solemnized in Azamgarh and Tinku, the middleman, had taken the money just before the marriage, claiming that the bride's family will prepare jewelry with it for their daughter as they are very poor."

Praveen, meanwhile, said: "I never thought that my wife would cheat me like this. My entire family is embarrassed in the village and we have suffered financially as well. I want her arrested."

<https://www.indiatvnews.com/crime/bride-drugs-family-runs-away-valuables-571416>

4. Woman Cheats Two Grooms After Marriage, Runs Away with Lakhs of Rupees in Gujarat

Rupesh Chavda, 32, of Rajkot faced bleak matrimonial prospects because of his dark complexion, so he paid Rs 1.11 lakhs to an agent to find a bride. But the marriage ended with an unfair twist when the con artist who played his wife vanished a week after the wedding.

Guarang Merani, a 31-year-old Wankaner resident, had great difficulty in finding a bride because of the skewed sex ratio in his community. Merani paid Rs 1.22 lakhs to an agent, got married, and a week later woke up to discover that his wife had deserted him.

The two men had fallen into a trap laid by agents. Chavda registered his marriage in March 2017 with a notary at the Mirzapur court in Ahmedabad. However, even that legal safeguard did not protect him from threats he started receiving two days after the

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disappearance of his wife, identified as Rinku Vaghela. A man from Patan claimed that Rinku was now his wife and told Chavda to forget her.

Chavda approached the Bhaktinagar police station in Rajkot and then submitted an application of complaint with the Shahpur police station in Ahmedabad naming Rinku and the agents - Kalbhai of Jetpur, Punam Soma of Ahmedabad, and Raju Thakkar of Modasa - as the suspects. Assistant sub-inspector of the Shahpur police station, Girish Patel, said that the man who had notarized the marriage of Chavda and Rinku has stated that he had adhered to all norms.

<https://www.indiatimes.com/news/india/woman-cheats-two-grooms-after-marriage-runs-away-with-lakhs-of-rupees-in-gujarat-328140.html>

5. Woman posed as a bride runs away with gold after wedding

A woman was arrested in Rajasthan for posing as a bride, only to run away with gold, silver and cash after the wedding was solemnized, police said on Tuesday. Four of her accomplices were also held.

Rajasthan Police busted a gang of five persons, who used to allegedly pose as bride, mother-in-law and maternal father-in-law, and two masterminds who trapped innocent families for weddings, and later ran off with gold, silver and cash soon after the marriage. According to Bharatpur Superintendent of Police Anil Kumar Tank, a complaint was lodged by one Biharilal against Riya alias Seema.

In the complaint, he alleged his son Pawan was married to Riya on March 8.

"Our relatives offered gold and silver jewelry to the bride and cash of Rs 8,000," said the complainant.

However, the bride, on March 10, ran away with the gifted jewels and cash, he alleged.

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Police registered a case on the basis of his complaint and started a thorough search for the fake bride and her family members.

A special police team was formed which started search operations for the gang members by collecting and going through their call details.

On Tuesday, police arrested Riya. She is married to Sanjay Nayak, a resident of Delhi. Her fake mother-in-law, Sanju, the widow of Sanjay Ghiyara, also a resident of Delhi was also arrested.

Police also nabbed the mastermind of the crime, Anil, a resident of Fatehabad, in Agra district and Ramdev, the resident of Agra, who played the role of maternal father-in-law in this context.

The gang leader, Gopal, a resident of Firozabad was also arrested and questioned to find out the details.

A thorough probe revealed some of the gang members were involved in such fake weddings in Dhaulpur in Rajakhedi and Basedi areas in Rajasthan as well.

The investigation was on to collect the stolen jewels and cash.

<https://www.eastcoastdaily.in/2018/05/09/woman-posed-as-a-bride-runs-away-with-gold-after-wedding.html>

6. UP: Newly married woman drugs family, runs away with money and jewellery

A newly married woman fled from her in-law's house with cash and ornaments after giving sedatives in the dinner to the entire family. The incident happened in the Chota Para area in the Badaun district on Friday night.

After getting up the following morning, the family found the bride missing along with the cash and valuables.

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According to the complaint lodged by the family, Pravin and Ria got married on December 9 and the woman belonged to Azamgarh.

Superintendent of Police (City) Jitendra Kumar Srivastava said that the bride fled with Rs 70,000 cash and ornaments worth Rs three lakhs.

Srivastava further said the investigation is on and further action will be taken soon.

The police are now looking for Tinku, a middleman who had got the marriage arranged. Tinku had accompanied the bride to her new home after marriage and he is also missing with the bride.

Groom's father Ram Ladete said, "We had spent Rs four lakhs in the marriage of Praveen. The marriage was solemnized in Azamgarh and Tinku, the middleman, had taken the money just before the marriage, claiming that the bride's family will prepare jewelry with it for their daughter as they are very poor."

Praveen the groom, meanwhile, said, "I never thought that my wife would cheat me like this. My entire family is embarrassed in the village and we have suffered financially as well. I want her arrested."

<https://www.thestatesman.com/india/newly-married-woman-drugs-family-runs-away-money-jewellery-1502833836.html>

7. Runaway bride: Woman disappears with jewelry two days after wedding

While philosophy may not have an answer yet, in Uttarakhand, at least, one woman imitated the character played by Sonam Kapoor from the Bollywood film Dolly ki Doli to allegedly con her husband and steal the family's gold jewelry within two days of marriage.

The victim of the con was Ajay Tyagi, a farmer in Roorkee's Kuvan Hedi village. In recent months, a woman from Dehradun put him in touch with a prospective bride, whom

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the family identified as Kaya. They found the girl "suitable" and on November 22, Ajay and Kaya were wedded in Kuvan Hedi, which is close to Uttar Pradesh.

The family said things were normal until Friday, when the bride complained of uneasiness and was taken to a doctor.

"The doctor prescribed some medicines and we decided to return home. At that point, she started insisting that she wanted to have chicken," Rahul, Ajay's younger brother who had accompanied the couple to the clinic, told HT on Saturday.

Since non-vegetarian food was not available in the vicinity, Ajay decided to take her to Purqazi, just across the state border in Uttar Pradesh.

"At the shop, she demanded to have soft drink. When my brother returned after fetching a bottle from a nearby outlet, she disappeared," Rahul said.

After waiting for hours and looking for her nearby, Ajay returned home, only to find that the new bride had allegedly made away with gold and silver jewelry that she'd been gifted by his family.

"Humari toh dulhan bhi gayi aur zavar bhi (my bride disappeared and so did the jewelry)," said Ajay. The family believes the woman must have taken the jewelry along when they left for the doctor.

The other woman who put the Tyagis in touch with the bride has also gone missing, the family alleged.

The Tyagis approached the Narsan police in Haridwar district and officials suspect the women may have been part of a gang that does this regularly.

"We have received the complaint but since the woman ran away from Purqazi, we have advised the family to report the case there. We are also keeping an eye on the developments and will provide all possible help (to the Purqazi police) in the case,"

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Narsan police chowki in charge Manoj Kumar told HT. The complainant's family had not looked into the bride's antecedents, the police said.

<https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/runaway-bride-woman-disappears-with-jewellery-two-days-after-wedding/story-B7wcV5HSAitqaDqfdd1V4N.html>

8. Bride drugs family, runs away with valuables

Badaun (Uttar Pradesh), Dec 15: A newly wed woman fled from her in-law's house with cash and ornaments after giving sedatives in the dinner to the entire family.

The incident happened in the Chota Para area in the Badaun district on Friday night.

When the family woke up the following morning, they found the bride missing along with the cash and valuables.

Superintendent of Police (City) Jitendra Kumar Srivastava said that according to the complaint lodged by the family Pravin and Ria got married on December 9 and the woman belonged to Azamgarh.

The SP said that the bride fled with Rs 70,000 cash and ornaments worth Rs three lakhs. He said the investigation is on and further action will be taken.

The police are now looking for Tinku, a middleman who had got the marriage arranged.

Tinku had accompanied the bride to her new home after marriage and he is also missing with the bride.

Groom's father Ram Ladete said: "We had spent Rs four lakhs in the marriage of Praveen. The marriage was solemnized in Azamgarh and Tinku, the middleman, had taken the money just before the marriage, claiming that the bride's family will prepare jewelry with it for their daughter as they are very poor."

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Praveen, meanwhile, said: "I never thought that my wife would cheat me like this. My entire family is embarrassed in the village and we have suffered financially as well. I want her arrested."

<https://www.socialnews.xyz/2019/12/14/bride-drugs-family-runs-away-with-valuables/>

9. Kundapur: Bride runs away from home, marries lover on wedding day

Kundapur, Dec 2: A woman who was supposed get married on Monday, December 2, went missing from her home. The family later found that she had eloped with her lover and got married with him in a temple.

The bride who hails from Maravanthe was betrothed to a boy from Trasi. The arranged marriage was fixed by the bride's parents and a wedding was planned on a grand scale. On Sunday evening, the bride was all decked up and she attended her Mehndi celebrations, which was conducted in grand manner.

However, on Monday morning, the bride's parents and relatives found that the girl was missing along with the wedding jewelry. This created a panic situation.

Meanwhile, the groom had already got ready and started off to the wedding scheduled at Konkan Kharvi Bhavan, Trasi. The matter came to light when they found the girl's family was missing.

Wedding for the missing bride in temple

The bride eloped with her lover in the wee hours of Monday. She later got married with him in a temple. The girl was in love with the boy and she had told her parents about her intention to marry him. However, her parents rejected the alliance and fixed the wedding with a boy of their choice. The girl agreed to their demands.

The girl then completed all the wedding customs for which her family spent a huge sum. However, on the wedding day, she decided to get married to the groom of her choice.

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Localities reported that they had seen two vehicles waiting at Trasi on Monday morning and it is said that the bride fled in one of them.

The wedding parties of the boy and the girl who were in an awkward situation did not know what to do. Meanwhile, it is said that a girl who had come for the wedding, agreed to get married to the groom.

A complaint regarding missing bride stands registered in Gangolli police station.

<https://www.daijiworld.com/news/newsDisplay.aspx?newsID=649482>

10. Bride, secret husband arrested for stealing gold, cash

In a "high voltage drama", a bride-to-be and a man, whom she had secretly married earlier, were arrested on Wednesday after the woman allegedly stole money and jewelry that her parents had saved for her wedding, police said.

Deputy Commissioner of Police A.K. Singla said the 23-year-old woman and Anish, 34, from Seelampur in east Delhi had secretly married in 2015.

But the woman's parents had planned her wedding with another man and made all the arrangements for the November 26 event.

When the woman's parents were away on Tuesday night, she locked her younger sister in a room on the first floor of their house in Seelampur and called Anish and gave him the money and jewelry.

She later complained that two unknown persons barged into the house at night, tied her up and stole the money and jewelry.

Their plan wasn't to run away with the stolen goods, but plotted that the woman would secretly carry it to the fiancé's house on the day of the wedding. She would then raise a hue and cry after discovering the stolen goods at her to-be in-laws' house, which she would make a reason to end the marriage, police said.

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"The accused thought that this will end her new marriage and after that she will get married to Anish," Singla said.

Singla said Anish was married for the past eight years but did not have any children.

Police claimed to have recovered Rs two lakhs and about 300 grams of gold from Anish's house.

Police said that during questioning, the woman told them that she did not talk to anyone on Tuesday over her phone.

But police checked her call records and found that she had spoken to Anish. The lead helped police solve the case in less than 24 hours after the crime.

Singla said it was a "high voltage drama" and the woman held on to her story throughout the night before finally confessing on Wednesday.

https://www.business-standard.com/article/news-ians/bride-secret-husband-arrested-for-stealing-gold-cash-117092001141_1.html

11. Woman posed as a bride runs away with gold after wedding

A woman was arrested in Rajasthan for posing a bride, only to run away with gold, silver and cash after the wedding was solemnized, police said on Tuesday. Four of her accomplices were also held.

Rajasthan Police busted a gang of five persons, who used to allegedly pose as bride, mother-in-law and maternal father-in-law, and two masterminds who trapped innocent families for weddings, and later ran off with gold, silver and cash soon after the marriage. According to Bharatpur Superintendent of Police Anil Kumar Tank, a complaint was lodged by one Biharilal against Riya alias Seema.

In the complaint, he alleged his son Pawan was married to Riya on March 8.

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"Our relatives offered gold and silver jewelry to the bride and cash of Rs 8,000," said the complainant.

However, the bride, on March 10, ran away with the gifted jewels and cash, he alleged.

Police registered a case on the basis of his complaint and started a thorough search for the fake bride and her family members.

A special police team was formed which started search operations for the gang members by collecting and going through their call details.

On Tuesday, police arrested Riya. She is married to Sanjay Nayak, a resident of Delhi. Her fake mother-in-law, Sanju, the widow of Sanjay Ghiyara, also a resident of Delhi was also arrested.

Police also nabbed the mastermind of the crime, Anil, a resident of Fatehabad, in Agra district and Ramdev, the resident of Agra, who played the role of maternal father-in-law in this context.

The gang leader, Gopal, a resident of Firozabad was also arrested and questioned to find out the details.

A thorough probe revealed some of the gang members were involved in such fake weddings in Dhaulpur in Rajakhedi and Basedi areas in Rajasthan as well.

The investigation was on to collect the stolen jewels and cash.

<https://m.dailyhunt.in/news/india/english/east+coast+daily+eng-epaper-eeastco/woman+posed+as+a+bride+runs+away+with+gold+after+wedding-newsid-87475798>

12. Fake marriage gang busted, five held

BATHINDA: The Bathinda police on Wednesday busted a gang involved in committing fraud with people across the three states of Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan as

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girls from this gang were married to innocent persons only to flee with cash and jewelry belonging to these families after the wedding.

The Bathinda police on Wednesday busted a gang involved in committing fraud with people across the three states of Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan as girls from this gang were married to innocent persons only to flee with cash and jewelry belonging to these families after the wedding.

Addressing a press conference, SP (PBI) Gurbinder Singh Sangha said, "They got a tip-off that around 10-12 persons have made a gang who pose as relatives of the girl and get their gang girl married to a person. After the marriage, they demand money from them or the girl runs away from the groom's house by stealing money, gold and silver jewelry."

After getting the information, the police have registered a case against 10 persons - Jagsir Singh, alias Jassi, of Rampura, Resham Singh of Mansa, Amarjot Kaur, alias Amaro, of Paras Ram Nagar in Bathinda, Mohinder Kaur of Rampura, Kulwinder Kaur of Baba Deep Singh Nagar in Bathinda, Shinder Kaur of Paras Ram Nagar in Bathinda, Mandeep Kaur, alias Bittu, of Mati Dass Nagar in Bathinda, Sultan of Hisar district in Haryana, Naresh of Bhiwani in Haryana and others under Sections 494, 495, 380, 420 and 120-B of the IPC at the Civil Lines police station.

The SP claimed that acting on a tip-off, the police arrested five members of the gang - Jagsir Singh, Amarjot Kaur, Mohinder Kaur, Kulwinder Kaur and Shinder Kaur - from Mati Dass Nagar in Bathinda.

The SP said accused Kulwinder Kaur had conducted around five marriages in Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan while Shinder Kaur, Mohinder Kaur and Amarjot Kaur had married 10-15 times. Jagsir Singh and others would pose as their relatives.

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SP Sangha said they would be presented in a court and would seek their police custody so that more details could be extracted from them.

<https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/archive/bathinda/news-detail-828009>

13. This bride who duped 11 men across India was finally arrested from Noida

Not one but this bride conned 11 men. On Saturday, she was arrested from Uttar Pradesh's Noida area.

Her targets were divorced and differently-abled men. She would first marry them and then rob them off their valuables.

She was caught just when she was on the lookout for her 12th victim.

Partners in Crime

The accused Megha would scan matrimonial websites and send marriage proposals to her targets. Her pleasant demeanour won her instant approval from prospective grooms.

The accused, Megha.

Megha's con gang included her sister and brother-in-law who would make all the wedding arrangements. A few days after the wedding, the accused would feed the groom and family milk or tea laced with sedatives, and then flee with cash and jewelry.

She would hand over the loot to her sister and brother-in-law and leave the city in search of her next target.

A Phone Call Led to Arrest

A native of Indore in Madhya Pradesh, Megha had duped men in Rajasthan, Kerala, and Pune and Mumbai in Maharashtra.

Among her targets was Loren Justin of Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, on whose complaint Megha and her two accomplices were arrested.

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On the lookout for her next target, Megha and her two accomplices started staying at Amrapali's Zodiac apartment in Sector-120 of Noida.

Tracing one of her calls to Noida, the Kerala Police, in a joint operation with the Noida Police, finally arrested Megha, her sister Prachi and brother-in-law Devendra.

<https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/bride-dupes-11-men-arrested-noida-358192-2016-12-18>

14. Con-bride, father loot over Rs 4 lakhs and jewellerys from groom in Rajasthan

A real-life incident on the pattern of Bollywood flick Dolly Ki Doli has been reported from Rajasthan's Jhunjhunu. Like this film, a con-bride and her father have looted over Rs 4 lakhs and jewelry from the groom's house.

Like the Sonam Kapoor starrer film, which did not do good on the box office, this con-bride fled her in-laws' house with all the valuables. And, demanded more money if they wanted to take her back home.

THE STORY

The story began in 2013 with a chance meeting between the then prospective groom, Prem Chand of Jhunjhunu, Rajasthan and future con-father-in-law Gulab Chand of Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh. During their casual conversation Premchand told Gulab Chand that he was a bachelor and the main bread winner of his family after his father's death.

Gulab Chand offered to marry his 24-year-old daughter, Usha to Prem Chand. They met again in a few days' time and Prem Chand agreed to marry Usha. Time was ripe for execution of plot.

The Con Plot

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Once Prem Chand agreed to marry Usha, Gulab Chand demanded Rs 4.0 Lakh from him in lieu of marrying off his daughter saying that he did not have enough money for a respectable wedding. In Bollywood flick, Dolly had a Doli (con-gang), here Usha's father was one man-gang.

Usha and her father received Rs 4 lakhs from Prem Chand, who, by now, madly wanted to marry the con-bride. The wedding was solemnized on 17th May, 2013.

The Escape

In reel version, Dolly used to escape from the groom's house on the wedding night itself, but in real life, Usha took close to two weeks. She fled with all the jewelries and money kept in the house. She came back to her father's house with no intention to go back. But, hold on for another twist in the tale.

The Blackmail

Shocked at the sudden disappearance of the new bride, Prem Chand looked for her at various places only to find that she was back with her father. When he demanded of her to come along, she refused. Her father, knowing well that Prem Chand wanted Usha back to save his social prestige, demanded another sum of Rs 1 lakh.

Gulab Chand told Prem Chand that if he did not pay the money, he should forget that he ever married his daughter, Usha. Unable to pay the blackmail amount, Prem Chand, at last, lodged complaint with Jhunjhunu Police. An FIR has been registered against con-bride Usha, her father Gulab Chand and three others for duping and blackmail.

<https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/con-bride-dupes-groom-rajasthan-jhunjhunu-blackmail-police-complaint-335430-2016-08-16>

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15. Bride fed Sleeping pills to her husband's entire family, then what she did is shocking

Jind: A surprising case has come up from Haryana. Where only three months after the marriage, the girl showed her true color. She escaped in the night by feeding sleeping pills of the well-to-do. After just three months of marriage, the bride Reshma took four lakhs rupees, jewelry, mobile phone and got upset at night. But his handiwork was captured in the CCTV camera located near the house.

Police has started investigation on the basis of victim family and CCTV. According to the information, Amit of Jind was married to a girl named Reshma, resident of Jalpaiguri district of West Bengal. Amit has told the police that everything was going well. He had no problem of any kind. But we could not understand its true purpose. We cannot believe the way he has committed the crime.

Amit has told the police that she has stolen the mobile and took it with her. The woman is threatening to kill them by calling from the same mobile. She calls and says that if we do not withdraw the case, she will kill the whole family. Today, our deeds are also bringing us into disrepute in the society. He did not leave anyone worthy to show us his face.

<https://english.newstracklive.com/news/haryana-jind-wife-ran-away-from-home-after-robbing-husbands-house-sc103-nu-1066426-1.html>

16. Wife flees home with cash and jewelry within seven days of marriage

This seems to be right out of a Bollywood script and surely not the first time that it has happened. A newly married husband in Jhansi from the state of Uttar Pradesh was in for a shock when he discovered his wife missing from home just within seven days of marriage.

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According to the man, last week the couple had dinner and went to sleep. However, later when the husband woke up at 3am, he couldn't believe that his newly married bride had vanished along with all the jewelry and cash from the house. The person who mediated the marriage is also suspected and accused of cheating.

As per the husband's version, the man who brokered the marriage was a resident of Pali Village in Odisha. He had informed suitor of an appropriate bride from the state. The former had then asked the groom and his family to gather at a particular location where the marital rites were performed according to the Hindu tradition.

It is often seen that many men and women approach match arrangers/brokers blindly, if they feel that they have crossed a certain biological age for marriage.

Match making has become a grand business today. There are matrimonial websites on internet for all most all communities. Besides these, you also find several matchmaking agencies and individuals who engage with you for finding a particular type of spouse for yourself. Since match making business does not require any specific qualification, certification or license from government many people have made this business as their source of income. It is imperative for all men to do a thorough background check for not just the bride, but also the mediator, to ensure a primary level assessment before getting into a legal bond for life.

In a country like India, even if the husband is on the right side, it is very difficult for him to allege any wrong done by his wife and thus understanding the spouse before marrying her is critical.

<https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/runaway-bride-jhansi/>

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17. UP Newly-Wed Drugs Her In-Laws, Runs Away with Money and Jeweler

Badaun, Uttar Pradesh: A newly wed woman fled from her in-law's house with cash and ornaments after giving sedatives in the dinner to the entire family.

The incident happened in the Chota Para area in the Badaun district on Friday night.

When the family woke up the following morning, they found the bride missing along with the cash and valuables.

Superintendent of Police (City) Jitendra Kumar Srivastava said that according to the complaint lodged by the family Praveen and Ria got married on December 9 and the woman belonged to Azamgarh.

The SP said that the bride fled with Rs 70,000 cash and ornaments worth three lakhs.

He said the investigation is on and further action will be taken.

The police are now looking for Tinku, a middleman who had got the marriage arranged.

Tinku had accompanied the bride to her new home after marriage and he is also missing with the bride.

Groom's father Ram Ladete said: "We had spent four lakhs in the marriage of Praveen. The marriage was solemnized in Azamgarh and Tinku, the middleman, had taken the money just before the marriage, claiming that the bride's family will prepare jewelry with it for their daughter as they are very poor."

Praveen, meanwhile, said: "I never thought that my wife would cheat me like this. My entire family is embarrassed in the village and we have suffered financially as well. I want her arrested."

<https://www.ndtv.com/cities/up-newly-wed-drugs-her-in-laws-runs-away-with-money-and-jewellery-2149074>

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18. Newly married woman runs away with cash and jewelry from husband's house

A newly married woman has allegedly run away with cash and jewelry from her husband's house in Latifpur village, police said.

The husband's family has lodged a FIR at Dankaur Police station on Monday. "Manhunt has been launched to trace the woman cheat and her gang," police said.

According to the police, Manu had married the accused Geeta at a temple in Firozabad a week ago. The middleman had taken Rs 1 lakh from the man.

On Sunday, Geeta's relatives came and took her to her parents' home. On Monday, when Manu went to Firozabad to bring his wife back, he found no one was there and their phone numbers were found switched off, police said.

<https://english.newsnationtv.com/india/news/greater-noida-newly-married-woman-allegedly-runs-away-with-cash-and-jewellery-from-husbands-house-156466.html>

19. Woman marries 8 senior citizens in 10 years, runs away with money, jewels

Ghaziabad Police has registered a case against a woman after she allegedly married eight senior citizens in 10 years and ran away with their money and jewelry. The crime came to light after a 66-year-old man filed a complaint that she ran away with valuables worth 15 lakhs months after their wedding. He met the woman via Delhi-based matrimonial agency.

<https://inshorts.com/en/news/woman-marries-8-senior-citizens-in-10yrs-runs-away-with-money-jewels-1599225421527>

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20. Woman steals cash, jewelry from her house to pay back debt

Unable to pay a debt, a woman living in Navi Mumbai decided to rob her own home. The woman stole Rs 3 lakhs from her home along with gold worth Rs 1.1 lakhs. The woman's husband was unaware that she had taken a debt.

The woman and her husband reside in Kopar Khairane area of Navi Mumbai. The woman's foul play came to light when the police were probing the robbery case filed by her husband.

On June 15, the woman's husband took her to a hospital in Ghansoli as she was not feeling well. At around 8 pm on the same day, the man dropped her to her maternal uncle's house which is close to the hospital as she was asked to come to back to the facility.

At around 2.30 pm on June 17, the man picked up his wife from her maternal uncle's home and took her to the hospital. After dropping his wife, the man went to work. At 7.30 pm, the man picked up his wife from her uncle's house and the two returned home, When they opened the door, the couple noticed that their house had been ransacked, Gold jewellery kept inside the house was missing and a window's tin shade was bent.

Following this, the man informed the police who checked the CCTV footage and spoke to neighbours as well as locals. However, the police did not receive any substantial clues. The police then decided to pursue the statement provided by the victim's wife as it seemed evasive. During further interrogation, the woman confessed to stealing the valuables and cash while her husband was at work. The woman's husband refused to press charges on her.

<https://www.faceofmalawi.com/2020/06/22/woman-steals-cash-jewelry-from-her-house-to-pay-back-debt/>

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21. Newly-wed woman flees with cash, ornaments from in-laws' place in Uttar Pradesh

A newly-wed woman fled from her in-laws' house with cash and ornaments after giving intoxicants in dinner to the entire family in Uttar Pradesh's Badaun district, police said on Saturday. The incident took place in Chota Para area under Dataganj Kotwali police station area on Friday night, Superintendent of Police (City) Jitendra Kumar Srivastava said quoting the complaint lodged by the family in this connection.

Pravin and Ria got married on December 9 and the woman belonged to Azamgarh, the SP said adding that she fled with Rs 70,000 cash and ornaments worth Rs 3 lakhs.

He said the investigation is on and further action will be taken.

<https://www.indiatvnews.com/news/india/newly-wed-woman-flees-with-cash-ornaments-from-in-laws-place-uttar-pradesh-badaun-571288>

22. Woman Drags In-Laws After Five Days of Wedding, Runs Away With Rs 70,000, Jewellery

New Delhi: Barely five days after the wedding, a newlywed woman fled her in-laws' house with Rs 70,000 cash and ornaments after giving sedatives in the dinner to the entire family. The incident happened in the Chota Para area in the Badaun district on Friday night. When the family woke up, they found the bride missing along with the cash and valuables. The ornaments stolen are worth Rs 3 lakhs.

Praveen and Ria got married on December 9. It was an arranged marriage. Police is on the lookout of the middleman, Tinku, who had got the wedding arranged.

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Praveen and Ria got married on December 9. It was an arranged marriage. Police is on the lookout of the middleman, Tinku, who had got the wedding arranged. Superintendent of Police (City) Jitendra Kumar Srivastava said that according to the complaint lodged by the family, Ria belonged to Azamgarh. Tinku had accompanied the bride to her new home after marriage and he is also missing with the bride.

"We had spent Rs four lakhs in the marriage of Praveen. The marriage was solemnised in Azamgarh and Tinku, the middleman, had taken the money just before the marriage, claiming that the bride's family will prepare jewellery with it for their daughter as they are very poor," Praveen's father said.

Praveen, meanwhile, said: "I never thought that my wife would cheat me like this. My entire family is embarrassed in the village and we have suffered financially as well. I want her arrested."

<https://www.india.com/news/india/woman-drugs-in-laws-after-five-days-of-wedding-runs-away-with-rs-70000-jewellery-3878643/>

23. Marries 11 times- runs away with money of 11 different husband

A sultry young Thai woman, over the course of about two years, convinced at least 11 different men to marry her.

Following Thai tradition, each man gave her a generous sum of money - a dowry - at which point she disappeared, the men told police.

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From each husband, she collected between \$6,000 and \$30,000 before vanishing, using various excuses such as she had to return to her family's home to deal with their fruit business or her horoscope advised her that it just wasn't a good time to be married.

So convincing was this woman that she married four times in the month of August alone, police told local media. Initially, police reported that there were 12 complaining husbands, but later reduced the number to 11. Then she ran away from all of them with the money.

<https://greattelangaana.com/english/marries-11-runs-away-money/>

24. Woman dupes NRI of 13 lakhs on promise of marriage

Sultanpur Lodhi Police have booked a woman, Amandeep Kaur, and her family for duping a Non-Resident Indian (NRI) of 13 lakhs on the pretext of marrying him. The NRI Kulwinder Singh, based in France, had sent her the money over three years for visa expenses; the woman had promised to marry him there, but pocketed the money, without even going to meet him. Kulwinder's father, Ajit Singh, is the complainant.

My son had befriended Amandeep's brother, Harpreet Singh, in France. Amandeep and my son took the marriage vows before the families at Sultanpur Lodhi in August 2016. She, however, stayed back and asked him to send money for her to travel to France. "In three years, my son sent over 13 lakhs during this period for her visa. Later, however, we discovered that she was already married and refused to marry my son. Her family refused to repay the borrowed money," Ajit added.

In addition to Amandeep and Harpreet, the others booked are their mother Balwinder Kaur, father Sukhdev Singh and an uncle, Ranjit Singh of Sultanpur Lodhi. They have been booked under Sections 420 (cheating), 406 (criminal breach of trust) and 120B (criminal conspiracy) of the Indian Penal Code.

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<https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/woman-dupes-nri-of-13-lakh-on-promise-of-marriage-5-booked/story-Syc6JkfSVRMFtoWvJvYKkk.html>

All the above news shows how Gold Diggers runaway with just married husbands money and valuable, its mostly women do so the word Gold Digger rightly suits them. Many Feminists claim that men marry for money, Dowry is another word for demanding money from bride at the time of marriage, by showing NCRB cases registered under section 498A IPC, without showing how many are acquitted. Feminists this theory will prove our other claim that these women centric laws are misused to blackmail men and make money with LEGAL TERRORISM.

RTI reply from NCRB of 498A IPC statistics of Madhya Pradesh

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No. STI(200)/RTI/293/2019/NCRB
Government of India
Ministry of Home Affairs
National Crime Records Bureau

National Highway-8, Mahipalpur,
New Delhi - 110 037
Dated : 21.10.2020

To

Dharmat Road, Chandrawatiganj,
Tehsil - Sanwer, District - Indore,
Madhya Pradesh-453551

Sub: Information Sought Under the RTI Act 2005

Sir,

Please refer to your online RTI application regn. No. NCREB/R/E/20/00408 dated 27.09.2020 addressed to National Crime Records Bureau, New Delhi.

- State/UT wise cases registered and conviction rate under U/s 498A in Madhya Pradesh during 2010-2019 is enclosed.

Latest published report "Crime in India" pertains for the year 2019.

An appeal, if any, against this reply may be made within 30 days to Shri Vivek Gogia, IG/Joint Director, National Crime Records Bureau, National Highway-8, Mahipalpur, New Delhi-110037 (Phone - 011-26782547).

Yours faithfully,

(Vikram Tanwar)

CPIO/Joint Assistant Director (Stat.)
Phone No. 011-26735570

Cases Registered and Conviction Rate under Cruelty by Husband or his relatives (Sec. 498A IPC) in Madhya Pradesh during 2010-2019

S. No.	Years	Cases Reported during the year	Conviction Rate
1	2010	3756	38.5
2	2011	3732	39.3
3	2012	3988	33.3
4	2013	4988	35.4
5	2014	6451	36.9
6	2015	5281	21.9
7	2016	6264	21.4
8	2017	6099	31.7
9	2018	4159	33.4
10	2019	5486	17.6

Source: Crime in India

This is how Indian women make easy money; either they run away with valuables or file false cases and force a man to shell out as much money as they want by settling cases out

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of court. This is because they have full Police support, Legal support from Government of India. Also Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD) and National Commission for Women (NCW) are behind these Gold Diggers racket.

Reference:

Madhya Pradesh - 82.4% fake 498A cases in 2019: <https://mynation.net/voice/fake-498a/>

How to make easy Money in INDIA: <https://mynation.net/voice/money/>

Read before you marry an Indian Girl: <https://mynation.net/voice/read/>

New Scheme for Indian women to make easy Money: <https://mynation.net/voice/easy-money/>

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Chapter: 14:

A Study on Indian Men Bias by Birth

Discrimination Against Men

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Summary:

Study on discrimination against Men covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. There is widespread discrimination towards men in every wake of life since birth, especially in India because of government policies. This article is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India.

Key Findings:

The majority of men feel shy to come forward to report discrimination, abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports of discrimination on men or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology:

Information for this report is sourced from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), various secondary sources, medical journals, and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics, etc.

Introduction:

There is no research data available on discrimination against Men nor are any Studies on their mental health recorded in any existing scientific literature. Any discrimination or bias on men affects their lives physically, mentally, emotionally, and psychologically. It

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is also a violation of basic human rights. Most of the discrimination on men is however unreported, unnoticed or simply ignored which may lead to denial in acceptance by their families, to divorce or depression, and even to suicide in extreme cases.

Abused and discriminated men often are victimized or side lined at early stage of their life or during childhood. However, many men also think that, for reasons of masculinity, they have no other option than silently suffer because most of the abuse and discrimination comes from their own kind.

Abused men are also more restrained than women in revealing their victimization partly for fear of being ridiculed and shamed. Many of the men had never even told close family members about the abuse. Men think expressing or fighting back discrimination makes them more vulnerable. Shame and fear of being ridiculed force men to keep their problems hidden, adding to this the societal views of proper masculine behaviour. Lack of support and resources has also ensured that the most shocking form of discrimination on men have remained hidden till date.

The long-lasting negative effects are seen to persist in those who are the bread winner for their family. The psychological harm visited upon men victimized by the society tends to contradict those who subscribe to the view that abused men do not suffer psychologically. Indeed, when the issue of psychological harm was examined, empirically, findings revealed no significant gender differences in psychosomatic illness or stress. Discrimination in everyday life forces men to live depressed and die early.

As far as men are concerned, no studies have addressed the repercussions of experiences of discrimination on men's health. All over the world, this issue is not a specific priority

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for research and overshadows the fact that men may also be badly impacted by such discrimination.

There may be many reasons including socio-economic, societal influences as well as consistent failure of the government to provide help when needed. These however can be dealt with provided that such men get all the required help and support so as to change and improve their way of life.

Society Vs. Men

No man is born a criminal. Society around makes him what he is. Society includes everyone around him. Family dependencies, social and economic deprivation of basic needs are also key factors. It starts from the initial days of upbringing with good education, a supporting family, healthy public environment, societal emphasis on ethics and values of the family system and nurturing good habits for physical and mental health, all playing important roles. But discrimination or bias towards men is not common in today's world. Because of masculinity, society considers only women suffer as they term women as weaker sex.

In the modern e-linked world, media content on TV, internet and print media are also important factors with any access to improper content having a devastating effect on immature children and teenagers. Women have all out support from everyone, but man has none.

This study has been conducted in India and on Indian Men only. As per the study of MyNation, in India despite there being no governmental support (like there is for women) majority of men try to survive by whatever means possible, struggling to make ends meet

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without engaging in any criminal activities. Majority of men travel to distant cities for employment and commute long distances only for better pay, often surviving on only one meal per day to keep their dependents happy. 95% of men and only 5% of women contribute or support families economically and financially to ensure proper meals and nutrition for their families. Society considers that it is the man's duty to pay all bills and women are excused.

Women Vs. Men

Most of the criminal codes (IPC/Cr.P.C) in India are blatantly biased in favour of women. Many of the special acts created for the welfare of women are drafted not actually for women but for appeasement of the feminist lobby. Quite often such acts are poorly drafted and deliberately kept wide open to misinterpretation, being totally biased and favoring women in general and thus are tailor made to abuse and misuse by disgruntled and vindictive women.

These half-baked drafts are publicly supported and intensely lobbied by feminist mafia and so in double quick time they become the law of the land without delving deep into the possible consequences. Most of such acts and amendments are introduced very quickly without taking proper measures for society to adapt to the same. They lack any clarity and appear to be created with the single motive of multiplying litigation in the country. There being little doubt but most regrettably such a result would always be welcomed by the legal fraternity, police and supporting departments.

With a country having 50% women population no government is brave enough to challenge such notions. As a matter of fact those who insist either on denying or repudiating countless, empirically sound studies showing women to be no less violent

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than men, act in a manner very similar to those who once vehemently insisted that the earth was flat and who then went on to brand the purveyors of new knowledge as heretics. But it is not just that the idea of women's complicity in interpersonal or intimate violence challenges the old ideas and what many regard as common sense, it also generates fear among those with vested interests in the perpetuation of government funding and other undeserved benefits based on the age old notion that spousal violence is a wholly male-perpetrated phenomenon.

Also it is perceived by some feminist chauvinists as undercutting of their power derived solely from the presentation of women only as helpless victims, a notion that leads uninformed and well-meaning sponsors to fund women's services (but not people's services), and to enact legislation, such as the *Prevention of Domestic Violence Act Against Women (PWDVA)*, that empowers only one gender i.e.women, but not people overall. Consequently, the notion that women are no less violent than men is very threatening to those wishing to empower only one gender at the expense of the other gender, particularly given the fact that there is virtually no data demonstrating that government-funded feminist approaches or organizations such as the *National Commission of Women* have been effective in resolving issues of domestic violence.

There is a women behind every crime listed above, either she is involved directly abusing/abetting or killing a man or is the reason for the crime. In India, Women are empowered to kill anyone and most of the time she escapes punishment because of the biased Indian laws which are favourable to Women and encourage them to take the lead in a crime. She will get away even though she is abetting the suicide of a man and even if she is charged, she will hardly be sentenced for 2/3

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years. But if a man is convicted, he will get a life in prison which shows how the Indian Judiciary is biased.

(CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN - <https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3704275>)

Abused Male victims tend to find that exiting an abusive situation is especially difficult. Male victims believe that it is their responsibility to provide for their children and in many cases they act as actual shields or buffers between their wives and their children to protect the latter, sometimes even becoming the targets of physical aggression that otherwise would have been directed towards their children. Many of the men also strongly believed that no matter how much their partners abused them, that the judicial system would always rule against them. Thus not only would they fail to gain custody of their children if they left the marital relationship but visitation also would be blocked by their wives as a continuation of controlling and abusive behaviour, with husbands having little or no recourse under the law.

There may be multiple reasons for committing crimes including socio-economic, and societal influence, as well as failure of government to provide minimum help for men in need, however petty crimes can be prevented if men can get the required help and support in time to change their way of life thus stopping them from becoming criminals.

As per the study of MyNation conducted in India and on Indian Men only, there is no government provided support for men. Although the Government of India has come out with many schemes and plans, none have been created to deal with the challenges and problems faced exclusively by Men in India. In contrast there is a multitude of various Government of India schemes for women as listed below.

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1. Mother and Child Tracking System (MCTS)
2. Pradhan Mantri Matritva Vandana Yojana
3. Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls –
 - a. Sabla Rashtriya Mahila Kosh
4. National Action Plan for Children
5. Digital Laado (Digital Laado) –
 - a. Giving Digital Wings to Daughters Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme
6. One Stop Centre Scheme
 - a. Emergency Response and Rescue Services
 - b. Medical assistance
 - c. Assistance in lodging FIR /NCR/DIR
 - d. Psycho - social support/ counselling
 - e. Legal aid and counselling
 - f. Shelter
 - g. Video Conferencing Facility to record statement for police/ courts
7. Women Helpline Scheme (24 Hours)

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8. UJJAWALA: A Comprehensive Scheme for Prevention of trafficking and Rescue, Rehabilitation and Re-integration of Victims of Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation Working Women Hostel
9. Ministry approves new projects under Ujjawala Scheme and continues existing projects SWADHAR Greh (A Scheme for Women in Difficult Circumstances)
10. Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women (STEP)
11. NARI SHAKTI PURASKAR
12. Awardees of Stree Shakti Puruskar, 2014 and Awardees of Nari Shakti Puruskar
13. Awardees of Rajya Mahila Samman and Zila Mahila Samman
14. Mahila police Volunteers
15. Mahila E-Haat
16. Mahila Shakti Kendras (MSK)
17. NIRBHAYA

Different schemes for women in the State of Goa:

Kanyadhan Scheme

This Scheme provide immediate financial assistance of Rs.25000 to the economically weaker section of the society for their daughter's marriage thereby achieving a goal of upliftment of the down trodden.

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Mamta Scheme

This scheme provides financial incentives of Rs.5000 to mother who delivers a female child.

Dhanalaxmi Scheme

Under this scheme the Government provide Rs.25000 in the form of fixed deposit in the name of newly born girl child which can be accessed by the girl on completing 18 year of age. The scheme aims at improving the sex ratio of girl child in Goa.

Yashaswini Scheme

This scheme aims to promote self-help group for self-employment. The state social welfare board will provide financial assistance to each self-help group to the tune of Rs.1 lakh.

Shelter home for women

This scheme has been implemented to provide temporary shelter and support to those women who have no family or social support. It aims to rehabilitate the women socially and economically by provision of skill training.

Grih Adhar Scheme

Goa Government provides Rs.1000 per month to those housewives whose family's gross income is less than 300000 per annum. The scheme is introduced to off-set the impact created due to price rise.

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From Government of Haryana:

Swayamsidha, Swa-Shakti, Balika Samridhi, Hostel for working women, Swadhar, Kishori Shakti Yojana, Ladli.

Kanyashree Prakalpa from Government of West Bengal

This scheme is implemented by the Department of Women Development and Social Welfare, Government of West Bengal in the form of conditional cash transfers.

The Kanyashree scholarship is Rs.750 annually for girls between the age of 13 and 18 years along with a one-time grant of Rs.25,000 for girls between the ages of 18 and 19 years.

Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree Scheme from Government of Maharashtra

The girl child's mother receives Rs.5000 every year for the first 5 years after the birth of the girl child. Subsequently, financial aid of Rs.2500 per year is provided till the girl child is enrolled in 5th class.

After this, the financial aid is increased to Rs.3000 per year till the girl child is enrolled in class 12. Once she attains the age of 18 years, she will receive Rs. 1 lakh annually for her education. Further payouts may be available to the girl child for further studies.

Bhagyashree Scheme of Karnataka government

The girl child receives health insurance cover up to a maximum of Rs.25,000 annually. The girl child receives an annual scholarship of Rs.300 to Rs.1000 up to class 10th.

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Ladli Laxmi Yojana of Madhya Pradesh

Rs. 6000 worth of National Saving Certificates will be purchased every year for the first 5 years in the name of the beneficiary.

Out of this investment, Rs. 2000 will be invested after the girl child is admitted in 6th class and subsequently Rs. 4000 will be invested in the admission of a girl in 9th class.

This is just a quickly compiled list of various support schemes available for women which highlights the gender biased approach of the governments and completely exposes it is hypocrisy in crying foul over the high crime rate by men while doing absolutely nothing to alleviate the same.

Other than above Government sponsored schemes, there are other perks sponsored by State/Organizations and Individuals.

Free Bicycle to Girl child

Education seat reservation quota for girls.

Transport seats Reservation.

Ladies only Bus/Train

Women only queue

Free Bus ride in Delhi

Free Legal Assistance/Aid

Fee PIL

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In fact, men are burdened by the very notions of 'Patriarchy' that feminists are so fond of attacking daily. The unjust burden so imposed on men leads them to take the heavy responsibility of the entire family which may extend to distant relatives and cover even two or sometimes three generations. Driven by notions of being the sole provider and having no support at all from the government nor from society at large, men may feel that they have no option other than to engage in criminal activity. Once apprehended neither the law enforcement nor the judicial authorities make any attempt to understand the critical circumstances that may have driven a man to commit a crime. Here too the contrast in society's hypocrisy while perceiving an accused becomes apparent as any woman committing a crime is immediately excused by claiming 'depression' or 'dispute with husband' or 'abuse' but no such reasoning is ever attempted in case of a man accused of a crime. Noteworthy is the fact that though Patriarchy is the evil that all gynocentric laws claim to be fighting against, no laws have ever been made to assist men burdened with the very same concept of Patriarchy and indeed no mention is ever made of the same by law makers nor by law enforcement nor even by the judiciary. In such a situation man feel absolutely helpless and desperate which may drive at least some men to turn to a life of crime.

There is another aspect also that is relevant here. The idea that women are the weaker sex is so deeply ingrained in the psyche of human beings that even when it comes to sentencing it is men who quite often get sentenced to longer sentences and who in general will face harsher penalties as compared to women quite often for committing the same crime. Longer sentences leading to greater exposure to criminal influences increases the possibility of a man turning into a full-fledged criminal when in fact had he been a woman he would stand a good chance of never going to prison in the first place.

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It looks like Government Ministries wish to Divide and Rule using Gender Politics with everything coming down to Women Vote Banks and Money-Making Businesses. Women's ministry receives more than Rs 50,000+ Crore grants from the Government but there is no proof that even 10% is utilized for Women's Empowerment. As per some prevalent conspiracy theories in fact a big chunk of the money may be ending up as party funds or even in some ministerial account.

The question that needs to be asked and answered is that when 95% tax payers are Men and 95% Men work hard, struggle and die early to fulfill the needs of their families, why is there not even a single Scheme or Plan or any Support whatsoever for Men in India then?

Legal System Vs. Men

Government of India has enacted various one sided and biased laws against men and favoring only Women. Unlike above mentioned Schemes for Women, there is not a single scheme to support Men nor any law to protect Men in India.

Men who had become trapped in the justice system have experienced severe social, economic, cultural and political disadvantages. Accordingly, these determinants of wellbeing are considered in order to provide a greater understanding of the factors which have permeated and shaped their lived experiences.

Men's experiences from their initial engagement with the police, then their experiences with lawyers, through to orders passed by courts, clearly reveal that there exist strong perceptions of unconscious bias, unjust practices and an unholy nexus between feminist's

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mafia, police and lawyers which the Government has not made any effort to address so far.

The use of legal terminology, the range of legal options made available to clients, and lawyers' willingness or lack thereof to defend non-guilty pleas has created barriers in the pursuit of justice for these men. When an individual is arrested for an alleged crime and subsequently tarred with a criminal record, there are long-term effects which may persist lifelong despite the individual getting bail or being acquitted from criminal charges. This is commonly referred to as the 'collateral consequences of conviction' which have a variety of impacts. Whilst this has broader socio-economic consequences, the stigma of having a criminal record provokes wide-ranging and subtle forms of discrimination and embarrassment. Once someone has been tagged as a criminal, it is almost impossible to get rid of the label; the public is easily persuaded that once a man is jailed, he must be a hardened criminal and must therefore be segregated and excluded from the rest.

The inability of men to access quality legal services can generate, and/or perpetuate, social exclusion for individuals, especially when they are unaware of their legal rights. This is driven by a dominant discourse within the criminal justice system underpinned by the notion of Article 14 of the Constitution of India which says '*All are equal in front of law*'.

A woman who killed her husband has been freed of murder charges by the Supreme Court on the grounds that the husband had called her a prostitute and that this amounted to "sudden and grave provocation" which led to his killing in a fit of rage (NAWAZ Vs. THE STATE REP. BY INSPECTOR OF POLICE) Question is if man do same thing will honourable Supreme Court pardon?

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One-night stand in an excusable situation not adultery: Gujarat HC (Sharmilaben vs. Pravinsinh Balvantsinh Solanki)

Such decisions leave one with no option other than to conclude that there exist unfortunate patterns of unconscious/conscious bias against Men in the Indian Justice System.

Some of the most compelling scientific evidence proves that women are no less violent than men. But it has been seen that women's groups have threatened and bullied researchers or media or law enforcement agencies even Judges by any means possible to stop them from presenting evidence of the tendencies of women to engage as much as men, in the perpetration of domestic violence, and additionally to file false reports of sexual harassment, rape or abuse.

As an example, there is the case of a judge who in his judgement had declared the IPC Section 498A as a tool of legal terrorism. Women's groups protested this judgement and broke several pieces of furniture and damaged public property in the court room.

Crime prevention is critical to maintain law and order in the country. National Crime Records Bureau mentions deterring criminals through deployment of more police force is one of the major strategies practiced. It also mentions reasons such as unemployment, poverty, a lower per capita income affects the crime rates in India.

The Government however has never tried to curtail crime by providing basic needs like education, training, spreading awareness of Law and ensuring guaranteed employment.

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Opportunities for men to earn decently are almost nil in the country. In the name of gender upliftment, government has been completely biased in the appeasement of women and mostly one particular sector of women.

It should not come as a surprise to check the below statistics for the arrests and the gender ratio. There are many poorly drafted Acts and amendments to IPC that define the perpetrator as only a Man. And a significant percentage of fake cases too contribute to these high figures of arrests of Men.

Unlike the Schemes created for the welfare of only women, there is not even a single Law or Act to protect vulnerable men from crime. Below listed Laws made only for women, and none for men and almost all of them are misused by women to make money or to control men.

1. Maternity Benefit Act, 1861
2. Special Marriage Act, 1954
3. The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956
4. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961
5. Indian Divorce Act, 1969
6. Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971
7. Equal Remuneration Act, 1976
8. The Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986

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9. The Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987
10. National Commission for Women Act, 1990
11. Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005
12. The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006
13. Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013
14. Nirbhaya Act.
15. Disha Act.
16. Shakti Act.

With above listed laws, only women can complain against Men and in most of the complaints there is no need to provide any proof for the allegation, only sob story is enough to send a man and his family behind bars. In all the cases, the Burden of proof lies on Men to prove himself innocent.

Most of the crimes could be prevented with better policies, employment opportunities and widespread awareness of law. This would help counter the petty crimes to a major extent but Government of India is turning a blind eye to the acute need to protect and support men in distress. When it comes to police custody again men are at a disadvantage as no policeman/woman in his or her right senses would dare lift a finger against any woman considering the multitude of woman centric laws, acts and regulations that protect women. Unfortunately, the same cannot be said to extend to men who can be treated like

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animals without any fear of repercussion thanks to the total lack of any legislation aimed specifically at protecting men. The most recent example occurred recently when a father-son duo was tortured, brutalized and murdered in a police station and it was only after a public outcry that action was taken against the culprits. Is it surprising then that given such wide ranging systemic discrimination against men and abuse of men, that a lot of men feel that they have no option left than to end their own life.

Government of India is over enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family and spiritual values that defines this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is clearly visible in the lack of support and help offered to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicides. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to rising numbers of fake cases, ill treatment by society and total neglect by the Government.

As per the statistics, India has around 3.3 crores people who pay tax and out of them 95% are men who work hard, struggle and even risk early deaths to satisfy the needs of their families but there is not even a single Scheme exclusively for men. 95% men work hard and pay taxes for the nation to run, but it is a shame to say that there are:

- No Laws to safeguard Men in the country
- No recovery or rehabilitation centers only for men
- No recent acts to look after the physical, economic and family welfare of men

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- No data capture or analysis to research the actual crime rates against Men
- No small-scale economic opportunities
- No one-stop centers to guide or train Boys and Men for proper employment
- No research on the needs and support required for Boys and Men.

A National Men's commission is the most critical need of Indian Men today.

BIAS BY BIRTH

Male-perpetrated violence against women is taken much more seriously than female-perpetrated violence against men due to real or perceived physical strength differences between women and men.

The feminist argues and claim the notion that domestic violence is primarily a culturally supported male enterprise and that female violence is always defensive and reactive. When women are instigators, in this view, it is a “pre-emptive strike”, aimed at defending against an inevitable male attack. In contrast, violence against males is not similarly contextualized and is always attributed to a broader social agenda. As a result of this perspective, feminists tend to generalize about violent men and about all men while completely ignoring the female pathology.

There are strong social prohibitions inhibiting men from being aggressive against women and harsh legal sanctions facing men who dare to transgress but rarely any social prohibitions or legal sanctions inhibiting women from being aggressive against men - that

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is the reason why it is often said that it's a crime being a Male or to be born as a Male Child in India.

Discrimination in Job Selection:

Men are more likely to face gender discrimination when applying for jobs than women, consistent with various studies done with around 1000 job applicants.

Research by the sociologist, examined how job applicants treated differently by employers supported their gender with an equivalent qualifications and experience.

In white-collar job employers in several occupational classes unevenly discriminate against men during early hiring practices. Hiring practices among employers across two gendered occupational dimensions:

- (1) Sex composition (male- or female-dominated jobs) and
- (2) Gender stereotyping (masculinized or feminized jobs)

Broadly, findings suggest a polarization of early sorting mechanisms during which discrimination against female applicants is concentrated in male-dominated and masculinized working-class jobs, whereas discrimination against male applicants at early job-access points is more widespread, occurring in women dominated and feminized jobs in both white-collar and working-class contexts. Interestingly, discrimination further compounds for male and feminine applicants-depending on the classed context-when these occupational dimensions align within the same gendered direction (e.g., male-dominated jobs that even have masculinized job advertisements). These findings have

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implications for the study of gender and work inequality and indicate the importance of a multidimensional approach to hiring-related inequality.

It is generally assumed that sex/gender discrimination are some things that only happens to women, but the research found that men face more discrimination when applying for jobs that are commonly related to the other sex.

Overall research found that men were more likely to be overlooked by employers supported their gender for both white-collar and working-class jobs. Women were also subject to discrimination when applying for working-class jobs because of their physical strength, but not white-collar jobs. This shows actual real statistics of discrimination against men

Gender discrimination was examined by first identifying whether employment advert involved stereotypically masculine traits, stereotypically feminine traits or was gender neutral. Their research measured whether this translated into a preference for male or female candidates, regardless of whether the work was during a male dominated or female dominated field.

Traits defined as stereotypically masculine included: physical strength; technical aptitude; leadership; independence; analytical thinking; assertiveness and ambition.

Traits defined as stereotypically feminine included: friendly; organized; team orientated and good communication skills.

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Sex/gender discrimination was measured by counting what percentage male and feminine candidates received a positive callback from the employer, which in most cases meant being invited to an interview.

Even there are reports of misuse of Sexual harassment at work place by women, still many corporates managed by men appoint women over men for white-collar jobs.

The study concluded that women applying for working-class jobs faced less discrimination in male-dominated roles, because of various types of schemes and reservation quota for women. But men within the study faced discrimination in female-dominated roles in both working-class and middle-class contexts, particularly when employers specified a preference for candidates with feminine traits and jobs specially reserved for women. Here is a latest AD from India's largest Group companies The TATA's

TATA Industries - Hosur, Tamil Nadu needs Assembly Line and CNC Operators - 3000 Members.

Only for girls with stipend ranging from Rs.15,000/- to 20,000/-

Qualification: +2 /ITI / Diploma - Any Stream.

Age: Girls between 18 - 22 Years

One-month free training at NTTF - Vellore.

Then to Tata Factory after Training.

Free Jobs, Training, Food and Accommodation during training.

Contact 0416 - 2244017 or send an email to banuprasads@nttf.co.in for more details.

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should apply before 30th October 2020.

TITAN-TIDCO Venture under the Tata Electronics

Conclusion:

Feminist research, feminist advocacy, and public debate so far have paid very little attention to the problems of gender bias and gender constructions in laws in general when it comes to Men which proves that such organizations are least interested in true gender equality.

Criminal laws must emphasize that violence and harm against other people is morally wrong and that domestic violence is not a shameful private matter but a societal as well as individual injustice.

One-sided governmental policies that fund women-only resources, based on the assumption that women rarely, or never, engage as perpetrators of domestic violence, lie at the heart of the problem. Primary prevention efforts to curb domestic violence rather than focusing on male violence alone, even assaults by women on their male partners should be paid as much attention as possible.

Priority needs to be assigned to the victims of domestic violence, regardless of gender, particularly given the fact that men can also be victimized brutally, suffer serious financial hardship and are no less required to visit physicians or take time off from work or seek urgent counselling following any victimization.

That victimization experiences of men are downplayed as compared to those of women is discriminatory and should never be allowed. Domestic violence must be viewed not

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through the prism of gender but instead be considered as an issue that may be encountered by any human being regardless of gender.

Suffering due to atrocities and without legal recourse an abused man may as a last resort commit serious crimes or even commit suicide. This may be seen in some cases:

Article 14 of the Constitution of India reads as under: **Equality before law** - *“The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India”* (Ref: <https://mynation.net/laws/coi/coi.htm>)

Article 15 of the Constitution of India reads as under: *“Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth.”*

But same Article 15 of the Constitution of India contradict with clause 3 of Article 15, which reads as *“Nothing in this article shall prevent the State from making any special provision for women and children.”*

This shows systematic bias against Men, overriding 'Equality before Law' and 'Discrimination on grounds of Gender' Articles. If so why to add clause in Article 14 - **Equality before law** and **discrimination on grounds of Sex** in Article 15? Same can be drafted in simple way saying **MEN ARE NOT EQUAL TO WOMEN AND THEY ARE DISCRIMINATED BECAUSE OF THEIR GENDER/SEX.**

Not only men are discriminated because of their gender but most of Women centric laws reflect only one aspect about men i.e., *“Guilty until proven innocent”*

All of the above-mentioned causes as well as Society, Spouse and System push men to take drastic steps finally leading to them to end of their own dear lives. Feminist mafia,

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prejudiced Indian society, one-sided media, bias from birth, and gynocentric, short-sighted Government Policies that completely neglect men are the main reasons which are responsible to cut short men's life.

Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that's one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their death. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was 70.2: 29.8, which is more as compared to the year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate for men is twice than of women, that's 13.9 per 100,000 for men and 6.3 per 100,000 for women. (Ref: **MEN'S LIVES MATTERS – SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH** - <https://mynation.net/vocie/ssrn-3717515>)

All the above statistics show why men are committing suicide. Most of the suicides are because of family problems, threats from wives to file fake cases, financial commitment towards the family, one sided laws, Reservation and Schemes meant only for females, zero support from government, zero protection from current laws against false accusations and fake cases.

Men are abused, vilified, exploited and are expected to suffer in silence while women on the other hand are treasured, protected and pampered. Every country in the world, and the governments are pushing agendas for women's empowerment making special provisions for women's reservations / schemes / funding and enacting gender biased laws in favor of women. More MEN are suffering at the hands of an abusive female – wife / girlfriend / live-in partner which leads to depression and suicide. Yet strangely enough, hardly any studies have ever been conducted to research the psychological trauma that men have to

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face. Truly men today are under attack from all sides and the day is not far when to be born as a male will be considered the biggest curse and liability.

Every aspect of above details depicts biasness and discrimination towards male child even before birth. Today's generation opt for female child over male child for gender selection. As, there are many schemes and reservation only for girl child (e.g.: BETI BACHAO / SAVE THE GIRL CHILD) and not a single Reservation and quota system in Education, jobs, travel etc. for male child. All this displays **SYSTEMATIC DISCRIMINATION** towards Men, it's really **BIAS BY BIRTH**. Being **MAN** is more of a **SIN** rather than a **SHAME** in today's World, especially in India.

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Chapter 15:

Toxic Feminism

From what feminists are afraid of?

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Men are not against women, not because they have mother, sisters and daughters but because there are few women who really suffer in the hands of other women. Even though they have father and brothers, most women do not think twice on calling men as pig /dog and rapists all under the influence of toxic feminism.

Traits of Toxic Feminism

1. It feeds off our fear and it travels fast.

Humans are hardwired to remember negative information over positive, it's how we learn. Feminists the Peddlers of disinformation know this and play on deep emotions, which make us far more likely to share it on social media – and so it spreads up to six times faster than factual news!

2. It thrives on social media and reaches billions.

The more time we spend on social media, the more money those companies make. They know that extreme and shocking content hooks our attention, so they program their sites to promote it. And it reaches billions. The biggest newspapers sell a few million copies, while news on Facebook reaches over a BILLION per day.

3. It is being weaponized against us.

Feminists in Western world along with some Henpecked Politicians are weaponizing feminism as the newest move in the playbook for age-old divide and rule politics with gender. Same was done in India with Religion too. But it's USA that leads the pack -- their huge 'troll farms' employ legions of people to set up millions of fake accounts to

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spread feminism. And its propaganda outlet is one of YouTube's most-viewed news channels with an estimated 2 billion views!

4. It is killing people and poisoning democracy.

Feminism is driving vigilante violence in India, in some countries in Asia and Arab world. It is also poisoning our politics. Fake feminism is destroying trust in mainstream media, our democratic institutions, and political leaders which is creating the perfect breeding ground for anti-establishment strongmen to rise to power and make money. Because of feminism, social media is now a threat to democracy.

5. No one is immune.

People across the political spectrum are being micro-targeted as part of a strategy to polarize and erode our societies. In the US and EU troll army created a fake page for fake feminism activists that drew more followers than the equal rights to women movement pages!. We think we'd never fall for this stuff, but studies show that even the most educated among us tend to believe fake news, and people over 65 are even more likely to spread it.

How to Stop Toxic Feminism?

As we celebrate the 20th anniversary of UN Security Council resolution 1325, we must also recognize that trends in the digital sphere have also undermined the very goals the men, Peace and Security (MPS) agenda has sought to realize. This absence of security online hinders men's participation in the public sphere, governance and leadership roles, especially in the context of conflict prevention and in promoting social cohesion. Should this deficiency in men's engagement online in the region continue, the status quo is sure

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to be preserved, maintaining influence in the hands of the very powerful few, Like WCD/NCW(India) UN Women and stalling the transformative change that the MPS framework envisages. Thus, men's digital engagement and use of technologies are at a critical juncture with regards to the achievement of the MPS agenda. The following recommendations are targeted towards governments, development organizations and researchers in South and South-East Asia:

1. Create a Ministry in each country or build the capacity of men in South and South-East Asia to identify, report and block hateful content. Also work on social media literacy and countering disinformation as the region witnesses increased volumes of misandry and hate speech targeting men online. It is crucial that men users of social media are aware of how to protect themselves. Likewise, misandrist tweets and Facebook posts especially in South Asia are often based on news stories that are fake or taken out of context. This suggests that increased levels of social media literacy among both men and women would limit the efficacy of such posts in spreading their hateful agendas.
2. Pass legislation that criminalizes cyber harassment and cyber stalking. Although States often have existing laws that prohibit stalking or harassment, these laws are sometimes inadequate to criminalize harms that happen online. Thus, specific laws to address cyber harassment and stalking can close this gap.
3. Monitor and remove misandrist content on social media platforms Social media companies have increasingly sought to regulate what content is publishable on their platforms, banning everything from election misinformation to photos depicting violence. However, no ban against misandry, particularly violent misandry has yet been introduced, which affects the safety and free speech of men users.

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4. Produce and disseminate gender empowerment-themed content targeted at women. The overwhelming majority of COVID-19 related misandrist content is posted by Women, male and shemale users, across platforms and countries supported by IT cells of legal terrorist supporters and vested interest feminist's organisations. One way to tackle the root of these gender biases and prejudices is by developing localized and engaging counter-narrative content. This could entail enlisting the participation and support of local entertainers and influencers who have large followings and using content styles and formats that women are likely to engage with.
5. Research the scope and impact of online misandry on closed social networks such as WhatsApp, private Facebook groups, and Telegram. Investigating the prevalence of online misandry on closed platforms and private groups would allow a comprehensive understanding of the full extent of online misandry in South and South- East Asia. Closed social networks can provide greater anonymity, allowing greater incitement to violence and hatred with impunity.
6. Research potential links between nationalism and misandry among social media users in Asia. The suggested intersectionality between nationalism and misandry among social media users outlined in this brief merit further investigation and validation. In an age of growing nationalism across the region, examining potential linkages between nationalism and misandry among online users would provide relevant insights into the root causes and consequences of online misandry.
7. There is a systematic effort by the misandrist to silence the truth as they have access to huge amount of funds from the government. When Men expose such legal terrorists and misandrist, they along with the help of ministry direct the website owners to

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remove the content which is against their vested interest, money making business. In case exposed, their source of income / funds from the government will be cut down or even stopped. Government should restrain such misandrist organizations from hiding truth from the public.

How to Control Toxic Feminists?

1. If you see something, say something!

Don't believe everything you read on the internet. Seen a random Facebook post with shocking info about a political candidate? Don't trust it!. Check the facts with reliable sources, and if you think you may have found a piece of news about Women brutally raped/murdered or harassed, let us know here. Most men are not doing anything about it even though they see other men are harassed or abused until they are in the same situation. Even if you tell others that men are harassed, they will laugh at you.

2. Keep supporting real journalism.

Most traditional media are covered by regulations and ethics that make it far more trustworthy than a random dude on the internet. They're not perfect, but they check their facts and can be held responsible! Subscribing to a high-quality newspaper with real journalism is one of the most powerful acts a citizen can take today.

3. Join the campaign to clean up social media.

MyNation has a simple and effective plan to push the tech giants to cure the fake news of Toxic Feminism epidemic on social media – by showing independently-verified factual corrections to fake news. Join MyNation.

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4. Don't give up on democracy!

The goal of the troll armies is to create such a climate of distrust that ordinary citizens walk away from democracy. When that happens, fanatic extremists can dominate it. We must keep showing up and voting, encouraging our friends and family to do the same, and holding our elected officials to account.

5. Choose hope in humanity.

Fake Feminism preys on our deepest fears, appealing to our natural negativity bias and bringing out our more anger and cynical sides. But if we can learn to engage with the arguments of people who don't think like us, with empathy, big ears and wisdom, we can connect across our differences. We have more in common than our fears make us believe. If we trust that, amazing things can happen.

Our civilization is the most successful in human history on so many fronts, from human rights to democracy. We're on track to end poverty within a generation, and we're close to putting every child in school. It's clear that democracy and great journalists, political leaders with accountability, and fellow citizens got us here. But the forces pushing toxic feminism are powerful and threaten to destroy all of that. Let's not let them win by just giving up hope!

From What Feminists are Afraid of?

Feminists do not want that their crimes and mistakes are exposed, they do not want their stories published in main stream media. Most of the media is under their control.

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As we published our articles, these Feminists forced SSRN to remove it. This shows how much these feminists are afraid of about the truth as most of the articles are based on NCRB statistic and statistics from Government websites and media.

The following is the list of all of our articles that was published on SSRN website:

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			Public View	Last Updated				Downloads		
	3738237 WPS	SILENCING THE TRUTH - SSRN WAY	Yes No	11/20/2020 11/30/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	104 23	View		
	3726695 APS	BIAS BY BIRTH - DISCRIMINATION AGAINST MEN	Yes No	11/07/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	172 95	View		
	3732850 APS	GOLD DIGGERS: HOW TO MAKE EASY MONEY IN INDIA - WOMEN SPECIAL	Yes No	11/01/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	357 142	View		
	3722012 WPS	COVID19 - A CHINESE FLU: STATISTICS AND CONSPIRACY THEORIES - THE YEAR WORLD STOOD STILL	Yes No	10/31/2020 11/02/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	87 7	View		
	3717010 WPS	MEN'S LIVES MATTERS - SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH	Yes No	10/23/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	204 59	View		
	3712902 APS	SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN	Yes No	10/10/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	359 105	View		
	3710115 APS	STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH	Yes No	10/12/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	678 339	View		
	3704275 APS	CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN	Yes No	10/03/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	274 66	View		
	3699991 APS	Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism	Yes No	09/20/2020 11/30/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	671 229	View		
	3697040 WPS	WMD's of India - Weapons of Men's Destruction	Yes No	09/22/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	397 131	View		
	3695017 APS	Legal Terrorism in Matrimonial Disputes - Solution for Legal Terrorism	Yes No	09/19/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	539 172	View		
	3695140 WPS	The National Commission for Women, Exposed	Yes No	09/10/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	154 28	View		
	3673754 APS	Violence Against Men - False Accusation of Sexual Harassment	Yes No	08/14/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	635 242	View		
	3665538 APS	Section 498-B IPC. - A Much Needed Reform	Yes No	08/02/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	116 60	View		
	3665274 WPS	Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health	Yes No	08/01/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	1,517 458	View		

Not only the articles, but access of writers associated to MyNation Foundation was removed without any intimation or justification.

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<input type="checkbox"/> WMD's of INDIA-WEAPONS OF MEN'S DESTRUCTION R D'Souza Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health, LEGAL ...		2020

Feminists feel that by forcing to remove the articles, they can hide the truth. Feminist's term exposing them is as misogyny, because they are afraid of the Truth. We have a message for such misandrists ***“You can hide the truth but you cannot erase it”***

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Feminists Demands

The laws that deal with 'Crime Against Women' are widely acknowledged as being overtly biased laws in support of the daughter-in-law alone. It is seen that such laws are made or considered for further amendments with strong recommendations and propaganda by the 'National Commission for Women' (NCW) and few prominent NGOs and feminists, but reviews and opinions of other sections, institutions and organizations are totally ignored and never considered by the government.

The meaning of '**Gender Sensitivity**' as per women organizations and feminists in India is as follows:

1. Adultery by a WIFE is not a crime.
2. Filing of false cases (dowry/rape/domestic violence) by WIFE, cannot be punishable.
3. The complaining woman's mother-in-law, sister -in-law or niece from the husband's side are not women.
4. Perjury, theft, fabrication, blackmail, extortion and kidnapping by women are not an offence.
5. Exposure of body-parts by women to entice/beguile men cannot be called exhibitionism.
6. Women can sleep their way up the corporate ladder, and they are allowed to lie, steal and fabricate without any penalty.
7. Crimes of passion (including murder) by women can be blamed on the hormones (beyond their control) and therefore cannot be punished.
8. If it is the case of a woman against woman, the woman who sheds tears is always right.

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9. The bigamous woman should be rewarded (latest scheme by the women's activists), and not punished.
10. Any attempts by the man to expose the truth about an abusive/deceitful woman, is an attack on her privacy/ modesty and misogyny.

In a diversified and democratic country like India, it's totally unjustified and insane to draft any law or any amendment only on recommendations of persons who are not representatives of all social classes and segments and whose interests could be affected by these legislations. Without such general inputs and considerations of the needs of all segments of society, such laws can only prove to be biased and would result in greater injustice and chaos in society at large as they disturb the very basic unit of any society, The Family.

It is hard to understand the disproportionate role played by the NCW in the making of such laws, which is not a representative of all sections. But it is ostensibly a government organization working for A MINORITY SECTION OF WOMEN and not for all the women.

Toxic Feminism is nothing to do with Equality;

It's not about empowered women.

They have ONE GOAL: **To dominate, control and destroy a man's finance, mental health, self-esteem and any hope for happiness.**

It teaches Women not to Listen to men be it her Own Father or Brother. Overpower Men, Dominate, control them and ruin their life and leave no room for any happiness.

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Chapter 16:

LEGALISING MISANDRY TO EMPOWER WOMEN?

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In today's world there is a tendency in our society to brand every man as a villain and every woman as a victim. Because of the rise in feminism and of the supporters of feminism, there has also been an increase in the numbers of white knights who has share in name, fame and money in feminist's victory. When the whole of society is against men, then it is very easy to brand men as sadists, child-molesters, pedophiles, genital mutilators, gang rapists etc.

In addition to what society is thinking and supporting, even the legal systems of most countries are aligned with Feminists.

Other side of the Indian judiciary

In India, Article 20 is one of the pillars of fundamental rights guaranteed by the Constitution. It mainly deals with the protection of certain rights in cases of conviction for offences. When individuals or corporations are accused of crimes, then the provisions of Article 20 safeguard their rights.

Our constitution is based on the fundamental principle of "***Let Hundreds of Guilty Persons Go Unpunished, But Never Punish an Innocent Person***" Right to obtain fair representation in criminal procedures is a facet of the Right to Equality (Article 14)

Article 20 mandates that "***no person shall be convicted of any offence except for violation of a law in force at the time of the commission of the act charged as an offence, nor be subjected to a penalty greater than that which might have been inflicted under the law in force at the time of the commission of the offence***". Thus, the Accused is given fair and equal treatment on par with other citizens. Also, by judicial pronouncements, a wider ambit has been imparted to the Right to life and liberty and thus the Accused are required to be treated humanely in jails fulfilling the reformatory approach (Article 21). Article 22 mandates that no person shall be detained in custody without being informed, as soon as may be, of the grounds for such arrest; nor shall he be denied the right to consult and to be defended by a legal practitioner of his choice. The exception to the right is that it is not to be applied in case of an alien. Thereby, these rights under the Constitution are inherent rights and cannot be altered or changed.

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In today's world, and specially in India; even when a case is still under investigation, the charge sheet not being filed and trial yet to begin with the Court yet to hear the Accused and the Prosecution and it remaining to be proved that the Accused is guilty, the Accused men are instantly branded as criminals by society, the legal system and the government preventing them from leading normal lives. As soon as women file any false case on men, the men are treated as antisocial elements and worse than terrorists. Their passports are seized, they are dismissed from their jobs, and they are prevented from travelling, all of which is enough to drive them to - and which in innumerable cases has led them to commit - suicide. The legal system treats them as "*Guilty until proven Innocent*" when all over the world it is Innocent till proven Guilty - this is the beauty of the Indian Legal System.

Misandrist Actors

Advertising companies produce misandrist ADs that promote men being slapped by women, and which proclaim that the Girl is always right while the Boy is always wrong, that Women perform better than Men etc.

The Indian Government has created more than 50 schemes, reservation and funds meant exclusively only for the girl child and women but none at all for boys and men; there is a separate government ministry to only look after the interests of and to take care of women but there is none for men.

Most tellingly, at the United Nations, there is an Un_Women but no UN_Men.

Exposing Feminist agenda, vested interests, ill-deeds is treated as misogyny and such men are branded as women haters - as bad as Jack the Ripper. Some radical feminists even claim men are biologically inferior and inherently immoral. At the same time feminists promote their agenda by claiming themselves to be victims of patriarchal society and that they are weaker sex and oppressed by men; when it comes to matters of alimony, they claim that men make more money and that women are financially oppressed by men. So if as per them, men are inferior then how is it that they also claim that Men earn more money and own more assets?

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Some Radical Feminists have in fact demanded Bachelor Tax be imposed on men who go their own way (MGTOW) and such men are described as anti-feminist and misogynist.

Legalising Misandry

There was an article by UN Women (Twitter Handle: @UN_Women) with the heading **SOCIAL MEDIA MONITORING ON COVID-19 AND MISOGYNY IN ASIA AND THE PACIFIC** which has deliberately ignored all facts, figures and statistics collected and published by Government bodies and reputed organizations like NCRB - this radical feminist organization then went on to demand legal action and even more laws favoring women.

Some of the one-sided and biased recommendations are as follows.

As we celebrate the 20th anniversary of UN Security Council resolution 1325, we must also recognize that trends in the digital sphere have also undermined the very goals the Women, Peace and Security (WPS) agenda has sought to realize. This absence of security online hinders women's participation in the public sphere, governance and leadership roles, especially in the context of conflict prevention and in promoting social cohesion. Should this deficiency in women's engagement online in the region continue, the status quo is sure to be preserved, maintaining influence in the hands of the very powerful few, and stalling the transformative change that the WPS framework envisages. Thus, women's digital engagement and use of technologies are at a critical juncture with regards to the achievement of the WPS agenda. The following recommendations are targeted towards governments, development organizations and researchers in South and South-East Asia:

1. Build the capacity of women in South and South-East Asia to identify, report and block hateful content, as well as for men and women on social media literacy and

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countering disinformation as the region witnesses increased volumes of misogyny and hate speech targeting women online, it is crucial that women users of social media are aware of how to protect themselves. Likewise, misogynist tweets and Facebook posts, especially in South Asia, are often based on news stories that are fake or taken out of context. This suggests that increased levels of social media literacy among both men and women would limit the efficacy of such posts in spreading their hateful agendas.

2. Pass legislation that criminalizes cyber harassment and cyber stalking Although States often have existing laws that prohibit stalking or harassment, these laws are sometimes inadequate to criminalize harms that happen online. Thus, specific laws to address cyber harassment and stalking can close this gap.

3. Monitor and remove misogynist content on social media platforms Social media companies have increasingly sought to regulate what content is publishable on their platforms, banning everything from election misinformation to photos depicting violence. However, no ban against misogyny, particularly violent misogyny has yet been introduced, which affects the safety and free speech of women users.

4. Produce and disseminate gender empowerment-themed content targeted at men The overwhelming majority of COVID-19-related misogynistic content is posted by male users, across platforms and countries. One way to tackle the root of these gender biases and prejudices is by developing localized and engaging counter-narrative content. This could entail enlisting the participation and support of local entertainers and influencers who have large followings and using content styles and formats that men are likely to engage with.

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5. Research the scope and impact of online misogyny on closed social networks such as WhatsApp, private Facebook groups, and Telegram Investigating the prevalence of online misogyny on closed platforms and private groups would allow a comprehensive understanding of the full extent of online misogyny in South and South- East Asia. Closed social networks can provide greater anonymity, allowing for greater incitement to violence and hatred with impunity.

6. Research potential links between nationalism and misogyny among social media users in Asia The suggested intersectionality between nationalism and misogyny among social media users outlined in this brief merit further investigation and validation. In an age of growing nationalism across the region, examining potential linkages between nationalism and misogyny among online users would provide relevant insights into the root causes and consequences of online misogyny.

THIS CLEARLY SHOWS RADICAL FEMINIST MENTALITY AND REVEALS THEIR FEAR OF LOSING GROUND WHEN THEIR FALSEHOODS ARE EXPOSED - THEIR INTENTION IS TO SILENCE THE TRUTH REGARDING FAKE FEMINISM BY MISREPRESENTING SUCH TRUTHS AS MISOGYNY WHILE PRETENDING TO BE INNOCENT VICTIMS AND ALSO DEMANDING LEGAL ACTION FOR EXPOSING THEIR BLATANT LIES.

Fake Propaganda

South Africa's government has introduced three Bills in Parliament to curb gender-based violence.

President Cyril Ramaphosa has termed them as the "*most far-reaching legislative overhaul in the fight against gender-based violence and femicide*".

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The proposed changes seek - among other things - to create a new offence of sexual intimidation, to allow names of sex offenders to be publicly available and to make it more difficult to grant bail to perpetrators of violence against women.

They also impose new obligations on police officers, prosecutors and courts in the handling of cases.

In Europe if law makers attempt to pass any laws to check abuse and misuse of the legal system and to punish women who file false rape cases against men, mass media immediately opposes the same by asking “*Are Europe's rape laws letting women down?*” - anyone can easily research this by searching online for more details.

This clearly shows that Feminists do not want women's complaints to be checked, scrutinized and verified properly, they want the Police/Legal Authority to accept any complaint made by a woman exactly as narrated by her. They want that the Authorities should not cross-check with the Accused man for his version. The reason is that most times Rape cases are in fact incidents of consensual sex, but when things go wrong or not as per what the woman wants, then such women falsely claim Rape.

In most countries only women have the option to report Domestic Violence since only women are considered as Victims and there is no system whatsoever for men to report Domestic Violence committed against themselves. Equality and equal protection of laws is only in the Law books and is not seen in actual practice. We have collected hundreds of cases of murders of husbands at the hands of their wives, (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3704275/>) in the earlier six months of the pandemic. Not even one such murder made national headlines, nor has the foreign media highlighted - or made any documentaries on - the same. This clearly shows strong media bias against Men.

At the same time we have reported suicides by men because of marital discord (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3717515/>), these also have not made any national headlines nor has any foreign media highlighted the same - and why? - because there is a systematic plan of radical Feminists to silence the truth.

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Indian Society, Spouse and System Push Men to take drastic steps finally leading them to end their own precious lives. Feminist mafia, prejudiced Indian society, one-sided media, negative bias from birth, and gynocentric, short-sighted Government Policies that completely neglect Indian men are the main reasons which are responsible for cutting short Men's lives.

Government of India is over enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women's empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family and spiritual values that define this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is clearly visible in the lack of support and absence of any help to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicide. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to the rising numbers of fake cases, ill treatment by society and total neglect by the Government.

Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that's one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their deaths. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was 70.2: 29.8, which is more as compared to the year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate for men is twice than of women. All of these statistics are not only deliberately concealed but also suppressed by chauvinistic feminist organizations like UN_Women.

TOXIC AGENDA

All the above statistics show why men are committing suicide. Most of the suicides are because of family problems, threats from wives to file fake cases, financial commitment towards the family, one sided laws, Reservation and Schemes meant only for females, zero support from government, zero protection from current laws against false accusations and fake cases. Men are abused, vilified, exploited and are expected to suffer

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in silence while women on the other hand are treasured, protected and pampered. Every country in the world, and their governments are busy pushing agendas for women's empowerment making special provisions for women's reservations / schemes / funding and enacting gender biased laws in favour of women without any safe guards against false cases. More MEN are suffering at the hands of an abusive female – wife / girlfriend / live-in partner which leads to depression and suicide. Yet strangely enough, hardly any studies have ever been conducted to research the psychological trauma that men have to face on a daily basis for years together. Truly men today are under attack from all sides and the day is not far off when to be born as a male will be considered the biggest curse and liability. Every aspect of the above mentioned details proves an unmistakable bias and discrimination against the male child even before birth. Today's generation in fact opts for the female child over the male child (gender selection) as there are many schemes and reservation meant only for the girl child (eg: BETI BACHAO / SAVE THE GIRL CHILD) and not a single Reservation/Quota system in Education, jobs, commuting etc. for the male child. Thus there is SYSTEMIC DISCRIMINATION against Men and in favour of WOMEN. Being born as a MAN is more of a SIN and really a CURSE in today's World, especially in India.

Government policies, media propaganda and societal attitudes are doing their very best to silence the truth of men's misery and problems by highlighting only a few crimes of men while shielding major crimes committed by women, by openly threatening legal proceeding against any attempts to expose the truth terming the same as misogyny, and by making laws to justify crimes committed by women portraying these as done in self-defense - murder of a Man is justified by (falsely) claiming that the Woman was saving herself from violence. These are the goals that radical feminists are planning to achieve.

Ultimate Goal

ALL OF THIS POINTS TO ONE AND ONLY ONE INTENTION:

TO CONTROL AND DOMINATE MEN, TO DESTROY ANY HOPE OF LIVING A HAPPY FAMILY LIFE AND TO MAKE MEN ABSOLUTE SLAVES OF WOMEN

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This is the ultimate aim of Extremist, Sadistic, Radical Feminists.

What feminists are afraid most of is losing all the years of their malicious efforts in which men - out of good faith - have mistakenly assisted. Most of the Laws, Rules, Perks and money granted were by and from men. Men made laws for women, Men granted them the right to vote, Men have generously promoted and supported them but in return these sadist feminists misused and manipulated their privileges - this has given birth to the Men's Rights Movement and a new dimension of the backlash against women's fake anti-violence advocacy is the rise of Indian Men's Rights Organizations formed to promote reversal of the bias against men. Feminists realize this will ultimately abolish all the free meal-tickets that they have been enjoying all these years, and have therefore falsely termed as misogyny the true facts disseminated by such men's rights groups viz. of women wreaking destruction on the Indian family system through their misuse of "gender-biased" laws. These feminists can hide the truth for some time but they can never erase it. The feminist's organizations do not want to admit that they are in fact digging the grave of their extremist ideology by distorting reality that will ultimately jeopardize their malicious advocacy efforts, and will end the unjustified socio-legal benefits that they are currently enjoying. This is the ultimate fear of feminists who are trying their level best to silence the voices of Men protesting the bias against and injustice meted to themselves.

Feminists should realize that in the modern internet age their false and misguided propaganda will no longer bear any fruit as an ever increasing number of people begin to realize that it is in fact Men who today are discriminated against right from birth, that it is Men who need to be protected against Domestic Violence committed by Women and that it is Men who are treated as second class citizens in many countries around the world with India regrettably topping the list. As more and more people - not only Men but also other Women and children - are falsely accused and unjustly convicted due to one-sided women-centric laws, the numbers of such Men's Rights Activists is only bound to increase and Governments will be forced to take notice of the falsehoods and hypocrisy of extremist feminist organizations like UN_Women who should keep in mind the words of Abraham Lincoln: *"You can fool all the people some of the time and some of the people all the time, but you cannot fool all the people all the time"*.

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**Conclusion: IT IS NOT, LEGALISING MISANDRY TO EMPOWER WOMEN;
IT'S LEGALISING MISANDRY TO EMPOWER FEMINISTS AND THEIR
TOXIC AGENDA.**

THE END

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